

VIRTUAL REALITY IN INITIAL TEACHER EDUCATION AS A TOOL FOR
EXPLORING AND UNDERSTANDING THE ORGANISATION AND
MANAGEMENT OF CLASSROOMS

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Declaration

I, Alan William John Matthews, declare that the work contained within this thesis is my own and has not previously been submitted for a DBA, DProf, EngD or PhD or comparable academic award.

Dedication

For all those friends and family who kept us together, you know who you are, I wouldn't be here without you.

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Abstract

This PhD investigated the potential for using virtual reality (VR) in Initial Teacher Education (ITE). VR has been successfully used to teach skills in multiple disciplines. VR and 360° videos were explored as a method of supporting preservice teachers to learn about organising and managing classrooms. Although setting up classrooms is important and complex, preservice teachers appear to learn mostly by experience.

This research took a pragmatic multi-methods approach, incorporating a sequential exploratory research design. Four studies were carried out, guided by the ADDIE design framework. Study 1 used semi-structured interviews to explore how teachers approached the organisation and management of their classroom. Eight themes were identified. Study 2 explored using 360° videos as a medium for teaching and learning. Findings informed the development of Best Practice Guidelines. Study 3 systematically reviewed nine studies, assessing the potential of using VR for teaching and learning in socially complex environments. Findings demonstrated VR's utility in a range of social contexts.

Studies 1-3 informed the development of three VR classrooms. The potential application of these VR experiences were explored in Study 4, a multi-methods study using the Think Aloud Method, semi-structured interviews and content analysis to examine participant responses. The results demonstrated that VR provided a suitable medium for exploration, reflection and discussion in relation to organising and managing classrooms.

In conclusion, VR can provide a medium for professional development and education of teachers learning the skills of classroom organisation and management. VR has the potential to bridge the gap between learning theory and real-world practice for preservice teachers. This would increase learning opportunities for the complex skill of establishing safe and effective learning environments. Future research should explore the feasibility of using VR within the ITE curriculum and evaluate learning outcomes for preservice teachers.

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Glossary

360° videos – Multiple overlapping camera angles rendered as one or two overlapping spheres which when viewed through a VR headset places the observer in the centre of the video environment.

3D environment – A computer designed environment which may be experienced either on a desktop or through a VR headset which displays objects and/or landscape with depth, length and width.

App/Application – A piece of software or program designed to be run on electronic hardware.

Augmented Reality (AR) - Augmented Reality is the enhancement of the real world by overlaying computer graphics. This can be accomplished via a smartphone or by using specialist semi-transparent glasses similar to a VR headset.

Cinematography – Generally the art of cinema (video or digital video) production. More specifically this refers to the use of a camera to capture a scene. This includes the use of lenses, filters, camera position, framing, etc.

Extended Reality (XR) - XR encompasses all the recent technological approaches to enhancing the real-world environment by overlaying or completely replacing it with computer graphics and virtual environments.

Field of View (FOV) –The visible arch of the observable virtual world that can be seen when using VR/AR/XR headsets. The greater the field of view the more can be seen without turning your head.

Force Feedback – The simulation of real-world physical touch on haptic devices by the inclusion of motorized resistance to movement.

Haptic – Relating to or based on a sense of touch.

Head Mounted Display (HMD) – Usually worn on the head or as part of a helmet structure this includes an optical display in front of the eyes which can be monocular (covering one eye) or more usually in the case of VR, binocular (covering both eyes and providing stereoscopic vision).

Initial Teacher Education (ITE) – is the education of preservice teachers, as they study to become qualified, practising educators.

Locomotion (in VR) – The apparent movement around a virtual environment usually triggered by user input.

Mise-en-scène – From French meaning “setting the stage”, this term refers to everything within the frame of a moving image (video, film or digital video) which is within the control of the filmmaker. This includes lighting, set design, props, actors, make-up, etc.

Mixed Reality (MR) – Combines computer generated elements with the real-world environment, but it may reverse the approach taken by AR by importing real-world elements into the virtual environment.

Montage – The technique of editing together several sections of film or video to form a coherent whole. This is one of the most basic and well-established techniques in filmmaking.

Optical Tracking – a means of finding the real-time position of an electronic device (including a HMD for VR) by determining the positions of active or passive infrared markers attached to the device.

Parallax – The apparent movement of objects at different distances when viewed from different positions. This can also refer to a technique used in computer graphics where background images move more slowly than foreground images to increase the illusion of 3D space.

Positional Audio (Binaural Sound) – A method of recording sound that uses two microphones, arranged to create a 3-D stereo sound sensation for the listener.

Raster Images – Created using pixels, each of which contains colour and tonal information which are saved in a specific order to create an image.

Skybox – A method of giving the illusion of scale in a 3D environment by enclosing the foreground, reachable elements in a large cuboid. Onto the cuboid is typically projected some image of a distant landscape this image remains at infinite perspective from the user.

Stereoscopic - The visual illusion of differential distances among objects by presenting side by side images to either eye with tiny changes to either image to give the illusion of depth.

Teleportation (in VR) – The apparent instantaneous movement from one part of a virtual environment to another usually triggered by user input (a form of locomotion).

Virtual Reality (VR) – Specifically refers to immersive systems which include a 360° fully simulated environment with which the user can interact using an HMD and motion-tracked controllers.

VR experience – A complete immersive system presented to the user including the software and the hardware.

Wire Frames (Vector Graphics) –Curved points and lines used to create an infinitely scalable picture. Vector graphics are based on mathematical formulas not square pixels.

Chapter 1. Introduction and Overview

This chapter will introduce the topic of this PhD, introduce the research questions being addressed and signpost the overall structure of the thesis. This introductory chapter is intentionally brief, being followed by an in-depth two-part literature review providing a detailed overview and justification for the research.

1.1. Brief Overview of the Topic

This PhD explored the potential for using virtual reality (VR) as a tool for teaching and learning in Initial Teacher Education (ITE). It specifically investigated the use of VR and 360° video within ITE for the organisation and management of classrooms. Child development research demonstrates a clear link between the learning environment and a child's learning experience (Ahmadi and Saiki, 2017). Many aspects of learning and development are impacted by the learning environment. These include attention, engagement, creativity, peer interaction, teacher interaction, a sense of safety and security, a sense of self-efficacy, ownership, empowerment, and overall academic achievement (Ahmadi and Saiki, 2017; Cardellino, Araneda and García Alvarado, 2017). The optimisation of a child's learning environment is, therefore, a key skill for teachers to learn. Unfortunately, classroom organisation and management is a significant cause of stress and dissatisfaction in new teachers (Evertson and Weinstein, 2006). Teachers may require years of experience to synchronise their approach to learning with the physical characteristics of the classroom (Unal and Unal, 2012). Current literature on classroom organisation and management will be discussed in detail in Chapter 2.

VR is an emerging technology but one which has a developmental history going back hundreds of years (Jerard, 2016). Recent application of modern computer graphics, optical tracking and mobile technology have, since 2016, created a new age of consumer VR technology (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). As a result, it has become possible to apply VR in fields where it would previously have been impractical. 360° videos use similar hardware to VR to place the user at the centre of a digital environment. VR and 360° videos have recently been applied to education and training in a variety of new and interesting ways (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). Examples include the fields of dentistry (Roy, Bakr and George, 2017), surgery (Yin *et al.*, 2018), safety training (Oliva *et al.*, 2019) and engineering

(Laseinde *et al.*, 2015). VR and 360° videos have also shown potential as tools for teaching and learning in fields that require affective skills such as listening and communication (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). For example, VR has been successful at improving communication skills (Kron *et al.*, 2017) and is widely regarded as a powerful means of generating emotional responses in the user (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). Researchers have begun to suggest the potential for using VR and 360° videos as part of teacher education (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). The potential of VR and 360° videos as a tool for teaching and learning will be discussed in detail in Chapter 3.

My own experience of school classrooms is very different to that experienced by my children. Classrooms seem to have become less teacher centred and more focused on the needs of the learner. My own experience of using VR suggests that it has great potential as a medium for teaching and learning. The immersive quality of VR has the potential to allow users to explore not just skills, but the feeling of being in a new environment. There is potential to apply VR to teacher education by recreating the physical environment of the classroom in a virtual world. This research brings together two threads. The first thread examines how teachers use, and are *taught* to use, the physical space of their learning environment to support student learning. The second identifies how VR can be used as a tool for teaching and learning when applied to complex social environments. This topic is fascinating because it brings together research from fields such as developmental psychology, environmental psychology, education, computer science and digital design. The challenge of this PhD was to apply a methodology suitable for bringing all these fields together to address the research aim. The overall methodology and structure of this PhD will be discussed in detail in Chapter 4.

1.1.1. Aims, Objectives and Research Questions

The aim and research questions of this PhD are presented in detail at the beginning of Chapter 4. To set the scene, they are also introduced here. The aim of this PhD was to investigate the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. It specifically explored the potential use of VR and 360° video in ITE for the organisation and management of classrooms. This research had two key objectives: (i) to identify how teachers (with various levels of experience) evaluate and use learning spaces; and (ii) to identify how VR can be used to support preservice teachers in their own learning of how

to create safe and effective learning environments. The aim and objectives were achieved by addressing five specific research questions:

- **Research Question 1:** What factors influence how teachers organise and manage their learning environment?
- **Research Question 2:** Can 360° video be used effectively as a medium for teaching and learning?
- **Research Question 3:** Can VR be used to learn affective skill sets in a professional or vocational environment?
- **Research Question 4:** What is best practice for using VR and 360° video to simulate classroom environments within Initial Teacher Education?
- **Research Question 5:** Can VR provide a medium for professional development for preservice teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?

1.1.2. Summary of Studies

Four interlinking studies were conducted to address the aim, objectives and research questions:

- **Study 1:** a qualitative study that undertook a series of individual semi-structured interviews investigating the factors that influence how teachers organise and manage their classrooms.
- **Study 2:** an exploratory study with feedback from participants on the use of 360° video in simulating a classroom environment and the potential for use of this technology in an education setting.
- **Study 3:** a systematic review of studies exploring the application of VR to professional training and education in non-procedural or non-technical fields, with particular emphasis on those fields that are socially or emotionally complex.
- **Study 4:** a multi-methods study using the Talk Aloud Method to assess the reaction of participants experiencing three different classroom layouts depicted in simulated VR environments (informed by Studies 1-3) using a head mounted display (HMD).

1.1.3. *Structure of the Thesis*

This research is presented in the following order:

Chapter 1: Introduction – This current chapter introduces the topic, its key terminology, aims and research questions, and signposts the structure of the thesis.

Chapter 2: Literature Review Part 1 – Learning Environment – A narrative review of the current literature on how teachers organise and manage the learning environment and how that impacts the learning experience. Chapter 2 will justify why exploring the learning environment should be a key area of learning within ITE.

Chapter 3: Literature Review Part 2 – Virtual Reality – A narrative review of the current literature on VR as a tool for teaching and learning with a particular focus on teacher education. This chapter will justify why VR is an important technology to explore for ITE.

Chapter 4: Methodology – This chapter provides a detailed explanation of the research questions, followed by a brief overview of the overarching methodology for this PhD. Detailed methods are provided under each subsequent study chapter.

Chapter 5: Study 1: Interviews – A detailed description of the methods, findings and discussion of this qualitative study exploring the factors that influence how teachers organise and manage their classrooms.

Chapter 6: Study 2: Optimisation of 360° Video – A detailed description of the methods, findings and discussion of this study exploring the use of 360° videos in simulating classroom environments for the purpose of teaching and learning.

Chapter 7: Study 3: Systematic Review – A detailed description of the methods, findings and discussion of this study exploring the use of VR for learning in professional or vocational fields that are socially or emotionally complex.

Chapter 8: Designing the Simulated VR Classrooms – A detailed description of the design and development of the three simulated classroom environments to be evaluated in Study 4.

Chapter 9: Study 4: Simulated Classrooms – A detailed description of the methods, findings and discussion of this study exploring insight from teachers engaging with three different simulated VR classroom environments.

Chapter 10: Discussion – A synthesis and interpretation of the overall findings, addressing the aims and research questions of the PhD. Chapter 10 also addresses the strengths and limitations of this research, and recommendations for future research.

Chapter 11: Conclusions – A summary of concluding findings.

1.1.4. Terminology

This thesis explores different aspects of education. The reader will encounter various terms such as *classroom*, *classroom management*, *learning environment*, *pupils* and more. A few key terms will be briefly defined here. The **classroom** will be defined as a specific physical environment which is arranged or designed to facilitate learning and is usually contained within the walls of a single room. The term classroom and the term learning environment are not interchangeable. Classroom refers to the physical characteristics of a location being designed to facilitate its intended purpose. A classroom may be a learning environment, or a classroom may be one element in learning environment. **Learning environment** would refer to the composition of any location where learning takes place. This includes the layout of the environment, the social atmosphere generated by those present and the wider social and physical context of the environment. Learning environment could refer to any social space, a school or an outdoor environment. More specifically, the **physical learning environment** refers to the physical elements that make up the learning environment. This might include desks, chairs, walls, windows, displays or technology depending on the context. The physical learning environment indirectly includes elements of the social environment but only insofar as they are represented by displays, photographs and other relevant material.

This PhD explores how classroom organisation and management is and may be taught in ITE. **Initial teacher Education (ITE)** is the education of preservice teachers, as they study to become qualified, practising educators. **Classroom management** will be defined as the collective management of multiple, overlapping classroom activities, including learning, behaviour and social interaction. **Classroom organisation** will be defined as the deliberate arrangement of the physical elements of the classroom.

Preservice teachers will be the term used to describe student-teachers who are enrolled in a teacher education program and working toward teacher certification. Preservice teachers can also be referred to as trainee teachers, teacher candidates, student teachers or probationary teachers depending on local conventions and the extent of their progression through the ITE experience. **In-practice teachers** are commonly referred to as professional teachers or just teachers. Throughout this thesis the term in-practice teacher or just teachers will be used to describe fully qualified working teachers. **Pupils** will be used to refer to children or young adults taking part in primary or secondary education. Similar, commonly used terms such as kids, children, pupils or learners may be used in quotations or when referencing specific studies. These instances will be clarified as necessary. The term **students** will only be used to refer to children or young adults taking part in higher education, college or university.

The next chapter will justify why exploring the learning environment should be a key area of learning within ITE. Chapter 2 will be a narrative review of the current literature on how the learning environment impacts the learning experience, and how teachers approach the organisation and management of their classrooms.

Chapter 2. Literature Review Part 1 – The Learning Environment

2.1. Introduction

This literature review has four objectives: (i) to address why classrooms are important; (ii) to explore how pupils are influenced by classrooms; (iii) to explore how teachers set up and use their classrooms; and (iv) to explore how preservice teachers learn about classroom organisation and management within ITE.

It is generally recognised that the primary goal of teaching is to assist pupils to gain a positive academic outcome (Vallikat, 2021). However academic achievement is not the only goal of teaching. Cremin and Arthur (2014) discuss four. First is the **acquisition of knowledge**. This knowledge can take the form of procedural knowledge, conceptual knowledge, skills acquisition and metacognitive knowledge (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). The type of knowledge emphasised by teachers has changed since the Victorian era with less emphasis on knowledge and skills and more on conceptual and metacognitive abilities (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). This reflects the evolution of education in the UK, and in some other countries, that the purpose of education is to teach pupils how to learn rather than to encourage the rote memorisation of information (Cremin and Arthur, 2014).

The second goal of teaching is the **classification of children into ability groups** in preparation for further education. Cremin and Arthur (2014) suggest that although the formal need for such classification has lessened, informal classification of pupils in preparation for national testing still takes place. The third goal of teaching is to **aid pupils in socialisation** and encourage positive relationships with their peers (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). Part of this is the shaping the pupils' character and attitudes, to promote awareness of international values (Vallikat, 2021). As described by Cremin and Arthur (2014), to induct the pupils, "*into the norms and values of British society.*"

The fourth goal of teaching, closely linked to socialisation, is to **promote pupils' physical, mental, emotional and social welfare**. In the modern world this goes beyond the provision of school meals and physical activity and recognises that schools may be the only safe environment that some children experience. Pezaro (2016) highlights the

importance of equipping pupils with the necessary skills to make their own decisions about their future, their families and communities.

The four overall goals described above may evolve over time based on government policy, cultural norms and what individual teachers believe to be in the best interest of their pupils (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). The important point here is that the goals of teaching go beyond academic outcomes and are influenced by social and cultural elements beyond the school.

2.2. Why Are Classrooms Important?

Important factors addressed in the design of learning spaces include: movement through the classroom; flexibility of use; furniture; materials used for furnishings; colours; lighting; structure; pupil ownership; acoustics; ventilation; humidity; temperature; noise; and safety (Martin, 2016). Within this, the *physical learning environment* refers to the material elements of a learning space, ranging from tangible elements such as tables, chairs, and equipment, to environmental elements such as temperature and lighting. Research demonstrates that the classroom environment influences different aspects of learning (Cardellino, Araneda and García Alvarado, 2017; Dovey and Fisher, 2014). Classroom layout is known to affect attention, engagement, social interaction and learning outcomes (Ahmadi and Saiki, 2017).

Higgins *et al.* (2005) undertook a review of literature on behalf of the Design Council to inform its *Learning Environments Campaign*. One important aspect that Higgins *et al.* (2005) emphasised was the interconnected nature of a learning environment, in comparison to disconnected nature of the relevant research. Extreme conditions, such as distracting noise or excessive heat, have a negative effect on pupils and teachers (Higgins *et al.* 2005). Current research can usefully identify the minimum environmental conditions for comfort. However, the research is unclear on which elements of the physical learning environment should be prioritised or how all the elements interact.

Although the available research literature covers a diverse range of topics from colours of walls (Smith and Call, 2008) to the inclusion of technology (Byers, Hartnell-Young and Imms, 2018), it is rare for research to examine these multiple facets together. This is a limitation of the current evidence base. Higgins *et al.* (2005) attempted to address this gap by adopting a conceptual framework for the design process. Their review took a

holistic approach to the learning environment, to model the whole system from a design perspective. However, it did not address the practical challenges faced by teachers. Higgins *et al.* (2005) did acknowledge that for a change in the physical learning environment to have a positive impact it would be necessary to involve teachers and pupils in the ongoing developmental process.

Classroom layouts are an important aspect of the physical learning environment. Gremmen *et al.* (2016) identified the four most common classroom layouts as the traditional layout in rows of desks, desks arranged in small groups, a U-shaped arrangement of desks and finally a undivided flexible arrangement adaptable to needs. Different layouts support different aspects of learning. For example, the traditional didactic arrangement of seating facilitates individual activity and the dissemination of information (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016), whereas peer interaction may be facilitated by layouts of small groups (McCorskey and McVetta, 1978).

Pupils' learning experiences are significantly influenced by the relationship with their teacher, whether positive or negative (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development., 2013). Several factors influence how pupils perceive their teacher. These include body language, tone of voice, facial expression and eye contact (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development., 2013). These are fundamental elements of communication. All pupils do not have the same visual interaction with their teacher in the classroom (Cardellino, Araneda and García Alvarado, 2017). Cardellino *et al.* (2017) propose guidelines for face-to-face interaction based on two variables: visual interaction and distance relation. In a classroom set up with rows of desks, children seated near the front and centre have greater opportunities for visual interaction and participation than children seated at the side or rear of the class (Marx, Fuhrer and Hartig, 2000; Weinstein and Mignano, 2011). Pupils sitting in the front row, as opposed to the rear of the classroom, have a different social experience with their teacher and therefore a different learning experience. Pupils in the front of the classroom are more likely to see, hear and be influenced by a teacher's non-verbal language (Weinstein and Mignano, 2011)

Classrooms are important because they are complex environments which can be influenced by several factors and because the combination of these factors can have a profound effect on a pupil's learning experience. Higgins *et al.* (2005) identified that the

current research rarely takes a holistic approach to understanding classrooms. The next section will look in more detail at how classrooms effect pupils' learning experience.

2.3. How Do Classrooms Influence Pupils' Learning?

Shussman (2017) described how pupils responded to their physical environment via four influences: (i) emotional influence; (ii) cognitive influence; (iii) social influence; and (iv) aesthetic influence. Their findings provide an overview of how pupils' respond to their learning environments, however, Shussman (2017) is extremely vague about the aesthetic influence of the classrooms on pupils. It is never made clear what is meant by positive aesthetic influences. Further research is required to determine how the appearance of a classroom effects pupils' aesthetic appreciation of the wider world. The remaining three influences will be discussed below.

Emotional influence is defined by Shussman (2017) as a sense of security in the classroom that promotes feelings of trust and self-confidence. Emotional learning is an integral part of education. It enables children to acquire skills and knowledge to identify and manage their emotions, form healthy self-identity, exhibit empathy, and make informed and caring decisions (Carr, 2021). A child's socio-emotional learning environment is 'book-ended' by interactions with both peers and teachers. Positive peer interaction and feelings of acceptance are known to promote positive cognitive and emotional development, however, rejection increases the risk of various negative outcomes (Parker, 2004). Feeling safe and secure is also known to facilitate creativity, social development and cooperation (Klein, 2008). Shussman (2017) suggests strategies to create positive emotional influences, including providing children with wall space to express themselves and a private space such as a drawer. They also encourage the understanding of personal space by giving every pupil room to work. These ideas, although valuable, do not take into account the teacher's consideration for behaviour management or the limitations of space in many schools (Barrett, Barrett and Zhang, 2016). In addition, the extent to which pupils feelings of security outweigh pedagogical considerations is often dependant on cultural trends and government policy (Cremin and Arthur, 2014).

Shussman (2017) also described the cognitive influence of the classroom. They highlight how classroom design can hinder or support learning, creativity, problem solving and overall cognitive development. This was explored by Ksantini-Hovev (2004) who compared exam results between pupils whose desk was covered in colourful paper and those whose desk was plain. Those at the plain desk performed significantly better, suggesting that the lack of distractions allowed better focus on the given task. There are also examples in the evidence base of sensory overload becoming detrimental to pupils' performance in the classroom. White painted walls are associated with disruptive behaviour and negative psychological symptoms such as anxiety, depressive moods and lack of focus (Grube, 2013); Noise in and around the classroom can negatively impact focus and test scores (Shield *et al.*, 2015; Shield and Dockrell, 2008). Some decoration of a classroom is required to provide the pupils and teachers with a sense of ownership, however, too much can be cluttered and visually overwhelming (Shussman, 2017). This is supported by Higgins *et al.* (2005) whose review demonstrated that excessive environmental conditions of any kind had a negative effect on pupils *and* teachers.

According to Bowers (2010) the social influence of the classroom should facilitate both privacy and personal work alongside interaction. Shussman (2017) suggests that setting up group desks rather than individual desks would promote a sense of community. However, this is a simplistic idea, addressing only a small part of the issue. The socialisation goal of teaching is about much more than encouraging pupils to talk (Higgins *et al.*, 2005). The classroom environment can promote different types of play behaviour and impact pupils' psychosocial and psychomotor development (Acer *et al.*, 2016). Mikyoung (2012) found that by minimising overcrowding and promoting feelings of belonging, the design and layout of classrooms could reduce violence in schools

Shussman (2017) presents a simplified view of the learning environment by ignoring important factors such as pupils with specialist requirements, the socio-economic status of the area, the personality of the teacher or the influence of different cultural expectations. The social influence of the classroom may be affected by cultural factors beyond the classroom or even the school (Higgins *et al.*, 2005). By omitting these factors there is a tendency in Shussman (2017) towards 'architectural determinism', implying that the right combination of physical characteristics will create the perfect learning environment and therefore the best outcomes. The learning environment exists

in a wider social, cultural and economic context. For example, McKeown *et al.*'s (2017) research in Northern Ireland found that seating plans imposed by the teacher, if not carefully considered, could negatively affect opportunities for social integration by children of different religious backgrounds. These examples demonstrate how the organisation and management of the classroom has the potential to socially influence pupils in several diverse and complex ways.

The socio-emotional environment of the classroom encompasses factors such as peer interaction, social acceptance, comfort, safety and security (Linney and Seidman, 1989). The interaction of these factors produces what is known as a hidden curriculum (Chisiu, 2015). The hidden curriculum is the 'unintentional' learning and development that takes place from the combined environments of school, local area and teaching practices. The elements of a hidden curriculum are not formalised as learning objectives or specific lesson content (Chisiu, 2015). They are typically unplanned, non-academic learning, brought about by direct or indirect influences of the environment. According to Cucoş (2001), hidden curricula ultimately influence the development of social skills in children and Chisiu (2015) suggests that it has a key role in the development of self-image, social relationships and patterns of social behaviour.

The recent COVID-19 phenomenon of 'online learning' further highlighted the importance of social-emotional learning for young children. Parents interviewed in a study by Carr (2021) reported their awareness that the home environment was not an effective environment for their child's learning. For example, one parent stated:

"... the classroom when you walk in and you feel safe and- and everything's cute and cosy, and the posters and the motivation is all around. And it's—it's like not at home."

(Participant quote from Carr 2021)

This illustrates that the learning environment has multiple influences on pupils and that the removal of one influence, in this case socialisation, may have a significant negative impact on pupils' development. The short and long-term effects of the COVID-19 lockdown on pupils' development will be better understood as more research is published over the next few years.

Barrett and colleagues have undertaken several studies exploring how the appearance and layout of a classroom influences pupils' academic performance and feelings of comfort (Barrett *et al.*, 2015; Barrett *et al.*, 2013). They attempted a holistic understanding of how the whole complex system of the classroom influences pupils. Phase 1 of their research involved 751 pupils occupying 37 different classrooms across 7 schools in the area around Blackpool in the UK (Barrett *et al.*, 2013). Phase 2 expanded the project to 3 geographical areas in the UK, with 27 different schools, 153 classrooms and 3766 pupils. The purpose of the project was to, "explore if there was any evidence for demonstrable impacts of school building design on the learning rates of pupils in primary schools" (Barrett *et al.*, 2015, p. 118). This study gathered a variety of data including pupils' academic scores, empirical environmental data about each classroom and questionnaires provided to teachers. This data was subjected to a two-part analysis. The first part applied bivariate analyses to each of the potentially influential factors. Significant factors were identified and inter-correlations were minimised. The second part applied a multi-level analysis intended to determine their combined effects. The results demonstrated that 16% of the variation in learning progress and academic performance could be attributed to the physical aspects of the learning environment. Approximately 55% of the variance was attributed to differences between pupils, approximately 45% to differences in the classroom environments and less than 5% to differences between schools. The author's acknowledged this might be influenced by their sample being based on state funded, mixed gender, local authority schools and the measure of one educational outcome. However, the significance of the classroom alone when compared to the wider school environment was important. This suggests that future studies could usefully focus on the classroom specifically and refer to the wider school environment for context.

A strength of Barrett's study was their use of a conceptual design structure to identify factors that influenced pupils' experience. This was informed by Roll's (2007) three design dimensions of naturalness, individualisation, and stimulation. Within each of these dimensions were grouped several factors that described the influence of the physical environment. For example, naturalness includes light, temperature, air quality and links to nature. Individualisation includes factors like ownership, flexibility and individualisation. Stimulation includes colour, displays and clutter. This conceptual

structure formed the basis of the data collected by Barratt and colleagues, and their subsequent analysis. This is a more comprehensive approach than focusing on the “big four” factors of heat, light, sound and air quality which, although easily measurable, are only a small part of the whole picture (Barrett *et al.*, 2015).

A potential drawback of this approach is that it does not consider the experience of teachers or pupils or their individual perceptions of the learning environment. It is unclear how much influence teachers and pupils had on the composition of the questionnaire and the direction of the data collection. Although the three-dimensional system used described a holistic view of the learning environment it is arguable that this should have been guided by the relevant stakeholders’ own experience. This is something which Barratt and colleagues revisit in their paper *Teachers’ views of their primary school classrooms* (Barrett, Barrett and Zhang, 2016). Another limitation is the focus on academic performance. There is no consideration of what may be the other goals of a positive learning environment (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). Although Barrett’s work was large in terms of participant numbers, it was focused solely on primary school education in the UK. The weighting of the results was dependent on the context of UK primary education and may not be transferable to other countries. It is unknown whether a similar study in a different country would find a different emphasis on the physical character of the learning environment.

Barratt *et al.* (2015) emphasised the importance of flexibility in the classroom arrangements. The degree of flexibility in the classroom can be extremely varied (Shussman, 2017). Fixed elements, that typically cannot be changed, include a classroom’s proportions, size and lighting. Elements which *may* be adapted by the teacher include: (i) furniture and desk arrangements; (ii) neatness; (iii) personal space; (iv) technology; (v) visual stimuli; and (vi) colours. However, not all these elements were modifiable in every classroom studied by Barrett *et al.* (2016). In overcrowded classrooms, for example, personal space and seating options were limited.

This section has highlighted the numerous ways in which the classroom impacts pupils’ learning experience. Teachers, therefore, have an important role in managing their classroom environment (Chisiu, 2015). The following section explores *how* teachers achieve this.

2.4. How Do Teachers Design and Use Their Classrooms?

Classroom organisation and management is recognised to be one of the most difficult, but also one of the more important, aspects of a teacher's job (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). It is of major concern to teachers and a primary reason for stress and job dissatisfaction in all countries (Evertson and Weinstein, 2006). Gremmen *et al.* (2016) claim that the problems of classroom management is one of the primary reasons for new teachers leaving the profession. The previous section demonstrated how changes in the learning environment influences the pupils' experience, however, the teacher may have limited agency with which to make choices on the physical characteristics of their classroom (Higgins *et al.*, 2005). They may be subject to pressures external to the school and they may only be able to influence a few elements of the physical environment (Shussman, 2017). For example, they may be able to change the desk layout, tidiness or decoration but may not be able to change the lighting, size or shape of the classroom. For this PhD, it is important to try to understand *how* teachers organise and manage their learning environment. Only by understanding these factors can we design and critically assess an appropriate VR learning experience for ITE.

Teachers are aware of their responsibility for supporting pupils' social and emotional learning (Blewitt *et al.*, 2021). However, studies in the USA, UK and Australia suggest they face barriers on how to implement this in practice. These can be institutional barriers and/or a lack of formal frameworks (Aubrey and Ward, 2013; Hollingsworth and Winter, 2013; Papadopoulou *et al.*, 2014). Conversely, many countries include national policy frameworks to highlight the importance of social and emotional learning. For example, in Scotland, Education Scotland implement the *Getting It Right For Every Child (GIRFEC)* policy, which incorporates the SHANARRI approach – an acronym standing for **S**afe, **H**ealthy, **A**chieving, **N**urtured, **A**ctive, **R**espected, **R**esponsible, and **I**ncluded. These are examples of how national government policy may influence decisions made by individual teachers when organising and managing their classrooms.

2.4.1. Teaching Pedagogies

A basic understanding of the effect of different pedagogies is useful when considering how teachers organise and manage their classrooms. It will also be important in later chapters when discussing teachers' reactions to different classroom layouts. Pedagogy is

the 'how' of education. It refers to the instructional style, strategies and techniques that take place between the teacher and the pupils to bring about learning. The precise definition of the term 'pedagogy' has been debated (Ko, Sammons and Bakkum, 2013). Many consider pedagogy to encompass additional factors such as the physical learning environment and the influence of family and community (Siraj-Blatchford and Sylva, 2004). The organisation and management of the classroom has a relationship with the pedagogical approach undertaken by the teacher.

Five key pedagogical approaches are highlighted in education literature (Waring and Evans, 2015). These are outlined below, alongside consideration for the learning environment.

1. **Constructivist pedagogy:** Teachers who use constructivism believe their pupils optimally learn by hands-on experience (Pritchard and Woollard, 2010). This type of learning can expose pupils to a wide range of experiences and guide them to reach their own conclusions. A constructivist learning environment encourages critical thinking and active participation of pupils in the 'process' of learning.
2. **Collaborative pedagogy:** A collaborative approach to learning encourages groups of pupils (or pupils and teacher) to work together, for example, to complete a task, solve a problem or create an output (Laal and Laal, 2012). Collaborative learning acknowledges that learning is social, and pupils can learn together as they discuss among themselves.
3. **Integrative pedagogy:** The goal of integrative learning is to facilitate aptitude in pupils for situations they will encounter in their life (Peyser, Gerard and Roegiers, 2006). This approach focuses on making connections across different topics rather than learning individual facts.
4. **Inquiry-based pedagogy:** Teachers who adopt an inquiry-based approach believe their pupils learn through investigation, research and exploration (Kuhlthau, Maniotes and Caspari, 2015). They facilitate this via multiple strategies, such as, simulation, demonstration, experimentation, field study and project work. Inquiry-based pedagogy can be effectively facilitated by advances in technology (Pedaste *et al.*, 2015).
5. **Reflective pedagogy:** Reflective teaching and learning explores the 'what, why and how' of what teachers and pupils do in the classroom. This process involves

evaluating whether those strategies, activities and tasks work, why they work or don't work and how they could be improved. Self-evaluation and self-reflection are key elements of reflective pedagogy.

These five pedagogical approaches reflect the *type* of learning. Another way of categorising pedagogy is by looking at *who* is 'central' to the learning (Waring and Evans, 2015). Three approaches were identified from the literature:

- I. **Teacher-centred pedagogy:** the teacher is central to the learning process, typically reflected in whole-class lectures, memorising information and answering as a group (Cicchelli, 1983).
- II. **Learner-centred pedagogy:** the pupil is central to the learning process, typically playing an active role in creating knowledge and understanding (Hancock, Bray and Nason, 2003).
- III. **Learning-centred pedagogy:** the teacher adopts a flexible and adaptable approach to learning, taking into consideration the surrounding context such as the physical environment, pupil class size and other changeable factors (Candela, Dalley and Benzel-Lindley, 2006).

The evidence base is limited regarding *how* particular pedagogies are facilitated by the organisation and management of the classroom. In the process of writing this PhD no research studies were found that described or explored the association between pedagogies and classroom organisation and management. This is a significant research gap. It *could* be suggested that: a constructivist learning space would require access to multiple experiences/activities; a collaborative learning space would need to facilitate social interaction; and an inquiry-based learning space would need access to multiple sources of information. However, there is very little information on the details of how this should be carried out within the constraints of a modern school. More research is required to provide evidence for how to affectively align pedagogies with the creation of a learning space. Future research should address the gaps regarding how to design classrooms to align with a teacher's preferred pedagogical approach or how learning spaces are influenced where overlapping pedagogies are used.

2.4.2. *Proactive Classroom Organisation*

Teachers are expected to employ a responsive pedagogy to meet a range of cultural expectations (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). They must balance the desired goals of teaching

with the needs of the pupils in an environment which is increasingly culturally diverse (Evertson and Weinstein, 2006). Inclusive classrooms are more difficult to manage because pupils may have a range of difficulties or additional needs requiring teachers to be flexible and inventive in their classroom organisation and management (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016).

Dillon (2018) makes the assertion that teachers must be proactive and aware of the impact of their decisions about organising and managing their classroom environment. They recommend that i) the design and layout of the classroom must support the teacher's style and intentions for the lesson and ii) the design and layout of the classroom should be informed by the needs of the pupils and where possible they should be actively involved in design decisions. Research suggests that having a sense of ownership over their environment allows pupils to be able to self-regulate because the pupils recognise the purpose for which they themselves have designed the environment. (Teaching Tolerance., 2016).

Although Dillon's overall points are supported by reference to academic studies, many of the specific recommendations are informed by anecdotal evidence or no evidence at all. For example, the assertion that placing images of ears around a classroom will encourage pupils to listen. In addition, the feedback provided by pupils on what they consider to be productive classroom design comes mostly from informal interactions rather than robust academic studies. Despite this, Dillon's (2018) primary recommendation remains strong, that ideally teachers should organise and manage their classroom by deliberate decisions that support their pedagogy and account for the welfare of their pupils.

Dillon (2018) did highlight that although different classroom designs were used by teachers, there was a lack of evidence detailing the teachers' thought processes. Gremmen *et al.* (2016) sought to address this gap in the literature by exploring the layout choices of 50 teachers from 4th, 5th and 6th grade classrooms in the Netherlands. Semi-structured interviews and a questionnaire were completed by participants, focusing on considerations and goals of seating arrangements. The data from the interviews were coded and scored to weight the teachers' motivations. A follow-up questionnaire again assessed the participants motivations and goals by asking them to weight the importance of statements using a Likert scale.

The results of their interviews showed that the most common seating arrangement was to have the pupils in small groups, with individual seating in rows being only slightly less common. A small percentage of participants favoured a different seating arrangement (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). The main reason given for arranging pupils in small groups was to promote social interaction. The main reason for arranging pupils in individual seats in rows was to limit distractions and promote concentration. In total, 417 reasons were mentioned as considerations for how the classroom seating should be arranged. No single reason was mentioned by all participants and there was no significant statistical relationship between the considerations given by participants and their preferred seating arrangements. These findings demonstrated the complexity of the learning environment and illustrated the potential challenges faced by teachers when trying to balance these considerations.

Participants in Gremmen *et al.*'s (2016) study identified multiple considerations for layout choice, including hearing and sight impairment, behaviour management, academic performance, social interaction, physical space of the classroom and personal attributes of pupils. It was also commonly suggested that teachers should begin the academic year with the class seated in rows and then move into groups as the pupils became more settled. This study provided some insight into the thought process of teachers when choosing their classroom layout. The study does not, however, measure if teachers' considerations and goals for classroom layout were reflected in outcomes such as academic performance or peer relationships.

Gremmen *et al.*'s (2016) findings were also limited in that data were gathered from Dutch schools, in middle class areas, with teachers who were all Caucasian. It is unknown how these findings would translate to other contexts and demographics. Another limitation of this study is that it focuses primarily on the arrangement of desks and fails to consider situations when the rearrangement of the desks is restricted or impossible such as schools with limited space or shared classrooms. In these cases, it is likely that other factors, such as displays, colour schemes or dedicated areas became a greater focus of expression by teachers and pupils. The findings, however, do broadly agree with a study by Gest and Rodkin (2011) who found that teachers' considerations on pupil seating arrangements were influenced by both behaviour management and facilitating social peer networks. In contrast, McKeown *et al.* (2015) found that teacher-driven seating

arrangements reinforced existing religious segregation in the class, and limited opportunities for inter-group interaction. Although the small sample sizes and geographic areas of these studies limit their generalisability, these collective findings do provide insight into an under-researched area. There is a need for further research into teachers' considerations when they organise and manage their classroom.

The interpretation presented above by Dillon (2018) and Gremmen *et al.* (2016) suggests that classroom organisation and management is a complex task, but central to creating safe and effective learning environments. Bosch (2006) assert that classroom management and organisation is a skill that can be taught and then refined through years of experience, and to which some teachers will adapt easily, and some will require more support. This is also demonstrated by Unal and Unal's (2012) study of 268 teachers in the USA, who reported that classroom management was one of their biggest challenges in their early years of teaching.

The question remains then: Why is classroom management a high source of stress for new teachers and the reason that many leave the profession? One hypothesis is that classroom design is not robustly taught in teacher training courses. That teachers require years of experience to master the necessary skills and that teachers' innate beliefs on learning, and their years of teaching experience, influence their approach to classroom organisation and management (Unal and Unal, 2012). The following section explores how preservice teachers learn about this within their ITE.

2.5. Classroom Organisation and Management in ITE

This final section now investigates how teachers are taught to use, organise and manage their classrooms in the course of their ITE. In the UK, where this research was undertaken, ITE typically follows two pathways of entry: (i) a 4-year undergraduate degree programme (e.g., Bachelor of Education, BEd); or (ii) a 1-year post-graduate qualification (e.g., Postgraduate Certificate in Education, PGCE). Other options include a Bachelor of Arts (BA) or a Bachelor of Science (BSc) degree with Qualified Teacher Status (QTS), or an apprenticeship pathway (National Careers Service., 2022). The typical skillsets that ITE provides trainee teachers are as follows:

- Education, values, and society
- Developmental psychology

- Equality and diversity
- Diversity in the classroom
- Meeting children's needs
- Philosophy of education
- Changing behaviours
- Situated communication

These are the typical core modules covered in ITE as reported by the University College Admissions Service (UCAS) (2022).

Preservice teachers are expected to use placement opportunities to develop the skills of classrooms organisation and management along with honing their teaching practice in various real-world classroom settings. Although teaching placements are integral to ITE, it is known that preservice teachers often struggle to cope with complex classroom interactions during teaching practice, resulting in difficulty managing lesson transitions and motivating pupils (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). Gremmen *et al.* (2016), when determining the motivation behind teachers' organisation and management of the classroom, considered three main factors. These were the teacher's beliefs (pedagogical approach), the teacher's years of experience and finally considerations of gender (both the pupils' and the teacher's). They gave no consideration to the teacher's ITE experience strongly implying that the teacher's understanding of how classrooms should be organised and managed begins and grows with their real-world experience.

Newly qualified teachers in the UK receive a handbook before embarking on their probation teaching year. Handbooks differ between local authority teaching areas, however, in general, they guide the new teacher through the expectations of their first year of teaching. Although they go into detail on activity preparation, managing challenging behaviour and other important aspects of teaching, they rarely mention classroom organisation. *Some* local education authorities provide open access to these handbooks online. For example, handbooks were accessed for Bedford Borough Council (2019), Brackness Forest Council (2020), Ealing Borough Council (2014), and North Yorkshire Country Council (2017). None of these handbooks provided new teachers with any guidance on classroom organisation or management. Some of the handbooks briefly mention the necessity of setting up a positive learning environment but fail to provide any

corresponding guidance or assessment criteria for new teachers, such as there are for skills like literacy and numeracy. Only one located, South Ayrshire Council in Scotland, provided detail and guidance on classroom organisation (South Ayrshire Council., 2020). This included suggestions on the inclusion of classroom wall displays, for good line of sight and in support of group learning.

As part of their teacher training preservice teachers typically attend practical placements in classrooms, where they engage in a range of learning such as shadowing teachers, contributing to classroom activities, and leading teaching sessions. In addition to this practical learning, anecdotal insight from online blogs suggests that ITE students typically use textbooks to gather information on how to establish positive learning environments via classroom design (Vallikat, 2021). The following sections will focus on those ITE textbooks that provide guidance on classroom organisation and management.

2.5.1. What guidance do ITE textbooks provide?

Typically, a PhD literature review explores the research evidence base on a given topic. However, a scoping search of studies exploring classroom management within ITE returned no relevant results. A detailed summary of this scoping search is provided in Appendix 2.1. The lack of research data on this topic is itself an insight, suggesting that how preservice teachers are taught to organise and manage their classroom is a topic requiring further examination. An alternative approach, instead, explored the information provided to ITE students within ITE related textbooks.

By examining examples of relevant textbooks, it was possible to scope the ways in which preservice teachers were taught to approach setting up a classroom. A search of the University of the West of Scotland's library catalogue identified approximately 400 textbooks related to teacher education. A convenience sample of these textbooks (n=75) were digitally searched for the keywords: *classroom management, layout, furniture, seating arrangements, physical environment, learning environment, space and flow, colour*, and other related terms. Only 9% (n=7) of this sample provided information to guide ITE students on creating and using their classrooms. A summary of information from these seven textbooks is provided below (Sangster, 2015; Roth, 2014; Immordino-Yang and Damasio, 2007; Hughes, 2008; Johnston and Halocha, 2010; Blatchford *et al.*, 2003; Allott and Waugh, 2016).

Information on classroom organisation and management provided in the textbooks was limited, generic and vague. No examples were identified that provided comprehensive guidance for ITE students to use in practice. There was no single consistent approach. Textbooks favoured different approaches or emphasised one specific aspect of classroom management. Preservice teachers may have learned that there are different environments to consider when creating learning spaces, most commonly the socio-emotional environment and the physical learning environment. Sangster (2015) emphasised the socio-emotional environment focusing on pupils as social learners. In this case, preservice teachers were guided to consider how their classrooms can be managed to engage children in each other's learning. Roth (2014) informed preservice teachers that their decisions impact the social mechanisms of the classroom and how the unique personalities of children could interact for learning. None of these textbooks provided practical examples of how this positive socio-emotional learning environment could be achieved other than to emphasising flexibility in the teacher's approach (Sangster, 2015). This lack of practical guidance highlights a gap in the literature and indicates the potential for new approaches to learning about classroom management in ITE.

Immordino-Yang and Damasio (2007) highlighted the emotional considerations of the learning environment. Emotions *directly* influence learning and also in subtle, complex ways such as through behaviour, relationships, health and overall wellbeing (Immordino-Yang and Damasio, 2007). Preservice teachers were encouraged to create emotional environments driven by enthusiasm, engagement, security and trust (Sangster, 2015). In some examples, preservice teachers were encouraged to think about the seating arrangements, wall displays, objects, lighting, floor space and more (Hughes, 2008). Although not explicitly stated in any of the textbooks, this may guide preservice teachers to link the socio-emotional environment with the physical environment constructed by the teacher. For example, objects influence our mood, perceptions and feelings about different circumstances (Sangster, 2015).

The approach taken by textbooks is often reminiscent of Dillon (2018) that teachers should be proactive and deliberate in their organisation and management of classrooms to best support their teaching goals. However, like Dillon (2018), the textbooks took a consistently theoretical approach that varied from source to source and rarely gave

practical examples. When planning class activities, ITE students were encouraged to use a variety of classroom layouts. For example, in groups, as individuals, as a whole class, or a combination of the options (Johnston and Halocha, 2010). Group work was defined as children working together as a team (Blatchford *et al.*, 2003), where they build collaborative skills by watching and listening to each other (Baines, Rubie-Davies and Blatchford, 2009). How and where groups of children are organised in the classroom can increase or decrease opportunities to learn from and with their peers (Johnston and Halocha, 2010). Although there was no consistent approach across different textbooks, the factors which were discussed are important in designing the latter studies of this PhD. For this reason, the practical considerations of classroom organisation and management are outlined in more detail below.

2.5.2. Organising the physical layout of the classroom

Roth (2014) informs preservice teachers that every aspect of the classroom requires thought and planning, including the floor space, desk arrangements, work areas for pupils, wall space, and access to pupil and teacher supplies. Roth (2014) suggests the time taken to organise and decorate the classroom is typically underestimated. Time is needed to create a classroom that feels comfortable and welcoming. Pupils who are coming to a new classroom often feel anxiety and stress. Preservice teachers are reminded that positive first impressions of the learning environment can help alleviate anxiety and prepare children for learning (Roth, 2014). This worthwhile advice does not consider the limited time provided to teachers to reorganise a classroom in each day. This is particularly true of secondary school teachers who may lack time between classes to give due consideration to each new group of pupils.

A more practical perspective would perhaps be to consider the most basic environmental requirements of the classroom. Johnston & Halocha (2010) consider as a starting point the basic requirements of heat, light and sound. They encourage preservice teachers to be aware of intense areas of sunlight and how these impact individual children and resources, for example, assessing whether some children are sitting in the glare of the sun, or whether the computer area is affected by glare on the computer screens (Johnston and Halocha, 2010). This links back to the work by Grube (2013), demonstrating that sensory overload can have a negative impact on behaviour and learning. With regards to heat, they suggest ensuring the temperature of the overall room is optimal for learning,

while also avoiding individual children being uncomfortably warm beside radiators. Finally, to effectively manage sound they use the example of the creation of quiet spaces for certain learning tasks or for children who learn more effectively in quiet environments. Johnston and Haloca (2010) do not provide any guidance beyond establishing the minimum environmental requirements, except to suggest that new teachers ask themselves, *“Could I learn in this environment?”* There is no evidence provided demonstrating whether this is the best question for new teachers to ask themselves. This very basic question does not appear to facilitate thoughts about alternatives or improvements. It could be argued that a more pro-active question may promote their learning, such as *“How do I optimise this environment for learning?”*

2.5.3. Space and Flow

Roth (2014) acknowledged that teachers are likely to work in different classrooms throughout their career. They will be faced with classrooms of varying size and shape, and varying opportunities for flexibility. According to Roth (2014) the priority should be to ensure that pupils and teachers can share and move around the space safely. Johnston and Halocha (2010) provided examples including ensuring children can move between desks without tripping over chair legs, and adults can stand up without hitting their heads on overhanging furniture.

Establishing a well organised classroom not only promotes learning but also impacts behaviour (Johnston and Halocha, 2010). The layout and flow of the classroom can be strategized to avoid the “bump factor” (Trussell, 2008) and bottle-necks (Harlacher, 2015). Hot spots should be placed away from children’s desks to minimise distraction. Optimal space and flow reduce opportunities for children disturbing one another and helps limit problem behaviour (Johnston and Halocha, 2010). These are at least practical suggestions that new teachers might be able to apply during their career. However, these textbooks provide no information on what these recommendations are based on. Presumably a great deal comes from practical experience. This highlights the gap in the evidence base of how theoretical underpinnings of classroom management relate to decisions by working teachers. Prioritising this advice and applying it to each unique classroom remains the responsibility of individual teachers. For example, Johnston and Halocha (2010) advised that pupils should have sufficient space for their activities, alongside space for the teacher to move around the classroom and engage with children.

This can be aided by changing the learning space throughout the day, firstly because this optimises children's position and comfort for specific activities, and secondly, this signals to children the start of a different learning task.

2.5.4. Doors, Hallways, Walls and Displays

According to Roth (2014) doors, walls and hallways are often the first thing that a pupil sees when entering a school or a classroom, and they have the potential to influence a pupil's feelings and promote an atmosphere for learning. Preservice teachers are encouraged to make these areas engaging for pupils. Roth (2014) provided examples including personalised banners on classroom doors, themed exhibition displays or the use of fabric, colour and personalised areas. Preservice teachers are also encouraged to involve children in the creation of wall displays, helping them feel ownership of their classroom (Roth, 2014). Again, it is unclear if this textbook's recommendations are based on research or from the author's own experience. However, according to Smith and Call (2008), there *is* evidence that children learn from the displays around them. Poorly used wall space can have a negative influence on learning. Bare walls may feel sterile and institutional. Bright, engaging, textured walls can help children feel relaxed (Smith and Call, 2008). Engaging children in their displays and linking those displays with current learning encourages children to look at the walls regularly, for example, maps, number charts and mental wellbeing prompts (Hughes, 2008). This is in line with suggestions made by Shussman (2017) that clever use of wall displays can promote engagement and feelings of ownership in pupils, however, it does not take into account the complexity of when an interesting display becomes a distraction (Higgins *et al.*, 2005).

The balance between display and distraction is something which perhaps should be carefully applied by individual teachers and therefore requires reflection and experience to get right. Gaines and Curry (2011) discussed similar ideas with regards to colour. They include considerations for avoiding overstimulation via large amounts of one colour; awareness of children with attention deficit disorders or autism who may be affected by colour differently than their peers; and the age of the pupils. Roth (2014) suggested that as a teacher builds relationships with their class their classroom colours should be re-evaluated and refined. There is no consistency between the few textbooks which discuss colour, decoration and displays. Presumably this is the result of how difficult

it is to balance the requirements of each unique classroom. The practical application of this advice depends on the experience of the individual teacher.

2.5.5. Desk Arrangements and Resource Access

Some textbooks, for example Allott & Waugh (2016), encouraged ITE pupils to think of their own childhood learning and ask themselves to reflect on their learning spaces. Did they sit alone or in groups? How did their classrooms change as they progressed through school? Other than the benefits of self-reflection it is unclear what guidance preservice teachers are expected to take from this. As with other aspects of classroom organisation and management the responsibility remains on the individual teacher.

It is a common theme in the available textbooks that there is no one right way to arrange furniture in a classroom, but rather different layouts to suit different learning. Preservice teachers are instructed to be flexible about rearranging their classroom to suit the needs of the current activity (Roth, 2014; Sangster, 2015; Hughes, 2008; Harlacher, 2015; Johnston and Halocha, 2010). Roth (2014) encouraged preservice teachers to consider how furniture can be easily moved to create different learning spaces. Allott & Waugh (2016) warned that when consideration hasn't been given to desk layout, the size of small group learning may be determined by the default furniture layout, rather than determined by the best approach for those pupils. This advice failed to account for the practical considerations of individual teachers who may lack the time, space or flexibility to rearrange the layout of their desks to suit different lesson requirements.

Johnston and Halocha (2010) encouraged that where possible pupils should have autonomy and independence in accessing resources. By resources they were referring to books, stationery, subject-specific equipment and personal items. These should be placed with consideration for safety, size, quantity and frequency of use. However, the available textbooks provide little guidance on how to balance this with other considerations, like managing distractions, or how to balance these considerations with desk layout in classrooms with limited space.

Harlacher (2015) offered some practical advice on maintaining lines of sight. Teaching equipment, such as projector screens and writing boards need to be visible but, most importantly, all pupils must see the teacher and the teacher must see all pupils. Beyond superficial observations, such as grouped tables being suitable for small group work (Sangster, 2015), it remains unclear exactly which desk layout supports which lesson

plan or pedagogical approach. The previous section identified key pedagogical approaches for teaching, however, there are no clear links in the chosen textbooks supporting the use of certain classroom layouts with different pedagogical approaches. This type of information could provide a strong foundation for ITE students learning about their classroom environments. The current lack of insight on this is an important area for future research.

In some textbooks, the advantages of different layouts are discussed. For example, rows of desks may promote discipline and individual learning and large circle formation can facilitate whole class communication, (Johnston and Halocha, 2010; Roth, 2014). Based on the advice of the few textbooks that discuss the subject, preservice teachers are encouraged to remain flexible and learn by experience. This lack of practical insight suggests that another approach to teaching *how* to organise and manage a classroom would be beneficial to new teachers in the first years of their career.

In summary, when examining the available material on how preservice teachers are taught to organise and manage their classrooms it is difficult to find consistent information. The few textbooks which *do* discuss the topic present a mixture of theoretical discussions and practical suggestions. Often the theoretical discussions are not linked to suggestions for practical applications. Practical suggestions, when presented, always appear to be based on the writer's own experience rather than research evidence. In many cases the prospective teacher is simply invited to consider a particular aspect of classroom management and then presumably to learn from their own experience.

The major limitation of this review of ITE learning is that, due to a limited evidence base, it relies heavily on textbook sources, which themselves have limited reference to any evidence base. Based on this it is challenging to say how these lessons of classroom management and organisation might play out in the lectures and tutorials of available ITE programmes. However, based on the information reviewed here the major tools used by preservice teachers to learn the skills of classroom organisation and management are observation, reflection and experience. This highlights opportunities for additional methods of learning, such as immersive technology, which the following chapter will discuss.

2.6. Summary of Key Findings

This literature review is an important foundation for this PhD. It demonstrates the complexity of the learning environment and the challenge faced by teachers to organise and managing an effective classroom. This review has demonstrated the importance of the learning environment for the learning experience of pupils. Aspects of classroom design are known to affect child learning in relation to attention, engagement, social interaction, creativity, sense of safety, empowerment, and overall learning outcomes. Considerations include: material factors such as light, colour, sound and furniture; socio-emotional factors such as peer interaction, acceptance, safety and security; and other factors of the learning space such as the pedagogical approach of the teacher. Where many studies examine a single factor and its relationship to pupils' learning outcomes few studies, Barratt *et al.*, (2015) being a rare exception, try to understand the whole complex system of the learning environment.

The organisation and management of classrooms is understood to be one of the most challenging aspects of a teachers' job, particularly in the case of new teachers. It is influenced by a complex network of issues. These include what aspect of the environment teachers can change, the intended lesson plan, the character of the pupils and the experience of the teacher. There is a need for further research on why in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning environment as they do and what they consider to be the important characteristics of a functioning learning environment. These questions are particularly important when tailoring the classroom organisation to a particular pedagogy. It is also unclear, other than at the most basic level, what approach to classroom organisation best suits which pedagogical approach.

There is a lack of consistent evidence on how teachers are taught to organise and manage their learning environments. It seems to be an accepted part of practice that new teachers will learn by observation, reflection and experience. There is also a lack of research that investigates this aspect of the ITE experience. It is possible that due to the constraints of school placements, trainee teachers lack opportunities to repeat their learning in a cyclic process. Experimentation with different approaches in real-world settings has the potential to have a detrimental effect on pupils. Preservice teachers, depending on where they undertook their education, may not have opportunities to

repeat teaching sessions, gain constructive feedback and consider different approaches to classroom organisation and management.

Preservice teachers may benefit from low-risk opportunities to discuss, reflect upon and practice the skills related to classroom organisation and management. This is within the scope of modern extended reality (XR) technology. Various forms of extended reality, including virtual reality (VR) and 360° videos, have been used in other professions to provide training access to complex environments. This research aims to explore if VR or 360° videos can be used to facilitate teacher training in relation to organising and managing classrooms. The second part of this literature review continues in the next chapter. It presents the use of virtual reality in various training environments and specifically examines how it has been researched in the field of teacher education.

Chapter 3. Literature Review Part 2 – Virtual Reality

3.1. Introduction to Virtual Reality

3.1.1. A Brief History

In the rapidly changing technological world of virtual reality (VR), it is useful to place this PhD in historical context. This section will demonstrate that the idea of creating simulated environments for entertainment or learning has a long history that precedes the use of modern mobile technology. In addition, this section will demonstrate that the development of VR over many decades has involved the use of a wide variety of technologies prior to the modern era of optical tracking and wireless interlinking. In fact, an important theme of this section is that VR is not a quirky offshoot of modern computing. VR is a field in its own right to which modern computing technology has only recently been applied.

Modern VR uses stereoscopic images in a head mounted display (HMD) to create the illusion of experiencing an artificial environment. The idea of a stereoscopic display providing the effect of depth perception goes back to 1832 when Sir Charles Wheatstone used angled mirrors to reflect different images into each eye (Jerard, 2016) (Figure 3.1). In the 1950s, Morton Heilig built a stereoscopic HMD showing a 140° image. He also provided breezes blowing in the face of the user to increase the sense of presence (Jerard, 2016). The Philco Corporation built the first HMD that included head tracking in 1961. The first HMD comparable to modern VR headsets was built in 1965 at the University of Utah (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). It used two integrated cathode ray tube (CRT) monitors and was so heavy it had to be suspended from the ceiling.

Figure 3.1: Sir Charles Wheatstone's stereoscope (Source: austerityphotos.co.uk)

This PhD explores the use of simulated environments, in the form of VR, for the purpose of teaching and learning. Simulated environments have been used in various contexts. The first flight simulator was developed by Edwin Link in 1928. This was an entirely mechanical device designed to mimic the movements of early aircraft by providing haptic feedback to the user. By the end of World War 2, Link had sold thousands of these devices to the US Army Air Corps (Jerard, 2016). Computer science made significant technological leaps forward in the 1970s, particularly in the field of computer graphics. Computers became faster and smaller, and the graphics improved beyond wire frames to include raster images (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). Among many other applications this allowed the creation of simulated realities based on digital technology. Flight simulators became realistic representations of aircraft cockpits and design simulations were used to model 3D environments (UCSanDiegoX., 2020).

Despite the technological improvements of the 1970s, VR technology was too expensive and cumbersome for commercial use and remained the province of university labs and industrial research. Several attempts were made in the 1980s and 90s to develop consumer VR technology. These included Atari Research in 1982 and the unreleased SEGA VR project in the early 90s (Wikipedia., 2022). It was an offshoot of Atari Research which, in 1985, coined the term “virtual reality” (Jerard, 2016). Also, in 1985 researchers at NASA produced the Virtual Visual Environment Display (VIVED) (Figure 3.2). This stereoscopic head-tracked HMD could be produced for research but was too complex for consumer use (Jerard, 2016). None of these technologies could provide users with a sense of presence sufficient to enable meaningful immersion in an artificial world (Jerard, 2016).

Figure 3.2: NASA the VIVED (Source: www.nasa.gov)

This PhD is based on the modern generation of VR. In 2013, Oculus VR ran a crowdfunding campaign so successful that in 2014 Facebook, Inc (now Meta) acquired Oculus VR with the intention of developing and marketing VR in several forms. These included consumer headsets for gaming, the Oculus Rift (Figure 3.3), and mobile VR headsets in cooperation with Samsung for use with Android smartphones. The improved user experience was in part due to the increased field of view (FOV), optical tracking and mobile technology. This facilitated greater immersion and sense of presence in the simulated world (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). The year 2016 began a new age of consumer priced VR. This also saw the first production of competing VR systems aimed at the consumer market including the HTC Vive, Sony Playstation VR and the Microsoft HoloLens (strictly an AR system) (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). 2016 is therefore a significant year in the development of VR technology.

Figure 3.3: The Oculus Rift (Source: en.wikipedia.org)

Since the commencement of this PhD the technological landscape of VR has changed considerably and continues to do so. This research should be seen in the context of the ongoing developments in VR technology and the various opportunities they continue to present. One important example is the rise and fall of mobile VR. In 2016, academic journals were explaining the potential of VR on mobile phones for education (mobile VR) (Cochrane, 2016). By early 2019, mobile VR was widely recognised as an affordable accessible option available to everyone with a smartphone (VR Innovations., 2019). However, by later that same year Oculus and Google had discontinued their headsets that supported mobile VR, the Gear VR and Daydream respectively (Robertson, 2019). By 2021, Samsung had announced that mobile VR would no longer be supported

Chapter 3. Literature Review Part 2 – Virtual Reality

on their devices (Mehrotra, 2021). In effect, mobile VR was no longer being developed commercially and only continued for specialist applications.

Other technological advancements have presented new opportunities to use VR for entertainment, education and research. In 2019, Oculus discontinued production of the Rift and in 2021 discontinued the Rift S, both of which required a physical link to a PC. At the time of writing, Oculus were focusing on production of the Quest and Quest 2, both of which do not require a linked PC to operate but can link wirelessly if required (Oculus., 2022). In addition, for certain applications the Quest and Quest 2 (Figure 3.4) no longer require handsets due to the high quality of the optical tracking. Recently, Meta (formally Facebook, Inc) announced the future development of the “metaverse”, an expansion of interconnected immersive technology, potentially as revolutionary as the internet (Ravenscroft, 2021). This received a generally mixed response worldwide. The Quest Pro and the Hololens 2 were commercially available before this PhD was completed. This PhD has been undertaken in the context of these developments in VR technology.

Figure 3.4: The Oculus Quest 2 and controllers (Source: www.meta.com)

Consumer priced, widely available VR and its application is a new and rapidly changing technology that requires research and investigation. To conduct this research in

a meaningful way it is necessary to have some understanding of the historical technological developments upon which modern VR is based. The idea of VR goes back several decades, it uses modern optical technology with haptic feedback, and it uses stereoscopic displays along with wireless tracking to immerse the user in an artificial environment. Based on the above historical summary, VR should not be thought of as an extension of modern computing technology but as the continued development of interactive artificial environments to which modern computing technology has been progressively applied. This history is important when considering the complex terminology that is applied to VR.

3.1.2. Defining and Describing Virtual Reality

3.1.2.1. Defining Virtual Reality

Clear definitions for VR and related technology are an important element of this PhD. “Virtual reality” has in recent times become a commonly used phrase. As the technology applied to VR becomes more advanced and more accessible, the terminology that surrounds VR becomes more complex. In research literature over the last decade the term VR has been applied to 360° videos (Reeves *et al.*, 2021), desktop applications (Hartley, Ludlow and Duff, 2015), CAVE systems (Wang *et al.*, 2018), head mounted displays (HMDs) (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018) and simulators (Roy, Bakr and George, 2017). Therefore, in line with the long history of VR described above, the traditional definition of VR was an umbrella term for all systems that create or partially create a simulated environment for the user. However, in the last few years terminology has evolved.

A modern definition of VR would specifically refer to immersive systems that include a 360° fully simulated environment with which the user can interact using an HMD (Figure 3.5) and motion-tracked controllers (Arm Blueprint, 2022). This more narrow definition of VR has been adopted increasingly over the last few years in order to differentiate it from other related technologies (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). In summary, a traditional and a modern definition of VR are as follows:

- **Traditional Definition** – mechanical or digital systems that create a simulated or partially simulated interactive environment for the user, this would include desktop VR, HMDs, flight simulators, CAVE systems and others.

- **Modern Definition** – specifically refers to immersive systems that include a 360° fully simulated environment with which the user can interact using an HMD and motion-tracked controllers.

Figure 3.5: Oculus Quest HMD and controllers (Source: www.meta.com)

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When using the modern definition, VR comes under the recently coined term, extended reality (XR). XR is the modern umbrella term that includes VR, augmented reality (AR) and mixed reality (MR). 360° videos, although often referred to as VR in research publications (Reeves *et al.*, 2021), are not VR by the modern definition. They lack the interactive component of VR (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). They are, more accurately, another medium that uses elements of XR technology. Clear definitions of these related technologies are as follows:

- **Extended Reality (XR)** – Extended Reality encompasses all recent technological approaches to enhancing the real-world environment by overlaying or completely replacing it with computer graphics and virtual environments.
- **Augmented Reality (AR)** – Augmented Reality is the enhancement of the real world by overlaying computer graphics. This can be accomplished via a smartphone or by using specialist transparent glasses similar to a VR headset (Arm Blueprint, 2022)
- **Mixed Reality (MR)** – Mixed Reality is somewhere between the technologies described above (Arm Blueprint, 2022). Typically, it combines computer generated

elements with the real-world environment, but it may reverse the approach taken by AR by importing real-world elements into the virtual environment.

- **360° Videos** – Uses similar technology to the above approaches to create a 360° moving image by combining video from multiple cameras filming simultaneously. Unlike the above approaches, 360° video is a non-interactive experience for the user.

3.1.2.2. VR in this PhD

The studies in this PhD focused on two types of immersive technology:

- 360° Videos
- Virtual Reality (VR)

The primary reason for this was that these were the two most commonly available and easily accessible forms of XR at the time of writing (Irvine, 2017). Both media could present immersive 360° artificial environments to the user. Creating VR applications or 360° videos required a degree of technical expertise but at the same time, over the last decade, this has become an easier and more user-friendly for researchers and developers. True forms of AR and MR still require specialist equipment (like the Microsoft HoloLens) and advanced programming skills for development (IONOS., 2023).

When reviewing research on the application of VR, a frequent problem is the broad inclusion of what constituted VR in past studies. For example, Fletcher *et al.* (2013) considers the potential for VR prototyping in the manufacturing industry, however, their study is almost entirely focused on haptic feedback devices and not HMDs. In addition, studies often fail to include the specifications of the hardware or software being examined (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). This material does often provide useful information about simulated environments, VR systems and their use in learning and teaching. Within the modern definition of VR there are a wide range of headsets available each with different attributes that provide different immersive qualities. This makes it difficult to make comparisons between different VR training experiences. Whether using the traditional definition of VR or the modern term XR, it is important to understand that these technologies create the user experience with a combination of hardware and software. The physical component of a VR experience is often as important to the sense of presence as the visual component (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b).

Some researchers make the distinction between immersive VR and non-immersive VR, for example Dubovi *et al.* (2017). This approach could be viewed as halfway between the traditional and modern definitions provided above. Immersive VR means that which is experienced through an HMD and handheld controllers, completely immersing the user in the artificial environment. Non-immersive VR is a 3D environment experienced through a computer monitor and controlled using a keyboard and mouse (Hamilton *et al.*, 2021). These two categories, although useful, do not consider the variety of other technological approaches which seek to immerse the user wholly or partially in a simulated environment. To understand the different types of XR and how it might be experienced by the user it is necessary to clearly define the terms by which VR is described.

As a result of the fluidity of the terminology and the rapidly changing technology it is important to be clear in all cases about exactly what technology is being used. Throughout this thesis, clear explanations will be provided for the technology used and why. This PhD has adhered, where possible, to the modern definition of VR provided above. When referring to other research papers or when providing quotations, it may be necessary to broaden these definitions (particularly that of VR) in a similar way to the papers described above. In other words, to revert briefly to the traditional definition. These instances will be highlighted and explained.

3.1.2.3. Describing Virtual Reality

In contrast to the commonly used terms “mobile app” or “computer application”, VR applications are often referred to as VR *experiences* because the physical component is as important as the visual or auditory (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). The term **VR Experience** usually refers to the software component of the simulation which includes the digitally generated 360° worlds and the interactive elements of those worlds. In literature, the terms “VR experience” and “VR application” are often used interchangeably (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). However, it may also refer to the hardware required to make the experience possible. In other words, given the immersive nature of VR, the requirement for it to be interactive through body movement and the potential for using haptic and force feedback devices, the term “experience” is sometimes used to refer to the whole package experienced by the user.

VR experiences, particularly in teaching and learning, are often attempting to partially imitate a real-world experience. For example, Stavroulia *et al.* (2018b) designed

simulations of working classrooms, and Real *et al.* (2017) created realistic clinical settings for their VR experience. These are **simulations**. They are the imitative representation of the functioning of one system by the functioning of another. The term **fidelity** is used to reference the degree to which a simulation emulates real life. Fidelity is often expressed in terms of degree, i.e., low, medium or high (Costiuc, 2021). Within the context of this research, fidelity is important because the fidelity of a training simulation is generally considered to be necessary in the transfer of learned skills to the real-world (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020).

In VR, although the terms “immersion” and “presence” are sometimes used interchangeably, they in fact represent different aspects of the user experience. **Immersion** is the extent to which a VR experience replaces your sensory input from the real environment with sensory input for a virtual environment. For example, an HMD would provide greater immersion than a desktop monitor. Immersion is objectively measurable. **Presence** is the subjective feeling that you are behaving and reacting in the virtual environment as if it is the real environment. It is the feeling that the virtual environment has, completely or in part, replaced the real world in your awareness (Jerard, 2016). Presence is the subjective response of the user. These two are also closely related. For example, it is possible to encourage a greater feeling of presence by increasing the level of immersion (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). Both are significant when conducting research into the value of VR as a tool for teaching and learning (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018).

3.2. Virtual Reality for Teaching and Learning

VR has been used to train professionals in multiple disciplines, in particular those which are technically complex and high-risk, such as medicine (Kron *et al.*, 2017), surgery (Huber *et al.*, 2018) and dentistry (Roy, Bakr and George, 2017). VR is considered suitable for these types of training as it provides a highly controlled simulation of a physical environment, which allows tasks to be repeatedly practiced with limited or no risk to the user (Kyaw *et al.*, 2019). The commonly agreed point of view about using VR is that it provides a sense of presence in a unique virtual environment and access to situations that would otherwise be dangerous, expensive or unethical (Ott and Freina, 2015). For example, it has the ability to provide feedback on safety training in simulations of

dangerous environments, such as offshore oil rigs or burning buildings (Howie, 2022). The following section will consider two of the key systematic reviews on the use of VR as a tool for teaching and learning. Based on the results of these two reviews this section will then consider the importance of presence and fidelity when creating VR learning environments.

Jensen and Konradsen (2018) carried out a review of the use of VR education and training. Unlike most preceding reviews, Jensen and Konradsen (2018) focused solely on VR applications that used HMDs and fully immersive VR environments. This would, therefore, conform to the modern definition of VR. They examined 21 studies that evaluated the effectiveness of VR applications in training cognitive, psychomotor and affective skill sets (such as listening and communication). They identified several factors that may limit or improve the effectiveness of VR as a medium for learning. These included but were not limited to the user's sense of presence, the familiarity of the user with VR and the fidelity of the VR environment (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). This is supported by the work of Chae *et al.* (2023) and Real *et al.* (2017) who respectively identified sense of presence and fidelity as being important to the learning process. A key observation made was that using an HMD and a VR simulation did not guarantee that learning would take place any more than sitting in a classroom would guarantee learning. Their findings indicate that VR does provide an environment where learning *can* take place (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). This combined with the inherent flexibility of VR, Jensen and Konradsen (2018) suggested it is more informative to assess the learning potential of an individual VR experience than to attempt to assess the general value of VR as a learning tool.

Jensen and Konradsen's (2018) review was limited by inclusion of only 21 studies. There was a limited pool of data to draw upon, particularly when dealing with affective skill sets, which accounted for only 5 of the 21 studies. Furthermore, the research quality of most of the included studies was assessed as low. Using the Medical Education Research Study Quality Instrument (MERSQI) they assessed the validity of the evaluation instrument to be poor on almost all the studies that employed quantitative analysis (19 out of the 21). Most were based upon user evaluations of VR. Those that assessed the learning outcomes failed to provide any justification for the validity of the evaluation instrument. Jensen and Konradsen (2018) also acknowledged that many of the studies suffered from a positive, novelty bias towards a new and interesting technology. Making

reliable generalisations from Jensen and Konradsen (2018) is difficult because of the breadth of their analysis and the small number of studies to draw upon. Their results indicate that closer assessment of the application of VR to *specific* teaching environments would be more insightful than general assessment of VR across a wide spectrum of training.

Jensen and Konradsen (2018) highlighted that many studies involved the comparison between VR and some other form of learning media, usually online learning or classrooms. For example, Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) compared VR training groups to a scenario played out with real actors. Eldred-Evans *et al.* (2013) compared surgical training in VR multiple other training methods. Cook (2005) argued that this type of research is not possible because there is no valid comparison between the two groups. Cook's (2005) suggestion is that research should focus on variations within a single type of media to arrive at a best practice when using that particular piece of technology for a specific educational scenario. This highlights the difficulty in evaluating a learning tool as complex and flexible as VR. Although Cook's (2005) approach may be technically informative there is clearly a need to compare the learner's experience between different learning environments, for example, to compare VR with traditional learning methods (Yiasemidou *et al.*, 2017) or to use VR in support of traditional teaching (Tretsiakova-McNally *et al.*, 2017). VR technology can be expensive for example, Raque *et al.* (2015) found that the use of training simulators for endoscopic surgery actually increased the cost of training per student without accelerating the learning curve or improving the students' skillset. Given the technical expertise still required to implement VR as a training medium it means we should at least try to address the question, '*is it worth the effort?*'

Kaplan *et al.* (2020) undertook a meta-analysis to assess the effectiveness of XR technology as a tool for education and training. Conforming to the modern definitions of XR technology, Kaplan *et al.* (2020) excluded from their analysis any simulation-based training on a two-dimensional medium such as tablets or desktop computers. Their analysis only included studies examining virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR) and mixed reality (MR) by modern definitions. The purpose of their analysis was to determine whether or not training carried out in an XR simulated environment measurably translated to performance improvements in the real-world and for this reason they only included studies that measured real-world performance after XR training (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). In

total they included 25 studies in their analysis, 21 of which had a VR component. Of those studies, 9 included the training of cognitive skills, 8 included the training of physical skills and 12 included skills which were mixed. Several included the training of multiple skill types. None of the studies examined by Kaplan *et al.* (2020) involved the training of affective skills, such as awareness, listening or communication skills. Examination of the potential effectiveness of VR in training affective skills is something that requires further research.

Kaplan *et al.* (2020) compared the effectiveness of virtual training to more traditional teaching methods. They concluded that XR technology provided at least as good a learning environment as real-world environments. They also concluded XR to have more advantages, as it gave safe access to dangerous or inaccessible environments like fires or oil rigs (Howie, 2022). By focusing on effect sizes in real-world data, Kaplan *et al.* (2020) attempted to provide measurable evidence of the effect of XR as a training tool. However, the value of their results was limited by the small number of qualifying studies they were able to draw upon. This meant that studies focused on specialist populations, for example soldiers or stroke victims, could disproportionately affect the analysis. Kaplan *et al.* (2020) acknowledged that future studies should examine the effectiveness of specific XR experiences with different population groups to arrive at more meaningful conclusions. In addition, presenting XR to be used as an alternative to traditional teaching methods rather than in cooperation with them is perhaps too simplistic. For example, Yin *et al.* (2018) identified the value of their simulated environment for training dental surgery was to be found in combination with traditional teaching methods.

By removing subjective reporting from their meta-analysis, Kaplan *et al.* (2020) omitted one of the most important aspects of XR experiences, user response. Other studies which examine XR and VR as training tools emphasise the importance of subjectivity, presence and the emotional impact of the experience (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). The experience of VR is to a large extent subjective. For example, consider a user's sense of presence in the VR environment (a subjective feeling by definition). Jensen and Konradsen (2018) in their review acknowledged that several factors could affect a user's sense of presence including, lag in the graphics, standing rather than sitting or even the personality traits of the user. Mikropoulos and Natsis (2011) established a set of "affordances," which were features included in each VR

educational experience that characterised the experience for the user. Key among these was the user's sense of presence in the virtual environment, which in three of the studies they examined, correlated with improved learning outcomes. For most studies it seems that an increased sense of presence encouraged the user to take the simulation more seriously and spend more time learning the task. Taken together this suggests that sense of presence could have a significant impact in determining learning outcomes.

According to Jensen and Konradsen (2018) and Kaplan *et al.* (2020), transfer of skills to real-world environments is certainly possible with VR but, based on their generalisation, no more or less reliable than by using traditional learning methods. To provide a specific example, Eldred-Evans *et al.* (2013) carried out a study comparing the development of real-world skills in laparoscopic surgery between 4 groups.

The groups:

1. Basic instruction along with the opportunity to practice on a "box trainer."
2. Basic instruction along with the opportunity to practice on a VR simulator.
3. Basic instruction along with instruction in mental visualisation techniques.
4. Only the basic instruction with no other opportunity to practice.

It should be noted that the VR simulator was not modern VR but in fact a 2D screen with responsive haptic controls – called a CAE Healthcare VR lap simulator. Despite this, the results are interesting. Groups 1 to 3, who received the additional training, all improved ahead of group 4. However, the level of improvement in all groups was similar. This suggests that in this instance, mental training and visualisation were potentially as effective as VR when used in support of traditional teaching. It may also be more cost effective given the hardware, software and training required to set up VR learning. Only when tested on the VR simulator did the VR group excel, suggesting, according to Eldred-Evans *et al.* (2013), that their learned skills required some additional step, or additional practice, to transfer to the real-world. In other words, the VR group got 'good at the game' more than they learned real world skills.

Participants and users of VR often comment on the realism or fidelity of the VR experience. For example, participants in Real *et al.* (2017) agreed that the VR experience captured the look and feel of a clinical environment and Chae *et al.* (2023) consulted with stakeholders to make the digital avatar interactions as realistic as possible. An instinctive understanding of VR teaching and learning would suggest that the greater the fidelity the

greater chance that learned skills will transfer to the real-world. The extent to which simulation fidelity contributes to the effectiveness of modern VR as a learning tool is still unclear from the body of available research. According to Jensen and Konradsen (2018) the effectiveness of VR in the acquisition of psychomotor skills seems to be greatly influenced by the fidelity of the experience. Fidelity, in the case of psychomotor skills, means that the simulation includes realistic physical sensations facilitating the transfer to real-world action (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). Physical fidelity (Kluwer, 2018), therefore, relies on interactive devices that are peripheral to the HMD (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). These include things like haptic devices, force feedback devices and optical hand tracking. Optical hand tracking has been a familiar part of consumer VR devices since 2016, however, modern consumer VR typically provides no force feedback or haptic response other than pushing buttons.

When considering simulated training for nursing students, Kluwer (2018) suggested that different degrees of fidelity are suitable for different learning strategies. Low fidelity simulations are suitable for the acquisition of knowledge, and medium fidelity suitable for improving competence through increasing realism. Finally, high fidelity simulations are most suitable for testing performance in action. Also, in addition to physical fidelity, conceptual fidelity (*Does the scenario make sense?*) and emotional fidelity (*Does the task feel real?*) are important to the user experience (Kluwer, 2018). Ragan *et al.* (2015) concluded that when attempting to simulate a visually and socially complex environment, visual realism and simulation fidelity were essential to an effective learning process. Their study examined the importance of simulation fidelity when training visual scanning techniques to allow security personnel to identify armed persons in a crowd. Their study used VR by the modern definition but found that, like Evans *et al.* (2013), learners often improved at 'playing' the simulation but required additional training to transfer learned skills to the real-world.

One important consideration that both Jensen and Konradsen (2018) and Kaplan *et al.* (2020) fail to fully address is *how* people learn in a VR environment. Both reviews group the studies that they examine according to the category of skills learned. However, neither review considers the pedagogical approaches which are employed in VR learning. In Chapter 2, the general categories of pedagogical approach were outlined, categorised either by *type* of learning or by the *focus* of the learning approach. It is rarely clear how

these different pedagogical approaches are best applied to the details of a physical learning environment. This is no less true in VR. In fact, when researching the potential of teaching and learning in VR, the approach taken by researchers to the pedagogical design of the VR experience is 1) to give the environment as much physical fidelity as possible (Roy, Bakr and George, 2017), 2) to give the environment as much conceptual fidelity as possible (Real *et al.*, 2017), and 3) to allow the user to learn by repetition and experience (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). There are some researchers who take a constructivist approach to learning in VR, for example Chae *et al.* (2023), however, further research is required to determine what the most successful pedagogical approach, or more likely approaches, are when designing and using VR experiences for teaching and learning.

3.2.1. Skills and Empathy

Kaplan *et al.* (2020) meta-analysis suggested that XR was most effective when transferring psychomotor skills in spatial or procedural tasks involving the three-dimensional environment. They found that the transfer of cognitive skills to real-world situations to be less effective. Similarly, Jensen and Konradsen (2018) found that the only study where VR clearly outperformed the others was in one where the skills acquired related to the space and layout of the virtual environment. This suggests that VR may have potential in teaching classroom layout and organisation. However, both analyses were limited by the few studies available to draw upon along with the large variation of results between studies. Kaplan *et al.* (2020) did not examine any studies which involved teaching affective skill sets or training in socially complex environments like a classroom. In contrast, Jensen and Konradsen (2018) suggested that modern VR has the most potential to be effective when applied the acquisition of an affective skills or social interactions. There is very little in their own study to support this assertion apart from the ability of VR to cause an emotional response in the user but this cannot be supported by the findings of Jensen and Konradsen (2018) or Kaplan *et al.* (2020). Further research is required to determine the effectiveness of VR teaching and learning when applies to affective skillsets in environments which are socially complex.

As with the other types of skills acquisition described above, it is unclear how consistently useful VR is as a training tool for affective skills and to what extent the skills acquired are applicable outside of the simulation. The potential for VR to be useful in learning complex social skills is in part supported by the recent fad of referring to VR as

an ‘empathy machine’ (Bevan *et al.*, 2019). Several researchers are currently attempting to test that assertion.

Many researchers have explored the potential of VR to elicit empathy, however, the results of the research are ambiguous and the value of VR in this capacity remains the subject of debate. The assumed utility of VR to create feelings of empathy or “perspective taking” (Ventura *et al.*, 2020) is based on the ability of immersive technology to allow the user to literally “see” from another’s perspective in an environment that generates a sense of presence. This phenomenon has been studied in fields as diverse as museums (Grotenhoff, 2021), bullying prevention (Ingram *et al.*, 2019), living with dementia (Adefila, Graham and Clouder, 2016), communication therapy (Kim and Chang, 2020) and pornography (Dekker *et al.*, 2021). Many researchers feel that the ability to generate empathy or allow perspective taking, is the most important aspect of modern VR (Bertrand *et al.*, 2018). However, some research suggests that the status of VR as an ‘empathy machine’ may have been overstated. Ventura *et al.* (2020) carried out a meta-analysis of existing research on the use of VR as a medium to elicit empathy. Their analysis of 7 studies found there was a small and not statistically significant change in participants with regards to empathy, but a moderate and significant change with regards to perspective taking. This suggested that the ability of VR to elicit empathy may not be as reliable as some researchers imply.

Other researchers have argued that using VR to create empathy is unethical, a form of forced perspective taking based on a social or political agenda (Schlembach and Clewer, 2021). Ramirez *et al.* (2021) argued that using VR to create empathy is unethical because it is based on the deception that you are experiencing the world as someone else. Lara and Rueda (2021) in turn have argued that there is legitimate difference between “being someone else” and “feeling like someone else”. Clearly the value of VR as an ‘empathy machine’ remains the subject of research. Researching the ability of VR to elicit empathy is not explicitly a part of this PhD. However, it is peripherally related to the potential for using VR in teacher education. Recent studies by Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) have explored the potential for VR to generate an emphatic response in teachers witnessing a simulated bullying incident. The potential for a preservice teacher to use VR to “see” the classroom from the perspective of a pupil is something that will be discussed later in this chapter.

3.2.2. *Limitations, Problems and Challenges*

Limitations exist in the application of VR as a tool for teaching and learning. There are clear inequalities and inconsistencies in the application of VR and its effects. These inequalities must be acknowledged when planning further studies. If not carefully addressed, they could result in different experiences between individual users and therefore a very low reliability for the intended results. For example, one inequality in the application of VR is in the negative physiological reaction that some users have (Kaufeld *et al.*, 2022). Most commonly this takes the form of nausea or motion sickness and sometimes vertigo (Recenti *et al.*, 2021). The extent to which this is a problem is difficult to assess because factors such as the type of VR experience, the user's familiarity with 3D simulations (like computer games) or the age of the participants can all affect the likelihood that participants will feel discomfort (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). The consistent factors that cause "cybersickness" are not well understood. Recent studies have examined the relationship between cybersickness and factors such as motion control (Venkatakrishnan *et al.*, 2020), head movement (Serge and Fragomeni, 2017), posture (Pohlmann *et al.*, 2020), and brain injury (Murphy *et al.*, 2009). The potential for cybersickness should be considered when designing any VR experience in to balance the fidelity of the simulation with accessibility and comfort.

The application of VR to teaching and learning can also create social challenges based on how users interact in VR. Some users can feel unsafe or bored because they appear alone in the VR experience (Reiners, Wood and Gregory, 2014). VR is often a definitively personal experience where users are shut away in their own personal reality. However, with the existence of modern wireless networking, VR can also be a shared experience like any online shared environment. This has additional challenges. For example, because VR allows users to "inhabit" a virtual body there is the potential for physical harassment in shared VR experiences. This has been reported in games where users complained that they were being touched inappropriately while playing the equivalent of handball in zero gravity (Reddit., 2017). It has also been reported in shared social spaces where users felt uncomfortable or intimidated by the behaviour of others (MIT Technology Review., 2021). This negative behaviour is a consideration for people who build, maintain and use VR experiences. Users can also feel vulnerable while using

VR as they become closed off from the real world. These ethical considerations should form part of any research design involving VR. The effect of these feelings of physical or mental threat is that it reduces the user's positive feelings about the VR experience, reduces or removes their sense of presence and consequentially reduces the effectiveness of the VR experience as a learning tool (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018).

The subjective nature of the VR experience adds to the difficulty of creating consistent experiences for every user. This is made more complex by the speed of advancing technology, making it difficult for the development of teaching software to keep up with advances in the available hardware (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). Creators of VR experiences have typically been engineers or computer scientists because the creation of such experiences required a high level of technical knowledge (Jerard, 2016). Jensen and Konradsen (2018) highlighted this as a potential reason for the underrepresentation of VR as a tool for education in non-technical fields such as social sciences and humanities. The accessibility of the creative software required to make VR experiences continues to improve, however, at time of writing, it still requires proficiency in computing and programming knowledge beyond the experience of most educators. For this reason, educators who are intent on using VR are forced to rely on experiences created by VR specialists. Therefore, an important element of future research should be to improve ways of co-designing VR experience in cooperation with stakeholders. For example, the adoption of a design framework that facilitates interactive input from stakeholders would allow the inclusion of relevant and specialist knowledge in the VR design process (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b).

There is a range of VR hardware available. Selecting hardware to use for a particular educational scenario is therefore significant. Jensen and Konradsen (2018) point out that VR hardware, mostly consumer level HMDs, are primarily designed for entertainment and not for education. This means they are complex to operate and designed to provide a multitude of experiences. This contrasts with other more traditionally defined virtual devices for teaching and learning such as flight simulators and dental simulators (Roy, Bakr and George, 2017). These often rely on haptic devices for user interaction and are purpose build for education, usually for training only a few specific tasks. Although the cost of the hardware is consistently reducing, the price is not trivial particularly when considering the requirement for additional training. In addition,

the cost of software (VR apps and experiences) remains prohibitively high, particularly when those experiences are the kind of specialist content required by education providers (Raque *et al.*, 2015). For example, Wang *et al.* (2018) found that the CAVE system used in Civil Engineering Education and Training (CEET), although effective, were prohibitively expensive. However, they also point out that the use of VR in operational task training can be cost saving in terms of equipment rental, fuel costs and safety considerations. It is, therefore, important to consider the choice of VR hardware used for educational experiences. The choice of which hardware to apply will be an important element of this PhD.

The introduction of modern VR to mainstream education remains technically challenging and prohibitively expensive. Cheaper and more accessible technology, like mobile VR and 360° videos, reduces the level of immersion, the sense of presence and therefore the potential value of the learning experience (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). Not to mention the fact that mobile VR is no longer being supported by major developers (Robertson, 2019; Mehrotra, 2021). Ragan *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that fidelity in the simulation can be an important factor in the effectiveness of the learning process. They also demonstrated that achieving that fidelity was a complex task involving specialist technical skills as well as a deep understanding of the real-world template. Therefore, at time of writing, educators are faced with a choice between the time and expense of creating an effective simulation or using a cheaper less effective alternative which, according to the research (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018; Kaplan *et al.*, 2020; Eldred-Evans *et al.*, 2013), may not be consistently better than traditional teaching methods. The complexity of creating and researching VR learning experiences means that generalisation is difficult. The remainder of this review will now focus on the use of VR in teacher education.

3.3. Virtual Reality in Teacher Education

Of primary interest to this PhD, is the potential for VR in teacher education. However, application of VR to professional situations that are emotionally rich and socially complex, such as a classroom environment, remains limited (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2018). Several studies have considered its use in teacher education, including recent work by O'Connor (2010), Dieker *et al.* (2013), and multiple studies by Stavroulia

and colleagues (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2017; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016a; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016b; Stavroulia, 2015; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2015; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2014; Stepan *et al.*, 2017). As demonstrated in Part 1 of this literature review (Chapter 2), organising and managing a classroom is a complex task involving factors that are social, physical and pedagogical. ITE students often struggle to cope with complex classroom interactions during teaching practice, resulting in difficulty managing lesson transitions and motivating pupils (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). Part 1 of this literature review (Chapter 2) identified that ITE students may not have experienced sufficient practice in classrooms, or experimentation with scenarios in realistic settings (Caena, 2014). This is where VR could provide opportunities to experience, repeat, rehearse and debrief teaching scenarios that would otherwise be difficult to replicate in real life. Importantly, it provides a space for experimentation and learning with minimal risk to pupils (Dieker *et al.*, 2013). It also provides trainee teachers with experience of using VR, enabling them to integrate this within their teaching. If it were demonstrated to be of practical value, these are the potential benefits to using VR as a learning tool for ITE students.

Dieker *et al.* (2013) undertook a study which explored the progress of the use of simulated environments in teacher education. This study makes several important insights while at the same time having several significant limitations. First, they concluded that simulated environments allowed teacher training to be carried out in “contextually meaningful settings.” They looked at three different simulated environments in teacher education and attempted to assess the benefits and potential of each. The first simulation was an online environment where the instructor provided coaching and rapid feedback. The second was ‘Second Life’, where the learner made use of interactive desktop learning environments. The third was a purpose build system called TLE TeachLivE™, produced by the University of Central Florida (UCF). The TLE TeachLivE™ simulator was described as “a mixed-reality, avatar-based simulation environment.” Dieker *et al.*’s (2013) study took place immediately before the explosion of consumer accessible VR headsets and so their description of VR and the language used is often archaic. However, they do point out approaches to traditional VR learning and some gaps in the literature that are significant for this PhD.

Dieker *et al.* (2013) proposed three fundamental factors that they believe are necessary for simulated environments to be effective. These are (i) personalized learning, (ii) suspension of disbelief and (iii) cyclical procedures to reinforce the learning process. They also state that for simulated teacher training environments to be useful they must define the specific target teacher behaviours being addressed. When discussing personalized learning it is difficult to know whether Dieker *et al.* (2013) were referring to learning targeted at particular individuals, or learning targeted at particular teaching behaviours. They discuss both. With regards to targeted learning, Dieker *et al.* (2013) state that to be effective in teacher education it is necessary to specifically identify the teaching behaviours to be addressed in virtual environments, the ultimate aim being to improve pupils learning outcomes. This echoes the comments made by Jensen and Konradsen (2018) suggesting that VR teaching experiences must be designed for *specific* learning outcomes. However, this is too simplified a view of teacher education. It is debatable that the ultimate aim of teaching is to improve pupils learning outcomes because this ignores the need for socialisation and welfare as discussed in part 1 of the literature review (Chapter 2) (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). Although researchers agree that VR research should be targeted at appropriate learning outcomes, it remains uncertain what those outcomes are. As previously highlighted, there is also need for further research into what pedagogical approaches are best suited to a VR environment.

Dieker *et al.* (2013) were limited by the technology available at the time. Of the three simulated environments discussed the first two were desktop environments and only the third attempted to create a kind of immersive simulation. The TLE TeachLivE™ simulator projected a simulated classroom onto a wall screen and tracked the user's movements using optical tracking camera like a Microsoft Kinect. This could be considered a simplified version of the CAVE systems mentioned above. Dieker *et al.* (2013) emphasised that "suspension of disbelief" is essential to the effectiveness of the learning process. Implying that the more immersive TLE TeachLivE™ simulator generated a greater sense of presence and was therefore a more effective learning tool than the desktop environments. However, they provided very little evidence to support this. Each of the three simulated scenarios they described explored different learning outcomes related to different aspects of teaching, such as classroom management, behaviour management and additional support needs. For this reason, it is difficult to compare effectiveness

between platforms. In only one case do they provide evidence that the skills from the simulated environment transferred to the real-world and that outcome was focused on procedural instructions rather than complex social interactions. Further research is required to assess the effectiveness of VR for teacher education when the learning outcomes involve complex social interactions and not procedural tasks. In addition, it is unclear, based on Dieker *et al.* (2013), if greater immersion correlates with better learning outcomes.

It is unclear why “suspension of disbelief” is necessary or even of benefit in the training of each of these tasks. It is apparent while reading Dieker *et al.* (2013) that the continually evolving language of VR is in its early stages throughout their study. They refer to each of their three simulations as immersive environments, but all would currently count as low immersion environments, and none would meet the definition of modern VR. In addition, they appear to use the terms “suspension of disbelief” and “presence” interchangeably. This is misleading. Presence, as discussed above, is the subjective feeling that you are reacting to the virtual environment as if it is real. The increased sense of presence is believed to be an essential component in the effectiveness of certain types of VR learning (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). Conversely, suspension of disbelief is the deliberate avoidance of critical analysis when examining something which is unreal or impossible. Suspension of disbelief relates the VR learning experience to something like entertainment, which is examined without critical thinking. This is a misrepresentation of VR learning. The strength of modern VR systems is that the user can feel present in the virtual environment (Chae *et al.*, 2023), can interact with that environment and can retain critical faculties to analyse and understand (Howie, 2022).

When learning in a simulated environment, Dieker *et al.* (2013) suggest the Action Review Cycle (ARC) as an appropriate model for learning in simulated environment (Parry, Pires and Sparkes-Guber, 2007). This is one of the few examples of researchers suggesting a pedagogical approach suitable for VR learning. ARC is a processual approach to learning which has its origins in military applications. The typical structure would be to undertake a Before Action Review (BAR) that identifies the intended learning outcomes. This would be followed by participation in the actual simulation. The final stage is an After-Action Report (AAR), where the difference between the intended learning outcome and the actual experience is examined. The process is intended to be repeated multiple times

according to the needs of the learner. ARC provides an opportunity for self-reflection but also to interact with instructors and other learners (Dieker *et al.*, 2013). This approach used with virtual environments creates a person-centred learning platform adaptable to individual learning styles and suitable for self-directed student-centred learning. Dieker *et al.* (2013) therefore provide a potential model for the effective use of VR as a teaching and learning tool. This is similar to the approach taken by Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) which envisaged the VR learning process as a cycle of experimentation, practice and reflection. Unfortunately, based on the information provided by Dieker *et al.* (2013) it is not possible to determine how effectively the skills learned in VR transfer to the real-world. Similarly, both Stavroulia *et al.* (2014). and Stavroulia *et al.* (2015) did not provide evidence transfer of skills to the real world.

The effective transfer of teaching skills or classroom skills from VR simulations to real world environments requires further research. Dieker *et al.* (2013) suggested that VR could be used to provide micro-teaching experiences, and practice teaching, in simulated environments to reinforce college lessons without the need for actual classrooms. They hypothesised that the application of virtual environments to teacher education would improve teachers' pedagogical and content knowledge and further, that pupils will learn more from teachers who've been exposed to virtual environments (Dieker *et al.*, 2013). Neither of these ideas is supported by the evidence provided. Although participants using virtual environments report positive outcomes, it is unclear how this translates to real-world environments. In addition, the long-term effect on students is, at best, speculation based on the feedback from participants and not supported by any study. Consumer VR has simply not existed for long enough to demonstrate what effect, if any, its inclusion in teacher education would have on the pupils in primary and secondary schools. So, how effective is VR as a teaching and learning tool for preservice teachers? Since the explosion of consumer priced VR several researchers are addressing this gap in the research.

Stavroulia and colleagues have written several papers exploring the use of simulations within teacher education (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016b; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2015; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2014; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b). These simulations typically involve providing experiences of a specific teaching scenario or environment and allowing the learner to experience that scenario repeatedly and from multiple perspectives. Usually, these simulations also have an intended learning outcome. Their work often focuses on

the emotional experience of working in a classroom environment (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2015), ultimately aiming to improve empathy shared from teachers to pupils (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b). Stavroulia and colleagues address the potential for VR to be used in social and emotionally complex environment such as classrooms. This is directly relevant to this PhD.

Stavroulia *et al.* (2014) demonstrated the potential for using desktop-based 3D environments to promote discussion and reflection on pedagogical approaches and improve teaching skills. Their study used *simSchool*, a first-person classroom simulation which presented various scenarios and allowed the learner/teacher to re-position around the simulated environment, interact with pupils and assess their teaching requirements. Although this was based on a desktop and not modern VR, Stavroulia *et al.* (2014) did provide evidence that simulated environments were a potentially useful learning tool for teachers by provoking discussion with peers, allowing repetition of specific scenarios and facilitating interaction with tutors. Using *simSchool* and using preservice teachers from two different higher education institutions in Greece, Stavroulia *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that participation in simulations as part of the learning process provoked both positive and negative emotions in learners. These studies were limited by the fact that they relied on participants self-reported impressions of the effect of the simulation on their training. In addition, it was unclear what aspects of the simulation (fidelity, immersion, presence) had a positive or negative effect on participants. Future studies of this kind would benefit from detailed feedback from participants regarding the design of the simulated environment and how it effects the learning process. For example, Amini *et al.* (2021) used VR to train dental students, and included measures of empathy, cognitive knowledge, affective knowledge and skill-based knowledge. This allowed a more complete picture of the effect of the training.

In a 2016 study, Stavroulia *et al.* investigated the potential for VR to act as a training tool to assist teachers in identifying incidents of bullying in a simulated classroom. The existence of this study is particularly significant in understanding the potential application of VR to teacher education. Their study of “A 3D Virtual Environment for Training Teachers to Identify Bullying” (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016b) has several attributes significant to this PhD. First, Stavroulia *et al.* (2016b) dealt with the application of VR to teacher education. Second, their study was based around the use of modern VR headsets, specifically the Oculus Rift (see Figure 3.4). Third, their study involved creation of multiple

immersive 360° 3D classrooms environments that facilitated experiences of complex social situations. Finally, Stavroulia *et al.* (2016b) attempted, within the limitations of their study, to compare user behaviour in the simulation to their real-world experience.

Stavroulia *et al.* (2016b) built and tested a VR application that could be used for training teachers. The application simulated several different classroom environments, used motion tracking to create realistic simulated students, and allowed the learner to experience an incident of bullying. They used eye tracking technology to facilitate user interaction with the environment and compared the behaviour of teachers in the study with their predicted behaviour based on real-world experience. Participants were asked to gauge their own experience of bullying in real-world classrooms. Most of the participants highly rated their ability to recognise and deal with bullying incidents based on working experience. Participants were also asked to assess the fidelity of the simulation, their own sense of presence and its application in teacher education with reference to the skills learned.

Participants' overall response to the VR simulation was that it did not improve their skills, mainly due to their existing high level of teaching experience and their daily experiences of dealing with bullying incidents (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016b). Participants did rate highly the fidelity of the VR simulation and suggested that less experienced teachers could learn more. However, most participants failed to recognise bullying behaviour in some of the simulations and often their chosen response was contrary to the established bullying guidelines. Stavroulia *et al.* (2016b) suggested this indicates the potential to train even experienced teachers or that participants' behaviour became modified when confronted with "new" pupils.

Overall, Stavroulia *et al.*'s (2016b) findings support the idea that VR can provide a classroom environment with sufficient fidelity to support training in complex social interactions. They also emphasised the importance of realism in the simulated environment and of tailoring the simulation to meet the needs of individual learners. Although Stavroulia *et al.* (2016b) attempted to assess the real-world application of the skills learned in VR, their data is limited to the subjective opinions of the participants involved. Further study would be required, perhaps with participants of lesser teaching experience, to assess the transfer of skills to real classrooms.

More recent studies assess the potential for VR to facilitate reflection and build empathy in teachers witnessing incidents of bullying. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) use VR environments in the form of simulated classrooms to allow the participants to experience a bullying incident from two different perspectives: (i) that of the teacher, and (ii) that of the pupil. This study was conducted using modern VR HMDs in the form of HTC VIVE (Figure 3.6). The VR environments were built using the Unity3D engine. Unlike previous studies that allowed the user to reposition around a desktop environment, this study uses the physical properties of VR and sense of presence to allow the user to ‘see’ from the perspective of another. Participants were split into a control group, who experienced and acted out incident of bullying in a real classroom, and the VR group who experienced the same incident of bullying conducted by simulated pupils in two virtual environments. Participants were then required to complete a questionnaire measuring their reflection and empathy based on the scenario they experienced.

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Figure 3.6: HTC VIVE (Source: www.vive.com)

Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) undertook an exhaustive and structured process to design the VR environments. This process was based on the Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation (ADDIE) model (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). This involved literature review, survey and interviews with in-practice teachers to ensure that the virtual experience resembled the experiences of teachers in the real-world. This background research was also carried out to identify the teacher competencies that would be addressed in the simulated environments. Finally, in-practice teachers were consulted

about the layout and design of the virtual classrooms. This resulted in a second classroom of a futuristic design, being added by request of those teachers who did not wish to learn in an environment identical to their work environment. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) found that a VR experience too complex or fanciful can distract the user from the assigned task.

Stavroulia and Lanitis's (2019b) approach to VR development allowed them to achieve a high level of fidelity in their design and facilitate a sense of presence in the virtual environment. It also allowed them to focus on a very specific scenario and learning outcomes, building on the previous VR research. Any future research, including this PhD, should emphasise cooperation and participatory design with stakeholders to achieve suitable fidelity in the simulation.

Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) demonstrated that participants who took part in the control group showed lower scores in both reflection and empathy than the VR group. The control group was generally less enthusiastic about the training experience and less convinced of its overall value. This suggested that the VR environments were more effective at engaging participants than the real-world scenario. VR was more effective in building feelings of empathy particularly because it was possible to place the participant in the position of the pupil being bullied. These results demonstrate the potential for VR to allow preservice teachers to engage with and review relevant teaching scenarios. However, the results are based solely on self-reporting by the participants. It appears that participants were given the questionnaire only after the teaching scenario and so the idea that the experience changed their opinion or increased their empathy is entirely the view of the participants themselves. In addition, there are several differences in experience between the VR group and the control group. It is unclear if the control group made any effort to experience the scenario from the pupil's perspective. The VR groups experienced two identical scenarios in different environments (one realistic and one futuristic). This was not emulated by the experience of the control group. Therefore, the novelty and additional training provided to the VR group may simply have provided more opportunity for reflection and a generally more interesting experience for the participants. Future studies which compare training in VR to real-world experiences should attempt to account for the novelty of VR and more accurately balance the experience between groups. It is

therefore important to build on the experience of Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) when developing future VR studies.

3.4. Summary of Key Findings

VR is a combination of hardware and software that creates an immersive user experience. These experiences have been successfully used as learning tools in different disciplines. VR provides an opportunity to repeat complex, dangerous or inaccessible tasks in a risk-free environment. There is potential for using VR as a learning tool for teaching affective skillsets in complex social situation such as classrooms, however, this potential is relatively untested in research literature. What the literature does suggest is that, depending on the intended outcomes, VR relies on a sense of presence, an increased level of immersion and fidelity in the simulated environment. In addition, the physical component of a VR experience is often as important to the sense of immersion as the visual component.

The complex nature of VR means that any assessment of its effectiveness as a tool for teaching and learning is best done by examining specific VR experiences targeted at specific audiences with specific learning outcomes. Most studies suggest that VR should be used in support of traditional teaching methods and not as a replacement to them. Although several studies have investigated the potential benefit of using VR in teacher education, the application of this research is in its infancy. The key findings to date suggest that VR has the potential to enhance the preservice teacher experience. This would most likely involve the careful design and building of VR experiences. Teachers and educators should participate in the design process. Such experiences would require several fundamental components including a sense of presence, opportunities for reflection, and a cyclic process of repetition and feedback. VR can engage users with its simulated physical environment, suggesting that VR could be a suitable learning tool for complex social situations such as organising and managing classrooms.

3.4.1. What's next?

Part 1 of this literature review (Chapter 2) explored the importance of learning environments, and how the physical characteristics affect pupils' learning experience and teachers approach to the organisation and management of classrooms. This chapter explored the history of VR, reviewed the research exploring its use in teaching and learning and its potential applications for teacher education. Both chapters critiqued the

current evidence base and highlighted several research gaps. Chapter 4 will outline the aims and research questions of this PhD and provide an overview of the methodology.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

4.1. Introduction

Chapters 2 and 3 highlighted the potential of VR as a teaching tool to improve how preservice teachers organise and manage their classrooms. These findings informed the aims, research questions and methodology of this PhD. The purpose of *this* chapter is to present the study aim and research questions. This chapter will also describe the overarching methodology and how this PhD's individual studies interlink to produce meaningful outcomes.

Firstly, the aim and research questions will be presented, and the overarching methodology will be described and justified alongside its strengths and limitations. The structure of the PhD has been built around the ADDIE Design Framework. This will be introduced, with an explanation of how it was applied (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). The four individual studies forming the PhD will be briefly summarised, alongside an illustration of how they link together. Overall ethical considerations for this PhD will be discussed. Finally, a summary of how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted this research will be presented.

4.2. Aim and Research Questions

The overall PhD aim was to investigate the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in Initial Teacher Education (ITE). It specifically explored the potential use of VR and 360° video in ITE for the organisation and management of classrooms. This overall aim was achieved by addressing the following five research questions:

Research Question 1: What factors influence how teachers organise and manage their learning environment?

- *This research question was addressed across one study:*
 - *Study 1 used semi-structured interviews to investigate factors that influence how working teachers organise and manage their classrooms (Chapter 5).*

Research Question 2: Can 360° video be used effectively as a medium for teaching and learning?

- *This research question was addressed across one study:*
 - *Study 2 explored feedback from participants on the use of 360 video in simulating a classroom environment (Chapter 6).*

Research Question 3: Can VR be used to learn affective skill sets in a professional or vocational environment?

- *This research question was addressed across one study:*
 - *Study 3 presented the findings of a systematic review on the application of VR to education in those fields which are socially or emotionally complex (Chapter 7).*

Research Question 4: What is best practice for using VR and 360° video to simulate classroom environments within Initial Teacher Education?

- *This research question was addressed across three studies:*
 - *Study 2 and 3 (as detailed above)*
 - *Study 4 used a multi-methods approach to evaluate participant experiences of different classroom layouts depicted in simulated VR environments using a head mounted display (HMD) (Chapters 8 and 9).*

Research Question 5: Can VR provide a medium for professional development for preservice teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?

- *This research question was addressed across one study:*
 - *Study 4 as described above.*

An overview of studies 1-4 are provided later in this chapter. Detailed methods for each study are provided in their relevant chapters (Chapters 5-9).

4.3. Epistemological Framework

Epistemology, ontology and axiology are key concepts considered in the decision-making for research studies (Rehman and Alharthi, 2016). Broadly, they refer to the **how**, the **what** and the **why** of research. A researcher's epistemological stance guides and influences the conduct of their research (Robson and McCartan, 2016). There are three key epistemological research positions: objectivism; constructivism; and subjectivism.

- **Objectivism** is about discovering the objective truth and sits with the positive theoretical perspective (Rehman and Alharthi, 2016). Positivist research is quantitative in nature and focuses on scientific enquiry and objectivity (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Using deductive logic, it tests pre-existing hypotheses (Bryman, 2016).
- **Constructivism** is concerned with how humans interact with the world and aligns with the theoretical perspective of **interpretivism** (Gray, 2021). The underlying idea of the interpretivist approach is that the researcher is part of the research, interprets data and as such can never be fully objective and removed from the research. Interpretivist methodologies are typically qualitative and inductive, exploring the understanding of situations rather than direct associations and relationships (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).
- **Subjectivism** holds assumptions of humanities and arts, proclaiming that social reality is made from the perceptions and actions of social actors (people). It refers to situations where subjects construct meaning from dreams and religious beliefs, and aligns with the 'becoming' ontology (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This stance directly opposes objectivism (Gray, 2021).

This PhD aimed to explore the use of VR within ITE. A key priority was to *understand* if and how VR could support preservice teachers to learn about classroom organisation and management. This research, therefore, took a constructivist and interpretivist approach. This choice guided a predominantly qualitative exploration of the research questions. Exploratory studies are particularly useful when little is known about a phenomenon, as is the case for this PhD. Saunders *et al.* (2019) suggest exploratory studies can be conducted by searching the literature, engaging with experts in the field, and conducting

interviews for related viewpoints and experiences. The remainder of this chapter will outline how these steps have been incorporated throughout this PhD.

4.4. Overarching Research Approach

This PhD took a pragmatic multi-methods approach incorporating a sequential exploratory research design (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Multi-methods is defined as two or more studies that use different methods to address either the same research question, or parts of a research question (Morse and Cheek, 2015). Methods can be used in parallel or in sequence, with data being integrated at an appropriate point in the research process (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007). The advantage of a multi-methods approach is that when integrated, the data from one study may be used to enhance or explain results of another study in the same project (Morse and Cheek, 2015). This PhD aligned with a multi-methods approach because it used multiple methods across four individual studies, with each study undertaken in sequence. Data ultimately inform the design of the final study.

The sequential exploratory design is suitable for a multi-methods approach because it adapts to the results of each study (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). In a sequential exploratory study, the research initially focuses on qualitative data to inform the design of later elements of the project. The final element of the project should contain a component of quantitative data collection (Fetters, Curry and Creswell, 2013). Typically, the multi-methods approach applied to sequential exploratory research has an inductive theoretical drive (Morse, 2015). This was the case for this PhD, with the exception of one small component that used a deductive analysis.

Although multi-methods, this PhD had an emphasis on qualitative analysis, driven by the subject matter and in response to study adaptations required during the COVID-19 lockdown. This PhD had a strong focus on stakeholder participation in the design and critical assessment of simulated classroom environments. This design process aligned with the ADDIE design framework (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b), and is described in detail below.

Several alternative approaches to addressing the research questions were possible. It is not the intention here to discuss every possible alternative. Two of them will be briefly mentioned along with discussion of their potential benefits and the reasons why

they were rejected for this PhD. One alternative would be to take a longitudinal approach. This would have involved establishing a participant group at the start and maintaining consistent contact with that group throughout the entire PhD. This approach has two key advantages. The first is that it could have allowed the adoption of a co-design iterative framework involving stakeholders at every stage of the process. This will be discussed in greater detail below. The second advantage is that it could have been possible to assess the impact of VR learning on participants over an extended period. Typically, longitudinal studies assess the same group of participants and use continuous or repeated measures (Caruana *et al.*, 2015). Longitudinal studies have been used successfully to assess teaching and learning applications in VR. For example, Hill and Preez (2021) gathered data from 566 students over an academic year, applying the Technology Acceptance Model and the Educational Framework from Immersive Learning, to assess the students' acceptance of VR interventions during the module. Similarly, Haber *et al.* (2023) assessed the value of VR in management training as an alternative to traditional video training. Both studies reported positive results for the using of VR in training. However, both studies are examples of including VR as part of an existing and established training programme. This PhD has adopted an exploratory research design specifically because there is no consistently established method of teaching classroom organisation and management in ITE (see Chapter 2). An exploratory research design allows the study to be flexible, to adapt to the results of each stage. There is less opportunity for flexibility and reorganisation in a longitudinal study (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Ultimately, the longitudinal approach would not have been possible due to the impact of COVID-19 restrictions (discussed in detail at the end of this chapter).

Another alternative approach would be to compare the application of VR for teaching and learning in ITE to another alternative method of instruction or to more traditional teaching methods. This approach has been adopted by several studies where an established approach to teaching a particular set of skills already exists. For example, Haber *et al.* (2023), compared VR to video teaching platforms. Eldred-Evans *et al.* (2013) compared the results of VR training to two alternative approaches alongside a control group who received only basic training in laparoscopic surgery. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) compared a VR teaching experience to live actors playing out the same scenario in the real-world. Although these studies usefully compare learning in VR with other

methods, this approach was not adopted for this PhD. Cook (2005) suggested that comparing two different methods was of limited value and that comparisons within a single medium were more meaningful. However, there is a need for research to examine the difference between teaching and learning in VR and more traditional methods (see Chapter 3). There is also no consistently established method of teaching the skills of classroom organisation and management in ITE (see Chapter 2). Finally, it had been the original intention of this PhD to compare the medium of VR with the medium of 360° videos for teaching and learning in ITE. However, COVID-19 restrictions prevented 360° videos being used in the final stages this PhD (with the exception of Study 2, Chapter 6). The work carried out using 360° videos did provide valuable insight into the design of the VR experience used in Study 4.

4.5. Design Framework

The ADDIE framework was used to design and conduct this PhD. This is one of the most widely used and flexible approaches for modelling an interactive design process (Allen, 2006). ADDIE (**A**nalysis, **D**esign, **D**evelopment, **I**mplementation and **E**valuation) is a continually evolving process which has been adapted from military training programmes created during the Second World War. The original versions of the process followed a rigid structure and focused on a behavioural pattern of learning (Allen, 2006). Later versions of the process, adapted for non-military use, emphasised the interactive nature of the design process and began to favour cognitive learning theory over behavioural approaches (Allen, 2006). Cognitive theory became the more dominant approach as the ADDIE design framework was increasingly applied to non-procedural tasks. All current versions of the model emphasise the iterative nature of the design process and facilitate co-design or participatory design with teachers and learners (Peterson, 2003).

The revised model of ADDIE, described by Allen (2006), emphasises simplicity and flexibility. The ADDIE model is typically described in terms of 5 phases, (analysis, design, development, implementation and evaluation). Allen (2006) describes how the developer (in this case researcher) may enter or re-enter each phase as required based on the scope of the development and the results of ongoing evaluation. The process of evaluation should be a continual part of the process, comparing study outcomes to the research questions, providing feedback at each stage, maintaining the principal of participatory

design and guiding the process (Allen, 2006). This made the ADDIE design framework a suitable structure for this PhD. Analysis, exploration and evaluation have been a part of every individual study in this project, and the results from each inform the design of subsequent work. The idea of placing evaluation as a central and continual part of the design process is demonstrated in Figure 4.1. This figure is adapted from Allen (2006) and illustrates that all phases of the ADDIE design process depend on each other and that the evaluation phase is a continual part of the process.

Another advantage of the ADDIE design framework is that it emphasises a learner centred approach rather than focusing on the instructor (Peterson, 2003). This approach is suitable for developing VR systems that are focused on individual learning experiences. The ADDIE design framework is an iterative process designed to evolve according to the ongoing needs of the project (Peterson, 2003). This conforms to the pragmatic sequential exploratory approach adopted for this thesis. The basis of this process are the 5 phases described above. Each of these phases is intended to have its own distinct value in the design process but the overall structure is intended to be flexible and adaptable to facilitate the desired outcomes (Allen, 2006).

In Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b), the five stages were described as follows. In the **analysis** stage they undertook an investigation of teachers' training needs through literature review and consultations with teachers and experts. Further analysis was undertaken to establish a competency framework and identify those skills which the VR training was intended to enhance. The **design** stage involved the design of the scenarios followed by their **development** using Unity. The final stages involved the **implementation** of the VR system and the **evaluation** of its effectiveness. The outcomes of Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) have been discussed in Chapter 3. There are some significant differences between the study described in Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) and those carried out during this PhD. For example, Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) focused on the ability of VR to generate an empathic response in the user. In addition, they focused on pre-arranged scenarios using animated 3D models and based on the experience of in-practice teachers. The most significant similarity between Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) and this PhD is in the design and building of simulated classrooms, based on real-world classrooms and for the purpose of teacher education.

Figure 4.1: ADDIE design process with evaluation as the central element

This PhD aligns with the ADDIE design framework applied by Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) while tailoring adaptations specifically for this PhD. There are three main reasons for these adaptations. First, and most importantly, the different subject matter and different competencies being examined meant it was necessary to make some changes to how data was collected and analysed. The second reason was that the COVID-19 restrictions meant that many avenues of data collection were not available. For example, it was not permitted to carry out research in schools, and opportunities for face-to-face contact were limited. Lastly, it was the intention of this PhD to place greater emphasis on the process of participatory design of the virtual experiences. For this reason, in-practice teachers, educators and learners were involved in the design process as much as possible (within the constraints of the COVID-19 lockdown).

The results of previous studies involving VR have suggested that there is a greater chance of having a positive effect on the learning outcomes if stakeholders are involved in the design process. For example, DeWitt *et al.* (2022) organised participants to create their own VR learning experiences using an online platform to showcase Chinese cultural norms. One alternative approach for this PhD would have been to adopt a fully realised

co-design framework. This would be similar to the potential longitudinal study previously described. The same groups of participants would have been maintained throughout the PhD and they would have been directly responsible for the design and the development of any VR experience. The co-design approach has been successfully used to build VR experiences for specialist groups. For example, Kim (2020) and Thevin *et al.* (2020) both successfully used a co-design process involving stakeholders in the design of VR systems for visually impaired people. Participatory design was chosen in favour of co-design as being more flexible and allowing the researcher a greater degree of control of the outcomes. Co-design would also have involved the participants having specialist knowledge and understanding of VR systems, how they work on a technical level and how they might be applied to teaching and learning. Although, co-design with teachers or ITE students remains a viable approach, participatory design was more suitable for this PhD.

4.6. Overview of Studies 1 to 4

To address the research questions, four individual studies were conducted:

- **Study 1** involved a series of qualitative interviews to explore factors that influence how working teachers organise and manage their classrooms. A thematic analysis was informed by the work of Braun and Clarke (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Braun and Clarke, 2023) and took an inductive exploratory approach.
- **Study 2** was an exploratory three-phase study using qualitative methods to investigate the potential for using 360° videos as a primary element of this PhD. A deductive approach was taken to the analysis (Jansen, 2010).
- **Study 3** used a systematic review design to explore the application of VR to training and education in non-procedural or non-technical fields. Methods adhered to the PRISMA guidelines (**P**referred **R**eporting **I**tems for **S**ystematic **R**eviews and **M**eta-**A**nalyses) (Moher *et al.*, 2009).
- **Study 4** used a multi-methods approach to evaluate participant experiences of different classroom layouts depicted in VR experiences. Data gathered using the Talk-Aloud method (Ericsson, 2006) and semi-structured interviews, were triangulated with Study 1 data using content analysis.

By applying the ADDIE design framework to this PhD, it was structured in the following way. The review of literature in Chapters 2 and 3, along with Study 1, forms the

analysis stage. The aim of this stage was to gain a better understanding of how teachers use and are taught to use their classrooms. Study 2 and Study 3 were the **design** stage, identifying the most suitable form of extended reality (XR) for this PhD by examining 360° video and virtual reality (VR). The **development** phase of the PhD is explained in detail in Chapter 8. This deals with the practical considerations of creating the simulated VR environment, as well as explaining how the data gathered in Studies 1, 2 and 3 fed into the development process. Finally, Study 4 was the **implementation** and **evaluation** stages where participants took part in and provided feedback on the VR experiences. Figure 4.2 shows the integration of data from each study according to the sequential multi-methods approach and supported by the ADDIE design framework.

4.7. Ethical Considerations

This section will outline the general ethical considerations for the entire PhD. All studies were designed to comply with the British Psychological Society's (BPS) Code of Human Research Ethics (Oates *et al.*, 2021). The specific ethical considerations for each study will be discussed in detail in their relevant chapter. The most important ethical considerations involved the use of VR as an element of conducting research with participants, maintaining participant anonymity, and the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The primary concern when using VR for research with participants is for the participants' safety and comfort. Chapter 3 already discussed that one of the limitations of modern VR is the potential for "cybersickness" (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). This can take the form of vertigo, motion sickness, headaches or dizziness. When gaining their consent, participants were fully informed of this possibility and reminded of their right to withdraw at any time if they felt discomfort. In addition, the VR experiences were designed to minimise the risk of cybersickness. This is something that will be discussed in detail in Chapter 8. Studies were also designed to minimise the continuous time spent by participants in VR experiences by providing regular breaks. Participants safety is also a consideration when using VR in research. To ensure their safety, participants were given appropriate instruction prior to using the VR equipment and the data collection took place in safe locations. Safe locations meant primarily that participants had enough space to move around freely while in VR and a comfortable place to rest in the case of cybersickness.

Figure 4.2: The four studies in this PhD aligned with the sequential multi-methods approach and supported by the ADDIE design framework

Participants were informed of the purpose of each study and the overall aim of the PhD. All participants were informed of their right to withdraw and provided with additional contact information. This conformed with Sections 4 and 6 of the BPS Code of Human Research Ethics (Oates *et al.*, 2021). Another important ethical consideration was to maintain the anonymity of participants. This was in part to allow them to speak more freely around the research topics but also to protect them from any potentially negative feedback resulting from the research being made publicly available. In the initial stages of this project, a further consideration was to maintain the anonymity of schools and pupils in the event that research was undertaken in working classrooms. As a result of the restrictions resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic this was no longer a consideration.

4.8. Impact of the COVID-19 Lockdown

The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the design and delivery of this PhD. The overall aim and research questions did not change, however, the research methods and the studies undertaken changed considerably from what was originally intended. The original intention for this PhD was to evaluate the potential for using 360° videos and VR as tools for teaching and learning in ITE. A proposed study would have included interviews with teachers in their own classroom. Digital photographs and 360° videos would have been taken of the classrooms. These would have been used to inform the development of VR simulations based on the same classrooms (Appendix 4.1). Ethical approval had been received from the UWS Ethics Committee for this study immediately prior to the commencement of the first COVID-19 lockdown (Appendix 4.2). At the same time an ethics application was made to Education Services Research Group (ESRG) of Glasgow City Council. This was refused on the basis that no further research of any kind would be permissible in schools. This remained the case throughout the key data collection timeline of this PhD and beyond. In effect the result of the COVID-19 restrictions was that no research in schools was possible, it was not possible to access classrooms for filming and teachers could not be formally asked to participate in any research. All research processes ceased, both in the University and schools. The initial plan was to pause and wait for schools to reopen. After several months it became apparent this was not feasible.

Discussions were held with the PhD supervision team to explore how the PhD could continue *and* produce meaningful outputs to inform future ITE. The PhD was

redesigned to accommodate the required research within the context of the COVID-19 lockdown. Although a challenging time, the pragmatic and sequential exploratory approach to this PhD meant the studies and their methods *could* be successfully adapted. The challenge remained to align the 'adapted' research with the ADDIE design process and maintain stakeholder engagement in the participatory design of the simulated VR environments. This aspect of the project will be discussed in detail in Chapter 8. Access to suitable filming locations for 360° videos was not possible. In effect this meant that any further use of 360° videos in this PhD was impossible. Study 2 (Chapter 6) remains an important element of this PhD because it helped to inform the design and development of the VR experiences used in Study 4 (Chapters 8 and 9).

4.9. Summary

This chapter has introduced and provided justification for a pragmatic multi-methods approach incorporating a sequential exploratory research design. The overall aim of this PhD was to investigate the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. Specifically, to allow preservice teachers to experience a simulated environment that had the potential to improve their skills in organising and managing their classrooms. The ADDIE Design Framework was applied to the entire research process, providing a flexible, interactive, learner centred design structure focused on repeated evaluation of the results at each stage. The four studies of this PhD were organised around the ADDIE design framework. The overall ethical consideration focused on the difficulties of using the relatively new technology of VR along with due consideration for the safety and anonymity of participants. The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the structure of this project. However, the nature of the pragmatic multi-methods approach and sequential exploratory research design accommodated the necessary adaptations required.

Chapter 5. Study 1: Interviews

Understanding Teachers' Perceptions and use of their Classroom Learning Environment

5.1. Introduction

The aim of this PhD was to investigate the potential for using VR as a teaching and learning tool for Preservice teachers. Specifically, how VR could support their learning around classroom organisation and management. Study 1, along with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3), formed the analysis phase of the ADDIE design framework (Allen, 2006). The analysis phase identifies the requirements of the design process and informs later design choices for studies 2-4. Study 1 aimed to address gaps identified in Chapters 2 and 3 by answering Research Question 1: *What factors influence how teachers organise and manage their learning environment?* This chapter presents the background for this study, the method applied, findings and finally a discussion of the results.

5.2. Background

Chapter 2 demonstrated that the learning environment is a complex system with multiple interacting factors (Barrett *et al.*, 2015). It is the combination of these factors that have influence on the learning experience of students. Teachers face the complex task of organising and managing their classrooms to achieve the desired goals for each lesson (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). It is unclear from the current available research *how* individual teachers approach the organisation and management of their classrooms. Dillon (2018) asserted that teachers should be proactive in their classroom organisation and conscious of how it effects the pupils' experience. However, Dillon (2018) gave only brief consideration of how this should be carried out or what the thought process of teachers should be when carrying it out. Gremmen *et al.* (2016) attempted to understand the thought process behind teachers approaches but focused solely on the arrangement of desks, ignoring significant elements of the wider context.

Barrett *et al.* (2015) demonstrated the advantages of using a holistic conceptual model of the classroom environment. However, Barrett *et al.* (2015)'s model, in an attempt to focus on the mental mechanisms of students, was built around Rolls (2007)

description of the brains implicit systems. This is a robust, generalisable approach, grounded in psychological theory, but requires little if any input from pupils or teachers. Study 1 has built on the work of Barrett *et al.* (2015) to gain a more detailed understanding of what teachers' approach is to classroom organisation and management and what influences their decision making.

Barrett *et al.* (2016) builds on the research of their previous studies and expand the work of the HEAD (Holistic Evidence and Design) Project. The HEAD Project aimed to assess how well the physical environment of schools addressed the needs of teachers and the learning outcomes of pupils. Barrett *et al.*'s next study (2016) explored the teachers' point of view by carrying out interviews and surveys with 222 teachers about their experience working in 193 specific classrooms. This study took place over 29 primary schools in 3 different parts of England.

Interview questions focused on light, temperature, air quality, noise and layout. Barrett *et al.* (2016) found that the results of their interviews aligned well with the results of their previous *quantitative* studies. However, there were discrepancies. For example, teachers generally undervalued natural light. Generally, teachers did not use classrooms as an opportunity to provide pupils with a sense of ownership. Also, teachers did not seem consider the correct degree of visual stimulation in the environment. One interesting result was that teachers generally found the physical environment of older schools more satisfactory than modern buildings (Barrett, Barrett and Zhang, 2016).

Barrett *et al.* (2016) provides a fascinating insight into teachers' attitudes to the physical characteristics of their classroom, particularly when combined with the results from their previous work. However, their study does have some significant limitations. The interview questions, apart from the opening question, were mostly closed questions focused on particular aspects of the physical environment. There was only a brief opportunity for teachers to expand on their own ideas. The analysis of the data collected by Barrett *et al.* (2016) took the form of inductive content analysis which counted the comments made by teachers on different aspects of the physical environment. For example, in 'school 8' with regards to lighting, "dark" was mentioned 2 times, "glare" was mentioned 2 times and whiteboard was mentioned 0 times. This kind of analysis provides a robust and comparable indication of how teachers comment on different aspects of the physical environment. However, this quantitative approach does not include any analysis

of the how or why. *How* do teachers manage the limitations in the physical environment? *Why* do they make the decisions they do? *What* influences how they organised the classroom? Although Barrett *et al.* (2016) claim that the interviews took the form of “informal conversation”, very little of this information is included in the analysis. A qualitative approach, which allowed the teachers to speak at greater length and explore their ideas, would have provided more information about how teachers organise and manage their learning environment. Study 1 will take a qualitative approach to understand how working teachers organise and manage their learning spaces.

Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) carried out a literature review along with surveys and interviews with teachers and other experts. This information fed into the design of their simulated classroom environment and the learning scenarios depicted in their study. Study 1 aims to fulfil a similar purpose, by informing, from the perspective of in-practice teachers, the design and evaluation of studies in the rest of this thesis, to provide guidance on the primary attributes of working classrooms and to provide, where necessary, a vocabulary for describing the learning environment.

The primary aim of this study was to answer Research Question 1: *What factors influence how teachers organise and manage their learning environment?* This was achieved by addressing the three specific study questions. The first two questions aimed to improve our understanding of the process by which in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces. The final question aimed to inform the design process for Study 4. These are:

1. How do in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces?
2. What are the major influences on how in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces?
3. What are the key attributes of a well-functioning learning environment?

5.3. Methods

5.3.1. Design

A qualitative design was undertaken, with the study being carried out in two parts. Phase 1 was a series of semi-structured interviews with in-practice teachers. Thematic analysis was applied to the data collected. Phase 2 was a series of follow-up interviews with the same participants to sense test the findings of Phase 1.

Phase 1 of this study used a qualitative design with semi-structured interviews. A qualitative approach was chosen because the study aimed to gather data based on the accumulated professional experience of participants. Much of that experience would be based on emotional reactions, pedagogical approaches and social interactions; subjects which are not easily expressed when using a quantitative approach (Coolican, 2009). Semi-structured interviews allowed the participants to speak freely around the topic while giving the researcher the opportunity to maintain focus on the study aims (Mattimoe *et al.*, 2021). Individual interviews provided an opportunity to hear participants' individual opinions unfettered by peer pressure as may be experienced in a focus group (Tai and Ajjawi, 2016). Semi-structured interviews require the researcher to maintain a balance between the study aims and allowing the participants to express their opinions (Coolican, 2009). This approach allowed experienced participants to guide the exploration of the topic with few restrictions (Mattimoe *et al.*, 2021).

Phase 2 of this study involved presenting the same participants with a summarised copy of the analysis and results from Phase 1 (Appendix 5.1). After being given a chance to read through the material, participants took part in a short semi-structured interview that referenced the material they had just read.

5.3.2. Participants

Insight from a range of teachers was sought using the following criteria.

- Inclusion criteria: qualified primary or secondary school teachers with experience of working in classrooms in Scotland.
- Exclusion criteria: trainee teachers and teachers working exclusively outside of Scotland.

Participation was limited to teachers who had experience working in Scotland so that all those taking part in the study had a common frame of reference. To maintain a balance between experience and current trends, it was decided to limit the number of retired teachers interviewed to one or two depending on total number of participants. Eligibility criteria for Phase 2 was the same, with the addition that participants had to have taken part in Phase 1.

Recruitment was carried out by snowball sampling. Potential participants, who were known to the researcher or supervisory team through social or professional

contacts, were initially approached. It was, therefore, important the Principal Researcher made clear that prospective participants were under no obligation to take part. They were reminded of their right to withdraw at any time up to one week after the completion of the interview, without penalty to themselves and with no detrimental effect on the study. Potential participants identified other individuals who were eligible to take part. All potential participants were initially approached by e-mail or by telephone. They were provided with a participant information sheet (Appendix 5.2), consent form (Appendix 5.3) and given opportunity to ask questions prior to providing informed consent. Appointment date, time and location for consented participants were finalised via email correspondence. All participants from Phase 1 were contacted again for Phase 2 of the study. A separate participant information sheet (Appendix 5.4) and consent form (Appendix 5.5) was provided.

There were no specific requirements for sample size in this type of study (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Given that this PhD aimed to explore approaches taken by participants at various levels of experience, a minimum of 8 participants was anticipated to reach a point of saturation in the data collection (i.e. when no 'new' information is identified from the data) (Saunders *et al.*, 2018). In practice, data saturation was achieved after interviews with 6 participants. This enabled insight across a variety of backgrounds and levels of experience. Four of the 6 participants returned to take part in Phase 2.

5.3.3. Data collection: Semi-structured interviews

Phases 1 and 2 interviews were carried out at a time and location convenient and safe for both the participant and the researcher. They did not take place within a school or other Local Authority setting. Interviews typically took place in a university setting (e.g., a bookable room on UWS Paisley campus) or in a community setting suitable to the participant (e.g., participant home, adhering to UWS lone researcher policy). A requirement of the setting was that it was suitable for audio recording the interview.

Phase 1 aimed to develop a general understanding of classroom organisation and management. No reference was made to VR or the overall aim of the PhD when speaking to participants, to focus the study on the organisation and management of classrooms and not the application of VR. The interview schedule (Appendix 5.6) was designed to last approximately 45-60mins. Participants initially responded to brief demographic

questions, designed to provide relevant background about their level of teaching experience. The interview then primarily focused on the physical characteristic of the learning environment, with sufficient flexibility to allow discussion of the wider context. Overall, interviews took a holistic approach to the learning environment and avoided focusing on specific details unless directed by participants' responses.

The interview schedule consisted of four main interview questions (Table 5.1), each with additional prompts. The first two questions were based on the work of Dillon (2018) and encouraged participants to provide general information about their approach to teaching and their approach to organising and managing the physical space of their classroom. The prompts for each of these questions were based on Gremmen *et al.* (2016) and Barrett *et al.* (2016) and encouraged participants to address specific issues like desk layout, access to resources and curriculum plans. Based on the literature reviewed in Chapter 2 it would seem to be neither consistent nor clear how teachers are taught to organise and manage their classrooms. The third question was designed to explore this topic. The question and prompts encouraged participants to talk about their relevant ITE experience and the first few months of classroom experience. Question 4 encouraged participants to talk about what they considered to be the important physical characteristics of a working classroom. The prompts drew from Shussman (2017) and Gremmen *et al.* (2016) in an attempt to determine the level of freedom participants had to alter the physical characteristics of their learning environment.

The interview schedule was piloted with two potential participants, one an experienced primary teacher and the other an experienced secondary teacher. Based on their feedback, the language was changed to more accurately represent the terminology employed by teachers and to improve clarity. The interview schedule was also expanded to cover additional topics. These topics included student participation, the organisation of the school and access to resources and technology.

Interviews were audio-recorded using an encrypted Dictaphone (and *Otter*® smartphone app as a back-up) with consent from participants. All interviews were transcribed verbatim.

Table 5.1: Phase 1 interview questions and prompts

Interview Questions	Prompts
<p>Can you please describe in general terms your approach to teaching?</p>	<p>How did/do you change or adapt your approach depending on the situation (e.g. cohort, stage/age or demographic)?</p> <p>How was/is your approach influenced by your curriculum plans?</p> <p>How do/did you allow students to access resources?</p> <p>What are the main factors which influence how you taught?</p>
<p>This study is mainly interested in with how teachers organise and manage their classroom in terms of the physical space. So, can you describe your approach?</p>	<p>What factors influenced your approach?</p> <p>How did/do you prefer desks to be arranged?</p> <p>How do/did you allow students to access resources?</p> <p>What other factors (e.g. layout, routines and behaviour management) are important?</p> <p>Do your children/pupils have any input?</p> <p>How often were/are you able to teach out of the classroom (e.g. outdoors, field trips)?</p>

	<p>What, in your opinion, are the key physical attributes of a learning environment which works?</p>
<p>How much was your approach to classroom management effected by your ITE experience?</p>	<p>What, if anything, would you have changed about your ITE experience?</p> <p>How did your approach change with experience?</p> <p>How was your approach effected by other teachers?</p>
<p>Question 4: What do you think are the important physical characteristics of a classroom/learning space?</p>	<p>Which of these characteristics did you feel able to change/improve?</p> <p>How often did/do you alter the physical characteristics of your classroom?</p> <p>In what ways did/do you adapt your classroom management style to the physical environment?</p>

Phase 2 used a respondent validation approach with participants (Busetto, Wick and Gumbinger, 2020). This approach, also known as ‘member-checking’, aimed to confirm with participants whether the qualitative summary of their interview accurately reflected their Phase 1 interview (Mays and Pope, 2000). Respondent validation allows participants to provide additional insight, context and clarification on the initial data, which in itself, becomes part of the data collection (Shenton, 2004). Firstly, participants were presented with a two-page summary of key points from their initial interview. They were given time to read the summary before taking part in a follow-up interview. The semi structured interview consisted of three questions each with additional prompts (Appendix 5.7). The questions (Table 5.2) were designed to review the summary analysis,

clarify any uncertainties, provide participants with an opportunity to comment on the accuracy of the analysis and finally provide participants with an opportunity to say if anything important was missing.

Table 5.2: Phase 2 interview questions and prompts

Interview Questions	Prompts
Did you manage to read through the Summary of the Interview Findings? What questions do you have about the summary?	Did you feel like it made sense? What parts, if any, would like some clarification?
How much do you feel like the Summary of the Interview Findings accurately reflected the experience of a teachers organising and managing their classroom?	What was obviously missing from the analysis? What errors do you think were in the analysis? Is there any way that the results could be improved to more accurately reflect real life?
Now having read the Summary of the Interview Findings what would you like to add to this study which you may have omitted from your previous interview?	Is there anything from your experience which was not reflected in the results? Is there anything in the results which was over emphasised out of proportion to its real life significance?
Knowing that this study is now going forward to create VR simulations off classrooms what other relevant information would you like to add regarding how they are represented?	<i>None</i>

5.3.4. Analysis

Thematic analysis was carried out on the interview transcripts according to guidance provided by Braun, Clarke and Rance (Braun, Clarke and Rance, 2014). Thematic analysis follows a systematic framework for exploring and coding qualitative data. The codes can then be applied across participant data to identify patterns that relate to the study aims (Braun and Clarke, 2014). Interview transcripts were read at least three times by the researcher to become familiar with the data. Relevant passages were highlighted and notes made about potential codes, themes and recurrent ideas. Transcripts were then imported into NVivo 12, a software programme used to manage qualitative data (Lumivero., 2020). NVivo 12 was used to navigate the data, provide quick access to relevant transcripts and quotations, and generate an initial set of codes. These codes were refined to make them more descriptive and to minimise duplication. Codes were then collated into preliminary themes that reflected teachers' insight.

Preliminary themes were checked in relation to the coded extracts and then again by re-reading the transcripts of all interviews. Codes were grouped and the themes structured in the way which most accurately illustrated the information provided by participants. At each stage, the codes and themes were checked with reference to the aims of the study. Themes were then named and finalised, and a thematic map of analysis was generated. The analysis of data from Phase 2 incorporated additional comments made by participants during the second phase of interviews and used to finalise the thematic map.

Thematic analysis is used effectively to establish consistent characteristics based on interview data. This makes it the most suitable method when the analysis is exploratory and cannot be governed by an established theoretical approach (Braun and Clarke, 2023). Similar to Barrett *et al.* (2016) an objective ontological stance was taken. This also acknowledges that there are multiple subjective perspectives on objective reality. An inductive exploratory approach was taken to the analysis and began by considering all the collected data as potentially relevant. Through repeated analysis, reporting patterns were identified. In this way relevant themes did not emerge from that data (Braun and Clarke, 2023) but were progressively fit together into a heuristic structure that placed the classroom at the centre of a large and complex system.

5.3.5. Ethics

Ethical approval for the study was obtained through the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee. To maintain participant anonymity each participant was given a unique identifier with which they were identified in any analysis or publication. Names of individual participants were not recorded in any notes or audio recordings. Audio recordings were downloaded on to a secure password protected UWS laptop with a single backup. After the analysis was completed all audio files were stored until completion of the PhD, at which time they were deleted. The audio recordings, notes and unedited transcripts were only accessed by the researcher and supervisory team. Ethical approval for Phase 1 of the study was received from the UWS Ethics Committee on 4th June 2019 (Appendix 5.8). Ethical approval for Phase 2 of the study was received on 27th April 2021 (Appendix 5.9).

5.4. Findings

The findings of Phase 1 and 2 will be presented here in sequence. The findings from both phases will be incorporated together for the discussion.

5.4.1. Phase 1

Six participants were interviewed, two females and four males. Participants' date of qualification as a teacher was recorded to gauge experience. This ranged from 1971 to 2007. Two were retired at the time of conducting the interview, one of whom retired only days prior to the interview. All participants had experience working as a teacher in Scotland, mostly in primary education. One participant had worked exclusively as a secondary school teacher. Three participants had teaching experience outside mainstream UK schools. This included prisons, military training, technical colleges and private schools. Two participants had teaching experience in England, and one had experience teaching in Thailand. Additional demographic information about participants can be found in Appendix 5.10.

Codes were identified by highlighting and grouping recurring ideas in the transcripts. In total, 60 codes were identified and grouped into eight themes (Table 5.3). For a description of individual codes see Appendix 5.11. A description of the themes is presented in Table 5.4.

Table 5.3: Eight identified themes and sixty codes

Theme	Codes
Cultural Influence	Multiple Languages Cultural Differences Results Driven National Government Influence Local Government Influence Socio-Economic Status Parent Influence Legal Issues
School Organisation	Teacher's Limited Autonomy Specialist Teaching Requirements Peer Influence Admin Influence Management Influence Time Pressure Limited Resources Closed vs Open Plan Room Size Number of Pupils Adapt to Physical Environment Type of School Building
Teacher's Approach	Training Influence Training Not Influence Pedagogy Teacher's Experience Teacher's Instinct
Physical Adaptation	Lines of Sight Pupils Access Resources Available Resources Space to Move Around Technology

	<p>Outdoor Space</p> <p>Desk Layout</p> <p>Dedicated Areas</p>
Work Adaptation	<p>Adapt to Subject</p> <p>Learning Objectives</p> <p>Group Work</p> <p>Flexibility in Curriculum</p> <p>Core Work</p> <p>Additional Challenging Work</p>
Learning Atmosphere	<p>Safe Environment</p> <p>Atmosphere for Learning</p> <p>Noise</p> <p>Light</p> <p>Temperature</p> <p>Clear Rules</p>
Engagement and Ownership	<p>Reality/Relevance</p> <p>Visual Engagement</p> <p>Engagement through Fun</p> <p>Play Based Learning</p> <p>Pupils Own Learning</p> <p>Teachers Own Space</p> <p>Pupils Work as Ownership</p> <p>Pupils Own Space</p>
Pupils/Teacher Relationship	<p>Communication</p> <p>Behaviour Management</p> <p>Teacher/Student Relationship</p> <p>Pupils' Varying Ages</p> <p>Pupils' Varying Abilities</p> <p>Teacher's Choice</p> <p>Pupils' Choice</p>

Table 5.4: Description of eight identified themes

Theme	Definition
Cultural Influence	The broad cultural influences which exist beyond the school. Factors such as local or national government legislations, regional cultural differences and the socio-economic status of the catchment area.
School Organisation	Elements of the organisation of the school which are broader than the organisation of an individual classroom. This includes factors such as the type of school building, the availability of resources and the influence of school management.
Teacher's Approach	All the personal and professional factors which combine to make up a teachers' individual approach to classroom organisation and management are included in this theme. This includes factors such as the teacher's experience, both inside and outside teaching, and their ITE experience.
Physical Adaptation	Physical aspects of the environment which the teacher may consider when organising and managing their classroom. For example, this theme includes lines of sight, students' access to resources and the desk layout.
Work Adaptation	Elements of the schoolwork carried out in a classroom which effect its organisation and management. This includes factors like learning objective, adaptation to subject and flexibility in the curriculum.
Learning Atmosphere	Aspects of the classroom which a teacher might think directly affect its suitability as a learning environment. This includes physical characteristics such as noise, light and safety but also social characteristics such as the establishment of clear rules.
Engagement and Ownership	The two separate but related ideas of engagement and ownership of the classroom are represented by this theme. These are factors which contribute to the pupils' engagement in the work of the class and the classroom itself as well as the sense of ownership of the classroom felt by the pupils and the teachers. For example, visual engagement and play based learning.
Pupils/Teacher Relationship	Factors which most directly influence the relationship and the interaction between the pupils and the teachers. For example, communication, behaviour management and the variable abilities of pupils.

5.4.1.1. Theme 1. Cultural Influence

All participants were aware of influences outside of the school. Many of these represented the social and cultural norms of the local community, the expectations of parents and the socio-economic status of the catchment area. These factors could affect how pupils were expected to interact with the teacher, whether the teacher was expected to focus on academic performance or social interaction or what resources the pupils were able contribute to their learning. This theme included national and local government policy.

“The Scottish government then decided, no, no, we need to have national assessments. And they introduced them for primary 1s, for primary 4s and primary 7s. So they made everybody accountable again and we went back into that same cycle of teaching for the test.”

Participant M4

Distinctions between cultural groups and multi-lingual class groups could influence a teacher’s approach to organising and managing their classroom. Pupils in modern schools are increasingly representative of a broad variation in cultural traditions and linguistic backgrounds.

“I worked in a school where there was children from 60 different countries. Over 40 languages spoken and many of those children, an increasing amount were children who were first stage learners in terms of English.”

Participant M4

Participants also expressed the different expectations pupils and teachers had based on different cultural backgrounds. In Thailand, for example, pupils were expected to take an active role in the organisation and management of their learning environment, however, the lessons were generally organised in a more teacher-centric way than in Scotland.

“The work that I've had in Thailand, coming to work in Scotland was a big sea change in culture, from teaching in Thailand to teaching here. And say, mainly, here, it seems to be mainly driven by the higher ups staff.”

Participant M2

Another significant factor was the socio-economic status of the catchment area closely tied to the influence of parents. Beyond social problems, which can be common in areas of high deprivation, participants explained that parents from different backgrounds had different expectations for their child's school experience. From the following example, parents from more prosperous areas were more concerned that their children enjoyed school than that they achieved academic success.

"I want them to be top of the class, I want them to be in a higher reading group than his child. Right? I want to know that they're up there. That aspirational aspect was not there in that school. Because those were parents who'd got academic success themselves and they were comfortable with the fact that those children were going to be successful in life."

Participant M4

This theme provides the broad context of participants' teaching experience. Factors in this theme are frequently beyond their control. This theme can also represent positive cultural influences, available resources and support. Different cultural influences, environments and government policies can provide opportunity for positive change.

"Even now with the curriculum for excellence. Which was like a breath of fresh air for many, many teachers. Right. It gave us back ownership. It gave us our own personalization and choice, and how we would develop things and construct things until about what six years ago, whatever. The Scottish government then decided, no, no, we need to have national assessments."

Participant M4

5.4.1.2. Theme 2. School Organisation

Within this theme are the physical characteristics of the school building as well as the social organisation that operates within it. Social organisation refers to the interaction between staff in the school and their influence on each other. The social organisation of the school was, for participants, a means to learn new skills and expand their ideas about organisation and management of their classroom.

“But our motivation was absolutely clear. It was coming from the management of the school. We’ve got very high expectations, we’ve got very very high standards for ourselves, but also for our children.”

Participant M4

Often the approach to the school organisation can be strongly influenced by its layout.

“If you're changing environments all the time, then you have to adjust to that environment, that environment doesn't adjust to you because you just end up with a brick wall.”

Participant M1

Open or closed-plan, big or small classroom, a modern building or Victorian architecture were all factors that influenced participants. They also acknowledged the need to adapt to the available environment by seeing beyond its limitations to find the opportunities for good practice.

“So, they adapted within, within the physical space that was available to them. And they, if you walked in and looked at the classrooms, and never mind all the aesthetics in it, all the layouts would more or less be the same.”

Participant M4

The availability and accessibility of resources influenced participants at several different levels. For example, the resources available in and around the school such as playgrounds or additional classrooms, or technological resources available to teachers. How a teacher manages the available resources is an important part of the organisation and management of the classroom.

“I think that’s essential, I think you need a teacher who’s very well organised and at they planned beforehand what they are going to do and they’ve got the resources to hand to be able to do it.”

Participant M4

Key in this process of adaptation and improvisation was the influence of the school management and the teacher’s peer group. Mostly this theme is outside the control of

the teacher, however, individual teachers can sometimes influence school organisation as part of their peer group.

“Everybody bought into that. In many many schools in Glasgow and beyond, Paisley certainly, you have to establish a climate for learning.”

Participant M4

5.4.1.3. Theme 3. Teacher’s Approach

According to participants, teachers are not reacting passively to the physical environment or the instructions of the school management. How the teacher chooses to react to these influences remains a product of their experience, their training and their pedagogical approach. Participants frequently drew on their experience, both in teaching and in other jobs, to inspire their approach to classroom organisation and management. Consistently, experience and peer interaction were much more influential for participants than anything gained through their ITE. Participants were able to share approaches to classroom organisation and management with their colleagues. Their peer group was frequently the biggest influence on their approach to teaching and they gained experience by watching more experienced colleagues.

“Normally young teachers... it’s experience, and working with older staff and you know, the different schools that allows you to... nick good ideas, you see, that’s the whole point is you just take what’s good, drop what’s crap and keep improving.”

Participant M3

The most important part of ITE was, according to participants, classroom experience. This experience meant a lot to those who had none but was quickly made superficial by the transition to in-practice teaching.

“To begin with... I just relied on what I had been told. I found within maybe six months, I realized what I was told, wasn’t actually practical, probably in perfect circumstances, or, you know, in theory, a lot of the sort of discipline techniques, class management and things like that sound great on paper, but when you actually sat with, you know, pupils coming in and having to manage pupils or manage a, manage a class and deliver lesson plans.”

Participant M2

Participants described the organisation and management of their classrooms as an extension of the organisation of the school. They were positively influenced by more experienced colleagues and supported by the school management. The organisation of the school is therefore represented by a team of people supporting and influencing each other.

"I talk a lot about positive energy and negative energy and you can go into a meeting and you can connect with somebody. And you generate really good ideas. Or you can go into a meeting ... and you just come out drained, right, your energy drained. This didn't have that impact... you actually had people saying, right how do we adapt to these circumstances, because their motivation. And I think that was down to our collective values as a school."

Participant M4

5.4.1.4. Theme 4. Physical Adaptation

Teachers can adapt certain physical attributes of the learning environment to improve its organisation and management. Physical attributes not under the teacher's control can present a challenge to overcome. Which are adaptable and which are a challenge, will change from room to room and from school to school. For example, in a classroom, desks may be easily portable or fixed, the class may be crowded or underpopulated, and there may be only one plug socket or many. This is related to the theme of *School Organisation* but focussed on physical aspects of the learning environment which may be within the power of an individual teacher to change.

All participants spoke about rearranging the desks as a means of encouraging good behaviour, holding the attention of pupils and overseeing their work. The proximity of pupils who may need extra attention or the ability to maintain eye contact with pupils could have a significant effect on their behaviour.

"I'd be sitting here writing like that, the kids on this side will be the most engaged, guaranteed, the ones who have got my back to because I'm right handed. They're the ones who at least engaged so guess who's pissing about the most."

Participant M1

Some teachers, if they are only temporarily using a classroom, may feel they have no right to alter the layout. In other classrooms the layout may be fixed. This is unfortunate because, according to participants, changing the layout can be extremely useful.

"I've got the P7 class coming up for this session, they're a right handful. It's a really tough class I got now... So there's going to be a lot more group work and teacher led stuff. Hence the islands, you know what I mean, and then I've also got it spaced out so I can get to an area quick. Horseshoe wouldn't allow me to do that."

Participant M3

It is important to note that most participants did not view the learning environment as limited by the physical space of the classroom. Participants looked beyond the walls of the classroom to outdoor spaces or other rooms within the school. Expanding beyond the limits of one classroom gives the teacher additional flexibility and may be used as a reward to move pupils to a less formal setting.

"Yeah, make a point of trying to get out as often as I can. So it was it was at least once a week, we spent a double block outdoors but as well as PE, do you know what I mean, especially when it's nice in the summer we'll be going out pretty much every day because the space is great."

Participant M3

This option was not available to all participants in all situations.

"I would normally stay in my room. We don't really have any space. We don't have anywhere kids could sit? I mean, that would be lovely to have tables and chairs outside and be able to take them outside. I would absolutely love it. But we just don't have that we've got playground."

Participant F1

Other important factors are the available resources, areas dedicated to specialist activities and the application of modern technology. These three factors conferred different benefits and presented different challenges depending on the participant or school. Modern digital technology, like computers, tablets and Smartboards, can create new opportunities for managing and overseeing the work of pupils.

“We’ve got interactive whiteboards in our rooms. And I use them a lot. That’s a big influence. On how I teach.”

Participant F1

New technology also requires additional training, sufficient power outlets and sometimes a Wi-Fi signal. Participants described situations where the design of the school did not keep up with the application of technology.

“In the 60s building that I worked in I only had one electrical socket at the back... halfway up the wall at the back of the room. So I had to use the television on top of a cupboard at the back of the room.”

Participant F2

Some participants described resources being concentrated into dedicated areas. These included a media suite, an art area or a nurture corner for pupils to self-regulate. These areas can be both a benefit and a problem depending on other factors such as the current curriculum, the available space for pupils or even the temperament of individual pupils.

“We had a problem with the computers, the media suite, as I said. So what did we do, we bought boxes of laptops or iPads, and instead of the travel time of children going from there, to the other end of the building. No, the computers came to the classroom. And that overcame timetabling issues in terms of use of a room.”

Participant M4

5.4.1.5. Theme 5. Work Adaptation

This theme has the least directly to do with the physical characteristics of the learning environment. An important element of this theme was the core work of the class and the objectives for each lesson. Through this we begin to see the importance of the relationship between the teacher and the pupils.

“So it’d be whole class teaching, but also what you’d be doing is you’d be discussing with the children, what your learning intentions are. And what the success criteria would be. And so children would be aware of what it is they’re getting taught and how do we know we’ve learnt it. And you’d have a bit at the end called the plenary session where, where we would recap.”

Where we go over the learning points. And that's, that's the structure of a good lesson."

Participant M4

There can be significant differences in what elements of the work or curriculum an individual teacher is able to adapt. For example, new government policies on standardised testing may be implemented by senior management of a school in a particular way. This may limit flexibility in the curriculum and remove time for additional work for more advanced pupils. A teacher may feel inexperienced in a particular topic and therefore lack the confidence to be inventive. They may also lack facilities or equipment. However, more positively, teachers can also adapt aspects of what they teach and how it is taught to more productively organise and manage their classroom. This process is akin to finding a balance between what is required by the curriculum and what is possible given the environment and resources. Participants described how useful it was to be able to give additional, more challenging, work to children who completed the core work more quickly.

"Sufficient resources, example sharing books is not good. It would be nice to have a, as is available more in primary schools, a bit more space. So that you could set up something I'm thinking of pupils who have, as it were done the basic work, and are looking for extension work. If there was some where if you had room so that you could set up something for them to go and do once they'd finished. Sort of the core of the work you were doing. But these things are difficult."

Participant F2

How a teacher adapted their curriculum also depended on their particular pedagogical approach as well as the facilities they have available.

"And there's just absolutely loads you can do, you can do maths, you can do your writing, you can do art, you can do gardening, you can do all sorts outdoors, you can do science So again, it's kind of, it sort of baffles me sometimes why people don't, when you've got a nice area to use, like we've got a, we have right now the school site's amazing."

Participant M3

5.4.1.6. Theme 6. Learning Atmosphere

In this theme, an atmosphere suitable for learning facilitated the management of distractions, the expectation that structured learning was taking place and that the environment was safe and comfortable.

“Children are very sensitive to those factors. And I think that in order to have successful learning, a teacher has to ensure a safe environment for their children. And people say to you that, you know, your job as a teacher most important thing for you to do is get children to learn actually it’s not it’s to make them safe. That’s your first priority as a teacher.”

Participant M4

Participants acknowledged that pupils often did not have a home environment in which they felt safe or was conducive to learning. Particularly in areas of high deprivation. Teachers were often responsible for introducing and maintaining the concept of a safe and comfortable learning environment.

“Calm environment, safe environment. Cos a lot of the children I’m dealing with have got pretty horrific home lives and the classroom needs to be somewhere where they know they’re going to get treated fairly and they’re gonna get support.”

Participant M3

The classroom should inspire learning by using sensory cues to make the children comfortable and put them in the right frame of mind. Participants used music along with appropriate work or maintained a neat classroom to focus the minds of pupils. Some of the participants felt that clearly established “classroom rules” helped establish the right atmosphere. The intention was to create an environment in which pupils were engaged while encouraging a sense of ownership for both the pupils and the teacher.

“And for the [pupils]. And for it to be a place where everybody knows this is a place of learning. It’s not a playground, it’s not, you know, it’s not a sitting

room at home, it's, it's a place and come in here. And we're going to do business where we're going to learn something."

Participant M2

The most difficult part of this process was in the management of unwanted distractions like direct sunlight, street noises or poor lighting.

5.4.1.7. Theme 7. Engagement and Ownership

All participants recognised the importance of engaging pupils and giving them a sense of ownership. These two ideas are closely related in the ways which they are achieved and the potential benefits for the learning experience. Both can relate to the curriculum as well as the physical layout of the classroom. There is a reciprocal relationship between these ideas. For example, pupils can engage with the organisation of the classroom if they have input into how the desks are arranged and pupils can feel a sense of ownership toward the classroom by seeing their work displayed on the walls. The nature of the displays can make them feel engaged in their own learning. As one participant put it:

"Children taking ownership of it, so it's their classroom, they've been involved with the management of it, they've got responsibilities for looking after it, they see what they see they day to day they're looking after it, they choose what's up on the walls, right what do we need on the walls then? Would it help if we had this? Would it help if we had that?"

Participant M3

It not sufficient to simply allow the pupils to decorate their own classroom but the act of organising the classroom must be relevant to the work and engage the pupils with the desired learning outcomes.

"This belongs to me. This is, I made, see that, I made that there. So there was a sense of pride. There was a sense of ownership and respecting of other children's work."

Participant M4

"Sense of ownership" does not only relate to the pupils but to the teacher as well. Being able to shape their environment to their own needs and style allowed participants to engage with pupils on their own terms and therefore more effectively.

“So when you actually see you can have it however you want because you’re the teacher and it’s your classroom, do what works.”

Participant M3

Those participants who had worked in primary schools mentioned play-based learning, particularly in the early part of primary school, as a means of engaging pupils. Visual engagement, engagement through fun and demonstrating the relevance of the lesson were also important.

“My main thing is, especially with the children that we teach is trying, you have to engage them, you have to have something visual, you have to have some, they can click with and go I understand that that’s really exciting.”

Participant F1

5.4.1.8. Theme 8. Pupils/Teacher Relationship

The pupils/teacher relationship was of primary importance in carrying out the role of being a teacher. The ability of teachers and pupils to work positively together was influenced by the character of the pupils, their age, abilities and background. According to participants, it is not simply that the pupils are well behaved and respectful. It is a reciprocal relationship based on good communication and informed choices some of which are within the teacher’s control and some of which are not.

“It doesn’t matter where you’re teaching. You’ve got to, as a teacher, you’ve got to be a teacher, not be a friend. And, you know, you’re basically taking on semi parent role or semi relative role where the pupils have to sort of respect your position. And you’ve got to maintain that you’ve got to, you know, be professional. And also let your children know that you are, or the pupils know that you are a step, half a step away from them not a full step away, but half a step away from them.”

Participant M2

The pupils/teacher relationship was important to the physical organisation and management of the classroom. It was what participants referred to as their base measure of success. It was often the key organising principal. Central to this theme is the idea of

communication, which all participants understood to be an important part of the classroom layout.

“You have to have a means of communicating with pupils. Other than yourself speaking, which could be a blackboard, a smart board, some other piece of technology.”

Participant F2

“So I’d have U-shaped desks with the Blackboard, or the whiteboard at the top of the room. And then I found that quite handy, because we could do a lot of things, I could either fit [pupils] on the inside on the outside, so we could work as teams, or if they were all set on the outside of the U shape, I was able to be in the middle of them all.”

Participant M2

Communication was also challenging when dealing with pupils of varying ages and ability. The ability to know the pupils, to understand their individual requirements and respond to their individual needs was central to the teachers’ role and could be made easier by deliberate organisation and management of the classroom. This means of communicating and managing behaviour directly relates to the physical adaptation of the classroom (theme 4), the management of sightlines and the ability of the teacher to move between pupils.

“All the classes have a nurture corner. Where kids are sent or can choose to go to to self-regulate. So if they're struggling with the lesson was struggling to manage their behaviour, it's a little place for a timeout where they can just calm themselves down and regulate the behaviour but these nurture corners are sometimes a catalyst for poor behaviour because then the child wants to go they rather than do work. So it's a balance between how you use it.”

Participant M3

Part of achieving a productive balance in the pupils/teacher relationship was in understanding what aspects of the classroom could be the pupil’s choice and what could be the teachers choice. Although ultimately the organisation and management remained the teacher’s responsibility pupils could gain a sense of participation and reveal significant

character traits by making their own choices. This is closely tied to the themes of Learning Atmosphere (theme 6) and Engagement and Ownership (theme 7). For example, one participant described an exercise where they allowed pupils to design their own layout for the classroom and then vote on which design should be implemented.

“And we want a teacher who is going to set the proper parameters and boundaries whenever children are doing their own learning. Whenever they’re leading their own learning. And very much a classroom, I think, is a combination of the two. Where children are very successful in leading their own learning, and take that out to a platform of say, an assembly or a presentation to parents or whatever but there’s other times when the teacher’s leading that learning.”

Participant M4

5.4.2. Phase 2

Phase 2 provided some interesting additional insights from participants. Four participants were interviewed, 2 male and 2 female, all of whom had taken part in Phase 1 of the study. Additional demographic information about participants can be found in Appendix 5.10. All participants validated the analysis of Phase 1 after being presented with a summarised copy (Appendix 5.1). They felt that the summary analysis accurately reflected the thought process undertaken by teachers in the organisation and management of classrooms. The influence on teachers’ decision-making process and the goals of classroom management were also accurately represented. This fulfilled the primary purpose of Phase 2 by member-checking the analysis of Phase 1. However, Phase 2 also gave participants an opportunity to provide any additional data which they had omitted or that they felt was lacking from Phase 1. The presentation of additional insight by participants amounted to fine tuning of the results of Phase 1. Participants were able to give their own perspective on the summarised analysis. A brief explanation of that additional data will be presented here.

Two of the participants warned against over generalising when it came to the organisation of classrooms. They emphasised that the combination of influences on each classroom are unique and that no two classrooms are ever the same, even in appearance.

“I have never been in a classroom which was like the previous one, even in the same school.”

Participant M2

By attempting to approach a generalised model of how teachers approach the organisation and management of classrooms there is a danger of missing the significance of exceptional cases. For example, the inclusion of children with additional support needs or schools in remote areas. According to participants this is something that could be improved by expanding the study and speaking to more teachers from a wide range of backgrounds.

Most participants emphasised that some aspects of classroom layout or organisation cannot be changed and that this varies from room to room. One participant described a classroom where the tables and furniture were designed to fit together in one arrangement which could not be altered. Individual teachers may have little or no control over things like cultural influence, but they can choose how to respond to them. For example:

“The inclusion of bilingual children could be seen as a problem or an opportunity for cooperative and collaborative teaching.”

Participant M4

Participants in general felt that it was difficult to represent the autonomy of teachers in a model that was a generalised representation of real-working classrooms. Particularly because, like many other factors, this varies from case to case.

Themes like “learning atmosphere” (theme 6) and “engagement and ownership” (theme 7) could be thought of as unattainable targets, often limited by the physical constraints of the classroom. Participants also pointed out that the degree to which a teacher achieves these goals may vary from day to day, particularly when seeing pupils for short periods like in a secondary school. There was a general desire with all the participants to state that in most cases the flexibility of classrooms and the facilities available have continued to improve throughout their teaching experience. Despite challenges such as pupils with additional support needs or multiple languages, the focus

remains on the teacher to overcome these challenges and see them as opportunities to create an environment for learning.

5.5. Discussion

The aim of this study was to investigate the factors that influence how teachers organise and manage their learning environment. Data were collected to answer three study questions:

1. How do in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces?
2. What are the major influences on how in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces?
3. What are the key attributes of a well-functioning learning environment?

Overall, findings demonstrate not only the complexity of understanding *how* teachers organise and manage their classrooms, but also inconsistency in how teachers *learn* this skill. Findings are discussed below in relation to the study questions.

5.5.1. How do in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces?

Participant insight highlighted the complexity of understanding all the factors that affect how teachers organise and manage their learning space. Asking “*How does a teacher organise and manage their learning environment?*” was akin to asking, “*How does a teacher teach?*” Most participants described their approach to classroom organisation and management as a combination of experience, instinct, observation, and trial and error.

The reasons why participants approached classroom organisation and management in a particular way went beyond the important physical characteristics described by Martin (2016), such as lighting or ventilation. For example, participants mentioned the age and stage of the pupils being taught, the expected quality of behaviour from individual pupils, the perceived relationship between teacher and pupils, the need to engage pupils and the need to provide pupils with a sense of ownership all as major influences. This aligns with the findings of Martin (2002) showing that the environment of

the classroom had a significant influence on how teachers related to their pupils and carried out their lessons.

Teachers in this study had an awareness of the emotional, cognitive, social and aesthetic influences described by Shussman (2017) and factored in the broader goals of teaching beyond the transfer of knowledge (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). As suggested by Evertson and Weinstein (2006), classroom organisation and management is of major importance to teachers. This is because classroom management and organisation are connected to many other factors, some physical, some social, some political and some emotional.

The factors influencing the teachers' choice for the organisation and management of their learning environment interact as part of one large system. This 'system' concept is similar to the model proposed by Higgins *et al.* (2005), which recognised several interconnected themes that all influence learning. The interconnectivity of this system means that small changes may impact the whole system. For example, the need to manage behaviour is a key factor in the pupils/teacher relationship. The behaviour of a few pupils may require the desk layout to be rearranged, which is a physical adaptation. The rearrangement of desks will affect lines of sight and how teachers adapt the work of the classroom (Martin, 2002). All of which may be limited by other factors such as the physical space available, the prescribed curriculum or the influence of senior management.

This interconnectivity and unpredictability, results in teachers learning by experience, adapting to and solving their own problems, until they develop an instinct (Barrett, Barrett and Zhang, 2016). When dealing with a complex environment it is understandable that teachers, under the normal pressures of their job, would find it preferable to react instinctively than to consciously calculate the outcome of multiple interconnected variables. It is also understandable why inexperienced teachers find the task of classroom organisation and management stressful and potentially overwhelming (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016; Evertson and Weinstein, 2006). That is not to say that an experienced teacher could not, upon reflection, explain their decisions but simply that in the moment they would be better served by their instinctive response. For this reason, as participants themselves indicated, teachers learn by experience how to organise and manage their classroom.

Gaps remain in our understanding of how teachers approach the organisation and management of their classrooms. This study identified that teachers learn by experience, intuition, observation, and trial and error. However, greater understanding is needed about the *mechanism* of how teachers learn. This gap aligns with critique of Barrett *et al.* (2016) who, although consulted teachers' on a broad spectrum of their classroom's physical characteristics, only scratched the surface of the wider context in which the classroom sits. It did not investigate how teachers attempted to improve their learning environment or what their goals were when they did.

During this study none of the participants credited their ITE experience as preparing them for this task. This would seem to confirm the varying and inconsistent approaches to instructing classroom organisation and management demonstrated in Chapter 2. ITE is therefore an opportunity for preservice teachers to learn more about the organisation and management of classrooms. This supports the need for a new approach, such as virtual reality (VR), to enhance the ITE experience in relation to classroom organisation and management.

5.5.2. What are the major influences on how in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces?

Data from this study demonstrates that all factors influencing the organisation and management of classrooms interact as part of one large system. The codes and themes generated during the analysis identified the influences on teachers as well as the attributes of the learning environment that teachers focus upon. These included the following influencing factors: cultural influence; school organisation; teacher's approach; physical adaptation; work adaptation; learning atmosphere; engagement and ownership; and pupils/teacher relationship.

Influencing factors extended beyond the four walls of the classroom. Participants consistently explained how influences beyond the immediate vicinity of the classroom, and outside their own control, had a major impact on their approach. These included the design of the school, the support of school management, national government policy, size of the school, and local socio-economic factors. This is supported by other studies who identified social and political influence as being significant factors (Veloso and Marques, 2017; Higgins *et al.*, 2005), and Jeon *et al.* (2014), who demonstrated that socio-economic

factors had a negative impact of pupils' cognitive ability and cognitive skills limiting their readiness for school.

This study aimed to inform the design of later studies in this PhD, including the design of immersive experiences for teaching and learning. The focus of this study was intended to be the physical aspects of the classroom. It quickly became apparent that an awareness of the physical and social context of the classroom was also necessary. Socio-economic factors (Jeon, Buettner and Hur, 2014), government policies (Higgins *et al.*, 2005) and classroom design (Shussman, 2017), had a clear and direct impact on how the teacher organised and managed the classroom. In future studies these external factors would not necessarily be part of the VR simulation but would instead be brought to the experience by participants, form the basis of interview questions or influence how the immersive experiences were designed. This is something that will be discussed in greater detail in Chapters 8 and 9.

Despite the systemic complexity of the learning environment, the findings of this study propose an overall model of establishing effective learning environments (Figure 5.1). To illustrate this point, the themes of *Cultural Influence* and *School Organisation* (Figure 5.1) provide context to the organisation and management of the classroom. Where *Cultural Influence* represents the broad cultural and political influence over which individual teachers have little, if any, control, *School Organisation* represents the more immediate context. *School Organisation* includes the type of school building, specialist teaching requirements and the influence of peers. Some of these factors may be influenced in small ways by the individual teacher.

The teacher's own attitude is key to the entire process. Martin (2002) found that teachers often have contradictory views of their classroom and in many cases were unwilling to take ownership of their surroundings. The findings of Martin (2002) may have been limited by their deterministic approach rather than viewing the relationship between the classroom and the teacher as reciprocal. The teacher's approach is central to how the teacher react to the various influences (Chisiu, 2015). This is represented in the theme *Teacher's Approach*. As suggested by Ünal and Ünal (2012), participant's ITE experience had little effect, however, all participants recognised the value of their working experience. Not only their experience in the classroom but in other occupations.

Figure 5.1: Proposed model of establishing effective learning environments

With regards to the proposed model (Figure 5.1), *Teacher's Approach* represents the filter through which problems are analysed, challenges are met, and influences are considered.

Physical Adaptation and *Work Adaptation* represent the things which the teacher may be able to use to better organise and manage the classroom. Contrary to Shussman's outline (2017), it is not always so easy to define what characteristics of the classroom teachers will be able to change and which they will be bound by. This is a limitation of Shussman (2017) who places the responsibility for classroom organisation and management onto the teachers without fully acknowledging the influence of external factors such as the school organisation or government policy. Which things the teacher can control will depend on factors represented by *School Organisation* and *Cultural Influence*. This part of the proposed model (Figure 5.1) is important because it is the part most easily represented by a VR simulation, the flexibility in the physical classroom and the work available.

When describing the proposed model (Figure 5.1), the themes of *Pupils/Teacher Relationship*, *Learning Atmosphere* and *Engagement and Ownership* collectively represent the goals of the process. As suggested by participants in Phase 2, the teacher adapts the physical characteristics of the classroom to create a sense of *Engagement and Ownership*, to create a positive *Learning Atmosphere* and to create a productive *Pupils/Teacher Relationship*. This aligns with the guidance provided by Rhodes (2019), who recommended that the first goal of behaviour management was a positive relationship with the pupils. Most of the factors represented by these themes are the teacher's responsibility. These three themes taken together are similar to the *hidden curriculum* described by Chisiu (2015) in that they are not formalised or academic but that they represent the influence of the social and physical environment on the development of the pupils.

The advantage of using the proposed model (Figure 5.1) as a heuristic device, is that it allows us to instantly recognise those factors to focus on when providing a meaningful learning experience for ITE students. This structure also allows us to separate the context of the learning environment from its physical and social attributes.

5.5.3. What are the key attributes of a well-functioning learning environment?

This study's findings have already demonstrated that learning environments exist within a complex system. They are influenced by the external environment. The importance of this was demonstrated by Kweon *et al.* (2017) who showed a correlation between the trees and green spaces around a school and pupils academic performance. To consider classrooms without reference to the wider environment would result in data lacking ecological validity (Lewkowicz, 2001). Almost any factor may change from being an impediment to the teacher to a management tool over which the teacher had complete control. For example, is the furniture fixed or mobile? Is there flexibility in the curriculum? Do the windows open? Barrett *et al.* (2016) noted factors such as glare, stuffiness and ambient noise effected teachers' perception of their classroom. To fully understand any teachers approach it is important to understand what aspects of the learning environment they have influence over and what aspects influence them.

This study identified what in-practice teachers saw as the goals of good classroom organisation. A functional learning environment was not described by participants as a series of physical characteristics. A functional learning environment was how those characteristics, taken in the wider social context, express a positive pupils/teacher relationship and created an atmosphere for learning. Chapter 2 demonstrated the multiple significant influences which the learning environment has on pupils' school experience. Chisiu (2015) argued for the importance of the pupils/teacher relationship as a major influence. Participants in this study considered the organisation and management of the classroom as a physical expression of the relationship between pupils and teacher. The goal of a functional learning environment was to provide pupils with a safe space for learning, to engage them with learning and social interaction and to provide them with a sense of ownership of both the classroom and the curriculum.

As previously suggested by Linney & Seidman (1989) the learning environment is truly a chaotic complex system. It is a dynamic system made up of multiple interconnected parts which is sensitive to small changes in any one of the many influential factors. It is possible, therefore, that there is no definitive answer to study questions 1, 2 and 3. This was emphasised by participants highlighting the risks of overgeneralising, pointing out that each classroom is unique, a unique combination of people presenting a unique

balance of challenges. It is also important to consider this study's findings in the context of Scottish education. Participants were in-practice teachers in Scotland. It is likely that a different geographical focus may have identified different influences on classroom organisation and management. For example, according to Marunda-Piki (2017) most African schools view the classroom as a functional space rather than an environment to actively engage and motivate the pupils.

In summary, each environment must be examined for its own merits. However, using the proposed model of organising and managing learning environments (Figure 5.1) as a guide, allows us to understand the classroom from the teacher's perspective. It is also important to further understand how to support teachers to achieve their 'classroom goals', what tools they have available to achieve them and what limitations they face. These are gaps to be addressed by future studies.

5.5.4. Strengths, Limitations and Future Studies

This study gathered insight on how teachers organise and manage their classrooms. It used a two-phase qualitative approach to address gaps identified by the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3). Its holistic approach, exploring multiple factors influencing learning environments, importantly builds on the work of other researchers who typically focused on specific or minimal factors. The findings of this study add to the evidence base, demonstrating the complexity of establishing safe and effective learning environments. It gathered data to inform the remaining studies in this PhD, a methodological strength of the sequential exploratory research design. It also addressed the **analysis** phase of the ADDIE design framework. Insight was gathered from a range of participants including retired and in-practice teachers, those with experience in primary and secondary teaching, and those with experience teaching in Scotland, England and Thailand.

This study had several limitations. During the interviews participants acknowledged that the challenges they faced were common to most teachers, however, all participants viewed their classroom setting as unique. How do these seemingly contradictory ideas come about? The answer is because of the complexity of the system being described. This study was conducted with a relatively small number of participants. Although this is a suitable choice for qualitative research, the results indicate that this topic is perhaps too complex to be comprehensively tackled in a study of this size.

Each learning environment is highly individualised and constantly evolving but based on common influences and ideas. Each learning environment is made up of similar elements and pressures, however, the significance of those elements and pressures varies according to the individuals involved. Even if somehow each classroom could be made physically and contextually identical, the personalities involved, both the pupils and the teacher, would be combined in a unique way and would interpret the environment according to their own experience.

When designing future studies, a greater understanding could be gained by focusing on specific learning environments. Future studies of this kind would benefit from interviewing teachers or pupils with specific reference to the learning environment which they currently use. Having tangible examples on hand which demonstrate how a teacher is attempting to engage pupils or how the layout had been altered to improve visual access and lines of sight would provide valuable insight into the process by which decisions were reached. Such a study would have to consider the physical layout of the classroom but also the social context, the type of school, the socio-economic status of the area as well as the teacher's pedagogical approach.

5.6. Conclusion

Teachers organise and manage their learning environment based on many complex factors. Eight overarching themes were identified. These were: cultural influence; school organisation; teacher's approach; physical adaptation; work adaptation; learning atmosphere; engagement and ownership; pupils/teacher relationship. The organisation of the classroom is so complex that teachers learn by experience, instinct, and observation rather than by any application of theory. Many factors influence teachers' choices including those which are external to the schools such as politics and socio-economic conditions. However, the major influences change depending on the pupils and the organisation of the school. The key attributes of a well-functioning learning environment are less a set of physical characteristics than a set of goals which define the learning experience and the pupils' relationship with the teacher. The codes and themes identified during the thematic analysis have provided a structure to describe the organisation and management of the classroom.

This study approached the subject of the organisation and management of the learning environment from a physical standpoint and aimed to focus on the alterable attributes of the classroom that could be manipulated to make a more productive environment. However, during this study it became apparent that even a detailed understanding of the physical environment would be of little use without understanding the political and social context. A realisation of greater significance is that the primary reasons for making alterations in the physical characteristics of the classroom are to engage pupils, give both pupils and teachers a sense of ownership and to create a safe learning atmosphere. Most importantly, to create a positive relationship between pupils and teacher. When organising and managing the classroom to best effect the classroom becomes a physical expression of the relationship between the pupils and the teacher.

This study has provided a basic understanding of how teachers organise and manage their classroom. It has demonstrated that the classroom is a complex and dynamic system with multiple influential factors. These results have the potential to inform later studies on the organisation and management of classrooms. These results also have the potential to influence the design, establishment and layout of classrooms in the future. This study will inform the design of later studies in this PhD.

Chapter 6. Study 2: 360° Video

Optimisation of 360° Video in a Classroom Setting

6.1. Introduction

360° videos are an immersive medium that would allow ITE students to experience simulated classroom environments. The significant advantage of 360° videos over other XR media is that the skill set required to produce 360° videos is less technically demanding than VR, MR and AR. 360° videos are more accessible both for the researcher and for potential participants. At time of writing, it continues to be supported in mobile VR through video sharing applications such as *YouTube*®. Nevertheless, skills and experience using the hardware and software for 360° video production are rare among non-technical researchers, even those investigating applications of VR technology. This study was undertaken to assess the suitability of using 360° videos as the primary medium for future studies in this PhD. Along with the systematic review presented in Chapter 7 this present study is part of the **design** phase of the ADDIE design framework (Allen, 2006). The design phase aims to identify the most suitable approach to answering the research questions. This study also aimed to optimise the use of 360° video technology for future research.

6.2. Background

Only with the recent application of mobile technology did 360° videos become widely available (Cochrane, 2016). When displayed on smartphones and combined with applicator headsets like the *Google Daydream* or the *Oculus GearVR* it provides an immersive experience similar to VR (Robertson, 2019). It is possible to view 360° videos on a desktop computer but at a greatly reduced utility that no longer provides the user with an immersive experience. The potential for using 360° videos in a teaching or learning environment is relatively new and unexplored.

Both VR and 360° videos present the user with an artificial reality. Both are simulated environments. It is misleading to think of one as more 'real' than the other. The technical difference being that one is based on 3D computer graphics and the other is based on spherical projection of overlapping digital images (Cameron, Gould and Ma, 2021). Izard *et al.* (2018) compared the value in medical education of what they described

as “two great general classifications for Virtual Reality.” The first being a completely artificial 360° environment, analogous to the modern definition of VR provided in Chapter 3. The second being the “reflection of our reality” using 360° videos. These ‘classifications’ of VR are out of date. Izard *et al.* (2018) conclude that 360° videos have similar potential for teaching and learning as other XR technologies. The most significant difference is that 360° videos typically are not interactive. Unlike VR which is, by definition, an interactive experience.

Izard *et al.* (2018) demonstrated 360° videos simulating a surgical environment with sufficient fidelity to be useful for teaching and learning. They added an interactive gaze system to their 360° video to provide additional information to the user. However, they did not provide any data on the transfer of learned skills to the real-world environment. Nor did they provide any detailed information about user experience when using their simulated environment. The primary value in Izard *et al.* (2018)’s study was to demonstrate that although 360° videos are a potential tool for teaching and learning, critical analysis of their effectiveness requires more research.

Several other papers have examined the potential for using 360° videos in other related fields. Yeo *et al.* (2020), for example, found that 360° videos, VR environments and 2D TV screens were equally effective in improving mood when showing users scenes of the natural world. Reeves *et al.* (2021) found that 360° videos were an effective therapeutic intervention to deal with public speaking anxiety. Several studies have investigated the effectiveness of 360° videos to effect user empathy. For example, Ventura *et al.* (2020) demonstrated the effectiveness of 360° videos, compared with narrative interactions, when developing empathy for victims of sexual harassment. Rodrigues and Loureiro (2022) demonstrated that 360° videos resulted in a different user perception of movies in the motion picture industry by generating greater empathy, coolness and positive word-of-mouth. These studies demonstrate the potential for using 360° videos in various settings.

Many of the long-established tools of traditional film production are either no longer applicable or are drastically altered in their application to a 360° environment. Cinematography, the art of film production by the application of creative camera angles, subject framing and camera movement, is conventionally designed to focus the attention of the user on the most important element of the frame and control the user’s point of

view (Kvisgaard *et al.*, 2019). In 360° videos, the user typically has the ability to focus attention wherever they like. This limits the effectiveness of other established filmmaking techniques such as montage. It is difficult for the filmmaker to make associations between edits when the user's attention may be focused away from key moments of the narrative (Cameron, Gould and Ma, 2021). Depth of field and other similar techniques are restricted in an immersive environment by the need to limit motion sickness (Kvisgaard *et al.*, 2019). It is, therefore, necessary to use other techniques to direct the user's attention and ensure that the desired information is being conveyed, particularly in a teaching and learning environment.

Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019) suggested that when producing 360° videos the user's attention could most effectively be directed using the *mise-en-scène*. This refers to the manipulation of the lighting, setting, props, actors, make-up and anything else in the scene that the filmmaker can control. The results of their study were ambiguous. Their analysis of the head movements of participants suggested that their focus was drawn towards those areas suggested by visual cues in the 360° videos. However, they found no difference in the recollection of the scene between participants who had experienced the visual cues and those who had not. Clearly further study and experience is required to understand the best practice when producing 360° videos. This present study aims to explore this while also assessing the potential for using 360° videos as an element of future studies in this PhD.

There are no real rules or guidance, as there are in other more established paradigms, for using technology like 360° videos in an education or research setting. As indicated in Chapter 3, 360° videos should be evaluated on such characteristics as the fidelity of the simulation, the level of immersion, the user's sense of presence and their utility as a learning and teaching environment (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). The user's level of comfort and their ability to access the desired experience are also of primary importance for the use of 360° videos in this PhD. It is on these characteristics that the 360° videos produced in this study will be evaluated. In assessing 360° videos as a potential research tool for this PhD they were compared to other more conventional media such as 2D digital video or still photographs but also to more technically complex methods like VR.

This study aimed to address two of this PhD's research questions: **Research Question 2: Can 360° video be used effectively as a medium for teaching and learning?;**

and **Research Question 4:** *What is best practice for using VR and 360° video to simulate classroom environments within Initial Teacher Education?*

It addressed these questions via the following three study aims:

1. To learn and practice the skills required to create and edit 360° videos.
2. To assess the potential limitations and advantages of using 360° videos as a primary element in future studies in this PhD.
3. To use the experience gained to inform best practice guidelines for future educators or academics who wish to use 360° videos in a similar setting.

6.3. Method

This study was undertaken in three phases. This allowed a pragmatic approach with the results of each stage informing the design and execution of the next. The three phases included:

- **Phase 1** – filming and editing of 360° videos in a classroom environment using equipment and locations available through UWS.
- **Phase 2** – additional filming of 360° videos using more specialist equipment and building on the perceived limitations of Phase 1.
- **Phase 3** – presenting the edited videos from Phases 1 and 2 (Video 1 and Video 2 respectively) to participants along with a questionnaire to gather feedback on the potential for using 360° videos in an education setting and of using 360° videos in future studies in this PhD.

6.3.1. Phase 1

Phase 1 involved creating a 360° video by filming students in a live classroom.

6.3.1.1. Equipment

Filming was carried out using a Samsung Gear 360 (2017) camera (Figure 6.1). The same camera used by Izard *et al.* (2018). A *Neewer* monopod with a stable base was also used. The camera was operated via a Bluetooth connection to a Samsung Galaxy S6 Edge mobile phone. The videos were downloaded on to a UWS HP EliteBook laptop, rendered and edited using a freeware editing app provided by Samsung, namely Gear 360 ActionDirector.

Figure 6.1: Samsung Gear 360 (2017) camera (Source: www.samsung.com)

6.3.1.2. *Environment*

Filming was carried out in an environment as close as possible to the intended research environment, a classroom. To avoid the ethical complications involved in filming pupils at primary or secondary schools filming was undertaken in a UWS lab with UWS students present. This was a suitable approximation for a school classroom.

Filming took place in the Science Lab on the Ayr Campus of UWS (Figure 6.2). The teaching session in progress at the time of filming was part of an ITE module conducted by Dr Stephen Day. Thirty-six students were present on the day of filming. All students were provided with a participant information sheet (Appendix 6.1) and consented to participation in the session (Appendix 6.2). The first half of the session involved the class being directed to a carousel activity and trying out a sequence of experiments that might be seen in the General Science classroom of a secondary school. The second half of the session involved feedback to the class relating to written reflections from lessons taught while on placement.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 6.2: Science lab on Ayr campus of UWS

6.3.1.3. *Filming and 360° video production*

In total 13 videos were recorded, each between 2 and 6 minutes in length, at a resolution of 4K with the camera being placed at various locations around the classroom. The camera locations were chosen to represent as much variety as possible, natural and unnatural camera locations including a “god’s view” which placed the camera high near the ceiling. The filming took a little less than one hour. The footage from the various camera positions was rendered and edited together into a single video to showcase the different locations around the classroom and with appropriate titles.

6.3.2. Phase 2

Phase 2 involved filming additional 360° videos using more specialist equipment and building on the perceived limitations of Phase 1

6.3.2.1. *Equipment*

Phase 2 of the study used a Vuze 3D 360 Camera (Figure 6.3), a more technically advanced camera and editing technology than that used in Phase 1. A Neewer tripod was used and operated via a Wi-Fi connection to a Hawuwei Y6 2018 mobile phone. The videos were downloaded onto an Omen HP Laptop 15 DC1xxx and rendered using the free software available for the camera, Vuze 3D 360 Camera. This software did not provide any editing capability. Editing was carried out using Adobe Premier Pro 2020.

Figure 6.3: Vuze 3D 360 Camera (Source: www.vuze.camera)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

6.3.2.2. *Environment*

Filming took place in the Physics Teaching Laboratory on the Paisley Campus of UWS (Figure 6.4). No-one was present during these filming sessions; the lab was not in use. The filming tested the technical qualities of the camera and provided footage for editing.

6.3.2.3. *Filming and 360° video production*

Six videos were recorded, each between 1 and 3 minutes in length, at a resolution of 4K with the camera being placed at various locations around the Lab. As before, the camera locations were chosen to represent a variety of natural and unnatural positions including a “god’s view”. The footage from the various camera positions was rendered and edited together into a single video along with music and titles to showcase the different locations around the classroom.

6.3.3. Phase 3

Phase 3 involved presenting the edited videos from Phases 1 and 2 (Video 1 and Video 2 respectively) to participants, along with a questionnaire, to gather feedback on the potential for using 360° videos in an education setting.

6.3.3.1. *Design*

A qualitative approach was taken to the design of the questionnaire to gather information from participants (Appendix 6.3). Phase 3 aimed to provide meaningful feedback on the value or problems of using 360° videos in an education setting and for future studies in this PhD. A qualitative approach was chosen because the information required was based on the participants experience and emotional reaction to the material (Mattimoe *et al.*, 2021). The feedback provided through the questionnaires rationalised the researcher’s observations while producing the videos and brought in other experience and expertise that had the potential to improve the creation and use of such videos for future research. The questionnaire was a series of open questions that allowed participants to think freely around the topic. Individual questionnaires were chosen because it was the approach most applicable to the restrictions resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic. The primary drawback of this approach is that the researcher is not present to pursue lines of enquiry, prompt the participant or guide the exploration of the topic (Tai and Ajjawi, 2016). The strength of this approach is that the participants had time to consider their feedback and their responses were not directly influenced by the researcher or by the presence of other

Figure 6.4: Physics teaching laboratory on the Paisley Campus of UWS

participants. Alternative methods may have been individual semi-structured interviews or focus groups conducted remotely via videoconferencing.

6.3.3.2. Participants

Participants were drawn from the UWS Immersive Group. The UWS Immersive Group included researchers from multiple disciplines within the University of the West of Scotland all of whom had an interest in XR technology. The main advantage of this was that it provided a breadth of expertise and reviewers who were familiar with 360° videos. This had the further advantage of maintaining the anonymity of the students who participated in Phase 1. The Informed Consent form signed in Phase 1, restricted viewing of the videos to members of the UWS Immersive Group. Although this did limit the pool of potential participants and introduce a potential bias in the results it was also the group of people most likely to have their own equipment upon which to view the videos. This factor was significant at the time of carrying out the data collection as it took place during the COVID-19 lockdown in 2020. This prevented any potential problems related to Covid-19 transmission because all participants viewed the material on their own equipment in an isolated environment with no need for sharing or borrowing equipment. Participants were provided with a participant information (Appendix 6.4) sheet and asked to provide informed consent (Appendix 6.5). Six participants watched the videos and provided feedback via the questionnaire.

6.3.3.3. Data Collection: Questionnaire

Video 1 and Video 2 were made accessible to participants via a secure YouTube account, not publicly accessible. Participants were emailed private links to the videos and the questionnaire. They viewed both videos before providing feedback. The questionnaire gathered feedback on production and presentation of the 360° videos. Specifically, what were the strengths and weaknesses of the medium, how best to present the videos and any thoughts participants had on its suitability as a medium for learning. The questionnaire included eight questions. The questions explored how it felt to view the videos, any obvious differences between the two videos and how the use of 360° videos might be improved in future studies. Questions 1, 2 and 4 aimed to gauge the experience of viewing 360° videos. Questions 3, 5 and 6 aimed to address how well the 360° videos were able to give participants a sense of the organisation and layout of the classrooms.

The seventh and last question explored participant insight on the advantages or disadvantages of 360° videos for use in education.

6.3.3.4. Analysis

Data analysis was informed by the ADDIE design process (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). This study provided data about user experience while using 360° videos. It also provided data to inform best practice for producing 360° videos. For this reason, the analysis was based on an iterative, user informed design process. This type of analysis uses open ended questions to reveal opinions or experiences and is often referred to as qualitative questionnaire analysis or a qualitative survey (Jansen, 2010). The typical aim of this type of analysis is to examine participants accounts of an experience to inform the design of future studies as is the case here. This approach has been successfully used in health research (Davey, Clarke and Jenkinson, 2019). In a study of this nature the aim is to gather data from a sample of a larger population, in this case educators, and look for diversity of experience while using the 360° videos.

This type of analysis has several strengths. It is a flexible approach to take in the early stages of a project when the ideas and experiences need to be explored (Jansen, 2010). It is also a responsive approach which can adapt to the feedback from participants. There are several limitations to this type of analysis. By presenting this to participants online and then receiving the data in a similar fashion there is no opportunity to expand on the information provided and the chance of misinterpretations of the data is increased. The narrow sampling, which is typical in this type of survey but also the result of the COVID-19 lockdown, means the results have the potential to be skewed by the limited base of participants. However, this potential bias is moderated by the aim of gaining general feedback on the experience rather than more specific or technical research aims.

The overall aims of the questionnaire were 1) To assess the positive and negative aspects of the user experience while watching the videos. 2) To gauge the ability of the user to discern the organisation layout of the classrooms. 3) To assess the users' opinion of the potential for using 360° videos as a medium for teaching and learning. This was informed by observations made in Phase 1 and Phase 2, and addressed the overall study aims. For this reason, the analysis took a deductive or pre-structured approach (Jansen, 2010). Data were sorted based on coding responses from the users which addressed the research aims of this study. A pragmatic exploratory approach was taken to the coding.

Specific responses from the participants were coded into categories that were relevant to the aims of the study. This was an iterative process involving multiple readings of the questionnaire responses.

6.3.4. Ethics

Ethical approval for Phase 1 was received from the UWS Ethics Committee on 21st March 2019 (Appendix 6.6). No extension of the original ethics application was required for Phase 2. No participants were present during these filming sessions. Ethical approval for Phase 3 was received from the UWS Ethics Committee on 4th October 2020 (Appendix 6.7). The following section will detail the results of all three phases of this study.

6.4. Results

6.4.1. Phase 1

The phase 1 filming session, using the Samsung Gear 360, was carried out successfully. The camera was easy to operate. The connected app on the Samsung Galaxy mobile phone allowed the user to see the video as it was being filmed along with being able to scan around the full 360° spherical projection. Using the editing software, Samsung, Gear 360 ActionDirector, it was possible to create a single file by editing together several examples of locations around the classroom.

Several limitations were already apparent when using this equipment. The first, although the HP EliteBook laptop was capable of rendering and editing the footage, it was not able to play the video files. The files were simply too large and had to be transferred to another system to be played. Second, the editing software allowed very little control over how the videos were displayed. There was no facility to enhance the image or correct errors in the rendering. It was not possible to reorient the sphere to a common forward facing so that between cuts the viewer appears to shift direction randomly.

The most significant limitation, however, was the poor visual quality of the video produced by this method. The level of detail was very low, the video was often blurry. This was because the video had necessarily been through several stages of conversion and editing, each one of which would have reduced the overall quality. In addition, there was also no sense of depth to the image. This is because the Samsung camera renders the two images from opposing lenses (Figure 6.5) onto into a single spherical image which is

viewed using the HMD (Figure 6.6). In Figure 6.6, the distortion in the flattened image is similar to cylindrical map projection. This negates the user's ability to use binocular methods of depth perception.

Figure 6.5: Two images from opposing lenses in the Samsung Gear 360 camera

Figure 6.6: Two images from the Samsung Gear 360 camera rendered as a single spherical image

It was possible to create several edited videos to showcase the potential of using 360° video technology in a learning environment. The viewer was able to look around and

experience a unique point of view on the scene at each of these locations. In addition, the camera is unobtrusive and omnidirectional, encouraging seemingly natural behaviour from participants. However, the poor visual quality of the videos produced along with the lack of binocular depth perception meant that although there seem to be some potential future utility in using 360° videos, limitations do exist. Phase 2 of this study would attempt to address the limitations by an overall improvement in the quality of the equipment.

6.4.2. Phase 2

The Vuze 3D 360 Camera, used in Phase 2 of this study, had eight lenses, two in each horizontal direction (Figure 6.7). This provides a “left eye” and “right eye” 360° projection and therefore stereoscopic depth perception. When stitched together and rendered using Vuze VR Studio this camera produces two spherical videos (Figure 6.8) that can be viewed as a stereoscopic image in an HMD. This provides a “left eye” and “right eye” 360° projection and therefore stereoscopic depth perception. The stereoscopic image allows the user to use both binocular and monocular cues for depth perception and, therefore, has a greater sense of depth than the single image produced by the Samsung Gear 360. The quality of the video was improved over the Samsung camera.

Adobe Premier Pro 2020 offered much greater editing utility than Gear 360 ActionDirector. It was possible to create various text overlays at suitable sizes for the frame. Multiple effects were available enabling the video to be enhanced, altered and edited in VR. It was possible to correct minor errors in the video which would have detracted from the experience. Crucially, Adobe Premier allows the editor to reorient the projected spheres so that the viewer is always facing in a direction that seems natural and meaningful. This is vital for drawing the attention of the viewer but also for minimising discomfort and nausea between edits.

360° video, when viewed stereoscopically through an HMD, is immersive and allows the viewer to experience multiple points of view in the same environment. The primary challenge is that the rendering and editing the video requires specialist equipment and software. The increasing quality of the specialist equipment results in a significantly higher financial investment. Care must be taken to produce the video at the best possible quality in order not to detract from the immersive experience and to maximize its potential value.

Figure 6.7: Two of the eight lenses around the Vuze 3D 360 Camera

Figure 6.8: Two spherical images rendered from the eight lenses of Vuze 3D 360 Camera

6.4.3. Phase 3

Six participants viewed Video 1 (Science Lab on the Ayr Campus of UWS with lesson in progress) and Video 2 (empty Physics Teaching Laboratory on the Paisley campus of UWS) and then provided written responses to the questionnaire. All had previous experience of using VR. Two of the participants had limited experience, using it only once or twice in their whole life, the remaining 4 were experienced and had a technical knowledge of how VR works. Of the 6 participants: 1 viewed the videos on a desktop monitor, 2 viewed the

videos via a mobile VR using a headset and 3 viewed the videos using an HMD. Although one participant viewed the videos on a desktop monitor, they were still able to rotate the video in 3 degrees of freedom and so could make valid comments on the experience of watching 360° videos. Additional demographic information about participants can be found in Appendix 5.10.

The research aims of this study were 1) to learn and practice the skills required to create and edit 360° videos, 2) to assess the potential limitations and advantages of using 360° videos as a primary element in future studies in this PhD, and 3) to use the experience gained to begin to inform best practice guidelines for future educators or academics who wish to use 360° videos in a similar setting. Phases 1 and 2 were mostly focused on study aim 1, learning and practicing skills, and the potential of 360° videos from the perspective of the researcher. Phase 3 provided feedback from educators. Phase 3 addressed study aims 2 and 3, and was built around three themes: 1) to assess the positive and negative aspects of the user experience while watching the videos, 2) to gauge the ability of the user to discern the organisation layout of the classrooms and 3) to assess the users' opinion of the potential for using 360° videos as a medium for teaching and learning. The responses provided by participants were coded and then categorised. The findings of Phase 3 will be presented in the following categories: sense of presence, camera position, visual clarity, advantages and disadvantages.

6.4.3.1. Sense of Presence

All participants agreed that they felt some sense of presence in both virtual environments. Participants attributed their sense of presence to several different factors. Most agreed it was increased by being in the familiar environment of a classroom. Some claimed that the presence of other students in the classroom made the environment feel more natural.

“The presence of being in the class with real students was enjoyable. It seemed natural as opposed to ‘staged,’ etc.... it made me feel as if was participating in the discussions going on.”

Participant P2

However, other participants thought that the lack of other students and the time given to look around in Video 2 allowed them to develop a sense of presence because it gave them time to experience the environment for themselves. Some commented on the

unrestricted freedom to look around in Video 2 and others preferred to have a focus, like the lecturer like in Video 1.

“I felt present in the environment, and the lack of students did help me to gain a sense of perspective and have a proper look around.”

Participant P2

Participants felt a greater sense of presence when the camera was placed in a more natural location, head-height as opposed to the “god’s view”. Their sense of presence could have been improved by the inclusion of positional audio. This would have also provided another way to focus the attention of the user, however, its inclusion in this study was beyond the scope of the equipment available. All participants commented on the quality of the audio. Some found the background noise to be too loud and distracting from the focus of the video (e.g., the lecturer in Video 1).

“Also the music was a little loud and distracting, especially when Mobile-VR has the speakers so close to your ears/face.”

Participant P2

The combination of 360° videos and VR headsets allowed the user to feel present in an artificial environment and that subtle changes in that environment could significantly alter the experience for the individual user. As with the creation of any complex media or audio-visual presentation care must be taken in establishing the composition, the focus of the presentation and the perspective of the viewer.

6.4.3.2. Camera Position

The preferred camera position for participants changed depending on the focus of the simulated environment. For example, when listening to the lesson, participants preferred the camera in a natural position like sitting at a desk. However, when attempting to understand the organisation and layout of the room participants preferred the overhead view, ‘god’s view’ or other vantage point.

“Really good feeling of classroom layout especially from ‘God view’ and centre of classroom on a stool.”

Participant P3

“The God view was the most effective to understand the layout of the classroom, however I did not feel I would be engage watching in that angle, it just felt odd.”

Participant P4

Participants responded more favourably to the camera being placed in a meaningful point-of-view. For example, at head height amongst a group of students or at a familiar location around the classrooms.

“I think sitting down next to students felt most natural and provided the best immersion out of all camera angles in both videos. However, this is coming from the perspective of me being a student within the classroom.”

Participant P6

Participants also reported being distracted by “clutter” in their immediate surroundings like bags, paperwork and things sitting on desks. Participant also reacted poorly to the camera being placed in a location close to a wall or other obstructions, which made them feel penned in and restricted their field of view. When the room was unoccupied, participants were able to easily understand the dimensions and layout with an uncluttered view of the whole room. In contrast, when the room was in use participants were better able to understand how people moved through the environment and the feeling of being present in the space.

“Layout was very very clear. Again, the lack of students, bags, jackets, personal belongings etc made the layout very easy to grasp.”

Participant P2

“Being placed next to a student as if I was sat next to them was the best view for me, this gave me the best immersive experience.”

Participant P5

Although participants mostly disliked the “gods view”, with some even feeling motion sickness, it was also recognised as a useful way to experience the whole layout from one point of view.

“The only thing I didn’t like about V1 was the “god’s eye” view at the end of the video. It made me feel slightly queasy and disassociated from what was going on roundabout me.

Participant P2

“The top view was good to overview the classroom and position myself on the space so I would have an idea of the layout, but it felt odd.”

Participant P4

The position of the camera effects the users’ comfort level, their sense of presence in the virtual world and their perception of the immersive experience. This demonstrates that the location of the camera, the point-of-view of the user, must be balanced between the user’s comfort and the intended purpose of the VR experience. To generalise, the camera should be placed in a location which is familiar, meaningful, uncluttered and with an unrestricted field of view for best overall effect.

“Natural camera positions were most effective (situated where a student would normally be located). Unnatural locations (above a desk) distract from the experience, changing the process from being part of the group of students, to being an external observer of the close.”

Participant P6

Participants also felt that they understood the layout and organisation of the classroom better when the 360° videos moved between different locations to give an overall impression of the layout. Participants frequently felt limited by the lack of ability to move around inside the artificial environment. The 360° videos offer only three degrees of freedom (DOF), as opposed to a true VR environment which would offer six degrees of freedom.

“[I] lacked being able to move in the 6DOF (lean forward/back). From watching both of these videos I would have been able to identify and spatially located myself within the environment, pointing to areas of the room for example.”

Participant P6

“I think having the ability to explore the environment would provide a better depth to understanding the layout. While the videos presented a good impression, I felt there was something missing... I think it might be the fact that I lacked control over moving from different perspectives, and had to wait until the video reached a new point to investigate and observe a new area of the environment.”

Participant P6

Several participants offered the suggestion that being able to move through the space would improve their understanding of the organisation and layout. Some participants felt that 360° videos simply lack explorable depth and that a 3D artificial environment in VR would allow the user a greater control over the experience along with the ability to explore at their discretion.

6.4.3.3. Visual Clarity

All the participants commented on lack of visual clarity of the image. The clarity of the visuals was sufficient to understand the environment although details at a distance were blurry and indistinct. Most of the participants commented on the difference in quality between the first and second video. The stereoscopic display and better-quality cameras giving the second video sense of depth and improved image quality respectively.

“The stereoscopic view and higher quality of this video add to that sense of presence.”

Participant P5

Participants commented that the lack of binocular depth perception in Video 1 made it more difficult to understand the organisation and layout of the classroom. Video 1 sometimes, *“felt more like I was in a spherical ball of video instead of a 3-dimensional room”* (Participant P5).

“I think there are issues with depth of perception because obviously this is a 360 monoscopic video therefore the sense of depth is reduced.”

Participant P4

In contrast, Video 2 did not give participants the same sensation of being *“in a spherical ball”*.

“This video [Video 2] had a great sense of depth and 3-dimensions, tables etc felt like they were placed next to me and I would be able to touch them and any items on place on them.”

Participant P5

In neither video was the resolution sufficient to read text or make out the diagrams on the whiteboard. Participants suggested that the problems with resolution, clarity and depth perception could be managed better in a true VR environment than in 360° videos. They suggested that, in a 3D artificial environment, *“movement through the space would be great and better resolution (especially at distances) would be good as you could then see what students were actually doing”* (Participant P3).

6.4.3.4. Advantages

All participants recognised the potential advantages of 360° videos to provide material for distance learning. 360° videos can also engage students in education that might otherwise be inaccessible to them because of a disability or, for example, due to social distancing restrictions resulting from a global pandemic. Participants recognised that being in a VR headset made them more engaged in the experience than the same video viewed on a flat screen. Participants were less likely to get distracted by something happening outside of the experience. There was an increased sense of presence in a 360° video when compared to a standard 2D desktop presentation. Participants described the illusion of being immersed in the experience rather than being a passive viewer.

“A recording of a learning experience in this way would allow me to feel like I have taken part in it. I would like to see more use of this technology as it provides multi-sensory and fully immersive learning experience.”

Participant P5

There were potential advantages for research since the participants were able to observe real-life activities, room layouts and how students behaved in the space without influencing their activities. The user could maintain an overview of the space and social actors in it, particularly because people being filmed seemed to forget about the 360° camera and acted naturally. This ability to observe without being seen and to replay the experience could be used when carrying out ethnographic research for example. One

participant demonstrated the usefulness of 360° videos as a medium to understand and organise space with the following observations:

“I suppose as the tables/chairs aren’t all facing the same way, it forces people to turn around and face the speaker – this might create some disassociation between the learner and teacher. However, the learning space quite obviously allowed the teacher to walk around and interact with the students one-to-one which I really liked. There was obviously space for him to do that.”

Participant P2

Being able to observe the environment at will, albeit from a fixed position, allowed participants to assess the learning space and make considered judgements about its attributes. A further advantage was the ability to edit videos together to present the environment from multiple positions and in different configurations. Clearly there are several potential advantages to using 360° videos if presented well.

6.4.3.5. Disadvantages

Several participants expressed the view that, at its current stage of development, 360° videos viewed via an HMD have, “... *more disadvantages in this approach to experiencing a lecture rather than traditional real-life experiences, or even conventional 2D video recordings.*” In fact, 360° videos viewed via an HMD take away several features of the normal lecture experience. For example, it is nearly impossible to take notes, it is more difficult to pause or replay portions of the video than if viewing the same on a desktop monitor. Despite the immersive quality of HMDs, the user remains a passive observer in the world. Constantly having to remove and replace the headset to take notes would negate much of the value of an immersive experience and would quickly become an irritation.

“I really felt ignored and powerless in a world where I could not interact with other individuals.”

Participant P4

The video quality was not adequate to be able to clearly see what written on a whiteboard from most natural seating positions around the classroom. Participants’ main

criticism of 360° videos was that they didn't offer anything that other approaches did not do better, particularly in terms of visual clarity, interactivity and multi-tasking.

“Although I felt involved, you are still watching other people so you can't interact, discuss etc which are important in the learning process.”

Participant P1

However, they suggested that the experience of a lecture, for example, could be improved by designing the presentation around the use of 360° video rather than simply recording a traditional lecture in progress. Another suggestion was that many of the technical limitations could be overcome by rejecting the use of 360° video altogether and using the HMD to present a purpose designed VR experience with 6DOF and an interactive environment.

6.5. Discussion

This study had three aims: 1) to learn and practice the skills required to create and edit 360° videos, 2) to assess the potential limitations and advantages of using 360° videos as a primary element in future studies in this PhD, and 3) to use the experience gained to inform best practice guidelines for future educators or academics who wish to use 360° videos in a similar setting. Overall, data from phases 1-3 suggest that, although disadvantages and barriers were identified, 360° videos demonstrate utility for learning in education settings. Nevertheless, 360° videos are an accessible and adaptable medium with promising benefits that warrant further exploration of how they can be used within ITE. Phases 1 and 2 of this study fulfilled study aim 1, which was to learn and practice the basic skills of 360° video production. Better equipment changed the viewing experience significantly, better editing software hugely improved the presentation. The most productive part of this study, in terms of informing future work, was consolidating the opinions of participants as they experienced 360° videos. The process of carrying out this study, along with feedback from participants, provided useful data that informed the design of later studies in this PhD. The results of this study also inform best practice when producing 360° videos for teaching and learning.

6.5.1. Advantages and Limitations of using 360° Videos for ITE

Based on this study, 360° videos are a suitable medium for providing remote access to any learning environment suitable for filming. 360° videos could provide access to remote or dangerous environments and can allow repetition of the same scenario for the purpose of learning. However, both characteristics are described by Kaplan *et al.* (2020) as consistent advantages of VR. VR has the added benefits of interactivity, six degrees of freedom and the developer has almost complete control over the design of the simulated environment. 360° videos have been used successfully in studies which manage social anxiety (Reeves *et al.*, 2021) or as training tools in medicine (Izard *et al.*, 2018). According to Izard *et al.* (2018) the main advantages of 360° videos is that they provide realistic imagery with an immersive environment. However, they go on to acknowledge that 360° videos lack an interactive component unless combined with VR elements and lack a sense of depth (their study did not have access to stereoscopic cameras). Two further limitations of Izard *et al.* (2018) is, one, that they use outdated terminology to refer to both 360° video and VR and two, that they do not have a robust method of measuring the effectiveness of 360° video as a tool for learning. They rely on user feedback at the testing stage and do not measure learning outcomes. Informed and critical user feedback is essential when developing 360° videos for teaching and learning. Based in these results the primary advantage of 360° videos over VR is that they are more easily able to recreate real-world environments, however, the disadvantage is the lack of movement, interactivity and control.

Participants suggested that the immersive quality of 360° videos was their primary advantage over desktop videos (2D media). This is supported by the work of Ventura *et al.* (2021), who used 360° videos to generate an empathic response to situations involving sexual harassment. Similarly, Han *et al.* (2022) noted the immersive quality of 360° videos to generate empathy and facilitate perspective taking. However, efficacy of 360° videos and VR to produce long term changes through an empathic response is still debated (Raz, 2022). The results of this present study suggest that 360° videos have the advantage of immersion over desktop media. However, they remain a largely passive experience (Izard *et al.*, 2018). Visual clarity was also a significant limitation compared to an equivalent desktop video. The 'realistic imagery' described by Izard *et al.* (2018), based on the results of this present study, is also limited by the clarity of the 360° videos. Participants were

unable to read text in the 360° videos unless the words were extremely large and clear (meaning more than 15 or 20cm and close to the point of view). Wang *et al.* (2018) is one of the few studies which discuss the problems with higher resolution and bandwidth when using 360° videos. However, the generalisability of their findings is limited by their use of terminology to describe XR which is applicable to the construction industry. This further demonstrates the need for a common technical language when describing XR technology. Despite their higher resolution and large size of 360° videos (often more than 1G of digital memory per minute of video) the user's eye is only able to focus on a tiny portion of the image when viewing in an HMD. The clarity of the video and the file size is limited by technological advances in the medium, however, desktop videos may be more appropriate for most applications.

In which applications would 360° videos be the appropriate choice? 360° videos may have an advantage by limiting external distractions. Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019) have already demonstrated that focusing the attention of the user in the 360° video required careful manipulation of the content of the scene. However, the effectiveness of their approach was debatable given that there was no significant difference in users' memory of the experience between the experimental group and the control group. Potentially limiting the effectiveness of directing the user's attention in a 360° video learning experience. When using VR participants in a study conducted by Real *et al.* (2020) claimed that VR focused attention in comparison to other media but no comparative data was provided to support this claim. The assertion that 360° videos (or even VR) can focus the user's attention is something which requires further research.

Participants also pointed out that 360° videos could be used in observational research by allowing researchers to feel *in* the space with minimal influence on participants. The utility of this idea could be limited by the clarity of the video and the lack of ability to take notes while using an HMD. The results of this present study, when combined with others, suggests that 360° videos have potential as an environment for learning and teaching, however, the limitations should be acknowledged. Future learning and teaching experiences in 360° videos should adopt an appropriate pedagogy, emphasise the advantages and adapt to the disadvantages of the medium.

6.5.2. 360° Videos in Future Studies

The second aim of this study was to assess the potential for using 360° videos as a key element of future studies in this PhD. There are several advantages of using 360° videos in future studies. Most importantly, that 360° videos can be effective in creating a sense of presence in the virtual world. Studies in XR technology have suggested that a sense of presence is important for teaching and learning (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). This suggest that 360° videos have potential as a tool for teaching and learning. The sense of presence was positively affected by the clarity of the video, the sense of depth in the video and by placing the camera in a meaningful location. In practice, this would have to be balanced against the technical limitations and the requirements of the virtual experience.

360° videos also provide an immersive experience which can be viewed repeatedly without increased risk to the user or the actors in the video. Kaplan *et al.* (2020) recognised this as one of the most important advantages of using XR for teaching and learning, the ability to view at leisure and repeat otherwise inaccessible scenarios. Participants in this study recognised the potential for using 360° videos to observe and understand the layout of a classroom environment. Viewing an empty classroom showcased the layout, however, viewing a 'live' classroom showcased flow and movement of the teacher and students through the space. The results of this study suggest that, when produced with an understanding of the intended learning outcome, 360° videos are a fast and reliable method of recreating a specific environment and simulating it using immersive technology.

For some learning scenarios, 360° videos have the potential to overcome the requirements of social distancing, disability access and safety. 360° videos presented in an HMD have the potential to limit distractions. Also, when used as a tool for research, 360° video can allow detailed observation of an environment while the researcher remains a remote observer. As Kaplan *et al.* (2020) suggested, researching the potential value of 360° videos for specialist tasks such as these, should be carried out on a case by case basis, evaluating each experience on its own merits and with due care and attention to the technology used and the production of the educational experience.

The results of this study suggest that the effectiveness of 360° video as a tool for education and research depends on the skill with which it is produced. The attention of the user has to be directed by the camera position, the environment itself and the audio

presentation. Editing together of multiple camera angles may be used effectively to give an overall impression of a larger environment. Evans *et al.* (2013) suggested that the fidelity of the simulation, considering elements like colour, audio and depth perception, also improves the value of the learning experience. However, it is unclear from their study to what extent these individual characteristics affect the learning experience. Based on this present study attributes of the 360° videos like clarity, audio and depth perception effect the user's experience but further research is required to assess how this affects the learning outcomes.

Interpreting the feedback from participants the primary limiting factors of 360° video may be broken down to resolution and interaction. The resolution of 360° video is limited by the rendering and production process. This means the resolution is typically lowered to create a file size manageable by a conventional computer. In practice, this means that faces could not be recognised at a distance and text could not be read. Even at this resolution, the file size still averaged around one gigabyte per minute of video. Meaning that in future studies participants would have to have access to equipment to download and run large file sizes.

The emphasis by participants on the lack of interaction in 360° videos may be partially attributed to the fact that the participant base was taken from people experienced in VR. Participants who were used to the 6DOF provided by VR may have felt restricted by the static point of view provided by 360° videos. However, it would be foolish to ignore participants desire to explore the simulated environment and to experience it from multiple points of view of their own choosing. For this reason, future studies could consider the option of using 360° videos in combination with other forms of XR presentation.

There are media that could be considered as an alternative to or perhaps used in combination with 360° videos to mitigate its limitations. One possible alternative would be to 3D laser scan the environment to build a three-dimensional simulation of the classroom (Arayici, 2007). This would solve the problems of camera position and movement in the virtual space by allowing the user to move in 6DOF around a digital recreation of the classroom. At time of carrying out the study, this would have been labour intensive and time consuming to produce requiring specialist equipment. However, more

recently online services, for example Matterport (Jackson, 2023), have provided a user-friendly alternative to creating virtual tours.

The lack of movement in 6DOF along with the limitations in resolution and camera position could also be solved by recreating a similar environment using a 3D game engine like Unity3D (Unity., 2022). Other useful features like positional audio and teleportation could then be included. This would involve building a wholly artificial simulated classroom for used in future studies. Another advantage of this approach is that it would give the researcher almost complete control over the *mise-en-scène*.

Findings from this study suggest it could be advantageous to include 360° videos in future studies in this PhD. Their relative ease of production, their ability to simulate real-world environments, their accessibility to participants and their ability to be viewed on multiple platforms all made 360° videos a suitable candidate for further research within this project. However, to address the limitations of 360° videos the intention was to present them in comparison to VR environments.

6.5.3. Best Practice Guidelines for Creation of 360° Videos

An important part of this study was participant feedback on how best to present an immersive environment to participants in future studies in this PhD. Building on the research carried out by Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019), these findings informed the development of best practice guidance (Table 6.1). Best practice involves four key steps. Firstly, and most importantly, clearly understand the purpose for which the immersive experience will be used and, if appropriate the intended learning outcomes. For example, if experiencing a lesson in a classroom the camera position should be natural. If trying to understand the layout of a classroom the camera position can be a more artificial vantage point.

Secondly, creating a sense of presence in the user is one of the most important characteristics of an immersive experience. This is particularly true if the purpose of the experience is teaching and learning (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). According to the data collected by the study this sense of presence can be increased in the user by placing the camera in a natural position in familiar surroundings. The user should be given time to visually explore then environment, to acclimatize themselves to the virtual space. The

degree of immersion is increased by use of directional audio which reflects what the user is seeing. This also has the potential to increase the sense of presence.

Table 6.1: Best practice guidelines for creation of 360° videos

360° Videos Best Practice - Summary	
Clearly understand the purpose of the Immersive experience.	<p>What feelings are you trying to create in the user?</p> <p>How will the experience be used/viewed?</p> <p>Who are the intended audience?</p> <p>What are the intended outcomes?</p>
Create a sense of presence in the user.	<p>Place the user in a natural position in familiar surroundings.</p> <p>Give the user time to acclimatize themselves to the virtual space.</p> <p>Use meaningful directional audio to increase the degree of immersion.</p>
Make use of the mise-en-scène.	<p>Manage the lighting, colour, actors, sound and objects present in the environment to direct the user's attention according to the identified purpose of the video.</p>
Chose the most appropriate technology.	<p>Understand the limits of the visuals. If details in the video need to be recognised, make sure the video quality is appropriate.</p> <p>Binocular depth perception provides a more convincing 3D environment.</p> <p>Limit user discomfort by using natural camera positions and smooth edits.</p>

Third, it is important to make use of mise-en-scène. As demonstrated by Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019) the mise-en-scène may be used when producing 360° videos to direct the user's attention. This present study demonstrated that sound, layout, colour schemes, objects present in the environment and the presence or absence of people all effect the user experience and the usefulness of a 360° video. Most of these can be controlled in a 360° video but only by arranging the location in advance as would be done in any film

production. This process is closely linked with the purpose of the video, for example, a cluttered populated environment to demonstrate the use of a classroom in ethnographic research or an uncluttered perspective with few other people so that a lecture might be clearly understood.

Finally, the limited resolution of the video, particularly at a distance means that details might be obscured. This can be partially managed by using appropriate lighting and the best camera available. Binocular depth perception gives a far greater sense of presence by creating a more convincing 3D environment. This can only be achieved by using stereoscopic images. Minimal camera movement, smooth edits and natural camera positions all help to manage the potential for motion sickness in users which can limit the value of the learning experience (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018).

Although this study has only explored the initial potential of 360° videos and how they might be used in teaching and learning, it has provided useful feedback on the design of immersive environments and the user experience. Several ideas are suggested for future studies involving 360° videos. One is that both the equipment and the production could be better chosen for purpose. For example, if experiencing a lecture, a single fixed camera position with a clear focus. If exploring a space, then multiple camera locations in an uncluttered environment. Future studies using 360° videos could also make better use of audio production and editing. 360° videos remain a flexible and useful medium the quality of which improved constantly with advances in technology. Further study is required to determine how they might best be used in research and education.

6.5.4. Impact of COVID-19

As described above, this PhD originally proposed to produce 360° videos within primary and secondary school classrooms. The aim was to evaluate their feasibility as a learning tool with ITE students in comparison to other media like VR. This version of the PhD was in progress at the time when the first COVID-19 lockdown was announced. Ethical approval had been received from the UWS Ethics Committee to carry out a study that included interviewing in-practice teachers in their workplace and producing 360° videos of their classrooms. As the lockdown commenced, schools closed, and a separate ethics application, which was under consideration by Education Services Research Group (ESRG) of Glasgow City Council, was refused. The information provided by ESRG was that no

further research of any kind would be approved in schools. This remained the case throughout the key data collection timeline of this PhD and beyond. Filming in schools was impossible. Interviewing teachers in their workplace was similarly not possible. Access to other locations, such as the UWS campus, for the filming of 360° videos was also extremely limited throughout the lockdown. In effect this meant that any further use of 360° videos in this PhD was impossible. Discussions were held with the PhD supervision team to explore how the PhD could continue *and* produce meaningful outputs to inform future ITE. The decision was taken to focus completely on VR experiences. Although disappointing, data from this present study exploring 360° video was not redundant. Study 2 provided valuable data for the design and presentation of the virtual environments described later (Chapters 8 and 9). The results of this present study also helped inform the conclusions and final recommendations of this PhD (Chapters 10 and 11).

6.6. Conclusion

The use of 360° videos as a tool for teaching and learning is relatively new. There exists very little guidance on best practice for using 360° videos as there is in more established paradigms. This study had three aims. These were 1) to learn and practice the skills required to create and edit 360° videos, 2) to assess the potential limitations and advantages of using 360° videos as a primary element in future studies in this PhD, and 3) to use the experience to inform best practice guidelines for future educators or academics who which to use 360° videos in a similar setting. Study aim 1 was achieved by undertaking the study. When addressing Study aim 2, it was found that 360° videos had many advantages that would make them suitable for inclusion in other studies in this PhD. Advantages included the accessibility of 360° videos compared to other XR media. 360° videos provide immersion and a sense of presence greater than desktop media. However, 360° videos also have limitations, these include the lack of interactivity and freedom-of-movement which is present in VR. Findings from this study informed best practice guidelines for using 360° videos in education settings. Four key steps are outlined by these best practice guidelines: 1) Clearly understand the purpose of the experience, 2) Aim to create a sense of presence in the user, 3) Make use of the *mise-en-scène* to direct the user's attention, and 4) Choose the technology most appropriate for the desired

outcomes. As described above, due to the COVID-19 restrictions, the production of 360° videos played no further part in this PhD. However, the conclusions of this present study informed the design of later studies. The remainder of this PhD focused on VR. The next chapter will continue to identify the most suitable approach to answering the research questions by assessing the effectiveness of using VR as a medium for teaching and learning in social complex environments like a classroom.

Chapter 7. Study 3: Systematic Review

Exploring the use of VR for professional teaching and learning in complex social situations

7.1. Introduction

Virtual reality (VR) in the form of simulated environments has been used as a tool for teaching and learning for decades (Jerard, 2016). Even before the development of modern consumer VR technology, the benefits of using simulated environments had been a recognised part of military training (Ahir *et al.*, 2019), surgical training (Izard *et al.*, 2018) and dental training (Joda *et al.*, 2019). Since the launch of the Oculus Rift in 2016, VR has become more accessible and cost effective. In addition, the definition of VR has narrowed to focus on those systems that include a 360°-computer generated environment, allow the user to interact with that environment and use an immersive display such as an HMD or CAVE systems (Jerard, 2016). In the modern world of Extended Reality (XR) technologies, VR is one of many technological possibilities including augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR) and 360° video. This systematic review will focus on the use of VR in teaching and learning. VR allows the user to experience 6-degrees of freedom and interaction with a simulated environment. The flexibility of VR, the ability to repeat complex scenarios and access dangerous environments makes it advantageous for certain types of teaching and learning, particularly technical or procedural tasks (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). Jensen and Konradsen's review (2018) demonstrated the potential of using VR to learn affective skillsets, such as listening and communication. These are skills required by preservice teachers in managing their learning environments. Their review, however, was limited by a small number of papers, highlighting a gap to be addressed by this PhD.

Overall, this PhD aims to assess the potential for using VR in teacher education. Specifically, for the organisation and management of classrooms. Study 1 demonstrated that the organisation and management of classrooms is a complex challenge involving physical and social factors. Study 2 demonstrated the potential for using 360° videos to simulate classroom environments, however, they limited the user's ability to move or interact with the environment. Along with Study 2, this systematic review is part of the **design** phase of the ADDIE design framework (Allen, 2006). The design phase aims to find

the most suitable way of addressing the research questions. This systematic review explores the potential for using VR for teaching and learning in socially complex situations. Teacher education involves professional and vocational instruction so this review will focus on studies that involve professional training.

This systematic review assessed the potential for VR as a tool for teaching and learning in contexts which are as similar as possible to that of a working classroom. *Similar*, is taken to mean contexts that require an appreciation of complex social factors, that do not rely on procedural or technical skills and that take place in a professional or vocational setting. Therefore, the aim of this systematic review was to assess the feasibility of using VR as a teaching and learning tool for complex social situations in vocational or professional environments. This was achieved by addressing three study questions:

1. How are VR experiences being designed to facilitate learning of complex social situations in vocational or professional environments?
2. How effective are VR experiences at facilitating learning of complex social situations in vocational or professional environments?
3. How do participants respond to VR experiences used for teaching and learning?

7.2. Methods

7.2.1. Study Design

This study used a systematic review design. Systematic reviews use a robust and replicable method of collating and synthesising published data (Patole, 2021). The review adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidance, a validated method of increasing quality of systematic reviews (Page *et al.*, 2021).

7.2.2. Search Strategy

A search strategy was developed to address the research questions of the review. This involved identifying relevant databases, developing search criteria and eligibility screening criteria. These are outlined below.

7.2.2.1. Database Sources

Four databases were identified as relevant and suitable for this review, including Scopus, EBSCO, Medline and Web of Science (WoS). These are large, well-documented databases

that include studies across a range of key journals and disciplines. Pilot searches in these four databases found relevant studies, reinforcing their suitability for this review.

7.2.2.2. Search Criteria

Key search terms were developed to identify studies exploring the use of VR as a tool for teaching and learning complex social situations in vocational or professional environments. Pilot searches helped identify alternative terms used by published studies. For example, “virtual reality” may also be identified in some studies as “extended reality” or “immersive systems.” Similarly, communication skills may be identified in other studies as “social skills” or “teamwork.” Searches were performed in the title and abstract search fields of the four identified databases. Search terms were combined with Boolean operators such as “AND” and “OR”. Truncated words were identified using an asterisk to help identify variations of a word. For example, *augment** would retrieve *augmented*, *augments* and *augmentation*. Quotation marks were used to retrieve precise phrases, for example, “*virtual reality*”. Parentheses were used to group categories of search terms together, for example, (“*virtual reality*” OR “*extended reality*”). The final search terms are presented in Table 7.1.

Table 7.1: Search terms

Search Terms
("virtual reality" OR "extended reality" OR immersive)[/Title] AND (social* OR empathy OR communication* OR emotion* OR affective OR kindness OR bullying OR mood OR peer OR relation*)[/Title/Abstract]

The final searches were performed in May 2023. All articles located via database searching were imported into Endnote referencing software (Version 20.2.1)(Clarivate., 2021). The reference lists of key articles were also searched to identify additional articles via the ‘snowballing’ technique (Patole, 2021).

7.2.2.3. Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were created to identify relevant papers for the review. Criteria were developed using the SPIDER framework (Sample, Phenomenon of Interest

Design; Evaluation; Research Type) (Table 7.2) (Cooke, Smith and Booth, 2012). The SPIDER framework is a tool for exploring articles expected to be mixed methods e.g. a mix of qualitative and quantitative data. SPIDER is endorsed by the Cochrane Collaboration, recognised experts in systematic review methodology (Noyes *et al.*, 2022).

Table 7.2: Eligibility criteria

SPIDER component	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Sample	Adult participants using VR to potentially improve their social or affective skills in a vocational or professional setting	<p>Studies with children or adolescents.</p> <p>Training that did not have a vocational or professional application.</p> <p>Studies exploring technological improvements rather than learning outcomes.</p>
Phenomenon of interest	<p>Studies providing insight on how VR experiences are designed to achieve the intended learning outcomes.</p> <p>Studies providing insight on how effective VR experiences are at achieving the desired learning outcomes.</p> <p>Studies providing insight on how participants respond to VR experiences used for teaching and learning.</p>	<p>Studies exploring VR factors other than social or affective skills.</p> <p>Studies exploring only empathy without assessing other relevant skills.</p> <p>Studies exploring procedural or technical training.</p> <p>Studies that did not involve training, teaching or learning.</p> <p>Studies exploring therapeutic or medical interventions and not skills training.</p>

Design	Various study designs may be relevant, including pre-post tests, questionnaires/surveys, interviews or focus groups	Systematic reviews, meta-analyses, literature reviews, editorials, and conference abstracts.
Evaluation	Studies providing data on learning outcomes, participants' experience of using VR or the effect of VR as a learning environment.	Studies providing data only on empathic outcomes. Studies providing no evaluation data.
Research type	Quantitative, qualitative or mixed methods.	None
Additional criteria	Studies published from 2016 onwards. Studies published in English. Studies exploring the use of VR – according to the modern definition (Chapter 3).	Articles published before 2016. This ensures data included in the review is up to date. Studies not available in English language. Studies only exploring desktop applications, 360° videos or augmented reality (AR).

Some papers were excluded because they dealt with 360° videos only rather than VR. This included papers that provided a computer-generated environment, but which limited the user to 3-degrees of freedom and with no interactive component.

Papers that examined empathy alone were excluded. A large number of research papers are currently available that explore the potential of VR as an empathy machine (Xu and Zhang, 2022). However, many researchers question the validity of the kind of training that uses VR experiences to induce empathy. For example, Raz (2022) questioned the capability of VR to generate true empathic feelings and identified ethical complications of using VR to manipulate the feelings of users via multisensory stimulation. Sora-Domenjó

(2022) suggested that there is little evidence to suggest that using VR to generate empathy has a corresponding effect on social behaviour. They go on to say that very few studies consider the long-term effects of using VR to generate empathy and that further research is required to understand the effects. Full consideration of the significance or dangers of VR as an empathy machine is beyond the scope of this review. However, papers that examined empathy along with another social and vocational skill (like communication or teamwork) were retained.

Papers that did not deal with professional or vocational learning were excluded, for example, Tidbury *et al.* (2020) examined the use of VR to develop teamwork in healthcare students. This study was excluded because the VR experience was a game involving bomb disposal and was not directly related to their professional skillset. For inclusion, studies required a focus on how VR influenced professional 'social' skillsets in a vocational or professional environment, for example, in DeWitt *et al.* (2022) the skills learned in the VR environment were directly relevant to professional context. Papers that explored VR to learn a language in a non-professional context were excluded.

Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) identified that several papers argue for the use of simulated environments in education accessed on a desktop computer screen. In research, this is sometimes referred to as desktop VR or low-immersive VR. For the purposes of this systematic review these expressions were not recognised as VR. As expressed in Chapter 3, the modern definition of VR mandates that the computer-generated world be experienced via an HMD or equivalent immersive device like a CAVE system. Papers where the participant experience does not conform to the modern definition of VR were excluded from this study.

7.2.3. Study Screening and Selection

All articles retrieved via database and snowball referencing were imported into Endnote reference software (Version 20.2.1) (Clarivate., 2021). Duplicates were identified via two methods: (i) the 'find duplicates' tool within the Endnote library tab; and (ii) manual searching for duplicates. The remaining articles were screened against the eligibility criteria in two phases. Phase 1 involved screening titles and abstracts. Studies not meeting the inclusion criteria were excluded. Phase 2 involved screening the full text of remaining

articles against the eligibility criteria. Reasons for exclusion were recorded for all excluded articles. All remaining eligible studies were included in the review.

7.2.4. Quality Appraisal

Assessing study quality is important when synthesising data from different studies. It helps identify limitations of included studies, identifies sources of bias and helps inform interpretation of the findings (Protogerou and Hagger, 2019). All included studies were assessed using quality appraisal tools from the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) (Munn *et al.*, 2014) and the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI Collaboration., 2020). CASP and JBI are widely used appraisal programmes, providing appraisal checklists for different study designs (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2022; Aromataris and Munn, 2020).

The appropriate appraisal checklist was chosen for each included study. For example, the cross-sectional appraisal tool was used for cross-sectional studies, and qualitative appraisal tool was used for qualitative studies etc. Each tool asks questions on items such as recruitment, outcomes measures and analysis methods. Questions are answered with either a “yes”, “no” or “can’t tell”. Final scores of 7 or more (of 10 max) indicate acceptable quality. The quality scores of all included studies in this review were recorded and will be presented alongside the results.

7.2.5. Data Extraction

An excel data extraction form, tailored to the research questions, was used to extract relevant information from the included studies. Data extracted from all studies included: Author, year of publication, country where the study was conducted, inclusion and exclusion criteria, key recruitment strategy, sample size, description of participants, research aims and objectives, outcome measures, key findings, and study quality ratings.

7.2.6. Data Synthesis

Results were collated and presented using a narrative synthesis approach. This is recognised as a strong approach when synthesising data from a range of study designs (Ryan and Cochrane Consumers and Communication Review Group., 2013). It allowed the data to be synthesised, grouped and presented in a narrative presentation. Meta-analyses were not appropriate for this study, where findings were heterogenous in relation to outcomes measures and study designs.

7.3. Findings

Database searches yielded 1,422 papers (Figure 7.1). No additional articles were identified by manual searching. After removing duplicates (n=463), 959 papers were included for title and abstract screening. After title and abstract screening, 69 papers were included for full text review. After screening full texts, nine research papers met the study criteria and were included in the final review. Table 7.3 presents a summary of study characteristics including assessment of study quality of which all were assessed as moderate to high quality.

Figure 7.1: PRISMA flowchart of study selection

Table 7.3: Table of characteristics of included studies (n=9)

Author, year, location	Study design and aim	Participants	VR scenario	Methods and outcomes measures	Key findings	Study quality ⁺
Amini et al. 2021 USA	A quasi-experimental pre-post design To evaluate a VR simulation for dental training	N=29 dentists (dental residents/faculty) Mean Age (SD) 36.34 (14.75)yrs	“MPATHI” (‘Making Professionals Able Through Immersion) - a simulation aimed at improving dentist-patient interactions. The simulation takes the role of “an English-speaking caregiver with limited socioeconomic resources seeking dental care for a child in a Spanish-speaking country”	<i>Methods</i> Participants engaged with the simulation in three parts - (i) 360° video of an ‘insensitive’ dentist-patient interaction; (ii) virtual group reflection of part one; (iii) a repeat dentist-patient interaction using health-literacy-informed practice <i>Measures</i> Data were collected at four points. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive knowledge (5 item multiple-choice quiz tailored to training content) • Skill-based knowledge (9 items tailored to the training) • Affective knowledge (9-item version of the California Brief Multicultural Competence Scale) 	MPATHI led to increased mean scores for cognitive (pre = 3.48 ± 0.80, post = 4.56 ± 0.51, p < 0.001), affective (pre = 4.20 ± 0.4, post = 4.47 ± 0.44, p < 0.001), and skill-based learning (pre = 4.00 ± 0.47, post = 4.52 ± 0.37, p < 0.001) immediately post-training. There was not a significant difference between skills measured immediately post-training and in the 1-month posttraining survey (p = 0.41). Participants reported high satisfaction with the content and methods used in this training.	6/6

Chae et al. 2023 South Korea	One group post-test design and qualitative follow-up To describe the development and feasibility testing of a simulation aimed at improving nursing skills in cross-cultural communication	N=15 Undergraduate nursing students	“SimCARE” (Simulation for Culturally Appropriate care in Real-life Episodes) – a simulation facilitating interaction with patients from different cultures SimCARE was developed using the ADDIE model	<i>Methods</i> Feasibility was assessed using a quantitative, pilot 1 group post-test design and 4 qualitative focus group interviews. <i>Measures</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15-item Virtual Presence scale • 12-item Perceived Usability scale • 20-item Korean version of the Simulation Design Scale • 19-item Korean version of the Post Study System Usability Questionnaire • 6-item task difficulty questionnaire developed by the research team 	SimCARE demonstrated a good level of sense of presence (mean score 5 of 7 sd 1.04) and high usability (mean score 4.58 of 5 sd 0.42) and high satisfaction (1.83 of 7 sd 0.84) by participants. Recommendations for optimising implementation, include: a VR tutorial; immediate feedback; opportunities for reflection through debriefing; and content selected to match learners’ level of understanding.	6/6
DeWitt <i>et al.</i> 2022 Malaysia	Quasi-experimental design To investigate whether students who design their	N=31 college level students undertaking a MFL class 22 female, 9 male	Students engaged with five 360-degree images Chinese culture aligned with the MFL curriculum	<i>Methods</i> In pairs, students designed an interactive VR element using at least two of the images. The resulting VR environment was to be made using Google Tour	Significant increase in all domains of the SSIC (knowledge, skills, attitudes and awareness)	6/7

	own immersive VR environments of Chinese culture for viewing could improve their Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) level in Mandarin as a Foreign Language (MFL)	Age range 21-25yrs	(i.e. Chinese home life, dining, traditional medicine, calligraphy, temple scenario, and tea ceremony)	<p>application and images had to be tagged and labelled in Chinese pinyin and traditional characters, alongside a brief summary of the item's use in Chinese culture</p> <p><i>Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey of Students' Intercultural Competence (SSIC) (five-point Likert scale) • Survey on Learning Chinese Culture through VR (SLCCVR), comprising of 13 items with a five-point Likert-scale and seven open-ended questions. • Qualitative interviews 	Qualitative findings demonstrated improved understanding and positive perception of Chinese culture	
<p>Mayor Silva <i>et al.</i></p> <p>2023</p> <p>Spain</p>	<p>Randomised controlled trial, with a pretest and a posttest.</p> <p>To develop and evaluate a VR simulator for improving communication skills compared with</p>	<p>N=100 undergraduate nursing students</p> <p>Intervention n=50 Control n=50</p> <p>84% female</p>	Not described	<p><i>Methods</i></p> <p>Intervention group was provided with a VR simulation. The control group was provided with a case-based traditional workshop. Both aimed to improve communication skills.</p> <p><i>Measures</i></p>	Both approaches significantly improved communication skills, however, the VR group demonstrated showed significantly greater improvement (P<0.01). The VR group also showed better results in older students.	5/7

	a traditional workshop			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Nursing Skills Assessments Scale (ECOEnf) - Skill Unit UC6 Communication and Interpersonal Relationships 		
Real <i>et al.</i> 2017 USA	<p>Quasi-experimental design</p> <p>To evaluate the potential role for immersive VR in medical education, specifically for relational skills training</p>	<p>24 paediatric doctors (of postgraduate level 2 or 3)</p> <p>Age range 25-29yrs</p> <p>Participants were primarily Caucasian female</p>	<p>Kern's six-step approach to curriculum development was used to create an immersive VR curriculum about communication skills to address influenza vaccine hesitancy</p>	<p><i>Methods</i></p> <p>Participants individually completed three scenarios within the VR curriculum (approx. 15mins duration)</p> <p><i>Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey immediately post-intervention to assess attitudes and effectiveness of VR curriculum Survey 1-month post intervention to assess trainee-perceived impact on clinical practice 	<p>Ninety-two percent (n = 22) agreed or strongly agreed that VR simulations were like real-life patient encounters. Seventy-five percent (n = 18) felt that VR was equally effective to standardised patient encounters and less effective than bedside teaching (P < 0.001).</p> <p>At 1-month follow-up, 67% of residents (n = 16) agreed or strongly agreed that the VR experience improved how they counselled families in cases of influenza vaccine hesitancy</p> <p>Despite positive feedback regarding the</p>	4/6

					VR curriculum, residents expressed preference for bedside teaching over VR	
Real et al. 2020 USA	One group post-test design and qualitative follow-up To assess the usability of a VR curriculum for physicians to address human papilloma virus (HPV) vaccine hesitancy in patients	4 female physicians working in an urban adolescent primary care clinic Mean age 43yrs	A 20-minute VR curriculum where participants verbally counselled animated caregivers (avatars) who were hesitant to accept the HPV vaccine for their children.	<i>Methods</i> Participants worked through the VR curriculum and reacted to avatar responses in real time with a facilitator. Participants had to pass tasks to proceed. <i>Measures</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Semi-structured interviews to assess usability 	All participants reported the VR simulation as realistic, captured their 'senses' and presence. They all reported learning new skills and appreciated the opportunity to learn in a safe environment	4/7
Sapkaroski 2022 Australia	Split-cohort design To determine whether the mode of delivery of training assigned to the groups (role-play or VR) gave a measurable difference in clinical empathy	Trainee practitioners (n = 70) and qualified practitioners (n = 9) 57% female	A VR simulation about communicating with claustrophobic patients following previous MRI scans. The scenario was developed in a guided format such that participants using	<i>Methods</i> Participants were randomly assigned to four groups: clinician VR (CVR), clinician role-play (CRP), trainee VR (TVR), and trainee RP (TRP). <i>Measures</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SE-12 communication skills questionnaire 	Participants in the TVR group reported significant improvements in communication confidence post training (+11% P<0.05), as did the CVR group (+7.2% P<0.05). Trainees assigned to the role-play intervention also reported a significant improvement.	6/7

			it explained the procedure of an MRI scan to a patient in nine scaffolded steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and assessment tool developed by a panel of experts 	Assessment of participant's ability to select empathic statements showed the TVR group performed 5% better on average than their role-play counterparts ($P < 0.05$).	
Stavroulia <i>et al.</i> 2019 Cyprus	Quasi-experimental design To explore whether a VR-based learning paradigm is more effective for the professional development of teachers.	25 participants (16 active teachers, 9 not currently working as teachers)	<p>Participants engaged in a simulated VR scenario from two different perspectives (the teacher versus the student).</p> <p>The scenario was related to substance use, and based on a real-life incident where a substance was given to a 12-year-old student by classmates</p>	<p><i>Methods</i> Paper presents the design process of a simulated VR scenario (substance use in schools) using the ADDIE design framework.</p> <p><i>Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A pre-test and post-test questionnaire, using Likert-scale questions to explore participants' empathy skills and mood states (based on validated scales such as the Positive and Negative Affect Scale) • Biometric measures: heart rate and electroencephalogram (EEG) brain signal recording 	<p>Post-test scores showed a significant increase in participant's negative mood states (including fear, nervousness, sadness, upset, shame or downheartedness). The authors conclude this suggests the VR scenario had a strong impact on participants.</p> <p>Post-test HR was significantly higher than pre-test HR ($Z=-2.86, p=0.004$). Beta brainwaves were detected when engaged in both scenarios. These increases in HR and EEG beta waves suggest a state of stress and anxiety.</p>	6/7

					There was no statistically significant change in positive mood states. No difference in HR when viewed from the teacher or student perspective.	
Stavroulia and Lanitis 2019 Cyprus	Quasi-experimental To investigate the possibility of using a VR-based approach aiming to enhance teacher's reflection and empathy skills	33 participants from the higher education sector 22 male and 11 female Age range 18-59yrs	The VR scenario dealt with multiculturalism and verbal bullying. Participants were able to experience the scenario from the perspective of both the teacher and also the student being bullied	<i>Methods</i> Three groups (n=11 per group) experienced one of three experiments: (i) the physical setting (PS) group engaged with a real-life scenario with real students; (ii) the VR group engaged with <i>either</i> a realistic classroom environment, or an imaginative classroom environment. <i>Measures</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A questionnaire developed by the research team to assess participant reflection and empathy 	There was a statistically significant difference between the VR and PS group for: challenging ideas and beliefs (U = 54.5, p = .003); how teachers may support students (U = 34, p = .000); the teacher's ability to enter the student's position (U = 20, p = .000); and teacher's ability to support students from racial and ethnic minority groups (U = 45, p = .001). The control group that did not use the VR system scored lower in all items of the reflection scale and tended to be	6/7

Chapter 7. Study 3: Systematic Review

					more undecided regarding the effectiveness of their training within the real classroom setting. There were no differences in perceived empathy between the control and VR groups.	
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*Measured using JBI quality appraisal tools (JBI Collaboration., 2020).

Of the nine papers, six examined the use of VR for teaching and learning in the field of medicine, one paper examined the use of VR in cultural competence and language skills and the final two papers examined the use of VR in teacher education. The majority of the papers ($n=6$), examined the development of communication skills in specific scenarios. These included teamworking, counselling, interprofessional skills and cross-cultural communication. The remaining papers ($n=3$), examined the use of VR as a tool for empathic or emotional development related to specific social situations. These three papers met the study criteria because they measured the outcome of knowledge and skills in addition to empathy. For example, identifying incidents of bullying, self-reflection on emotional situations, cognitive knowledge and skill-based knowledge.

The participants in each of the studies were working professionals or higher education students working towards a relevant vocational qualification. Most of the studies had small participant groups of between 15 and 32 participants. The exceptions were Real *et al.* (2017) who had four participants and Sapkaroski *et al.* (2022) and Mayor Silva *et al.* (2023) who had 79 and 100 participants respectively. Most participants in all studies were female. In the case of Real *et al.* (2017) and Real *et al.* (2020) all participants were female. The exception was Chae *et al.* (2023) who did not provide demographic data. The age range of participants across the nine studies varied considerably depending on the target group. Those studies that recruited participants from student groups had an age range between 18 and 25 years. Those that recruited from groups of qualified professionals had an age range between 18 and 59 years. The studies came from a wide geographical range. Three of the studies were carried out in the USA, two were carried out in Cyprus. The remaining four were carried out in Australia, Malaysia, South Korea and Spain. Details about how the VR experiences were designed, what outcomes were measured and what feedback was provided by participants varied considerably across the nine papers.

7.3.1. Designing VR Learning Experiences

This section presents the design choices made by researchers and how it impacted their studies. All the papers used some form of modern consumer VR technology. The majority ($n = 4$), used the Oculus Rift headset and controllers. One used the Oculus Go. One used the HTC VIVE. Two used unspecified VR headsets. Papers inconsistently identified the

engine or method by which the software was designed unless this information was expressly part of the overall study, as with Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b), Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022). Three of the papers gave no indication as to how the VR experience was developed. Three of the papers clearly outlined that the VR experiences were designed using the Unity3D game engine. Often Unity3D was used in combination with other software for additional functionality. For example, Chae *et al.* (2023) used DAZ 3D software to develop digital avatars and iClone 7 to develop the avatar movement. Similarly, Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) used Autodesk to create avatars and 3D models for inclusion in their Unity3D environments. This systematic review attempted to ensure that each included paper conformed to the modern definition of VR, however, despite this it often remained difficult to determine details of the design and character of the VR experiences used by participants in each of the studies.

One study that was unique among the final nine papers was DeWitt *et al.* (2022). In this study, participants were tasked with creating the VR environment themselves using online tools and then providing that experience to other participants. Participants created 360° images using their mobile phones and then converted those images to VR environments using Google Tour. Google Tour also allowed participants to add interactive labels and information to the environment for the benefit of the user. The experiences could be viewed on mobile VR headsets like Samsung Gear VR or Google Cardboard. This simplified form of VR, although with less available functionality, was accessible and allowed the users/participants to be directly responsible for the design process.

Only three of the papers followed a particular model of design. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b), Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) and Chae *et al.* (2023) all used the ADDIE design method. This is a common method when designing new technological applications because it provides an iterative framework designed to facilitate co-design or participatory design with stakeholders. This is also the design method used throughout this PhD, therefore the details of this design framework have already been discussed in detail (Chapter 4). The remaining six papers either gave no information about the actual design process or stated simply that it was the work of a team of relevant experts. What is apparent is the different amounts of information provided by researchers on how the VR experiences were designed, what stakeholder input was considered and what formed the theoretical basis for their design choices.

Ideally, a research paper addressing the use of VR should acknowledge some theoretical basis for the design of the VR experience. A particular pedagogical approach or learning theory that justifies the use of VR over other media would be informative. Two of the papers, Chae *et al.* (2023) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022), proposed a constructivist approach to learning, where the user is supposed to construct knowledge through their interactions with the VR experience. Both were studies where the VR experience aimed to increase cultural competence and where the end users played a key role in the design. None of the other papers suggested a theoretical basis for their learning experience.

Of the final nine papers, seven of them have a digital human avatar that is central to the VR experience. Of those, five papers included some kind of scripted interaction with the digital avatar as part of the learning process. In three of the papers the learning process involved observation of a scripted scene, in one case partially provided by watching 360° videos. All the VR experiences simulated an environment that was relevant to the learning experience, for example, a culturally significant place, a relevant medical building or a classroom. All papers attempted to create a realistic and faithful environment. All but one ($n = 8$) required interaction with or observation of the digital human avatar as part of the learning. Only DeWitt *et al.* (2022) relied solely on an understanding and observation of the digital environment. There were several different approaches to design of the virtual learning environment. What is perhaps more significant is how these environments helped users achieve the desired learning outcomes.

7.3.2. Measuring the Learning Outcomes

There was no single or consistent instrument used to assess the potential of VR as a tool for teaching and learning. Generally, researchers attempted to measure two factors. The first, was any potential for improvement in the desired learning outcomes. In all nine papers, VR was considered to have a positive effect on the learning outcomes. In all the papers the instrument used was specifically designed for that study or developed by the researchers based on similar existing instruments. The second factor was an assessment by the participants on the usability of VR as a tool for teaching and learning. In most cases this took the form of qualitative data gathered through semi-structured interviews after the VR experience.

Three out of the nine papers (Mayor Silva *et al.*, 2023; Sapkaroski, Mundy and Dimmock, 2022; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b) used some form of control group, exposed to similar training either without the VR component or with a more traditional alternative. Mayor Silva *et al.* (2023) undertook a randomized controlled trial with a pre-post design. They found that the communication and interpersonal skills of nursing students significantly improved after VR training when compared with traditional training methods. Their interpretation was that the cost of resources required to build a virtual training simulator was offset by the improvements in learning. Sapkarouski *et al.* (2022) undertook a split-cohort study with a pre-post design concerned with improving communication skills between trainees/clinicians and patients. There was no significant difference in the results between the trainees and the clinicians, however, there was a significantly greater improvement in the groups who used VR compared with those who did not. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) used a post-test questionnaire to measure reflection and empathy in groups of teachers. The groups watched an incident of bullying dealing with multiculturalism, one group via VR and the other played out with real actors. The VR groups scored significantly higher in reflection than the control groups but approximately the same in measures of empathy. In those papers where a control group was used, those participants who received VR training generally outperformed participants who did not.

Five out of the nine papers (DeWitt, Chan and Loban, 2022; Mayor Silva *et al.*, 2023; Sapkaroski, Mundy and Dimmock, 2022; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b; Amini *et al.*, 2021) adopted a pre-post design method. Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) assessed the potential for a VR-based learning paradigm for the professional development of teachers. The study measured participants' emotional states in reaction to the VR experience and their ability to recognise incidents of bullying. The VR experience caused a significant change in their negative emotional state. A Wilcoxon signed ranks-test indicated a statistically significant difference in participants' state of being nervous (before VR - $M = 4.6$, $SD = 1.73$ and after VR - $M = 3.3$, $SD = 1.73$, $Z = -2.31$, $p = 0.21$), state of sadness (before VR - $M = 5.1$, $SD = 1.55$ and after VR - $M = 3.2$, $SD = 1.96$, $Z = -2.94$, $p = 0.003$) and state of being upset (before VR - $M = 5.6$, $SD = 0.91$ and after VR - $M = 3.0$, $SD = 1.96$, $Z = -3.91$, $p = 0.001$). Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) attributed this to the content of the scenario. DeWitt *et al.* (2022) used a quasi-experimental research design involving language students making VR experiences to promote intercultural communicative competence (ICC). Their findings showed a

significant increase in measures of ICC skills after implementation of the VR experiences (before VR – $M = 2.61$, $SD = .61$ and after VR – $M = 4.34$, $SD = .38$, $t(31) = -13.5$, $p < .001$). Amini *et al.* (2021) used a pre-post design to assess if VR training could improve the knowledge, skills and attitudes (KSA) of medical students regarding the social determinants of health (SDOH). Three separate instruments were used to measure changes in cognitive learning, skill-based learning and affective learning. A significant increase in mean scores was reported for all three categories of learning: cognitive (pre = 3.48 ± 0.80 , post = 4.56 ± 0.51 , $p < 0.001$), affective (pre = 4.20 ± 0.4 , post = 4.47 ± 0.44 , $p < 0.001$), and skill-based learning (pre = 4.00 ± 0.47 , post = 4.52 ± 0.37 , $p < 0.001$). It was possible to demonstrate, based on the results of these studies, that learning in VR facilitated a significant improvement in relevant skills and attitudes.

The remainder of the papers (Chae *et al.*, 2023; Real *et al.*, 2017; Real, Meisman and Rosen, 2020) relied on self-reported measures after the VR experience. Chae *et al.* (2023) used a multi-methods approach to provide feedback from nursing students on the design of a VR simulation to develop cross cultural communication skills. The data gathered suggested that participants found the experience beneficial and highly usable. For example, mean scores for sense of presence was 5.01 of 7 ($SD = 1.04$); simulation design was 4.43 of 5 ($SD = 0.47$); and, usability score was 4.58 of 5 ($SD = 0.42$) (Chae *et al.*, 2023). Real *et al.* (2017) and Real *et al.* (2020) both reported high levels of usability and usefulness expressed by physicians learning communications skills and patient interactions. In Real *et al.* (2017), 92% ($n = 22$) of participants agreed or strongly agreed that the VR experience was similar to real-life experiences and 67% ($n = 16$) agreed or strongly agreed that the VR experience improved their ability to counsel families. These three papers relied on participants perceptions of VR and their assessment of their own skills sets, unlike the others six papers which provided comparisons either with a control group, with pre and post-test or both. Overall, VR was reported to have a consistently positive effect on learning outcomes. All nine of these papers reported the potential for VR to be used as a tool for teaching and learning in these types of contexts.

7.3.3. Participant Responses

All nine studies collected participant feedback about the VR experience. Usually this was in the form of qualitative data from semi-structured interviews or questionnaires. This

involved the investigation of such characteristics as sense of presence, usability, simulation design, task difficulty, fidelity and satisfaction. This data was gathered to inform on the educational value of the VR experience, to assess the design quality of the VR experience and to assess participants' perceptions of an emerging technology. The reporting of this data often provided insight into what participants and researchers perceived to be the limitations of the medium of VR. Generally, the response from all papers was that the participants' experience was a positive one. It should be noted, however, that novelty of VR was an important factor in participant responses. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) reported that the newness of the VR experience could distract participants and encourage them towards a more positive perception of the experience.

Participants across the nine studies reported several different factors as being important to the VR experience. A sense of presence was commonly reported as being a primary advantage of the VR experience and important to the learning process (Chae *et al.*, 2023; Real, Meisman and Rosen, 2020). In multiple papers, participants identified the realism or fidelity of the simulation as being important. The degree of fidelity related generally to the graphical realism of the simulated environment (Sapkaroski, Mundy and Dimmock, 2022) or to the cognitive fidelity of the learning scenario (Chae *et al.*, 2023). One aspect of the realism of the environment, that could affect both physical and cognitive fidelity, was participants' interaction with digital human avatars. This factor played a part in seven out of the nine papers, however, only three provided specific feedback on the experience. Real *et al.* (2017) reported that in general participants found the interactions to be realistic. In Real *et al.* (2020), participants reported that improvements could be made to make the movements of digital human avatars more realistic. Sapkarouski *et al.* (2022) reported that the human/avatar interactions in their study were an improvement over previous studies that lacked access to modern VR technology and graphical processing. Participants, therefore, identified a sense of presence, physical realism and cognitive realism to be important factors in a VR learning experience.

Based on the feedback from participants, researchers reported several advantages of using VR as a tool for teaching and learning. One perceived advantage was the ability to take the perspective of another person, literally. Participants felt that taking the role of another person was an aid to the learning process (Amini *et al.*, 2021). They also felt that

it offered the opportunity to take multiple perspectives to better understand a complex situation (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). Participants also identified VR as being an immersive and engaging learning process that was better than more traditional methods. Participants in Real *et al.* (2017) said that VR was an improvement on reading and online lectures. Participants in Real *et al.* (2020) identified VR as being an immersive experience that focused the learner's attention. Similarly, participants in Mayor Silva *et al.* (2023) identified VR as being a more efficient way of developing skills despite the additional work required to prepare the experience. Also, in most of the papers, the VR experience was reported to have a high level of satisfaction and usability (Amini *et al.*, 2021; Chae *et al.*, 2023; Real, Meisman and Rosen, 2020). These are important factors when introducing a new technology. Despite the overall positive response, several negative factors were identified. Sapkarouski *et al.* (2022) identified the cost in resources of developing realistic VR experiences particularly the complex dialogue structures required for social interactions. Chae *et al.* (2023) reported that participants with glasses felt discomfort while wearing the headset and limited participants to 15 minutes in the VR experience to mitigate cybersickness. Mayor Silva *et al.* (2023) noted a greater enthusiasm to engage with this type of learning among older students than younger ones. Real *et al.* (2017) observed that some traditional forms of teaching were still preferred over the VR method.

7.4. Discussion

The aim of this systematic review was to assess the feasibility of using VR as a teaching and learning tool for complex social situations in vocational or professional environments. It addressed three study questions:

1. How are VR experiences being designed to facilitate learning of complex social situations in vocational or professional environments?
2. How effective are VR experiences at facilitating learning of complex social situations in vocational or professional environments?
3. How do participants respond to VR experiences used for teaching and learning?

Overall, the findings from nine studies demonstrate that: there are several different approaches to the design of VR experiences for teaching and learning; the effect of VR experiences on learning outcomes is consistently positive; and in general, participants

respond positively to the inclusion of VR experiences. These key points are now discussed below in relation to the wider evidence base.

7.4.1. Designing VR Experiences

It was not always clear in each paper what design choices had been made and why. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b), Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) and Chae *et al.* (2023), which used the ADDIE design model, provided some details and a framework for design decisions. Researchers providing details of the design process made it easier to relate the feedback provided by participants to the actual VR experience. It was possible to understand more fully what technology the participants were describing. For example, Chae *et al.* (2023) used the Oculus Rift S headset and noted that participants with glasses felt the headset was uncomfortable. This may not have been true with alternative hardware.

Seven out of the nine papers specified what kind of hardware was used in their VR experience, four out of the nine specified a particular piece of software used in development and only three specified a particular design framework. Design choices can have significant bearing on the user's experience. Dozio *et al.* (2022) proposed a methodology for VR that would allow the developer to combine design elements (such as sensory cues and interactive elements) to elicit specific emotions. Pöhlmann *et al.* (2022) demonstrated the connection between certain design choices (such as methods of locomotion and depth cues) and incidents of cybersickness. In addition, Marcolin *et al.* (2021) proposed some guidelines to impact the emotions of users when designing a virtual space.

The design choices made by researchers when developing VR environments can have a notable effect on the participants' experience. Participants in Chae *et al.* (2023) reported that the fidelity of the simulation was low. Participants in Sapkarouski *et al.* (2022) suggested improvements in the animation of human avatars despite the care taken by researchers to create realistic facial expressions and emotional cues. In addition, the choice made in DeWitt *et al.* (2022) to create the VR environment using an online platform, allowed participants to take an active role in the development process. It is important for VR researchers to be specific and clear about the definitions used and about the design of their VR experience. For example, Molka-Danielsen *et al.* (2019) provided detailed insight into the design process and pedagogical underpinnings of their VR

experience for developing communication strategies between emergency management professionals. Overall, the findings about design processes in this systematic review are limited by the lack of detail in included studies.

The lack of standardisation, combined with the lack of detailed information provided by researchers, makes generalisations or comparisons difficult. This review identified that when designing VR experiences for teaching and learning, developers should provide clear details and justification for design choices. Where possible they should specify the hardware and software used as this makes meaningful comparison with other studies possible and gives the reader a greater appreciation of the participants' experience. Finally, when developing and assessing a new VR experience, researchers should employ an established iterative design framework which includes input from stakeholders. The ADDIE design framework has been used successfully in several studies of this kind.

7.4.2. Is VR Effective for Teaching and Learning?

Overwhelmingly, the results of the nine papers demonstrate that the inclusion of VR had a positive effect on learning outcomes. Each of these papers dealt with a purpose-developed VR experience for teaching skills involving complex social interactions in a vocational or professional setting. Three papers (Mayor Silva *et al.*, 2023; Sapkaroski, Mundy and Dimmock, 2022; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b) used control groups. Participants in groups who had VR as a part of their training achieved consistently higher scores than those using more traditional teaching methods. However, the mechanisms behind this difference are unclear. This is an ongoing research gap that requires further exploration. Three papers is a small sample upon which to base conclusions, however, Mayor Silva *et al.* (2023) did suggest that the medium suited the skills being taught. Similarly, Sapkaroski *et al.* (2022) suggested that VR allowed the user time to immerse themselves in narrative. This explanation is supported by the work of Bolinski *et al.* (2021). Their study demonstrated that VR was more effective at emotional arousal and cognitive restructuring than directed imagination (Bolinski *et al.*, 2021). In addition, Gall *et al.* (2021) suggested that the embodied nature of the VR experience heightens the user's response to stimuli. When teaching skills that involve social interactions, empathy, emotional intelligence or instinct, the evidence suggests that VR provides a safe learning

environment where the experience can be felt more intensely by the user. This heightened intensity is one possible explanation for the improvement in desired learning outcomes observed by this systematic review.

Across the five papers that used a pre-post design, all of them reported a significant change in scores resulting from the VR based training (Amini *et al.*, 2021; DeWitt, Chan and Loban, 2022; Mayor Silva *et al.*, 2023; Sapkaroski, Mundy and Dimmock, 2022; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). This suggests that VR is not only a medium where learning can take place (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018), but also a medium that significantly improves learning. There are two major limitations to this generalisation. The first is in the small number of papers (only 6 of 9) that provide comparative data. Looking beyond the nine papers assessed here, we can see that Allcoat and von Mühlennen (2018) undertook a study which tested psychology students' ability to learn about plant cell biology using various media. They demonstrated that participants learning in VR showed increased knowledge acquisition, retention and engagement compared to the other group. Which brings us to the second limitation. The value of VR for teaching and learning in complex social situations has been assessed in very few professional settings. Based on the results of this systematic review these are limited to: 1) cultural awareness and communication skills while learning languages, 2) communication skills in the medical professions, and 3) social awareness and empathy in teaching. This is a very small sample of studies upon which to base an assessment of the use of VR in education when applied to complex social situations in vocational environments. However, the papers assessed in this review should be considered in the context of the many papers that demonstrate the positive use of VR in professions which require technical or procedural education, for example, Chiu *et al.* (2019) for surgical skills or Zhu *et al.* (2022) for engineering. In addition, several papers demonstrate the potential of VR for education in a non-vocational setting. For example, Ivanov and Ramos (2020), to educate children about bullying, or Knowlin *et al.* (2023) to train high school pupils in cardiopulmonary resuscitation. Based on the results of this systematic review and the positive results for other fields, the use of VR to teach social skills in a vocational setting has potential and should be researched further.

Two of the papers (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b) applied the idea of a VR learning experience to teacher education. These two are, therefore, the

most directly relevant to this PhD. The results of both studies were positive, showing that participants demonstrated increased empathy, self-reflection and recognition of bullying incidents after the VR experiences. This indicates that the application of VR is a suitable addition to teacher education and warrants further exploration in Study 4 of this PhD. Very few studies address the inclusion of VR in teacher education. Huang *et al.* (2021), in their review of 46 studies found that most of them were used for developing procedural knowledge. Based mostly on self-reported data from participants, the results of these studies were mostly positive. However, there were some differences between the two papers (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b) and the studies carried out in this PhD. Stavroulia's studies were primarily about generating empathy in participants with the additional aim of improving reflection skills and understanding of bullying incidents. In addition, both papers used interaction with digital human avatars to recreate relevant scenarios in an appropriate teaching environment. This PhD is primarily interested in how VR learning might be applied to the organisation and management of the physical environment of the classroom by teachers. Therefore, papers that consider the simulated environment to be an important element in the learning process are also directly relevant and their results should be considered.

DeWitt *et al.* (2022) was unique among the nine included papers, in that their participants actually built multiple VR experiences. As a result, their study involved participatory design and the sharing of the VR experiences promoted peer to peer interaction and communication. The researchers described the interactive environment as a *cognitive scaffold* for the participants learning. Participants described improved cultural knowledge and understanding and even, in a few cases, improved language skills. Based on this individual study, a relevant simulated environment can provide adequate stimulation to encourage understanding and reflection and learning. Further study is required to assess if exploration of a purpose-designed simulated environment can enable learning in fields other than the one described by DeWitt *et al.* (2022).

Both Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022) acknowledged that the novelty bias of the VR experience was distracting to some of their participants and may have contributed to the positive results. It is difficult for researchers to separate the positive feedback from participants from the novelty bias inherent in dealing with a new and interesting technology. A dedicated longitudinal study would be required to see if

participants' responses to the novelty of VR changed over time. Would they continue to find VR a useful addition to the learning experience? Participants in Real *et al.* (2017) were approached for a second time, one month after the VR training, to provide additional feedback. No additional VR training was provided in the intervening time. The majority maintained the opinion that the VR experience had improved their communication skills, however, they continued to express a preference for bedside teaching – a more traditional training method.

Based on this systematic review, VR experiences have a positive effect on learning outcomes. Further research is required to determine the factors and mechanisms that contribute to positive learning outcomes and how the effect of VR might change over time. VR is a feasible medium for study applications in teacher education.

7.4.3. How do Participants Learn in VR?

Participants responded positively to the VR experiences. Participants spoke about the realism of the VR experience (Real, Meisman and Rosen, 2020), reported high levels of satisfaction (Real *et al.*, 2017), suggested areas for improvement (Chae *et al.*, 2023) and contributed to the design process (DeWitt, Chan and Loban, 2022; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). Based on the results of these studies, when used as a tool for teaching and learning, VR can promote creativity, communication, collaboration and social skills. Directly relevant to this PhD, Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) consider VR to be a means of experimental learning that enables users to bridge the gap between theory and practice in teacher education. VR can reflect real-world classroom situations and facilitate reflection and empathy in the users. Parong and Mayer (2021) suggested that with the proliferation of VR as a medium for teaching and learning it was important to understand how VR affected the learning process. In their study, one application of educational VR showed that VR environments created an affective and cognitive distraction that led to poorer learning outcomes. Makransky and Peterson (2021) propose the Cognitive Affective Model of Immersive Learning (CAMIL), which describes the relationship between the method of learning and media used. Their study identifies the design choices that affect sense of presence, agency and cognitive affordances and which make learning possible in VR. Makransky and Peterson (2021) recognised the importance of developing

a theoretical model of how learning takes place in VR. However, only two of the papers examined in this systematic review describe their theoretical basis for VR learning.

Chae *et al.* (2023) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022) both took a constructivist approach to learning in VR. In constructivist learning theory the active participation of the learner is central to the process (Pritchard and Woollard, 2010). The learner is expected to build and improve their understanding based on their experience and reflections. This would also align with the approach taken by Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b), where teachers were expected to witness a social situation from multiple perspectives and improve their understanding with self-reflection. However, is constructivism the only effective approach to learning in VR? For example, if users in VR are interacting with digital human avatars, as they are in seven out of the nine papers, would that not be something closer to social constructivism? In social constructivism, knowledge is constructed through interactions with others, for example, like Amini *et al.* (2021) who used a VR discussion group as an element of the learning experience. Alternatively, VR experiences like those in Amini *et al.* (2021) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022), which do not require interaction with avatars but rather interaction with a digital environment, could be closer to exploratory learning. In exploratory learning, the learner is required to interact with their environment to understand relationships (Njoo and Jong, 1993). Rho *et al.* (2020) took an experimental learning approach to sign language communication skills using VR with positive results. This demonstrates more than one theoretical approach can be effective.

The other seven papers assessed by this systematic review are less specific about their theoretical basis. Several papers acknowledged the advantage that VR allows in repetition and practice. Real *et al.* (2020) suggested that VR allowed the user to deliberately practice and therefore develop skills. This is less a theoretical basis for learning and more a description of a place where learning may or may not take place. Those papers that deal, in part, with empathy, mention the importance of 'perspective taking' (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b; Amini *et al.*, 2021). Critics of the use of VR to generate empathy would suggest that the learner is literally compelled to take the perspective of another and directed towards a particular learning outcome (Raz, 2022). This is not empathy. In VR it is literally possible to see from the perspective of another. The user experiences the scenario for themselves and has their own emotional reaction. This systematic review has included papers that used VR to provoke empathy, but only if

the learning process included other skills. However, based on the idea that VR is the “ultimate empathy machine” (Xu and Zhang, 2022), several researchers seem to have taken the view that taking the literal perspective of another is a sufficient theoretical basis for a learning experience. Stavroulia *et al.* (2019b) described their VR experience as systematic and individualised learning, which in reality gives very little indication as to how learning will take place other than by organised observation. Future studies should attempt to determine what theoretical approaches to learning are best represented by VR experiences. Despite the overall positive response from participants to the VR learning experience, further development and research is required to fully explore the capabilities and limitations of the technology.

7.4.4. Strengths

This systematic review has provided a critical analysis of the use of VR as a tool for teaching and learning across disciplines, and with a focus on affective skill sets in situations that require complex social skills. A strength of this study is that it appears to be the first systematic review exploring this topic. Using strict eligibility criteria, it successfully identified and synthesised data from nine papers. This number identifies the topic as an emerging field, meaning the data from this review can be influential on the direction of future research. Another strength of this study is that it asks the question: Is VR a suitable medium for this type of learning? Many researchers assume that VR has potential for teaching and learning across all disciplines because of its track record in medical and technical fields. In addition, many researchers assume that VR is a machine for generating empathy even though the efficacy and ethics of that assumption are debated. This systematic review has assessed the potential for modern VR to assist in the development of skills which relate to the social complexity of the modern work environment. This review has also examined how these VR experiences were designed and developed to inform future studies. In addition, the feedback provided by participants has indicated what they thought to be the important characteristics of a VR learning experience and how they could be improved.

7.4.5. Limitations

One limitation of this systematic review is that the nine papers were heterogenous in terms of study design, sample and outcomes measures. This made it challenging to

contrast and compare data. This may change as the speciality evolves and researchers identify the best methods and measures to use.

A further challenge when carrying out a study like this is determining what defines VR. Throughout this thesis the accepted definition of VR has been a system that includes a 360°-computer generated environment, allows the user to interact with that environment and which uses an immersive display. This definition would exclude 360° videos as lacking the interactive component. However, the static 360° environment provided by Google Tour, as was used in DeWitt *et al.* (2022), provided interactive components and allowed the users to transition between scenes or perspectives. Conversely papers that were excluded from this study, for example Liaw *et al.* (2023), used AI driven computer avatars to provide complex social interactions while the user explored a computer-generated 3D environment. Liaw *et al.* (2023), was excluded because the study was conducted entirely on desktop computers. The complexity of modern XR technology is such that even the current definition of VR excludes a large amount of research.

The aim of this systematic review was to explore the potential of immersive VR as a teaching tool for complex social situations in vocational environments. For this reason, immersive VR using some form of HMD was the primary criteria for inclusion. However, future studies could perhaps take a broader approach and examine what aspects of computer-generated simulated environments most significantly affect the learning experience. For example, immersion, sense of presence, fidelity, interactivity. Is it more important for an experience to be physically immersive or realistically interactive?

7.5. Conclusion

The aim of this systematic review was to assess the potential for VR as a tool for teaching and learning in contexts which are as similar as possible to that of a working classroom. VR has many advantages as a medium for learning and teaching. For example, it allows repetition of complex situations, provides access to dangerous environments, and gives a high degree of control over the learning environment.

This systematic review of nine studies, demonstrates there are several different ways which a VR experience can be designed for teaching and learning. A design model, such as ADDIE, provides an iterative framework that helps the developer balance the requirements of the project with repeated input from stakeholders. In fact, input from

stakeholders and relevant experts was a repeated element of all the studies assessed here and a necessary element of building an effective learning environment in VR.

In all the studies identified, the VR experience had a positive effect on the desired learning outcomes. However, the means of measuring those outcomes was not consistent. The most common approach was a pre-post design, however, researchers rarely took into account the potential novelty bias of using VR or the long-term effects of VR learning. Nevertheless, the combined results of these studies suggests that VR is a suitable and effective medium to promote learning in complex social situations in a vocational environment.

Participant feedback was also consistently positive throughout the nine studies. Participants said that they felt immersed in the VR experiences and that they found it satisfying from a learning perspective. Participants' critical responses focused mainly on the fidelity of the experience and the realism of the interaction with digital human avatars. This emphasised that fidelity, both cognitive and physical, is very important when developing a VR learning experience.

Finally, all studies recorded the learning outcomes over a very short period of time and it remains uncertain what long term effects VR experiences would have on learning outcomes. Very few of the papers provided an established learning theory for how participants are expected to acquire knowledge or skills in VR. Those which did, took a constructivist approach to learning in VR. To facilitate future research and help to understand why learning in VR is effective it would be useful to establish how people learn best in VR and what approaches to learning are most effective. This has the potential to make the design of VR experiences easier and make VR an even more effective tool for teaching and learning in the future.

This is the first known systematic review exploring this topic. It has produced meaningful data to inform further research. The systematic review was limited by heterogeneity across the included studies, by the assessment of VR across a small number of fields, and by short-term data collection. Overall, its findings have informed the design and development of the simulated classrooms for Study 4 (Chapters 8 and 9), and will influence the direction of future research.

Chapter 8. Designing the Simulated Classrooms

8.1. Introduction and Background

This chapter provides a detailed account of the development of the simulated VR environments that are central to this PhD, and around which Study 4 is based. Study 4 is presented in Chapter 9. A description of the design process, including decisions about hardware and software, is advantageous when undertaking research involving VR experiences. However, findings from Study 3 (Chapter 7) highlighted that published studies often lack this information. This chapter addresses that gap by providing a comprehensive account of the simulated classrooms to be used in Study 4. It relates to the **development** phase of the ADDIE design framework (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). In this phase, the accumulated knowledge and understanding from the **analysis** and **design** phases is brought together to inform the creation of the desired product. In this case, the development of a VR experience that allows users to explore a simulated classroom environment. This will be informed by the data gathered in the literature reviews, studies 1-3, and an additional information-gathering 'micro study' outlined in this chapter. This chapter describes five stages of creating the simulated classrooms:

- Stage 1: Setting Design Criteria
- Stage 2: Creating a Prototype Classroom
- Stage 3: The 'Drawing Classrooms' Micro-Study
- Stage 4: Re-examination of Study 1 Findings
- Stage 5: Creation of Final Designs

8.2. Stage 1: Setting Design Criteria

Because of the exploratory nature of this research, it was necessary to clearly define the design criteria that would guide the development of the VR experiences. The potential for VR to support this kind of learning experience was demonstrated by the results of Study 3. VR is a constantly evolving field and there were a great many options in both hardware and software for developing the artificial environments. Based on the data gathered in

the literature reviews and the three preceding studies the process of developing the VR experiences began with the following criteria:

1. It had to be a wholly artificial 360° environment.
2. It had to be feasible to create using Unity development software.
3. It had to have sufficient detail in the graphics to realistically represent a classroom.
4. It had to have 6 degrees of freedom.
5. It had to have a minimum level of user interaction (in this case the ability to teleport around the room).
6. The resulting application had to be compatible with the Oculus Quest HMD.

An important element of the ADDIE design framework is that the data collected in the analysis and the design phases inform the design criteria and the development phase of the process. How these design criteria were informed by the literature reviews and studies 1-3 will be described in this section.

The first criteria, being *a wholly artificial 360° environment*, was established in Chapter 3 as being a basic element of a VR experience (Arm Blueprint, 2022; UCSanDiegoX., 2020). In addition, participants in Study 2 (Chapter 6) reported that the immersive quality of 360° environments was the most significant factor in generating a sense of presence in the user. Papers examined in Study 3 reported the importance of sense of presence to the utility of a VR based learning experience (Chae *et al.*, 2023; Real, Meisman and Rosen, 2020). Sense of presence has been identified, by most researchers, as directly affecting the value of learning experiences in VR (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018; Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). Jensen and Konradsen (2018) emphasise the importance of presence, emotion and subjectivity. Presence is a subjective feeling that, as discussed in Chapter 3, can be affected by several factors. An aim of this development process, therefore, was to maximise the potential for users to feel a sense of presence in the VR experiences by creating 360° environments.

Papers examined in Study 3 also demonstrated the importance of fidelity in the creation of a VR learning environment (Sapkaroski, Mundy and Dimmock, 2022). This was supported by the findings of the literature review (Chapter 3) where Jensen and Konradsen (2018), Kluwer (2018) and Ragan *et al.* (2015) identified fidelity as an essential consideration. This was the rationale for the next two design criteria: The experience had to be *feasible to create using Unity* and it had to have *sufficient detail in the graphics to*

realistically represent a classroom. Creation of extremely high fidelity or photorealistic graphics takes a lot of time, money and computing power beyond the resources of this project. Unity provided 3D graphical assets, through an online store, that would simulate the contents of a working classroom. It was, therefore, necessary to use available assets in Unity to create a sufficiently high level of fidelity to make the classrooms environments look and feel realistic. It was important for the simulated classrooms to be grounded in reality. Alongside realistic digital assets, the classrooms had to make logical sense and feel real (Kluwer, 2018). The results of Study 3 also identified the importance of cognitive fidelity (Chae *et al.*, 2023). To achieve this cognitive and emotional fidelity, it was necessary to gather more data from in-practice teachers and this will be discussed in Stage 3: The 'Drawing Classrooms' Micro-Study.

Based on the results of Study 3 it is important for VR learning experiences to be based on a particular pedagogical approach or learning paradigm. Of the nine papers examined in Study 3, only two, Chae *et al.* (2023) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022), specified a particular pedagogical approach to learning in VR. Both took a constructivist approach, which is a learner centred pedagogy emphasising active learning, reflection and viewing a problem from multiple perspectives (Pritchard and Woollard, 2010). Both Chae *et al.* (2023) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022) reported positive results from participants resulting from their VR learning experience. Study 4 required participants to explore, analyse and understand a series of simulated classroom environments. According to Dieker *et al.* (2013), a cyclical learning process is most effective when using VR. Deiker *et al.* (2013) suggested the ARC (Action Review Cycle). These approaches are compatible with a constructivist pedagogy and so this has been the approach taken by this PhD. Participants in Study 4 were required to take an active part in the learning process, to view the classroom from multiple perspectives, to construct solutions to problems based on their own experience and to reflect on the process after the VR experience is completed. To support this approach of goal, exploration and review, the VR experience must fulfil the criteria of moving *in 6-degrees of freedom* and with a *minimum level of interactivity*. The minimum level of interactivity was the ability to teleport to any part of the simulated classroom. By providing this facility, along with 6-degrees of freedom, the user is able to fully explore any part of the VR environment.

As discussed in Chapter 3, XR technology is a complex and rapidly changing field. The available technology has advanced considerably, even over the course of this PhD. In addition, many research papers exploring VR fail to clearly identify the technology used and so it is unclear how representative or generalisable the results are. Study 3 highlighted the importance of providing details of the hardware and software used in studies of VR. For the creation of the simulated classroom environments, this PhD used the Unity Game Engine. The hardware used by participants to experience the simulated classrooms was an Oculus Quest. The Oculus Quest consists of an HMD and two hand-held controllers (Figure 8.1). It operates independently of a desktop computer using an Android Operating System. The Quest was chosen because it was the most accessible and user friendly fully immersive VR headset available at the time of development. It was easily portable and easy to keep clean (COVID-19 guidance on the risks of using VR in research were at the time unclear). At time of writing, the Quest remained representative of the capabilities and limitations of modern VR systems.

Figure 8.1: Oculus Quest HMD and controllers (Source: www.oculus.com)

The simulated classrooms were designed using the Unity Game Engine. Unity has several advantages when used for VR. Unity is available free of charge. This means that, as well as reducing costs, there is considerable support available online from other creators. Unity actively supports the creation of VR environments, unlike other game engines that either lack VR support or are designed specifically for the creation of desktop

environments. Unity also has VR support in the form of ready-made development kits and toolkits provided by Unity and Oculus, as well as providing online access to a marketplace of compatible 3D models in the form of the Unity Asset Store. Alternative game engines would have advantages and disadvantages depending on the needs of the researcher. For example, Unreal Engine (<https://www.unrealengine.com>) has the potential to create far more realistic 3D graphics, however, it requires an expensive licence and, at the time of carrying out this study, was arguably less well adapted to VR environments.

8.2.1. Alternative Approaches

It is important to acknowledge that there are many alternative approaches to providing a simulated classroom environment for teacher education. The choice of which software, in this case game engine, producing the artificial environment has significant implications for the experience of the user. An example of this would be the potential to experience classrooms environments in 360° videos. As discussed in Study 2 (Chapter 6), 360° videos allow 3 degrees of freedom, as opposed to the 6 degrees allowed by most VR environments. Also, 360° videos do not allow any interaction with the environment, meaning the user remains a passive observer. The limitations in the size of the camera lens and the effects of compression on the digital image mean that 360° videos have poor visual clarity in comparison to an artificial environment created in a game engine like Unity. Another significant factor that prevented this study from using 360° videos of classroom environments was the restrictions resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic and the resultant lockdown (described in Chapter 6). Based on the limitations demonstrated by Study 2, if 360° videos had been used in this research it would have been in combination with VR experiences.

An alternative option for hardware was to provide the VR experience of the simulated classrooms for download onto a mobile device (mobile VR). Mobile VR had the potential to reach more participants and allow Study 4 to be undertaken remotely. However, this possibility was rejected at the developmental stage for several reasons. As discussed in Chapter 3, mobile VR is no longer supported by major developers (Robertson, 2019). Mobile VR dramatically reduced the amount of user interaction that was possible in the VR experience and so correspondingly reduced the potential to create a sense of presence in the user (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). Further, the visual quality and the field of view are also reduced in mobile VR (Sauer *et al.*, 2022). Finally, to install a bespoke

VR experience on a participant's mobile device would involve disabling all security measures and installing an untested app (Samsung., 2023). As well as being a complex task, there are ethical implications of having potential access to private information on a participant's mobile device.

Another option would have been to recreate existing classrooms, like the approach of filming 360° videos, but using a 3D laser scanner. With this type of device, an individual can make a 3-dimensional map of an environment, usually a room or building (Mura *et al.*, 2014). Online alternatives are currently available, for example Matterport (Jackson, 2023), but with more limited freedom of movement. This map can then be used to recreate the environment on a computer desktop or in a VR headset. The fidelity of the simulated environment is dependent on the complexity of the equipment used and the amount of time spent gathering the mapping data. This kind of artificial environment has the advantage over 360° videos that the user can move around and explore the environment in 6 degrees of freedom. This approach, however, would have had many disadvantages. Recreating the classrooms in any usable detail would have been a time consuming and technically complex process. Access to real-world classrooms would have been required just like 360° videos. Without access to schools, or the technical expertise to carry out this method, this option was not feasible. However, this approach remains a viable and potentially interesting method that could be addressed in a future study.

8.3. Stage 2: Creation of Prototype Classroom

A prototype classroom was created using the Unity game engine (Figure 8.2). The primary purpose of creating the prototype was to test the look and feel of creating a classroom in Unity, as well as to test the experience using the Quest HMD. A further purpose was to test the functionality of moving and teleporting around the VR environment. The outcome of creating the prototype was that several factors were identified that would affect how the final VR simulations would be created.

Figure 8.2: Images of the prototype classroom

Feedback was provided by researchers in the UWS Immersive Group. These researchers were chosen to provide feedback because of their expertise and familiarity with the technical aspects of VR development. Initially, this feedback was intended to address only the technical aspects of the prototype, however, as several members of the UWS Immersive Group had teaching experience they also provided feedback on the fidelity of the prototype classroom. Stakeholder feedback is an essential component of the development of VR experiences for teaching and learning. Other studies have incorporated feedback from relevant experts in their development process (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). Most of the papers examined in Study 3 engaged with stakeholders to ensure the fidelity of their designs and relevant experts to develop the functionality.

Feedback from the UWS Immersive Group was that the prototype classroom looked and felt like a real space. However, certain elements of the classroom's layout were unrealistic. For example, insight suggested that the desk models used would not be present in a UK school. This and other inaccuracies identified the need for additional data about real-world classrooms upon which to base the final designs simulated classrooms. Originally it had been the intention to film, photograph and record working classrooms and base the designs on this data. As a result of the COVID-19 restrictions, access to classrooms was not possible. To maintain this PhD's approach of participatory design, and engage stakeholders in the development of the VR classrooms, another approach was taken. This approach will be described in detail in *Stage 3 The 'Drawing Classrooms' Micro-Study* of this present chapter.

The visual quality of the 3D models used was constrained by cost and contributed to a "*cartoonish feel*." This limitation was addressed in the final design by purchasing higher quality 3D models from the Unity Asset Store (Appendix 8.1).

Teleportation was identified as the most appropriate and most comfortable form of locomotion in the VR space. This was intended to limit vertigo and cybersickness (Venkatakrishnan *et al.*, 2020). This was supported by Clifton and Palmisano (2019) who found that teleportation limited, but did not eliminate, cybersickness in comparison to other forms of locomotion.

Finally, once basic functionality, design and layout were established it was a relatively quick process to create the prototype classroom. For this reason, and to allow

comparison between different layouts in the analysis, multiple simulated classrooms were created and used in Study 4 (Chapter 9).

The final designs of the simulated classrooms were informed by data from three sources. The first was to draw on relevant academic literature as described in Chapters 1 and 2. The second source was data gathered in Studies 1, 2 and 3. This data would be re-examined to inform the design of the simulated classrooms. The third was to interview in-practice teachers, this time with the objective of having them describe in detail a classroom with which they were familiar.

8.4. Stage 3: The ‘Drawing Classrooms’ Micro-Study

This section describes a supplementary ‘information gathering’ component with a small group of 4 teachers (akin to a ‘micro study’). This approach formed a part of the **development** phase of the ADDIE design framework (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2018b; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). The design of this component was constrained by the COVID-19 restrictions. The original intention had been to interview teachers in their own classrooms. This was not possible. An alternative approach to participatory design was used, which still aligned with the ADDIE design framework. In-practice teachers were interviewed while drawing and describing a classroom with which they were professionally familiar. This could be carried out remotely via online meetings or in person if the COVID-19 restrictions permitted, but did not require access to schools. The aim of this component was to provide additional data, based on real-world classrooms, to inform the physical layout and organisation of the simulated VR classrooms created for Study 4.

8.4.1. Background

This component follows on from the work carried out by Barrett *et al.* (2016), by Gremmen *et al.* (2016) (Chapter 2) and from the results of Study 1 (Chapter 5). The interviews carried out in Study 1 allowed participants to talk freely around the topic of classroom organisation and management. Part of the results of those interviews was to demonstrate the importance of the wider physical and social context of the classrooms. The physical components of the classrooms were a part of a large and complex system. However, a focus of this PhD was the creation and critical analysis of simulations of the physical environment of the classroom. To gain additional data for the simulations it was necessary

to encourage participants to focus on the physical environment of the classroom rather than the wider context.

8.4.2. Method

Four participants from Study 1 were invited to take part. Participants were all qualified primary or secondary school teachers with experience of working in classrooms in Scotland. Participants were approached by e-mail or by telephone to ask informally if they would be interested in taking part. Those who expressed interest were provided with a participant information sheet (Appendix 5.4) and consent form (Appendix 5.5) and given opportunity to ask questions before taking part. Additional demographic information about participants can be found in Appendix 5.10.

The objective was to acquire data on a minimum of 4 classrooms. Data collection took the form of semi-structured interviews consisting of a single question (*“In order to provide guidance for the design and layout of classrooms in VR simulations, please describe in detail a classroom from your own experience.”*) and a series of prompts (Appendix 5.7). Participants were provided with sheets of A3 paper and pens and asked to draw and describe in detail a classroom from their own professional experience. Prompts included, rough dimensions, windows, utilities, storage, displays, desk layout and technology. Interviews typically lasted between 30 and 45 minutes.

Analysis of the data took an inductive approach (Morse, 2015) and involved coding the information and grouping the codes into categories that would inform the design of the simulated classrooms. Although each participant was describing an objective reality, their subjective opinion on what were the most important physical characteristics and how they described the classroom layout, proved to be valuable in forming the design of the simulated classrooms as well as the process of data collection in Study 4 (which will be discussed in greater detail in Chapter 9). The objective was to gather data on a minimum of four classrooms, however, one participant provided two drawings and so a total of five classrooms were discussed in the interviews.

The intention on the part of the researcher was not to directly copy the classrooms described by participants, but instead use the data provided to provide grounded inspiration for the physical layout of each of the simulated classrooms. The data gathered would also provide additional justification for design choices in the simulated classrooms. This would ensure that important details of the classrooms were retained in the

simulations and give an indication of how teachers might be expected to react to a particular layout.

Ethical approval was obtained through the University of the West of Scotland (Appendix 5.9). To maintain participant anonymity each participant was given a unique identifier with which they were identified in any analysis or publication. Names of individual participants were not recorded in any notes or audio recordings.

8.4.3. Findings

Participants engaged with the drawing part of the data collection based on their comfort level with drawing pictures. This meant that all participants approach the drawing as a teaching exercise where they were required to create an explanatory diagram. Most participants drew their own classrooms. One participant requested assistance and their classroom was drawn by the researcher according to their instructions. Participant F1 drew two classrooms. The first was a primary school classroom with the desks arranged in a horseshoe and with a central desk (Figure 8.3). The second was another primary school classroom with the desks arranged in four rectangular groups (Figure 8.4). Participant F2 drew a more traditional secondary school classroom with the desks arranged in rows (Figure 8.5). Participant M2 drew and described an open plan primary school classroom with the desks arranged in pentagonal groups (Figure 8.6). Participant M4 described a primary school classroom with four rectangular groups of desks and a large window overlooking a park (Figure 8.7).

While completing the drawings, participants also provided a verbal description. After coding the responses from participants, the data provided were arranged in four broad categories. **Communications and technology** – participants drew and described the positions of smartboards and chalkboards. Participants also emphasised how their classrooms could be organised around new technology like AppleTV Projectors or tablets. **Storage and working space** – participants' descriptions often focused on the location and the amount of storage. They also pointed out potential breakout areas in the classrooms where students could work on individual tasks. **Desk layouts and teacher's space** – central to their descriptions was the layout of desks. Of major importance was the teacher's ability to move around the classrooms and have space to carry out their own administrative tasks. **Windows and beyond** – all participants provided descriptions of the location of windows and the influence of the space beyond the classroom walls.

Figure 8.3: Participant F1, drawing A

Figure 8.4: Participant F2, drawing B

Figure 8.5: Participant F2

Figure 8.6: Participant M2

Figure 8.7: Participant M4

All participants were aware that the data they were providing was intended to inform the development of VR experiences. Technical advice, which did not easily fit into the above categories, was also provided by participants as to how best to represent classrooms in VR. This included the importance of keeping a consistent scale when placing 3D objects, the importance of realistic lighting and the importance of having an overall structure to the layout. Participants also recommended that not everything in the VR simulation should be perfect. Some elements of the classroom could be broken or out of use. The data provided by participants would be used to inform the broad choices for the design of the VR classrooms.

8.4.4. Analysis

Based on the information provided by participants, combined with the results of building the prototype classrooms, it was decided that Study 4 should consist of three VR experiences, meaning three different VR classrooms. However, to allow comparison between participants' reaction to the three experiences, certain physical elements of the classrooms would have to remain consistent. These included things like the size of the

classroom and the height of the ceiling. Other elements would be varied from room to room to reflect different pedagogical approaches or different teaching styles. This will be discussed in greater detail in the next section when bringing in elements from Studies 1, 2 and 3.

The layout of desks and the space provided to teachers was recognised by participants as central to the organisation and management of the classrooms. It was reasonable, therefore, that the three VR experience should be varied around this same idea. As discussed in Chapter 2, Gremmen *et al.* (2016) identified the four most common ways to arrange the desks in a classrooms. Three of these are *fixed* and include the traditional layout in rows of desks, arranged in small groups or a U-shaped arrangement. The fourth option being a flexible arrangement where the desks are moved according to the needs of the lesson. Analysis of the data provided in the classroom drawings supported the idea that the three simulated classrooms should consist of the three fixed layouts described by Gremmen *et al.* (2016). This would be representative of typical classrooms and informed by the results of the classroom drawings. A flexible arrangement with mobile furniture, while technically possible, was beyond the scope of this research.

Other elements of classroom design described by participants informed the design of the simulated classrooms. For example, no participant described a classroom with more than 33 students. They typically described classrooms accommodating between 20 and 33 students. Each simulated classroom should accommodate a similar Number of Pupils. In addition, the average size of room described by participants was approximately 35m². This varied depending on the type of school building and if the room was open plan. To remain consistent, all the simulated classrooms had the same floor area of 35m². None were designed as open plan as this was a divisive topic among participants and had the potential to overshadow other observations.

Several physical elements of the classroom were consistently identified by participants as affecting how they organised and managed their classroom. These included heating, lighting, storage, wall decoration, computer technology and visual displays. When developing the VR experiences these elements would all have to be accounted for and justified in the simulation. Participants also emphasised the importance of what lay beyond the walls of the classroom. This was not only in reference to the world outside the window but also the corridors and classrooms beyond the door. This was,

therefore, an important element to recreate in the simulations. None of the classroom drawings were copied exactly in the VR experiences, however, elements of each were used to justify the design and layout of the simulated classrooms.

8.4.5. Future Studies

This micro-study was carried out with the specific purpose of providing additional data for development of the VR experiences used in Study 4. The advantage of this component was that it provided a verbal response to prompts with a corresponding visual reference. This process was so successful that it was apparent that in future research a larger study could be developed from this idea. One possible option, which was suggested by participants, would be to ask participants to draw their *perfect* classroom. This could take a similar form to Pedro (2017), where groups of participants were asked to construct 3D models of an idealised future classroom. Participants were asked to focus on key concepts such as spatial organisation, lighting and air quality. The analysis carried out by Pedro (2017) focused on the models but also the words used by participants to describe their model and how it related to the key concepts. They found that participants' designs avoided traditional classrooms layout and promoted a more active social space designed to incorporate new technologies. This is perhaps unsurprising as the study carried out by Pedro (2017) was designed to promote future classrooms, new pedagogies and emerging technology. Allowing individual participants to draw the advantages and disadvantages of their existing classrooms is perhaps a more accessible and flexible way of approaching a similar dataset. In addition, how participants draw their classroom, and in what order they create the different elements, may indicate the relative importance placed upon them. Exploring these ideas could be the subject of further research.

8.5. Stage 4: Re-examining the Interviews – Study 1

Without access to real-world classrooms, it was necessary to re-examine the interviews conducted in Study 1 to inform the design ethos for each of the three simulated classrooms. In the restricted circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic, access to schools for the purpose of academic research was not possible and so the idea of making the simulated classrooms as copies of existing classrooms was not practical. One potential advantage of making the simulated classrooms as copies of existing classrooms would have been that existing classrooms would come with information from the associated

teacher about the layout, management, strengths and limitations of that room. In simple terms, an explanation of how that classroom was organised and managed. Without access to working classrooms an alternative approach was taken. That approach involved examining the data collected in Study 1 (Chapter 5). The aim of the re-examination of the data collected in Study 1 was to determine a design ethos for each of the three simulated classrooms.

8.5.1.1. The Framework Method

The method adopted for re-examining the data collected in Study 1 was the framework method (Gale *et al.*, 2013) but adapted to suit the circumstances of this component of the PhD. The primary purpose of the framework method is to chart the data into a matrix that can then be used to recognise patterns (Gale *et al.*, 2013). A key advantage of this method is that it provides a systematic method of creating the matrix structure. It also creates a visual presentation of large volumes of qualitative data. This method typically involves an inductive approach, coding qualitative data in a similar way to that which is applied during thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2023; Braun and Clarke, 2006). The codes are then charted into a framework matrix from which patterns in the data may be interpreted (Gale *et al.*, 2013). The primary drawback of this method is that it is typically undertaken with a team of researchers combining and therefore validating their collective interpretations. This present analysis will use a simplified approach by adopting the same codes identified in Study 1 and categorising them according to their relevance to the creation of a simulated VR environment. The aim of this analysis was not to reinterpret the meaning of the data from Study 1 with regards to how teachers organise and manage their classrooms. Instead, this analysis took a deductive approach to categorising and reorganising that data to inform the development of the VR experiences used in Study 4.

8.5.2. Reorganizing the Interview Data – Study 1

The thematic analysis conducted on Study 1 data provided an overview of the context, opportunities, restrictions and goals that influence the decisions teachers make when organising and managing their classroom. By going back to the 60 codes identified in that process, we are provided with a list of those factors which in-practice teachers repeatedly emphasised as being important in classroom layout, design, organisation and management (Appendix 5.1). To determine the relevance of each code in the context of

creating simulated classrooms in VR they were first split into four categories (see Table 8.1). These categories are as follows:

1. **Contextual** – Factors beyond the physical classroom like government policy, the socio-economic status of the surrounding area or the management style of the whole school. These factors were not feasible to represent in the VR environment proposed for Study 4. When carrying out the study this contextual information would largely be represented in the mind of the participant, in their experience and in their interpretation of the simulated classrooms.
2. **Not For VR** – Similar to the Contextual factors above, ‘not for VR’ factors were usually non-physical characteristics of the learning environment that cannot be directly represented in VR. This category included factors like temperature, time pressure or the social relevance of the curriculum. These factors were different to the Contextual factors in that they did not provide broad context and tended to be specific to classrooms or teachers.
3. **Measure in Interview** – Factors in this category mostly represented how the classroom was perceived by the teacher and the students using it. The results of Study 1 demonstrated that these factors are key in understanding how teacher organise and manage their classrooms, in some cases representing the goals of effective classrooms management. These factors are often large-scale concepts like pedagogy or learning atmosphere. This category informed the interview questions and prompts in Study 4.
4. **Change in VR** – This category was the most important when designing the simulated classrooms. Each of the factors in this category could be represented in the virtual physical space of the VR environment. These were factors such as room size, line of sight and number of desks. Each of these factors would have to be consciously represented or deliberately absent in each simulated classroom and a combination of these factors would, therefore, form the basis of the differences between each simulated classroom. The design ethos of each classroom would be represented by a specific combination of these factors.

Table 8.1 shows how the 60 original nodes from Study 1 divided into the four categories. Four factors in the “Measure in Interview” category have been highlighted with a **. This indicates their importance, based on the results of Study 1, and the need to include them as key elements in the design of Study 4. Study 1 identified that teachers were able to use the physical characteristics of the classroom to achieve three broad goals of, a positive learning atmosphere, engagement and ownership in the classroom, and perhaps most importantly a positive relationship between students and teachers.

Table 8.1: Study 1 nodes sorted according to relevance

Contextual	Not for VR	Measure in Interview	Change in VR
Admin Influence	Adapt to Physical environment	**Atmosphere for learning	Available Resources
Cultural Differences	Adapt to subject	**Behaviour Management	Closed vs Open Plan
Legal Issues	Additional Challenging work	**Communication	Dedicated Areas
Limited Resources	Clear Rules	**Safe Environment	Desk Layout
Local Government Influence	Core work	Group work	Light
Management Influences	Flexibility in Curriculum	Pedagogy	Lines of sight
Multiple Languages	Learning Objectives	Play based learning	Noise
National Government Influence	Reality/Relevance	Specialist Teaching requirements	Number of Pupils
Parent Influence	Results Driven	Students Access Resources	Outdoor Space
Peer Influence	Pupils' Varying Abilities	Pupils' Choice	Room Size
Socio-Economic Area	Pupils' Varying Ages	Pupils own learning	Space to move around
Teacher's Limited Autonomy	Temperature	Pupils' Own Space	Pupils' Work as Ownership
	Time Pressure	Teacher's Choice	Technology
		Teacher's Experience	Type of School Building
		Teacher's Instinct	Visual Engagement
		Teacher's Own Space	Engagement through Fun
		Student/Teacher Relationship	
		Training Influence	
		Training NOT Influence	

8.5.3. The Design Ethos of Each Simulated Classroom

Three simulated classrooms were created to facilitate three VR experiences in Study 4. Each simulated classroom was inspired by one of the three pedagogical approaches identified in Chapter 2: learning centred (*AMClassroom1*); learner centred (*AMClassroom2*); and teacher centred (*AMClassroom3*). These provided variety to provoke discussion without overloading the VR experience (for example, risking cybersickness by keeping participants in VR for too long). The three simulated classrooms are illustrated and described in greater detail in Section 5. This section focuses on the design ethos of the simulations.

Table 8.2 summarises how the factors categorised under the heading “Change in VR”, were adapted into a matrix to inform their representation in VR. The combination of these factors created the design ethos for each classroom and identified the physical characteristics emphasised in each. Certain elements remained consistent across all three classrooms as shown in Column 2 of Table 8.2. These factors were *Room Size*, *Type of School Building* and *Number of Pupils*. The primary reason for this was to provide a consistent basis of comparison between the three rooms. Deliberately keeping these three factors consistent, factors which individual teachers would typically have no control over, allowed other characteristics of the rooms to be emphasised.

Column 3 of Table 8.2 lists the three elements that differed in every classroom. The three elements were *Desk Layout*, *Lines of Sight* and *Space to Move Around*. Most importantly was the desk layout because the other two were influenced by it. The desk layout in each simulated room was based on the pedagogy that inspired the design of the room, as described in Chapter 2. Gremmen *et al.* (2016) found that teachers applied different desk layouts to suit different teaching styles. The desk layouts were applied to the simulated classrooms accordingly. Once this was applied, the overall layouts and additional details were inspired by the classrooms drawn by participants in *Stage 3: The ‘Drawing Classrooms’ Micro-Study*.

8.5.4. Matrix of Representation in VR

Table 8.2: Design of each simulated classroom sorting relevant codes

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5	Column 6	Column 7
	Common to all Rooms	Change in all Rooms	Room 1 – Physical Adaptation	Room 2 – Engagement/ Ownership	Room 3 – Learning Atmosphere	Not directly represented in this study
VR Experience filename			AMClassroom1	AMClassroom2	AMClassroom3	
Suggested pedagogy			Learning Centred	Learner Centred	Teacher Centred	
Explanation and Design Ethos for each Simulated Classroom	The factors described below should be common and consistent in each of the simulated classrooms.	Should be based on the suggested pedagogy and inspired by the layouts suggested in Study 3.	This room is designed to have an adaptable physical layout with accessible resources and technology on display.	This room is designed to engage the students and let them feel a sense of ownership with their environment.	This room is teacher focused and have a good or bad learning atmosphere depending on the participant’s views.	Open plan and outdoor environments were identified as too divisive to form a useful comparison in Study 4.
Nodes taken from Study 1 – “Change in VR” column	Room Size Type of School Building Number of Pupils	Desk Layout Lines of Sight Space to Move Around	Available Resources Technology	Visual Engagement Pupils’ Work as Ownership	Light Engagement Through Fun <i>(both of these will be expressed as a negative)</i>	Closed vs Open Plan Outdoor Space Noise Dedicated Areas

Columns 4, 5 and 6 show the pedagogy that inspired the layout of each simulated classroom. These columns also provide a brief explanation for the design of each. The bottom row of columns 4, 5 and 6 show the elements that will be deliberately emphasised, by their presence or absence, to suggest the pedagogy and approach to learning of each room. *AMClassroom1*, for example, demonstrated physical adaptations to organising and managing classrooms by displaying *Available Resources* and making use of *Technology*. Obviously, both factors would be represented in all rooms if only by their absence. For example, in a modern real-world classroom the presence of technology (computers, laptops, smartboards, etc.) would be significant, as would its absence. The aim was to give each of the simulated classrooms a different feel, one which could be justified in the context of previous studies, one which represented a different pedagogical approach but which was still grounded in reality. Column 7 of Table 8.2 shows the four elements, derived from Study 1, that were not represented in the simulated classrooms. These were *Closed vs Open Plan*, *Dedicated Area*, *Outdoor Space* and *Noise*.

Closed vs Open Plan was not represented in the simulated classrooms because, based on the data from the previous interviews and the advice of in-practice teachers, it was such a contentious topic that it would likely dominate all discussion. Participants would either instantly like or dislike a particular classroom because it was open plan. In addition, making a simulated classroom open plan would, by definition, necessitate designing a large portion of the rest of the school which would be both time consuming and beyond the scope of this study. A similar view was taken with the representation of *Outdoor Space*. In the simulated classrooms this would be represented by a view beyond the windows but not form part of the usable virtual environment of the study.

Dedicated Areas were also not included in the simulated classrooms. By this it was meant that the simulated classrooms would not include areas of the classrooms for quiet time, arts and crafts, play-based learning or other specialist activities. The reason for this is that it would make that classroom appear too specialist. Either by being only suitable for a particular activity or only suitable for a particular age group. The overall intention of the study was to make each simulated classroom as general as possible to draw comment from as wide a participant base as possible.

The factor of *Noise* was not represented in the simulated classrooms for technical reasons. It is feasible to add noise into VR simulations and the potential benefits of adding

positional audio (binaural sound) to a VR environment were discussed in Study 2. In contrast, Fernandes *et al.* (2016) found that adding directional audio, or graphical representations of the user's hands, was distracting for the user. However, recording suitable audio to imitate a classroom environment and then adding that audio to the simulated classrooms in a way which would be meaningful, but not uncomfortable for the participants, was technically beyond the scope of this study. In addition, the potential problems of communication between the researcher and participants while experiencing the simulated classrooms, along with potentially interfering with the audio recording of the participants' feedback, meant that the factor of *Noise* was not included in the simulations.

8.6. Stage 5: Creation of the Final Designs

The final designs of each of the simulated classrooms were inspired by the drawings provided by participants and the three different pedagogical approaches suggested by the reinterpretation of data from Study 1. They were also informed by the results of Studies 2 and 3, in line with the ADDIE design framework. Each simulated classroom was from a modern school building, was of identical size (35m²) and had the same number of chairs and desks for students (n=24). Each had a different desk layout, different lines of sight and different areas of space to move around. Participants were able to move freely in the space as well as teleport around within the confines of the classroom. A corridor beyond the open classroom door was depicted as well as other school buildings in the distance. The world beyond the classroom window was a rural community with grass and trees depicted using a Skybox. The Skybox and other 3D assets used for the classrooms were purchased from the Unity Asset Store (Appendix 8.1).

AMClassroom1 (Figure 8.8) was inspired by a learning centred pedagogy. The desks were arranged in groups. Resources and technology were available around the classroom as if they are being used. There was a lot of storage space and some relevant material on the walls including some of the students work. The colour scheme was bright. The teacher had a large desk and computer at the front of the class but facing away from the students. There was a whiteboard and a projector. The room was crowded and there was not much space to move around because the design used all the available space.

AMClassroom2 (Figure 8.9) was inspired by a learner centred pedagogy. The desks were arranged in a double horseshoe facing away from the windows. The colour scheme was even brighter and more vibrant than *AMClassroom1*. Lots of the students' work was displayed on the walls. There was no dedicated space for the teacher to work. Like *AMClassroom1* there was a whiteboard and a projector. Examples of students work (drawings) were laid out on the desks but there were fewer resources on display compared to *AMClassroom1* and less available storage. This design was aimed to encourage participants to think about engagement and ownership.

AMClassroom3 (Figure 8.10) was inspired by a more traditional teacher centred pedagogy. Desks were arranged in rows facing the front of the class, with the windows to the side. The teacher had a large desk and computer which was facing the students. There was a whiteboard and projector. The colour scheme was deliberately subdued. The interior and exterior lighting levels were reduced by 20% compared to *AMClassroom1* and *AMClassroom2*. Very little student work was on display and the other decorative material was generic with no reference to schools or class work. This room aimed to promote focused learning and limit distractions.

The landscape depicted beyond the window (Figure 8.11) of each simulated classroom was identical. A rural landscape was chosen because it did not imply any particular socio-economic status. Trees were included in the space immediately beyond the window for two reasons. First, the effect of parallax between objects outside of the classrooms' windows (where the position of an object appears to change when viewed from different positions), increases the illusion of the user occupying a multi-layered 3D environment. This potentially increases the sense of presence felt by the user (Jerard, 2016). The second reason was that Kweon *et al.* (2017) showed a correlation between the number of trees on a school campus and the academic performance of the students. Acknowledging that all participants in Study 1 emphasised the important of the outdoor environment, the inclusion of trees in the VR simulations represented the outdoor environment in the most basic way but also in a way which was suggested to be positive in the available literature.

Figure 8.8: AMClassroom1 – learning centred approach

Figure 8.9: AMClassroom2 – learner centred approach

Figure 8.10: AMClassroom3 – teacher centred approach

Figure 8.11: Space beyond the classroom (not accessible to participants)

8.6.1. *The Introductory Environment*

Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) acknowledged that some of their participants were distracted by the novelty of VR. This was particularly true in experiences that had an unreal quality, for example, their space age classroom (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). Other studies have acknowledged the potential novelty effect of VR and the time taken by some participants to acclimatise to the experience (DeWitt, Chan and Loban, 2022; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). To address this novelty bias, an introductory environment was created for Study 4. This aimed to give participants with little or no experience in VR an opportunity to acclimatise. The introductory environment had identical functionality to the three simulated classrooms with the exception that it was a deliberately unrealistic environment.

IntroEnvironment (Figure 8.12) depicted two chairs and a table, along with some other objects, on a rectangular floor area that appeared to be floating in space. The floor's space was the same size as the available floor space in the three simulated classrooms and the functionality of teleporting and turning around was also identical. This was intended to introduce participants to moving in a virtual space. Chapter 9 will describe in more detail how the *IntroEnvironment* was used.

8.7. Summary

In summary, this chapter described in detail the five stages of developing the simulated classrooms for Study 4. It highlighted how, using the ADDIE design framework, the final classroom designs were informed by the evidence base, findings from Study 1, Study 2, Study 3 and the 'drawing classrooms' micro-study. This chapter also described the final designs of each of the three simulated classrooms and how each was informed by a particular pedagogical approach. Study 4 is presented in Chapter 9.

Figure 8.12: The introductory environment

Chapter 9. Study 4: Classroom Simulations

9.1. Introduction

This chapter is the culmination of this PhD. The aim of this chapter is to critically assess the potential effectiveness of VR classrooms as a teaching tool for ITE. This chapter forms, what would conventionally be termed as, the **implementation** and **evaluation** phase of the ADDIE design framework (Allen, 2006). It also addresses research questions 4 and 5, as described in Chapter 4.

The previous chapter, Chapter 8, provided a detailed account of the design and development of the simulated classroom environments. The results of the interviews described in Study 1 (Chapter 5), provide a framework for the analysis of the data collected by the study described here. It will, therefore, be necessary to refer to data provided in previous chapters to clarify the process undertaken here. A simplification of the relationship between the three chapters is shown in Figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1: Relationship between Study 1 (Chapter 5), Chapter 8 and Study 4 (Chapter 9)

This chapter provides a detailed account of Study 4, where participants experienced and provided feedback on the simulated classrooms described in Chapter 8. The aim of this study was to assess the potential for using VR in teacher education. More specifically, to assess the potential of using simulated classrooms in VR to improve teachers' ability to organise and manage their own classroom.

9.2. Background

Chapter 2 demonstrated the importance of the classroom environment, its effect on the learning experience of pupils and the inconsistent education that preservice teachers receive about classroom organisation and management. The organisation and management of the classroom is reported as a key source of teachers' stress (Evertson and Weinstein, 2006) and the main reason why recently qualified teachers leave the profession (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). The results of Study 1 (Chapter 5) demonstrate that classroom organisation and management is an extremely complex undertaking and that teachers must consider a variety of factors when making relevant decisions. The eight themes defined in Study 1, derived from 60 codes, demonstrated that the organisation and management of the classroom results from the manipulation of factors relating to the physical environment and the schoolwork conducted. It is influenced by the organisation of the school as well as factors beyond the school. It is a primary factor in the engagement of pupils, giving them a sense of ownership and providing a suitable learning atmosphere. In many ways the classroom is a physical expression of the relationship between the pupils and the teacher. The aim of this PhD was: to investigate the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in Initial Teacher Education (ITE) and to explore the potential use of VR and 360° video in ITE for the organisation and management of classrooms.

Modern consumer VR has been widely available since 2016 but remains an emerging technology. This is partly due to the improvements and advances that have continued since that time (Jerard, 2016). The term VR is now considered a subset of XR technologies. Modern VR may be defined by three characteristics. These are: a complete 360° immersive environment; the environment is wholly artificial; and the user is able to interact with that environment (UCSanDiegoX., 2020). This has the advantage that the user can experience otherwise inaccessible environments, can repeat scenarios that

would otherwise be unique and for developers to have a high level of control over the user experience. All of these characteristics have the potential to make VR suitable or even advantageous for teaching and learning in some scenarios (Kaplan *et al.*, 2020). The results of Study 3 (Chapter 7) indicated that attempts to apply VR as a tool for teaching and learning for socially complex situations was consistently positive. Therefore, the results of Study 3 suggest that VR is a suitable medium to carry out Study 4.

Stavroulia and colleagues have explored the potential for using VR in teacher education. This has involved identifying incidents of bullying (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016b), and experiencing bullying incidents from multiple perspectives to induce an empathic response in the user (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). The limitations of Stavroulia and colleagues' work informed the design of this present study. For example, they noted that participants were sometimes distracted by the novelty of the VR experience and hence had a tendency to report positive results (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016b). In their 2019 study, Stavroulia and Lanitis focused on the empathy that the VR experience induced in participants. Their simulated social interactions relied on animated characters that participants identified as a fellow human being. However, several researchers have questioned the validity of using VR as a tool to generate empathy in some cases questioning the ethics involved (Raz, 2022).

VR is, by definition, designed to simulate a physical space and so this present study focused on the strengths of VR by allowing participants to explore and comment on the physical space depicted by the VR environment. Specifically, to simulate a classroom and ask participants to comment on its organisation and management. This is also informed by the results of Study 3 (Chapter 7), which suggested that VR learning experiences should be designed around a specific pedagogy or learning paradigm. This present study has adopted a constructivist approach (MacLeod, Burm and Mann, 2022). Participants were asked to explore, analyse and understand each of the simulated classrooms. Participants were required to take an active part in the process, to develop solutions based on the environment and their own experiences and to reflect on the experience afterward.

The Think Aloud method (described in more detail below) is a response to the view put forward by Nisbett and Wilson (1977) that participants often inaccurately report their cognitive process while undertaking tasks because their access to these processes is limited. Ericsson and Simon (2006) proposed that having participants speak aloud while

undertaking tasks gave the researcher more direct access to the process of cognition. This idea was based on the information-processing paradigm where short-term memory contains a portion of the information being processed during ongoing cognition (Eccles and Aarsal, 2017). The Think Aloud method used this idea to have participants concurrently verbalize thoughts while performing a task (Ericsson and Simon, 1993). In the case of this present study participants explored the positive and negative aspects of a simulated classroom environment while also describing how they would change it to reflect their own ideas about organisation and management. The Think Aloud method has been used successfully when researching other technological developments, for example, medical user interfaces (Jaspers *et al.*, 2004). It has also, more recently, been used in the development of VR systems and to assess their effectiveness (Su *et al.*, 2020; Koch *et al.*, 2019). The application of the Think Aloud method to the use of VR for ITE is a logical next step in the assessment of this emerging technology as a tool for teaching and learning.

The overall aim of this PhD was to explore the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. This study was the final stage of the ADDIE design framework where the VR experience was implemented and critically assessed. The primary aim of this study was to answer the research question: *Can VR simulated classroom environments provide a medium for professional development and reflection for teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?* The secondary aim of this study was to answer the research question: *What best practice can be identified for VR and 360° video being used for simulating classroom environments or use in Initial Teacher Education?*

9.3. Methods

This section will provide an overview of the methods: design, ethics, participants, data collection and analysis, which were applied during this study. For a detailed description of the design and development of the simulated classrooms and the VR experiences see Chapter 8.

9.3.1. Design

This study took a multi-methods approach to the design. A purely quantitative approach would have provided measurable results but would have lacked the user's subjective experience (Mattimoe *et al.*, 2021). The subjective perspective of users is important when

critically assessing VR experiences. This was illustrated by the different results between Jensen and Konradson (2018) and Kaplan *et al.* (2020) as discussed in Chapter 3. However, focusing solely on user experience, as in a qualitative approach, would not provide quantitative data on the potential effectiveness of VR as a tool for teaching and learning. Given that this study was designed to be a first step in assessing the applicability of VR to teach preservice teachers about classroom organisation and management the best approach was a multi-methods approach. A multi-methods study provided information about the user experience along with measurable results about the effect of that experience. Data collection was undertaken in two steps: (1) the Think Aloud method (Ericsson and Simon, 1993), followed by; (2) semi-structured interviews.

9.3.1.1. Step 1: The Think Aloud Method

The Think Aloud method involves participants speaking about their thoughts and actions in real time while carrying out assigned tasks in the VR experience. This method is believed to provide unfiltered access to the participant's thought processes while taking part in the study (Eccles and Aarsal, 2017). In addition, it provides instant feedback on the participants' ability to utilise new technology in each situation. Some researchers argue that, when collecting data by this method, input from the researcher should be kept to a minimum to preserve a genuine connection to the thoughts of the participant (Eccles and Aarsal, 2017). Prompting by the researcher has the advantage that it maintains the structure and relevance of the data collected, however, it can force the participants to make inferences about their thought process thereby limiting the effectiveness of concurrent reporting (Ericsson, 2006). It was not the primary purpose of this study to provide a deep understanding of the cognitive processes of teachers organising and managing their classrooms. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of VR as a potential teaching tool in ITE. For this reason, two methods were employed to mitigate the balance between maintaining relevance and limiting researcher interference. The first was that a series of prompts were available to the researcher to provide guidance to the participants during the Think Aloud process. This helped maintain the relevance of the data collected. In this way the interaction between the participants and the researcher took the form of a semi-structured conversation, when necessary, while keeping the researcher's input limited to the prompts provided.

The Think Aloud method is ideal for this study because it has several relevant advantages. It provides a direct insight into participants thoughts while they interact with the VR experience. It is a simple study to organise and may be carried out with a small or limited number of participants (Ericsson, 2006). This makes it suitable for the assessment of developing technology or technology which is being applied to new fields (Su *et al.*, 2020; Napa, Moore and Bardyn, 2019). However, the Think Aloud method does have some limitations. The most significant is that it relies on participants verbalising their thought processes. This is an inherently subjective measure that may be influenced by researcher input or social bias. Proponents of the method would argue that the Think Aloud method limits these influences when compared to traditional interviews (Ericsson, 2006). Finally, the Think Aloud method cannot directly assess the outcomes of the VR experience. This study did not aim to measure if teachers' organisation and management skills improved after using the VR experience. Rather it aimed to allow teachers to reflect on their approach to classroom organisation and management and therefore to assess the potential for using VR in ITE.

9.3.1.2. Step 2: Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews were carried out immediately following the Think Aloud method and the VR experience, giving an additional opportunity for participant insight. Based on the experience of previous researchers (Napa, Moore and Bardyn, 2019; Su *et al.*, 2020), the semi-structured interviews aimed to cover the same topics as already covered during the Think Aloud element of the data collection. The interviews did cover some additional topics, particularly the participants perception of the strengths and weaknesses of VR as a tool for teaching and learning. Semi-structured interviews were chosen because the researcher could maintain the relevance of data collection through a prepared list of questions and prompts, while allowing the participants to talk around the topics into areas not previously considered (Mattimoe *et al.*, 2021). The interviews aimed to provide an opportunity for immediate retrospective reporting, allowing participants to speak about the VR environments in more general terms and reflect on their experiences (Eccles and Aarsal, 2017).

9.3.2. Participants

Insight was sought from a range of stakeholders. Participants were recruited from four groups: in-practice teachers, retired teachers, ITE educators and preservice teachers. These four groups were representative of those users who may find utility for the application of VR experiences to ITE. The four groups were also indicative of different levels and types of experience within the participant pool. To maintain a balance between experience and current trends the number of participants was limited to four from each group. A total of 16 participants took part in this study. There are no requirements for sample size in this type of study (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Ericsson, 2006). Sampling should be based on the expected number of participants required to be consistent and representative of the target group (Wolcott and Lobczowski, 2021). Generally, with Think Aloud studies the number of participants should be suited to the analysis which is proposed (Eccles and Arsal, 2017). In this present study the number of four participants from each group was a balanced representation of each group while providing sufficient variation in the data for the proposed analysis. The purposeful sampling of the four groups ensured that the sample was as heterogeneous as possible and that all perspectives were considered equally. This made comparison between the groups easier because no one group of participants was overrepresented. In addition, 16 participants were a manageable number given the quantity of data being recorded and the difficulty of recruiting participants during a time of COVID-19 restrictions.

Recruitment was carried out by snowball sampling. Beginning by approaching potential participants who were known to the researcher or supervisory team through social or professional contacts. It was, therefore, incumbent on the researcher to make clear that prospective participants were under no obligation to take part and maintained their right to withdraw at any time up to one week after the completion of the interview, without penalty to themselves and with no detrimental effect on the study. Potential participants were typically approached by e-mail or by telephone to ask informally if they would be interested in taking part. The researcher also made clear the potential risk of COVID-19 transmission when using the VR equipment and how these risks had been minimised. Potential participants who expressed interest, were provided with a Participant Information Sheet (Appendix 9.1) and consent form (Appendix 9.2).

Data collection was carried out at a time and location convenient and safe for both the participant and the researcher. They did not take place within a school or other Local Authority setting. Interviews typically took place on a UWS campus or in a public setting suitable to the participant. A requirement of the setting was that it was suitable for audio recording the interview. A further requirement was that it had a safe open area (approximately 4m by 4m) within which the VR experience could be set up.

9.3.3. Data Collection

Data collection was carried out using an Oculus Quest (see Figure 9.2). This was the most accessible standalone VR HMD at the time of development of the simulated classrooms. Over the course of this study, this headset had been surpassed by the Oculus Quest 2 and other devices, however, it remained representative of the capabilities of modern consumer VR technology and therefore suitable for data collection.

Figure 9.2: Oculus Quest, HMD and controllers (Source: www.oculus.com)

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For each participant, all data collection was carried out in one single stage, as described in the Interview Schedule (Appendix 9.3). Participants were asked two introductory questions. The first to gauge their experience in teaching and the second to gauge their experience using VR and understanding of its technical aspects. These questions were also designed to be informally presented to relax participants and

encourage a conversational exchange. Participants were then introduced to the VR equipment and given opportunity to experience the introductory VR environment (Figure 9.3). As described in Chapter 8, the *IntroEnvironment* took the form of a carpeted area (the same floor area of the classrooms in the other scenes), with two chairs, a table and other random items on a platform that appeared to be floating in space. This deliberately unrealistic environment was designed to allow the participants to acclimatise to the feeling of using VR and to practice the functionality of the experience. The teleportation and rotation functions were identical in *IntroEnvironment* to the simulated classrooms. The intention behind the introductory environment was to allow participants with minimal VR experience to gain experience before beginning the study proper. Also, the introductory environment aimed to minimise the distraction of the novelty of VR reported by Stavroulia *et al.* (2016b).

Figure 9.3: The Introductory Environment (IntroEnvironment)

Each participant then took part in the Think Aloud method (Step 1), where they experienced three simulated classrooms: *AMClassroom1* (Figure 9.4), *AMClassroom2* (Figure 9.5) and *AMClassroom3* (Figure 9.6). Simulations were presented to participants in a randomized order to minimise response bias. In each of the three simulated classrooms (*AMClassroom1*, *AMClassroom2* and *AMClassroom3*) participants were given two tasks to perform while speaking out loud about their thoughts and actions. The first task was to identify strengths and weaknesses of each classroom layout. Table 9.1 shows

Figure 9.4: AMClassroom1 – Learning Centred

Figure 9.5: AMClassroom2 - Learner Centred

Figure 9.6: AMClassroom3 - Teacher Centred

the intended characteristics and suggested pedagogy for each room (a more detailed matrix has already been provided in Table 8.2 in Chapter 8). The second task was to identify as many ways as possible to reorganise the classroom to suit the participant's approach to teaching.

Table 9.1: The basic design characteristics of each simulated classroom

Simulated Classroom Identifier	<i>AMClassroom1</i>	<i>AMClassroom2</i>	<i>AMClassroom3</i>
Suggested suitable pedagogy for room	Learning Centred	Learner Centred	Teacher Centred
Design Ethos for each Simulated Classroom	This room was designed to have an adaptable physical layout with accessible resources and technology on display.	This room was designed to engage pupils and let them feel a sense of ownership with their environment.	This room was designed to be teacher focused and to have a good or bad learning atmosphere depending on the participant's views.

For both tasks the researcher used four prompts with which to encourage the participants to speak. In Chapter 8 the codes from Study 1 were divided into four groups. The prompts were based on those codes from Study 1 which were identified as suitable for constructing interview questions and directly relevant to VR (see Table 9.2).

Following the completion of the Think Aloud section participants immediately took part in a short semi-structured interview (Appendix 9.3). The interview covered similar topics to those prompted in the Think Aloud portion of the data collection. However, the questions were deliberately phrased differently to allow cross referencing with the data provided during the Think Aloud session. Additional topics addressed participants' positive and negative experiences while using VR. Participants were also asked their opinion of the potential for using VR as an element of ITE.

On completion of the interview, participants were asked if there was any additional information or observations they wished to add.

Table 9.2: Think Aloud prompts and relevant codes from Study 1

Question and Prompt from Think Aloud Study	Related Code from Study 1
Task 1: classroom Your first task is to describe the room. Please describe what you consider to be the important physical characteristic of the? (3 minutes, approximately)	All codes but focusing on the physical characteristics.
Prompt 1a: Describe the desk layout, lines of sight, is there space to move around?	Desk Layout Lines of Sight Space to Move Around
Prompt 1b: What pedagogy, if any, does the layout of the room best suit?	Pedagogy Number of Pupils Group work
Prompt1c: What are the obvious problems with the room's layout?	Teachers' Experience Training Influence Training NOT Influence Peer Influence
Prompt 1d: What other things catch you eye or seem to be important?	Teachers' Instinct
Task 2: Your second task is to describe as many ways as you can in which you would change the physical layout of the room to better suit your own ideas about teaching. (3 minutes, approximately)	Again, focusing on the physical layout allowing the participants to speak around the topic.
Prompt 2a: How would you change the room to improve the learning atmosphere (expectation to learn, enthusiasm for class)?	Atmosphere for Learning Safe Environment
Prompt 2b: In what ways could the room be changed to better engage students in their learning?	Visual Engagement Engagement through Fun
Prompt 2c: How could you change the room to provide a sense of ownership (sense of belonging, desire to improve) for you and your students?	Pupils' Own Space Teacher's Own Space Students' Work as Ownership
Prompt 2d: In what ways does the layout of this classroom contribute to a positive or negative student/teacher relationship? How could that be improved?	Student/Teacher Relationship Communication Behaviour Management

Participants were then provided with a debrief document (Appendix 9.4) and asked if they wished any further explanation about the aims of the research. Typically, data collection took approximately one hour for each participant. This included time to set up, introduction to the VR equipment, Think Aloud and semi-structured interview, and debrief at the end. All resulting dialogue between the participants and the researcher was audio recorded and transcribed verbatim (by a professional transcription company).

9.3.4. Analysis

The qualitative data from the Think Aloud method and semi-structured interviews were triangulated, supported by data from Study 1, using a quantitative focused content analysis.

The aim of analysis was to identify which topics participants talked about while participating in the Think Aloud method and the frequency with which each topic was addressed. This was based on the approach to content analysis described by Stemler (2015). Similar to the work of Jaspers *et al.* (2004), each transcription was divided into sampling units called segments. These were syntactic units with the separation defined by the speech of the participants (Stemler, 2015). Each segment represented a single sentence, information item or thought expressed by the participants. The coding scheme took a bottom-up approach (Jaspers *et al.*, 2004). Stemler (2015) described this as *a priori* coding. In this approach, the codes are determined in advance of the analysis being carried out and based on an appropriate theory or the input of experts. In this present study, the codes were generated from the themes and codes identified by Study 1 (Chapter 5). This resulted in 8 themes and 60 codes that provided a vocabulary to describe the key attributes of a working classroom as described by teachers (Table 9.3). For a detailed description of each code see Appendix 5.11. Each time a participant made a statement about the simulated classrooms it was recorded against the related code. In this way, the frequency with which each code was mentioned was recorded, representing the topics each participant had discussed while in the VR experience.

Coding was manually carried out by the researcher. Each segment of the Think Aloud transcript was annotated with a single code that described the topic being addressed by participants (Stemler, 2015). It was then possible to group the codified

segments according to the category of participant (e.g., retired versus preservice teacher), by each simulated classroom or by frequency of individual codes.

Table 9.3: Eight identified themes and sixty codes

Theme	Codes
Cultural Influence	Multiple Languages Cultural Differences Results Driven National Government Influence Local Government Influence Socio-Economic Status Parent Influence Legal Issues
School Organisation	Teacher's Limited Autonomy Specialist Teaching Requirements Peer Influence Admin Influence Management Influence Time Pressure Limited Resources Closed vs Open Plan Room Size Number of Pupils Adapt to Physical Environment Type of School Building
Teacher's Approach	Training Influence Training Not Influence Pedagogy Teacher's Experience Teacher's Instinct
Physical Adaptation	Lines of Sight Pupil's Access Resources Available Resources Space to Move Around

	<p>Technology</p> <p>Outdoor Space</p> <p>Desk Layout</p> <p>Dedicated Areas</p>
Work Adaptation	<p>Adapt to Subject</p> <p>Learning Objectives</p> <p>Group Work</p> <p>Flexibility in Curriculum</p> <p>Core Work</p> <p>Additional Challenging Work</p>
Learning Atmosphere	<p>Safe Environment</p> <p>Atmosphere for Learning</p> <p>Noise</p> <p>Light</p> <p>Temperature</p> <p>Clear Rules</p>
Engagement and Ownership	<p>Reality/Relevance</p> <p>Visual Engagement</p> <p>Engagement through Fun</p> <p>Play Based Learning</p> <p>Pupils own learning</p> <p>Teachers Own Space</p> <p>Pupil's Work as Ownership</p> <p>Pupil's Own Space</p>
Pupil/Teacher Relationship	<p>Communication</p> <p>Behaviour Management</p> <p>Teacher/Student Relationship</p> <p>Pupil's Varying Ages</p> <p>Pupil's Varying Abilities</p> <p>Teacher's Choice</p> <p>Pupil's Choice</p>

Typically, when using content analysis (Stemler, 2015) and with the Think Aloud method (Napa, Moore and Bardyn, 2019; Su *et al.*, 2020), validation of the inferences is achieved by triangulation of multiple sources of data. For this reason, the semi-structured interviews were intended to cover broadly the same topics as already covered during the Think Aloud element of the data collection. Triangulation is a means of increasing the validity and credibility of research inferences by comparison with other data sources (Noble and Heale, 2019). This study undertook a methodological triangulation between the result of the Think Aloud method and the semi-structured interviews using data gathered in Study 1 (Noble and Heale, 2019). As Ostlund *et al.* (2011) demonstrated in their methodological review, triangulation can inform the link between theory and empirical data.

The final part of the semi-structured interview asked participants their opinion of using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. The aim was to critically examine the positive and negative feedback about VR. This took the form of three questions: 1) *How would you describe the experience of using VR to simulate a classroom environment?* 2) *In what ways do you think VR simulated classrooms have potential as a teaching tool for ITE students?* and 3) *What do you think are the limitations involved in VR as a teaching tool for ITE students?* This type of interview uses open ended questions to reveal opinions or experiences. Analysis of this part of the interview took the form of a qualitative survey (Jansen, 2010). The aim of this type of analysis is to gather representative data from a subset of a larger population. This is a flexible approach to analysis which allows participants and researchers to explore a chosen topic. The responses of participants were categorised according to the recurrent themes which were apparent from reading the transcripts.

9.3.5. Ethics

Ethical approval for this study was obtained through the University of the West of Scotland. To maintain participant anonymity each participant was given a unique identifier with which they were referred to in any analysis or publication. Names of individual participants were not recorded in any notes or audio recordings. Audio recordings were downloaded on to a secure password protected UWS laptop with a single backup. After the analysis was completed all audio files and transcripts were to be stored

until completion of the research at which time they were deleted. The audio recordings, notes and unedited transcripts were only accessed by the researcher and supervisory team.

To mitigate the potential for cybersickness, participants' time in VR was limited to approximately three minutes to respond to each task. Given that participants were asked to complete two tasks in each simulated classroom this resulted in an approximate total of six minutes in each. In practice, the three-minute limit was considered a guideline which could be exceeded to allow participants to finish expressing a thought or an idea. Participants were also allowed approximately two minutes in the introductory VR environment at the beginning of their session to acclimatise to the use of VR. This resulted in a total of approximately 20 minutes for each participant using VR. Participants were offered a break from VR between each simulated classroom or at any time upon their request. Participants were offered, if necessary, time to sit and recover from using VR as well as being made aware of the potential dangers of cybersickness.

An additional ethical consideration for this study was the risk of COVID-19 transmission. As expressed in previous chapters the design of this PhD was adapted in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and resulting lockdown. Data collection for the study described here took place after the mandatory lockdown was over but when access to schools and other places of work was still restricted. In addition, there was the potential for the use of VR HMDs to be a source of COVID-19 transmission. To minimise the risk to researchers and participants, the headset was thoroughly cleaned between participants. Participants were spaced out so that a minimum time of 2 hours was between each. Track and trace data were recorded for each participant and kept confidential. Finally, no one took part in the study who had any COVID-19 symptoms or who had recently had a positive result on an antigen test. Ethical approval for this study was received from the UWS Ethics Committee on 22nd September 2021 (Appendix 9.5).

9.4. Findings

The findings of this study will be presented in three sections. The first section will focus on the data collected during the Think Aloud portion. This data will be summarised, and the results of the content analysis will be presented. The second section will focus on the triangulation between the results of the content analysis and the follow-up interviews.

The third section will examine the feedback provided by participants on the use of VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE.

Sixteen participants took part. Four retired teachers, four preservice teachers, four in-practice teachers and four ITE educators. Thirteen out of the sixteen participants (81.25%) were female. Participants were asked the date of their qualification as a teacher as an indication of their experience. The dates provided ranged from 1970 to an expected date of 2024. The average date of qualification as a teacher was 1999. Participants were also asked how many classrooms they had worked in. This number ranged from around three to 50 classrooms. Participants were also asked to describe their level of experience using VR and their understanding of how it worked technically. Most participants had little or no experience using VR. Only four of the participants had used VR regularly for entertainment. Only two had used VR in a professional context for teaching and learning. Only one participant had a technical understanding of VR. Additional demographic information about participants can be found in Appendix 5.10.

9.4.1. Content Analysis

Content analysis of the Think Aloud portion of this study quantified participants' reactions to the simulated classrooms environments. The transcript of each participant's audio recording was compared to the list of identified themes and codes from the thematic analysis carried out in Study 1 (Table 9.4).

Table 9.4: Summary of themes, codes and content analysis

Number of themes identified in Study 1	8
Number of codes (based on the thematic analysis carried out in Study 1)	60
Number of individual statements coded during the content analysis.	1423

Results are presented in several different ways to provide insight on the influence of the VR environment on the thought process of participants. Figure 9.7 shows the frequency of coded statements made by participants in each simulated classroom.

Figure 9.7: The frequency of coded statements in each simulated classroom

This shows that participants were marginally more talkative regarding the organisation and management of *AMClassroom1* than the other two. It should be noted that each participant was presented with the three simulated classrooms in a randomised order and so the above result is not simply the result of participants having more to say the first time. The results of the content analysis provided an indication of what topics participants chose to address, which topics they emphasised and which they avoided while experiencing the simulated classrooms. Comparison between participants, or groups of participants, is intended to indicate the potential for meaningful discussion and feedback in an ITE setting.

9.4.1.1. The Themes Described in Study 1

Participant statements were grouped according to the themes identified in Study 1. This is shown in Figure 9.8.

Figure 9.8: Proportion of codes recorded, grouped by each theme from Study 1

Certain themes were discussed by participants more than others. For example, *Cultural Influence*, representing influence from outside the school like government bodies, was rarely spoken about. In contrast, *Physical Adaptation*, meaning the organisation and management of the physical elements of the classroom, was talked about a great deal. Approximately one third of the statements made by participants were coded under this theme.

It is also possible to compare the frequency of themes discussed between the three difference simulated classrooms. For example, the theme *Teacher's Approach* was spoken about more in *AMClassroom3* than the other two (Figure 9.9). *AMClassroom3* was the simulated classroom designed to represent a teacher centric pedagogy.

Figure 9.9: The frequency with which recorded codes were assigned to the theme *Teacher's Approach* in each simulated classroom

Figure 9.10 shows that participants discussed the theme *Work Adaptation*, meaning changing the curriculum to affect the organisation and management of the classroom, in *AMClassroom1*. *AMClassroom1* was the simulated classroom designed to suit a Learning Centred pedagogy and set out to encourage group work.

Figure 9.10: The frequency codes assigned to the theme *Work Adaptation* in each simulated classroom

The theme *Engagement/Ownership* was discussed approximately equally between the three simulations (Figure 9.11). However, it was discussed slightly less in *AMClassroom2*, which was designed to be learner centred and engaging, and slightly more in *AMClassroom3* which was designed to be teacher centred and less engaging.

Figure 9.11: The frequency codes assigned to the theme Engagement and Ownership in each simulated classroom

9.4.1.2. The Frequency of Individual Codes

The results are now presented in more detail in relation to the 60 codes identified in Study 1. This section looks at the different frequency with which individual codes were discussed between each simulated classroom. Figure 9.12 shows the relative frequency of individual codes spoken by participants during the Think Aloud study. Figure 9.12 shows that certain codes, and therefore certain subjects, were addressed more frequently than others. The subjects of *space to move around the classroom*, the *layout of the desks*, the *relationship between pupils and teachers*, *group work*, *visual engagement* and *pedagogies* were mentioned the most by participants. Twelve codes received a frequency of zero indicating these subjects were not mentioned at all by participants. These subjects included the influence of parents on teachers' choices, socio-economic status, the influence of local government and the impact of ITE on their classroom organisation and management.

Figure 9.12: Relative frequency of individual codes – Think Aloud Study

Superficial observation would suggest that those topics mentioned the most by participants were the ones connected with the goals of classroom organisation and management and the physical elements of the classroom. Those topics which were mentioned least involved the external or political influences on teachers' choices. This is perhaps unsurprising considering how this study was designed. Additional insight can be gained by looking at the frequency of particularly codes in relation to each simulated classroom. One obvious example is the code *Group Work*. According to Figure 9.13, *Group Work* was mentioned eighty-three times by participants. Figure 9.13 shows how this number breaks up according to each classroom.

Figure 9.13: The frequency of the code *Group Work* in each simulated classroom

Group Work was mentioned approximately twice as much in *AMClassroom1* than in the other two rooms. This is unsurprising given that the desks in *AMClassroom1* were set out in four groups and the classroom was populated with technology and resources designed to support a learning centred pedagogy. In *AMClassroom2* the desks were arranged in a horseshoe and in *AMClassroom3* the desks are arranged in rows. For comparison, please consider Figures 9.14, 9.15 and 9.16.

Figure 9.14: The frequency of code *Technology* in each simulated classroom

Figure 9.15: The frequency of code Student Access in each simulated classroom

Figure 9.16: The frequency of code Available Resources in each simulated classroom

From this figure we can see that *Technology* was discussed in *AMClassroom1* more than twice as much as in the other two. *Pupils Access Resources* was also discussed approximately twice as much in *AMClassroom1*. *Available Resources* was discussed an approximately equal amount. In this case the codes *Group Work*, *Technology* and *Pupils Access Resources* were discussed noticeably more in the simulated classroom designed to reflect these characteristics. However, the same cannot be said in every case. Simulated classroom *AMClassroom2* was designed to express the ideas of visual engagement and the use of pupils' work to express ownership of the space.

It is possible to see from Figures 9.17 and 9.18 that despite the design of *AMClassroom2* being intended to emphasise the codes of *Pupils' Work as Ownership* and *Visual Engagement* these codes were discussed an approximately equal number of times in *AMClassroom2* as the two other classrooms. Only the code *Behaviour Management* was discussed noticeably more in *AMClassroom2* perhaps relating to the desks being arranged in a horseshoe shape (see Figure 9.19).

Figure 9.17: The frequency of code *Pupils' Work as Ownership* in each simulated classroom

Figure 9.18: The frequency of code *Visual Engagement* in each simulated classroom

Figure 9.19: The frequency of code *Behaviour Management* in each simulated classroom

The code *Communication* was discussed less than half as much in *AMClassroom3* than in the other two simulated classrooms (Figure 9.20). *AMClassroom3* was designed to represent a teacher centred pedagogy with all the desks in rows, reminiscent of a more traditional classroom.

Figure 9.20: The frequency of the code Communication in each simulated classroom

AMClassroom3, unlike the other two, was designed to negatively reflect the relevant themes. In this case, *Light* and *Engagement Through Fun*. This was accomplished in the design by several different methods but most notably the reduction in the lighting intensity by 20%, the use of drab neutral colours on the walls, the removal of almost all decorations, the removal of almost all examples of pupils work and the removal of evidence of any art-based work in progress.

Figures 9.21 and 9.22 show that in *AMClassroom3* the codes *Light* and *Engagement Through Fun*, were not discussed noticeably more or less than in the others. In fact, in both cases *AMClassroom3* holds the median score. The result of this is that it is not possible to consistently relate the intended characteristics of the simulated classrooms to the topics which they inspired participants to discuss.

Figure 9.21: The frequency of the code Light in each simulated classroom

Figure 9.22: The frequency of the code Engagement Through Fun in each simulated classroom

Simulated classroom *AMClassroom3* did achieve notably higher scores than the other two with regards to the topics of pupils being allowed to take ownership of the space (see Figure 9.23) and the establishment of clear rules for the classroom (see Figure 9.24).

Figure 9.23: The frequency of the code Pupils Own Space in each simulated classroom

Figure 9.24: The frequency of the code Clear Rules in each simulated classroom

9.4.1.3. The Frequency of Codes Relating to Participants Categories

It was also possible to examine the data from the Think Aloud study based on the four categories of participants. Figure 9.25 shows the frequency of codes recorded arranged according to the category of participants.

Figure 9.25: The frequency arranged according to the category of participants

Preservice teachers, in-practice teachers and retired teachers made only a marginally different number of statements regarding the organisation and management of the simulated classrooms. ITE educators made slightly more. Given that each participant was held to a roughly three-minute time limit in each simulated classroom this may suggest that ITE educators engaged more with the prescribed tasks than other participants.

There were also some marked differences in the frequency with which participant groups discussed certain topics. This can be illustrated by comparing the frequency with which certain codes were recorded by each participant group. For example, the topic of behaviour management was mentioned by retired or in-practice teachers noticeably more than preservice teachers (see Figure 9.26).

Figure 9.26: The frequency of the code for Behaviour Management according to the category of participants

The differences in the results between participant groups can be demonstrated by examining the frequency of other codes according to the category of participants. For example, the code *Teacher's Experience*, in Figure 9.27.

Figure 9.27: The frequency of the code for Teacher's Experience according to the category of participants

It is perhaps unsurprising that preservice teachers mentioned their experience less than the three other categories. Retired teachers discussed their experience noticeably more than the other groups. A less obvious example would be the discussion of pedagogies (see Figure 9.28).

Figure 9.28: The frequency of the code for Pedagogy according to the category of participants

All participants were asked about which pedagogy they thought most suited each simulated classroom. This was one of the prompts used during the Think Aloud study.

However, ITE educators mentioned pedagogies more than the other groups, with retired teachers discussing it the least.

Other codes stood out as having an uneven distribution between the four participants groups. For example, retired teachers mentioned the number of pupils in the class twice as much as any of the other categories (Figure 9.29). Conversely, Figure 9.30 shows that preservice teachers mentioned areas for dedicated or specialist activities more than twice as much as any other category of participant.

Figure 9.29: The frequency of the code for Number of Pupils according to the category of participants

Figure 9.30: The frequency of the code for Dedicated Areas according to the category of participants

There were several codes where the difference in frequency between participant categories was almost the same. For example, all participant categories mentioned *space to move around the classroom, arrangement of desks and group work* a similar amount.

Of course, there were also several categories that were mentioned by no participants, as was already apparent from Figure 9.12. These included *parental influence on classroom organisation*, *socio-economic factors*, and the *influence of ITE* on their approach to classroom organisation and management.

9.4.2. Triangulation with the Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were carried out immediately after the participants had completed the Think Aloud portion of the study. The interviews were intended to cover similar topics. The aim was to triangulate the results of the Think Aloud method with the data collected during the interviews and explore consistencies and inconsistencies between the two sets of data. Participants often continued to talk about thoughts and ideas in the interviews which had previously been expressed during the Think Aloud method. However, participants also provided additional information and clarification of ideas having been given a moment to reflect on their experience using VR. For example, all participants remained consistent about their preferred classroom out of the three simulated environments between observing it in VR and responding in the interview, however, all participants provided *additional* information about why they held particular preferences.

The results of the content analysis showed that participants discussed *physical adaptation* the most followed by *engagement*, *ownership* and the *relationship between pupils and teachers*. This was reflected most strongly in the interviews by the responses provided by in-practice teachers. In-practice teachers responded to the interviews with practical considerations for what desk layout would work best for their teaching style and what would work best for the pupils.

*“I suppose a lot of it’s based on the pupils age, who the classroom is for.
That’s going to impact a lot.”*

Participant Y5

“It was where – so the basis for all interaction is where the children are sitting, and the layout of the tables either made learning more or less conductive.”

Participant Y3

In-practice teachers also discussed the importance of the relationship between the pupils and the teachers. They emphasised a strong connection between the relationship between the pupils and the teachers, the teacher's ability to communicate with each pupil and the layout of the desks in the room.

"You're trying to build in more relationship. That's your first thing that you want to do. You want to be relating to everybody in the room and taking down barriers from that... the importance of the relationship between the teacher and their pupils. I think that makes a difference for everything else; learning, behaviour, all of that."

Participant Y7

Other participants mentioned these factors briefly, but noticeably in-practice teachers made this the focus of their discussion in the interviews.

One apparent consistency between the results of the content analysis and the follow-up interviews was that participants' responses seemed to broadly reflect the suggested pedagogy for each of the simulated classrooms. This can only be suggested in a very general sense because few participants directly discussed their pedagogical approach in the interviews. However, most participants expressed a preference for one classroom layout based on their own preferred approach to teaching. Retired teachers, for example, preferred the pupils to be focused on them and emphasised being in control of the lesson and managing behaviour. For these reasons they preferred *AMClassroom2* and *AMClassroom3* both of which could be adapted to a teacher centred pedagogy. For example:

"[I] used primarily classroom set up number one [AMClassroom3 – desks in rows], and occasionally for very specific purposes, classroom setup number two [AMClassroom1 – desks in groups]. It was an attempt to try and find something that I could achieve a measure of control over a class that I was struggling with, and classroom setup number one."

Participant X1

In a similarly way, preservice teachers expressed a preference for *AMClassroom1* and *AMClassroom2*, both of which could be adapted to learner centred or learning centred

pedagogies. This was reflected in their focus on a flexible adaptable space that could be split into dedicated areas of learning as necessary along with a focus away from behaviour management and control. Similarly, in-practice teachers were split between favouring *AMClassroom1* and *AMClassroom2*. However, this preference was most often justified by referencing the age of the pupils being taught rather than the specific pedagogical approach of the participant. ITE educators, among all the participants, provided the only specific discussion of pedagogical approaches in their interview responses. On several occasions ITE educators would refer to a specific pedagogical approach when justifying their preference for one classroom layout or another. For example, when justifying their preference for *AMClassroom2* (desks in horseshoe) one participant replied:

“Because it is invitational; because the children are facing one another; and particularly... that the conversation is not about what the teacher knows... but about what the children understand of the world in that moment and how they can construct understanding together. It’s a social-constructivist classroom.”

Participant Y8

This seems to be consistent with the results of the content analysis, that ITE educators discussed pedagogy more than any other participant groups. However, what was apparent in the interviews was that all participants organise and manage their classroom according to their own pedagogical approach but only ITE educators used formalised academic language to describe the process.

All participants mentioned the need for flexibility in the layout of desks and the importance of the teacher being able to alter the layout of the classroom to suit the needs of the lesson. Preservice teachers mentioned the need for additional space in the classrooms and that the desk layouts of the simulated classrooms did not leave much room for flexibility.

And I think that different set ups of desk lend themselves better to different pupils, different year groups, different situations. So having flexibility within desk spacing is really much more important than having an optimum desk set up you like.”

Participant Y9

In contrast to the results of the content analysis, few retired teachers mentioned the importance of the number of pupils. What they did speak about, and what seemed to be the primary influence on their decision-making process, was their ability to control the lesson – *behaviour management*. This was consistent with the results of the content analysis. Retired teachers were split in their preference between *AMClassroom2* (desks in a horseshoe) and *AMClassroom3* (desks in rows). However, in both cases their justification was that they believed their preferred layout offered the best opportunity for managing behaviour and communicating with the class. In this case, the process of reflection and discussion provided by the interviews added an additional layer of understanding to data provided by the content analysis.

In the follow-up interviews preservice teachers all mentioned the importance of having dedicated areas of the classrooms. *Dedicated areas* in this case meant areas of the classroom which were marked off or equipped to enable a specialist activity. This supported the findings of the content analysis, that found preservice teachers talked about dedicated areas more than any other participant group. Suggestions for dedicated areas in the classrooms included libraries, reading areas, a sink, an area for artistic activities, a quiet area and an open area for yoga. For example:

“I’ve seen classrooms that have a lot more dedicated areas in them. So, that’s something that I didn’t pick up in these environments, so this was very much desks and chairs, but I’ve been in classrooms where there’s dedicated, you know, reading corners, or computer corners, or arts and crafts corners.”

Participant Y12

The simulated classrooms were designed to be applicable to as general a group of teachers as possible. Dedicated areas were deliberately excluded from the simulated classroom designs because they had the potential to make the rooms too specialist. However, it is noteworthy that the focus by preservice teachers on dedicated areas in the Talk Aloud method is strongly reflected in the follow-up interviews.

Consistent with the results of the content analysis, none of the participants discussed external influences such as national or local government as an element of their decision-making process. However, some participants did discuss other factors that influenced their approach to classroom organisation and management. The results of the

content analysis showed that retired teachers talked about experience noticeably more than the other participants group. However, this was not so obviously apparent in the follow-up interviews. In the interviews all participants drew on previous experience of different classrooms to justify their decisions and illustrate their approach to teaching and learning. Most participants emphasised that learned experience was the primary way they developed and improved their approach. Preservice teachers did not speak in detail about the influences on their approaches. Only one provided any data on influences and they emphasised that training was of little importance next to the experience of being in a classroom.

“Training? No, I don’t feel I’ve had much training on it. I think a lot is based on my own experience as a learner. And also, having the opportunity to be on placements where I’ve seen things done in different ways.”

Participant Y12

Similarly, participants who were retired teachers emphasised the importance of experience and instinct when making decisions about classroom management and organisation. None considered their ITE experience to be relevant to how they chose to organise and manage a classroom. When asked what the biggest influence on their decision making was, one participant responded:

“My ability to have control over the classrooms setting.”

Participant X1

Retired teachers typically believed that their approach to classroom organisation and management was a result of the system in which they had worked, their collected experience and an evolution of their own experience as a learner. For example:

“I think its work experience and instinct and what me as a teacher is comfortable with. I was comfortable with [AMClassroom3 – desks in rows] because that was the system I came through myself... younger teachers, they would come through a system where they were exposed to group work or horseshoes or that.”

Participant X2

Similarly, in-practice teachers described their learning process as one of trial and error, of gaining experience by watching other teachers and discussing the best approaches to classrooms organisation and management. None of the in-practice teachers considered their ITE experience to have provided them with the skills for classrooms organisation and management. For example:

“It is definitely your experience. You know, you gain – there’s only so much knowledge that you can gain through lectures and tutorials and things, but it’s learning by osmosis, when you’re out in the actual physical environment.”

Participants Y3

Participants whose preferred classroom was *AMClassroom1* (desks in groups – accessible resources and technology) talked about the inclusion of technology in lessons and groups working in the interviews. For example:

“It was good storage in that one. There was a good wee computer area in that one. Good storage. It was good technological provision. There was a smartboard, whiteboard, whatever you call it.”

Participant Y6

AMClassroom2 was designed to be a learner centred classroom, to be visually engaging and to display lots of examples of the students’ work creating a sense of ownership. In the interviews, participants in the preservice teachers group tended to focus on ideas of communication and lines of sight. For example:

“I liked the fact that you were closer to all of the students and the ability to connect. I liked the fact that they could see each other. It feels like there was less of a place to hide.”

Participants Y13

Preservice teachers also considered the horseshow layout of *AM Classroom2* to have advantages for behaviour management, which is consistent with the findings of the content analysis.

“If they’re not looking they don’t know you’re looking at them, so to get their attention if anybody is not facing you, they need to be physically turned, so

that struggles with behaviour management. The horseshoe helps you because you can work out who's looking, who's not, what they're doing."

Participant Y11

In-practice teachers who favoured *AMClassroom1* and *AMClassroom2* emphasised the flexibility of the layout. This sentiment was repeated with less emphasis by preservice teachers. It was unclear why these classrooms were perceived to be more flexible than *AMClassroom3* when all contained the same number of desks, the same type of furniture and had the same floor area. Retired teachers expressed a preference for using *AMClassroom3* more than any other group. However, the data provided during the interview did not reflect the results of the content analysis. The results of the content analysis suggested that communication, light, engagement though fun and students' ownership of the space were the most talked about topics in *AMClassroom3*. However, when discussed by retired teachers in the interview, *AMClassroom3* was mostly considered for its advantages for behaviour management. Communication was also discussed as *AMClassroom3* was considered suitable for holding the attention of pupils in a formal, teacher centred, environment.

By triangulating the results of the follow-up interviews with the results of the content analysis it is possible to see some consistency in the results but also possible to provide additional detail and understanding about observations made during the content analysis.

9.4.3. Feedback from Participants on VR in ITE

The final part of the semi-structured interview asked participants their opinion of using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. The response from retired teachers was overwhelmingly positive. All four retired teachers commented on the realism of the simulated classroom and the feeling of actually being there. Two of the retired teachers commented on the emotional significance of the experience and said that it felt like returning to work. Perhaps most significantly, they all responded positively to the idea of VR being used in ITE. As one participant described it:

"I think that a lot of folks that are entering teaching won't have had much experience of standing in front of a classroom or moving around a classroom."

So the idea of being able to discuss the layout, be in the layout but not necessarily in a classroom... what we basically have done here today."

Participant X1

The idea of creating a less idealised classroom was also suggested by the retired teachers. The necessity to work around limitations or resource problems would potentially add to the ITE experiences.

"It might be interesting to create a less pleasant classroom and see how that works. One that has obvious problems."

Participant Y1

The retired teacher participants saw no obvious limitations with the use of VR in ITE. Two of the participants expressed that there was a short period of acclimatisation as they got used to VR. All of them expressed the idea that the VR experiences would have to be set up to facilitate the desired learning outcomes.

"I don't see many limitations. I think, if the person setting up the programme is prepared to put in the effort and create, as I say, difficult classrooms, or classrooms with particular problem or situations with particular problems... I think there are immense possibilities."

Participant Y1

The responses from in-practice teachers were mixed with regard to their enjoyment using the VR experience and its potential applicability to ITE. All in-practice teachers commented on the realism of the virtual experience and that they very quickly felt like they were *actually in* the classroom.

"I think it is surprising how quickly you can – your brain just adapts and – it very quickly felt natural, very familiar."

Participant Y7

Those in-practice teachers who spoke positively about the VR experience mentioned the ability to explore and fully understand the 3D space. That the experience was more real and more immersive than any 2D equivalent.

“If you were looking at a flat version of that, even a 3D flat version of that – you’re not going to get the same depth perception that you are being in the classroom... the first thing I saw [lack of available space] became an obvious thing.”

Participant X3

Those in-practice teachers who spoke negatively about the VR experience agreed that it looked and felt real but also felt that, for the purposes of learning classroom organisation and management, a video or other 2D media would be just as useful. They also felt that the expense of using VR and the additional training required could be prohibitive when using it for entire student year groups. Participants who spoke negatively about VR felt that it could never be a substitute for actual work experience.

“The same with any job, you need to be in there to learn it. So like with my first classroom I must have changed the layout six times... I just hadn’t worked it out, what layout works best... also knowing your kids; knowing who can sit together... a lot of it depends on the variable, real-life factors.”

Participant Y5

One participant pointed out some of the potential problems when using VR with hearing impaired students. Partly this involved the technical challenges of linking VR technology to the technology provided to support students who are hearing impaired, including Bluetooth headphones, hearing aids and audio transmitters. In addition, there would be a problem with lip reading or communication by sign language.

“If you’re talking to them and they can’t see you, they can’t lip-read you... as a teacher of the deaf, if I was showing the kids a video on YouTube, I can... attach their transmitter to the computer so, whatever YouTube is saying, it is going straight to their ears.”

Participant Y5

The response from preservice teachers to the use of VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE was mixed. Overall, as before, preservice teachers felt immersed in the realism of the VR experience. Participants liked the ability to move around and explore the room and to see the classroom from different perspectives.

“To ask people to go into different seats and to be that student... I was using the little trigger [the teleport function] to move around the classroom to see what it was like if I sat there or if I was a student sitting there.”

Participant Y12

Two participants expressed that it was useful to be able to experience multiple different classroom layouts quickly and see all the different possibilities. However, both participants felt that this facility would be more useful for designers and architects and far less use for teachers. In response to being asked if VR would be useful in ITE one participants said:

“No, because – for teacher training, it’s more about developing your style of teaching and strategies. The facilities, we’re never going to be able to influence the facilities... I think it’s for people who design and build schools. It’s more for them.”

Participant Y6

The same participant continued to say that in their opinion VR could not substitute for real-world experience because only by seeing the classroom in the real-world, and how the pupils interacted with it, could the teacher understand the context for any organisational changes they made. In a less theoretical response, one preservice teacher commented on how uncomfortable they found the VR equipment to be:

“The headset is horrible, it’s really heavy. I don’t know how I could have tolerated it much longer, my face is still recovering, and there was pressure on the back of my head and my cheeks.”

Participant Y13

ITE educators were consistently positive about the VR experience and its potential use in ITE. One participant who claimed to normally suffer from bad motion sickness felt no such sensation while using the VR. ITE educators generally believed that the depictions of classrooms were realistic and immersive. They valued the ability to explore the space in detail and demonstrate modern classroom layouts in a way which would not have been possible while using a 2D medium.

“You feel the space in a weird way that I don’t really understand why but you definitely have a sense of what that space feels like in a way that just looking at a picture of it or just looking at it on a screen wouldn’t do.”

Participant Y9

“ITE students, that none of them have been in a class since they were at school. And for some people... not since the 80s or 90s – things have changes a lot. So, to be able to see and experience that...”

Participant Y3

However, where ITE educators provided the most feedback was in the context of how simulated classrooms might be applied to ITE. For example:

“I like the fact that you made me think about different ways of thinking about the classroom. So although you offered me three layouts it forced me to have the conversation in my head about why I do – why I might choose to have my classroom like this or like that or the other? So I think that’s its value.”

Participant Y8

Participants also expressed the idea that a VR experience like this could be used to bridge the gap between learning theory and working practice in schools. According to participants, ITE students are taught strategies for teaching and learning that they are not able to practice until they are in front of a real-world classroom. However, if ITE students were presented with simulated classrooms they could be asked:

“What would you do with this space and how do you justify it in terms of what you know about learning theory? Here is the practice, here is the theory, where is the connection? Where is the disconnection? And I think that this offers the opportunity to have that conversation.”

Participant Y8

“When we often talk about pedagogical approaches with the students and you know, different learning and teaching strategies they might use, it’s good for them to see. How would you do that in this environment? When you’re limited in terms of what you can do.”

Participant Y2

With regards to limitations, ITE educators believed that the primary limitation was in the limited variety and the interactivity of the simulations. Their comments included the need for more varieties of classroom including more exotic, experimental or outdoor environments. ITE educators also suggested that the ability to move objects and rearrange the room would contribute to the value of the experience.

Overall, the participants were split evenly between primary and secondary education. Three of the four preservice teachers were focused on primary education, three out of the four retired teachers were from secondary education and the other two categories were an even split. Generally, participants from a primary background identified the three simulations as secondary classrooms and participants from a secondary background identified them as primary classrooms. All participants acknowledged the limitations imposed upon the study by making the classroom designs as generalisable as possible. Some participants suggested that futures studies should focus on less general classroom designs reflecting the specialist needs of primary and secondary education.

Three participants reacted badly to the *IntroEnvironment*. This serves as an example of the care which must be taken when designing and developing VR experiences to limit the effects of cybersickness. The introductory environment was a deliberately unrealistic environment which was intended to allow the participants to practice the functionality of the VR experience and acclimatise them to using VR. Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) had found that participants, with limited to no experience of using VR, were often distracted by the virtual world and failed to engage with the intended tasks. To overcome this potential problem and to limit the distinction between participants with VR experience and those without all participants were able to spend time in the *IntroEnvironment* before transferring to the simulated classrooms and the study proper. Unfortunately, the choice of a science fiction star-scape as the backdrop for the introductory environment was not comfortable for all participants. A few reported a fear of heights or even vertigo when presented with an environment which appeared to be floating in space. In these cases, *IntroEnvironment* had the opposite effect than intended by making individual participants uncomfortable when using VR. Future studies which use a similar approach to acclimatise participants to the use of VR should attempt to create a more neutral environment to alienate as few participants as possible. In this study only

19% of participants reported negative feelings while in *IntroEnvironment*. However, in a larger study that percentage has the potential to skew results particularly when the study is examining participants feelings towards VR.

9.5. Discussion

The overall aim of this PhD was to investigate the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. This present study was the culmination of the ADDIE design framework, where the VR experience was implemented and critically assessed. The primary aim of this study was to answer the research question: *Can VR simulated classroom environments provide a medium for professional development and reflection for teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?* The results of this study indicate that VR can provide a flexible and controllable medium for reflection for teachers and educators regarding classroom organisation and management. In addition, in the opinion of most participants, VR could provide a medium for professional development and ITE. However, there were several viewpoints on how it might be used and the potential limitations of its use.

There was an obvious pattern to how each of the 8 themes were addressed by participants. Approximately one third of participants' statements were under the theme of *physical adaptation*. This is hardly surprising given that the VR experiences simulated the physical environment of classrooms with only minimal reference to the outside world. However, it may also demonstrate a very basic ability of VR to faithfully simulate a physical space. Other studies have demonstrated the importance of creating VR learning environments with physical fidelity. For example: Ragan *et al.* (2015) suggested that when simulating socially complex environments the physical fidelity of the experience had a direct effect on the learning process. However, their study had limited success in the transfer of skills from the VR environment to the real world. Similarly, Real *et al.* (2017) found that the physical realism of the simulation contributed to its ability to teach communication skills to medical residents, however, their study relied heavily on data from self-reported measures. The actual significance of physical fidelity to learning outcomes remains uncertain and should be assessed based on the relevant competencies. Participants in this present study commented on the physical realism of the classroom simulations and implied that it contributed to their sense of presence in the virtual

environment. It should be noted that, as with Ragan *et al.* (2015) and Real *et al.* (2017), realism and a sense of presence does not guarantee learning, it simply suggested that participants were engaged with the virtual environment. Participants focused mainly on the physical elements of the learning environment. This could be a predictable consequence of creating the experiences in VR and of this PhD focusing on how teachers organise and manage their physical learning environment.

The next two most discussed themes were *engagement and ownership* and the *pupil/teacher relationships*. In contrast to physical adaptation, these two themes represent attributes of the classroom that are often less tangible and more open to individual interpretation. Other studies have demonstrated that VR can be effective when teaching intangible social skills, such as DeWitt *et al.* (2022) using the immersive medium of VR to teach cultural competence. In contrast to this present study, DeWitt *et al.* (2022) utilised the development of the VR experiences as part of the learning process. It is unclear from their study if the creation or the use of VR experiences played the greater part in the development of cultural competence. Similarly, Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) intended the VR environment to provoke an emotional reaction in teachers viewing a particular scenario. Their study effectively demonstrates the ability of VR to provoke an emotional reaction in the user, however, based on their results it is unclear if this reaction can be adapted into a learning experience. It is clear from this present study that the immersive quality of VR can generate an emotional reaction in participants and allow discussion of topics that deal with complex social issues, such as the relationship between pupils and teachers or the ability of a teacher to engage pupils in lessons. Participants' justification for preferring one classroom over another was often based on the choice that generated the more favourable relationship between pupils and teachers, something that is very difficult to demonstrate physically. However, the connection between the physical attributes of a classroom and the social interaction it facilitates was often used by participants to explain their approach to its organisation and management.

It was difficult to determine the extent to which the language used by participants in each simulated classroom was a result of the pedagogy inspired design ethos of that classroom. In a sense, this was an attempt to control the *mise-en-scène*, as previously suggested by Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019), to use all the available characteristics of the virtual environment to suggest a particular learning approach or pedagogy. The results presented

by Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019) were ambiguous at best, suggesting that the user's attention could be drawn using the *mise-en-scène* but that it did not significantly alter the remembered experience. In this present study, the codes that were disproportionality discussed in *AMClassroom1* reflected the intended characteristics of that room. However, the codes that were disproportionality discussed in *AMClassroom3* were the opposite of the characteristics that room was intended to reflect. It should be noted at this point that no distinction was made between positive and negative comments made regarding a particular topic when codifying the results. For example, a participant could say, "*the lighting in this classroom is terrible.*" Another participant could say, "*the lighting in this classroom is wonderful.*" Both would have been recorded as a single count under the code *Lighting* in the theme *Learning Atmosphere*. This approach was taken because distinguishing between positive and negative statements adds additional uncertainties to the recording. For example, how to classify a statement that is positive but not about the simulated environment, such as "*the lighting in my own classroom is really good.*" Neutral statements would also need to be categorised separately, for example, "*the first thing I notice is the lighting.*" Coding participant responses to the sixty original codes *and* positive and negative and neutral or unrelated' may have diluted the results and introduce a level of complexity that was inappropriate for this study.

Without considering this level of complexity, the only way to suggest why participants discussed specific topics in relation to specific classrooms is to look to the results of the interviews. Broadly speaking, the interviews suggested that those participants, usually retired teachers, who focused on behaviour management and a teacher centred approach favoured *AMClassroom2* and *AMClassroom3*. Those participants who focused on interaction with the pupils in a learner centred approach preferred *AMClassroom1* and *AMClassroom2*. This is supported by the work of Gremmen *et al.* (2016), who found that the primary reason for teachers arranging pupils in groups was to promote social interaction and the reason for arranging them in rows was to limit distractions and promote concentration. In this present study, the topics discussed the most in each simulated classroom were not always the ones which the design of the simulated classroom would have predicted. Further research would be required to determine to what extent the language used in each VR classroom is reflective of its design and layout. Another potential avenue for further research would be to consider the

different approaches to the three classroom layouts between participants whose background was primary or secondary education. The fact that, generally, participants from a primary background identified the three simulations as secondary classrooms and participants from a secondary background identified them as primary classrooms may be a result of the rooms being too generalised in design. Future research should explore the different approaches to classroom organisation and management between primary and secondary education and reflect this difference in the design of the simulated classrooms.

Participants commented that experiencing the simulated classrooms in VR allowed them to reflect on their own approach to teaching and how they organised and managed their classrooms. Chapter 2 briefly discussed the definition of what constitutes a pedagogy (Ko, Sammons and Bakkum, 2013). Although all participants justified their comments in terms of their approach to teaching, only participants in the ITE educators group used academic language to discuss specific pedagogies. Participants typically described their approach to teaching as an accumulation of their life experience, with little or no reference to their ITE. This supports the assertion made by Bosch (2006) where classroom organisation and management is a skill that *can* be taught, but is refined through years of experience, however, this is mainly supported by anecdotal evidence and personal experience. It also supports the results of Study 1 which identified ITE had little effect on a teachers approach to the organisation and management of their classroom. In the content analysis, preservice teachers mentioned areas for dedicated or specialist activities more than twice as much as any other category of participant. Conversely, retired teachers mentioned behaviour management more than all other participants combined. This difference was confirmed in the follow-up interviews. It is possible this indicates a different approach to teaching or, more likely, a different approach to the organisation and management of classrooms. Perhaps one that has evolved with experience or perhaps the difference between an older and more modern approach.

Some participants also commented that simulated VR classrooms had the potential to allow teachers to reflect upon and discuss different classroom layouts and teaching approaches outside of the working school environment. The ability of VR to encourage reflection and discussion was previously demonstrated by Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b), who used simulated classrooms to stage bullying incidents and allow teachers to observe and reflect on the experience. In their study, the opportunity for

reflection after the VR experience was as important to the learning process as the experience itself. This aligns with the results of this present study. The ability to facilitate discussion of pedagogies and reflection on the organisation and management of the learning environment strongly suggests that VR has potential as a tool for ITE.

Participants' response to the idea of VR being used as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE was mostly positive. A small number of participants felt that nothing could be a substitute for real-world experience and so the application of VR was limited. Perhaps surprisingly, this view was predominantly held by less experienced participants in the preservice teachers or in-practice teachers group. This age distinction was also noted by Mayor Silva *et al.* (2023), who found that younger participants were less likely to be engaged with VR learning than older ones. It was also mentioned by participants in this present study that VR had the potential to exclude some people. Examples given included those people suffering from vertigo or cybersickness as previously expressed by Kaufeld *et al.* (2022) and Recenti *et al.* (2021). Other participants found the HMD awkward and difficult to wear. This is something that was found in other studies, for example Chae *et al.* (2023) limited participants to 15 minutes to reduce cybersickness and noted that participants with glasses found the HMD uncomfortable.

The most promising idea put forward by participants for the use of VR in ITE was as a bridge between the theory of classroom organisation and management and the professional reality. Particularly by participants in the ITE educators group, who expressed that the teaching of learning theory went from exposition to freedom in the real-world with nothing in between. VR has the potential to bridge that gap. ITE students could be presented with a VR classroom and asked "*what would you do with this space*" and "*how would you justify it in terms of what you know about learning theory*" (Participant Y8). In a sense, VR offers the opportunity to reflect and have that conversation in a way that other media does not. This is supported by the work of Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) whose results suggested that VR was a more effective medium for reflection than seeing the same scenario played out in the real world. The idea of VR being a bridge between learning theory and real-world practice raises the question of, *can the skills participants learn in this VR experience transfer to real-world practice?* This is a question raised in multiple studies involving VR training. Ragan *et al.* (2015) concluded, when training security personnel in VR, that skills did not easily transfer to real-world scenarios.

Participants in Amini *et al.* (2021), for example, demonstrated an improvement in their overall skillsets after VR training but it was unclear what long-term effect it had on their real-world practice. The results of this study have shown that VR has potential as a tool for teaching and learning classroom organisation and management in ITE and suggested that it may provide an opportunity for ITE students to practice learning theory in a controlled and repeatable environment. Its findings will inform the next stages of research i.e., studies exploring the effectiveness of VR in improving skillsets in real-world practice.

9.5.1. Creating VR Experiences for ITE

The secondary aim of this study was to answer the research question: *What best practice can be identified for VR and 360° video being used for simulating classroom environments for use in Initial Teacher Education?* The design of the VR experiences in this study were informed by the three studies preceding it (Study 1-3), as described in detail in Chapter 8. Based on the feedback provided by participants in this study, there are several observations that can be added to best practice processes when creating VR experiences for teacher education.

Perhaps most significantly, participants commented positively on the realism and fidelity of the simulated environments. It seems that the realism of the environments contributed to participants' sense of presence while using the HMD. Participants commented on both the physical fidelity and the conceptual fidelity of the VR experiences. This was something noted by other studies where participants in Real *et al.* (2020) noted the physical fidelity of the VR experiences when providing medical training. Also, in Chae *et al.* (2023) participants noted the cognitive fidelity of the interaction with digital avatars. In this present study, participants' positive reaction to the simulated environment seemed to be in part based on their physical fidelity (the physical elements appeared realistic and detailed) and the conceptual fidelity (it was arranged like a believable working classroom). Participants made two general comments about the simulated classrooms, neither of which was wholly negative. The first was that the classrooms were a little unoccupied and devoid of the personal touch that a teacher and pupils would impart. Second, it was not always clear what age group the classrooms were designed for. These were the result of deliberate design choices to make the simulated classrooms as generalisable as possible. Perhaps future similar research could create more specialist classrooms, aimed at a particular age group.

A second important factor when designing these VR experiences was the ability of participants to freely explore the virtual environment. This was recognised as a potentially important element of the virtual environment by participants in Study 2 (Chapter 6). The findings of Study 2 were supported by the responses of participants in this present study. Several participants commented on the usefulness of being able to view the virtual environment at will, and from different angles and perspectives. A small number of participants also suggested the potential of making the experience more interactive by allowing participants to rearrange the contents of the room. This interactivity is an important element of all VR experiences but has particular relevance for VR learning environments because it changes how the user is able to learn. The results of Study 3 (Chapter 7) suggested that few researchers have considered what learning approach is most effectively applied to VR learning. Chae *et al.* (2023) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022) both took a constructivist approach. The remaining seven studies examined in Study 3 emphasised perspective taking, repetition and experimentation, if they considered anything at all. Few researchers have considered an inquiry-based pedagogy for VR. One in which participants are encouraged to investigate, interact with and explore the VR environment (Kuhlthau, Maniotes and Caspari, 2015). The ability to explore the environment seemed to be an important part of participants experience in this present study and so this pedagogical approach for VR should be researched further.

9.5.2. Strengths and Limitations

Study 4 had several key strengths: (1) it used the structured ADDIE design framework to inform the design and development of the three simulated classrooms; (2) it involved a participatory approach; and (3) it triangulated data from three sources to produce a deeper understanding of what is an innovative method of learning. By using the ADDIE design framework, it was possible to create the VR experiences based on an understanding of the process by which teachers organise and manage their classrooms. This framework also facilitated a better understanding of the advantages and limitations of XR media, specifically VR. The participatory approach meant that stakeholders were involved at each stage of the design process and were able to contribute valuable insight to the design of this present study. Triangulation of the data provided methodological bridge between the results of the content analysis and the data gathered through semi-

structured interviews. By this method it has been possible to identify patterns in the data, determine their consistency between the two sources and provide additional depth to the interpretation of the results (Napa, Moore and Bardyn, 2019; Su *et al.*, 2020).

There are several limitations in this study that should be noted and may usefully inform future work. First, although the results of the Think Aloud method and the content analysis show patterns in the data, their generalisability is limited by a small sample focused on the Scottish education system. Second, although the sample size of 16 participants was justified for an exploratory study, it did not allow for any inferential statistical analysis of the data. For a true statistical analysis of the content analysis, and increase ecological validity allowing generalisation to a larger population, a study like this would require a much larger groups of participants. However, the marked difference in frequency with which certain participants groups addressed certain topics may indicate the difference in experience. The differences in the results between participant groups may still be a useful guide as to how users of varying experience react to the VR environment.

There are also limitations in how the data was coded. Coding was completed by one researcher. Without consultation and validation by multiple researchers, there is a danger in compounding errors in interpretation by relying on a single perspective (Stemler, 2015). Future studies of this type could increase the reliability of the data by involving multiple researchers in the coding process and the interpretation of results. As previously stated in the discussion, there is also the potential to use a more detailed coding system that involves positive, negative or neutral responses.

9.5.3. Future Studies

Study 4 was a first step in investigating the potential for using VR as a teaching tool in ITE. Its findings will inform the development of subsequent studies. For example, future studies could focus on the sense of presence felt by participants while in the VR experience. Sense of presence is often considered to be an important element in the effectiveness of a VR learning experience (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). Other studies, such as Chae *et al.* (2023) and Real *et al.* (2017), have identified the user's sense of presence as being an important element in the effectiveness of the learning process. The idea of presence, of reacting to the simulated classrooms as if they were real

environment, was certainly spoken about by participants in this present study but it is unclear exactly how much it contributed to the effectiveness of the VR learning experience. There are multiple ways to measure presence in VR. These include: physical signs, by assessing biomarkers such as heart rate or galvanic skin response; psychological measures, such as questionnaires; and behavioural markers, involving a subjective observation of a participant's actions (Toet *et al.*, 2021). Questionnaires would perhaps be the most applicable to this present type of study and, in parallel with other data, would provide an indication of the effect of presence on the VR learning experience (Schwind *et al.*, 2019).

One potential direction for future studies would be to critically analyse the long-term effectiveness of VR as a teaching tool in ITE. Based on the results of Study 3 (Chapter 7), few researchers investigate the long-term effects of learning in VR. Such a study should attempt to investigate the transfer of skills from the VR experience to a real-world classroom. As demonstrated in Chapter 3, transferring learned skills from VR to the real-world is not always reliable. However, this could be particularly difficult to measure in this instance as there is no obvious performance standard by which to measure a teacher's organisation and management of their classroom, a task known to be complex and challenging (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016). A study which assessed the real-world application of VR learning in classroom organisation and management would necessarily begin with participants describing the challenges they face in their working classrooms. Participants could then use the VR environment to facilitate discussion or reflection on new and creative ways to meet those challenges. In a follow-up interview carried out weeks later, participants would be asked to what extent they felt the VR experience influenced their approach to classroom organisation and management and in what ways.

9.6. Conclusion

The aim of this PhD was to investigate the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. Study 4 aimed to answer the research question: *Can VR simulated classroom environments provide a medium for professional development and reflection for teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?* The results of this study were able to demonstrate that the VR experience of simulated classroom environments provided a medium for exploration and reflection. Participants were able to discuss

different approaches to the organisation and management of classrooms. They were also able to reflect on pedagogical approaches that related to the different layouts of the three simulated environments. Most participants reacted positively to the VR experiences and felt that they would have a place in ITE. The most promising suggestion was that VR experiences would provide ITE students with a medium for practicing the practical applications of learning theory before they carried their knowledge into a professional reality. This study demonstrated the potential for using VR in ITE, but future studies would be required to explore the effectiveness of transferring learned skills of classroom organisation and management to the real-world.

With regards to the research question: *What best practice can be identified for VR and 360° video being used for simulating classroom environments or use in Initial Teacher Education?* This study was able to demonstrate that physical and conceptual fidelity are important elements in creating a simulated learning environment for ITE. In addition, the ability to explore and interact with the environment was also important. Further research should investigate how these characteristics inform the best pedagogical approach for learning in VR.

Chapter 10. Discussion

The aim of this PhD was to investigate the potential for using VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. It specifically explored the potential use of VR and 360° video in ITE for the organisation and management of classrooms. This PhD consisted of four interlinking studies. Their findings, and how they fit in with the current literature, have been discussed in each of the study chapters. This chapter will now discuss how these findings address the five research questions of this PhD:

- **Research Question 1:** What factors influence how teachers organise and manage their learning environment?
- **Research Question 2:** Can 360° video be used effectively as a medium for teaching and learning?
- **Research Question 3:** Can VR be used to learn affective skill sets in a professional or vocational environment?
- **Research Question 4:** What is best practice for using VR and 360° video to simulate classroom environments within Initial Teacher Education?
- **Research Question 5:** Can VR provide a medium for professional development for preservice teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?

The key findings related to the five research questions will be discussed in turn below and presented in the context of the wider evidence base. Ongoing research gaps will be highlighted and areas for future research identified.

10.1. Addressing the Research Questions

Research Question 1: What factors influence how teachers organise and manage their learning environment?

This research question was addressed by Study 1 (Chapter 5), a qualitative interview study with in-practice teachers. Study 1 was a series of semi-structured interviews that aimed to investigate the factors that influence how in-practice teachers organise and manage their classrooms. The results of this study demonstrated the multiple complex factors that influence the choices made by teachers. In-practice teachers discussed how these factors constantly overlap and influence each other and that the balance of these factors is unique to every classroom. Eight themes were identified from Study 1: cultural influence;

school organisation; teacher's approach; physical adaptation; work adaptation; learning atmosphere; engagement and ownership; and the pupils/teacher relationship. Those themes could be loosely grouped into three categories: 1) those that were external and outside the teacher's influence, 2) those that formed the day-to-day make-up of the classroom and 3) those that represented the goals of classroom organisation and management.

Teachers organise and manage their learning environment based on many complex factors, as previously suggested by Shussman (2017). Participants in Study 1 discussed how the learning environment is so complex that they establish their classrooms through learned experience, instinct and observation. The eight themes indicate that many factors influence teachers' choices, including those that are external to the schools such as politics and socio-economic conditions, and unique factors such as pupils/teacher relationships. Key attributes of a well-functioning learning environment were aligned more with classroom goals and learning experience than with physical characteristics of the classroom. This required teachers to be flexible in their approach and adapt to multiple factors.

The results of Study 1 support the early work of Linney and Seidman (1989) who identified the learning environment as a chaotic, complex system with multiple interconnecting parts. The eight themes highlighted in Study 1 do indeed highlight a broad and complex network of factors, more so than other recent studies in the current evidence base. For example, our complex network of factors are in contrast to Martin (2016), whose review focused on physical characteristics, Jeon *et al.*'s (2014) socioeconomic factors, Kweon *et al.*'s (2017) ecological factors, or Veloso and Marques's (2017) political factors. Participants in this PhD also identified additional factors, such as, the age and stage of the pupils being taught, the expected quality of behaviour from individual pupils, the perceived relationship between teacher and pupils, the need to engage pupils and the need to provide pupils with a sense of ownership all as major influences. These findings informed the development of the simulated classrooms developed for Study 4 (Chapters 8 and 9).

Limitations of studies in the evidence base include: (i) studies undertaken with a majority demographic, such as Jeon *et al.*'s (2014) self-report measures gathered from predominantly European or American 'middle-class' parents; (ii) studies lacking causal

relationships due to non-randomisation of included schools (Kweon *et al.*, 2017); and (iii) studies focusing on subject-specific teaching such as Veloso and Marques's (2017) science laboratories. Likewise, limitations of Study 1 also include a majority demographic in the form of Scottish-based schoolteachers. However, Study 1 *did* explore insight from a range of participants, including male and female participants, primary and secondary education, teaching experience inside and outside the UK and a range of experience post-qualification. It is possible that a geographical focus outside of Scotland would have resulted in a different balance of influences. This is demonstrated in other studies, such as Marunda-Piki (2017), who report teachers in many African schools view the classroom as a functional space rather than an environment to actively engage and motivate pupils.

The results of Study 1 identified a large list of factors influencing how in-practice teachers organise and manage their learning environment. By grouping those factors into themes, it was possible to suggest an overall framework of external influences, physical and social classroom attributes and teaching goals that illustrated how teachers approached classroom organisation and management. This interpretation was strengthened by a process of respondent validation (Shenton, 2004), which allowed participants to confirm that the interpretation of their responses accurately reflected their own approach to teaching (Mays and Pope, 2000). Future research could explore if the framework identified by Study 1 accurately represents the thought process of in-practice teachers and if so, how could that framework be refined to allow a better understanding of classroom management and organisation.

Research Question 2: Can 360° video be used effectively as a medium for teaching and learning?

This research question was addressed by Study 2 (Chapter 6), a three-phase study that aimed to: (i) learn and practice the skills required to create and edit 360° videos; (ii) assess the potential limitations and advantages of using 360° videos as a primary element in future studies in this PhD; and (iii) to inform best practice guidelines for future educators or academics who wish to use 360° videos in a similar setting

The design phase of the ADDIE design framework is intended to identify the most suitable platform or media to facilitate the intended outcome. Findings from Study 2 demonstrated that 360° videos have utility for learning in education settings. This finding is supported in other studies, for example, Linton *et al.* (2022) who used 360° videos with

health science students, and Amini *et al.* (2021) with dental providers. Study 2 found 360° videos to be an accessible and adaptable medium with promising benefits that warrant further exploration of how they could be used within ITE. Advantages include the accessibility of 360° videos compared to other XR media and their ability to simulate a real-world environment quickly and faithfully. 360° videos provide immersion and a sense of presence, attributes that are lacking in desktop media. Study 2 also demonstrated that when better equipment (i.e. Vuze 3D 360 Camera versus Samsung Gear 360) and better editing software was used (i.e. Adobe Premier Pro 2020 versus Gear 360 ActionDirector), the viewing experience was significantly improved. Two key limitations of 360° videos were also identified by Study 2. These include the lack of interactivity and freedom-of-movement that is present in VR. 360° video limits the user to three degrees of freedom and reduces them to a passive observer in the immersive environment. Amini *et al.* (2021) overcame this disadvantage by using 360° videos in combination with VR and other media.

These advantages and disadvantages are similar to those found in studies of 360° in different environments. For example, Izard *et al.* (2018) reported that realistic imagery within an immersive environment was beneficial for medical training, but was limited by lack of movement and interactivity. Reeves *et al.* (2021) found 360° videos to provide a sense of presence in their study of managing social anxiety. Similarly, other studies in XR technology have suggested that a sense of presence is important when using XR technology for teaching and learning (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018), suggesting that 360° videos have potential as a tool for teaching and learning.

As explained in Chapter 6, 360° video did not feature further in this PhD. Restrictions resulting from COVID-19 limited access to working classrooms. The potential to use 360° video was heavily restricted and, therefore, other media became the sole focus. However, a key strength of Study 2 was feeding the advantages, disadvantages and participant insight of 360° video into the design and development of the simulated classrooms for Study 4 – the finale of this PhD.

Research Question 3: Can VR be used to learn affective skill sets in a professional or vocational environment?

This research question was addressed by Study 3 (Chapter 7), a systematic review of the application of VR to education in those professional fields that are socially or emotionally

complex. Although VR has been used for teaching and learning in medical and technical fields, it has not been evaluated for affective skill sets in situations that require complex social skills, such as the classroom. This systematic review addressed that gap.

Findings from nine included studies identified several different approaches to the design of VR experiences for teaching and learning. Included studies also identified that the effect of VR experiences on learning outcomes was consistently positive and that participants typically responded positively to the inclusion of VR experiences in the learning process.

VR was used for affective skills training in a variety of settings. These included: dentistry; nursing; medicine; teaching; and foreign language education. More specifically, the contexts within which the VR simulations were undertaken included: addressing vaccine hesitancy; bullying; communicating with patients from different cultural backgrounds; and general patient communication skills. Two of the studies were directly related to teacher education (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b). They both demonstrated positive results, specifically increased empathy, self-reflection and recognition of bullying incidents following their VR experience. Although neither study used a control group, one did use objective measures in the form of heart rate and electroencephalogram (EEG) (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). These measures demonstrated a physiological stress response when engaging with the VR bullying simulation (increased beta brainwaves via EEG and increased heart rate). This supports the utility of VR to provide immersive, realistic experiences that have the potential to reinforce learning for affective skills sets.

Findings from the included studies were generally positive, however, when examining *how* VR experiences were designed to facilitate learning in socially complex situations there were several limiting factors. Firstly, not all papers included sufficient detail of their VR design processes and technology choices. This made it challenging to fully interpret the VR experiences. Future publications should aim to include sufficient detail to enable effective interpretation, replication and/or translation of VR experiences to other settings. Most usefully for this PhD, three papers used the ADDIE design framework to provide an iterative structure to their design decisions and facilitate their reporting of design decisions (Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b; Chae *et al.*, 2023; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). The ADDIE design framework also facilitates input from stakeholders,

something which was important when ensuring the physical and conceptual fidelity of the VR experiences (Allen, 2006). When studies provided detail about hardware, software and design choices this made it easier to align feedback provided by participants with VR experiences in the included studies. This demonstrates the advantage of providing clear background information when reporting research on applications of immersive technology. This also demonstrates the utility of the ADDIE design model and supports its use as a key methodological tool throughout this PhD.

The nine included papers all reported that the inclusion of VR had a positive effect on learning outcomes. This strongly suggests that VR can be an effective tool for teaching and learning in socially complex situations in a professional or vocational environment. This supports the assertion made by both Jensen and Konradsen (2018) and Kaplan *et al.* (2020), that VR can be effective for training in affective skillsets. However, neither Jensen and Konradsen (2018) or Kaplan *et al.* (2020) had sufficient evidence upon which to base their assertion. The results of Study 3 suggest that VR training in affective skills or social interactions is applicable across a range of professional scenarios. However, there remain some limitations to this assertion. Firstly, Study 3 is based on a small number of papers that represent the application of VR to a limited number of professions (including two papers focusing on teacher education). Secondly, there was no standardisation of tools and measures across the nine included studies. This made it challenging to make direct comparisons. For example, some studies used valid measures such as the 15-item Virtual Presence scale (Makransky, Lilleholt and Aaby, 2017), whereas others used study specific questionnaires developed by individual research teams. Finally, included studies were limited by a lack of controlled comparisons (only 3 included a control group) and by small sample sizes (range 4-100 participants).

For all nine included papers, the feedback from participants was generally positive about the use of VR as a tool for teaching and learning. However, what was unclear from examination of these nine papers was what was the most effective approach to learning (or pedagogy) in VR. This is an area of academic research that requires further investigation. Particularly if the use of VR as a tool for teaching and learning continues to expand into other fields. Only two of the included papers specified a pedagogy in their design of an educational VR experience. Chae *et al.* (2023) and DeWitt *et al.* (2022) both took a constructivist approach to the design. Others did not specify except to say that VR

allowed participants to experiment and repeat the learning experience. Although researchers such as Bolinski *et al.* (2021) demonstrate that VR can be effective for emotional arousal, other researchers question the ethical conduct of such studies when they begin to focus on inducing empathy. For example, Raz (2022) discusses ethical complications of using VR to manipulate the feelings of users, while Sora-Domenj6 (2022) suggests there is limited evidence to suggest that using VR to generate empathy has a corresponding effect on social behaviour. This highlights ongoing gaps for future research.

Study 3 demonstrated the potential effectiveness of VR as a learning tool for complex social situations in a vocational or professional environment. However, this study also demonstrated the need for further research, particularly in the areas of teacher education, of the design of VR experiences and of how different pedagogical approaches might be applied to VR learning.

Research Question 4: What is best practice for using VR and 360° video to simulate classroom environments within Initial Teacher Education?

XR technology remains an emerging field when applied to teaching and learning. The technology is constantly changing (Jerard, 2016). Several significant changes, as outlined in Chapter 3, have taken place over the course of this PhD. Research that examines the potential for using XR for teaching and learning often focuses on the emotional experience of the participants or the desired learning outcomes. As demonstrated in Study 3, very few academic studies provided detailed information about the design process or provide best practice guidelines when creating XR experiences for teaching and learning. This PhD was initially focused on the potential for using VR *and* 360° videos in ITE. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, the latter half of this PhD focused solely on the use of VR. An important element of this PhD was to use the learned experience of creating 360° videos and VR experiences to contribute to best practice guidelines for future researchers undertaking similar studies.

This research question was addressed by Studies 2-4. As discussed in Chapter 6, 360° videos are still an emerging technology within education settings. Best Practice Guidelines will therefore be a useful tool for future researchers and educators. Study 2's findings helped identify four key best practice steps. The first was to **clearly understand the purpose of the immersive experience**. This supports the assertion made by Jensen and Konradsen (2018) that VR research should focus on specific applications to well

understood educational scenarios. The second was to **create a sense of presence in the user**. Several studies now support the idea that creating a sense of presence in the user enhances the educational effectiveness of VR (Chae *et al.*, 2023). The third heading was to **make use of the mise-en-scène** as suggested by Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019). Finally, the fourth, to **choose the most appropriate technology**. This is more difficult to demonstrate as many academic studies do not give details about the technology used, however, DeWitt *et al.* (2022) stand as an example of choosing technology that permits participants to be central to the design of the VR experience. It is noteworthy that the results of Studies 3 and 4 have reiterated these four headings as guidance for the creation of VR experiences. However, the results of Study 3 also emphasised the importance of **fidelity in the simulated environment** and **choosing an approach to learning which is appropriate for VR**. Study 4 further reinforced these guidelines while emphasising the importance of the **user's ability to explore and interact in VR**. Something which is not possible in 360° videos. The validity of these guidelines is limited by the small sample size of each of the four studies, the fact that most of the participants were drawn from a small pool of people in Scotland and that the focus of these studies is the relatively narrow application of XR to ITE. Future research should consider these guidelines, while considering participants feedback from other similar studies, to understand best practice when designing VR experiences as the technology continues to develop.

Research Question 5: Can VR provide a medium for professional development for preservice teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?

This research question was addressed by Study 4 (Chapters 8 and 9), a multi-methods design reflecting the final implementation and evaluation phases of the ADDIE design framework. Study 4 used the Think Aloud method (Ericsson and Simon, 1993) and semi-structured interviews to gather feedback from 16 participants who engaged with three different VR simulated classroom environments. The three simulations represented three different teaching pedagogies:

- **Learning centred** – designed to have an adaptable physical layout with accessible resources and technology on display (*AMClassroom1*);
- **Learner centred** – designed to engage the students and let them feel a sense of ownership with their environment (*AMClassroom2*);

- **Teacher-centred** – designed to be teacher focused and to have a good or bad learning atmosphere depending on the participant's views (*AMClassroom3*).

Participants explored these three environments while commenting on the positive and negative characteristics of how each simulated classroom was organised.

Content analysis of the results for the Think Aloud portion of this study suggested that participants reactions to the three different classrooms was in part based upon their level of experience but also on their approach to teaching. Participants also spoke about different topics depending on the physical layout and environmental factors that changed in each VR simulation. This suggests that the *mise-en-scène* in each simulated classroom could be used to facilitate discussion on different topics of classroom organisation and management (Kvisgaard *et al.*, 2019). Although this study did not undertake any inferential statistical analyses, the results of the content analysis do provide a useful indication of the topics discussed by teachers using the simulated classrooms for the purpose of teaching and learning. Particularly when triangulated with the results of the follow-up interviews. The semi-structured interviews aimed to provide an analytical comparison to the results of the content analysis. The initial analysis of the follow-up interviews suggested that participants responses were basically consistent between their feedback while in the VR experience and after. For example, preservice teachers continued to focus on splitting the classrooms into dedicated areas of learning, and ITE educators talked, in academic terms, about the pedagogical approaches applicable to each room. By triangulating the results of the content analysis and the interviews it was also possible to gain a better understanding of the information provided during the Think Aloud method. These results taken together indicate that simulated VR environments could be used as a tool to provoke reflection and discussion regarding the organisation and management of classrooms.

A key strength of Study 4 was its development phase (Chapter 8). The development of the simulated classroom environments formed a core part of this PhD. In this development phase the results of the previous three studies and the two literature reviews were brought together to inform the design of the simulated classrooms and the design of Study 4.

Another strength of this study was the breadth of participants. Insight was gathered from teachers with a range of teaching experience (ranging from preservice

teachers to retired teachers with 40+years teaching experience), a range of classroom experience (ranging from experience in 3-50 different classrooms); and a mix of male and female teachers (81.25% female). Most participants had little or no prior experience of using VR, providing what is likely a true reflection of the teaching population. However, it should be noted that the participant base was limited to participants from Scotland. This was a practical consideration. Providing participants with access to VR equipment was more practical when participants were locally available. Snowball sampling from personal or professional contacts meant that participants were drawn from approximately the same area. This is a limitation of this study, and it is possible that participants drawn from another country would have a different reaction to the VR experience.

Findings from Study 4 demonstrated that VR *is* a feasible medium for professional development and reflection for teachers and educators regarding classroom organisation and management. Most participants agreed that VR could provide a medium for professional development and ITE. It is true that some element of this enthusiasm should be attributed to the novelty of using an unfamiliar technology (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2016b). However, their opinion is supported by the ability of VR experiences to provoke discussion targeted at specific topics based around the simulated physical space as borne out by this study. A small number of participants felt that nothing could effectively substitute for real-world experience. It is true that, similar to studies carried out by Eldred-Evans *et al.* (2013) and Ragan *et al.* (2015), it is unclear if using VR to teach classroom organisation and management would allow learned skills to effectively transfer to the real-world. Assessing the transfer of skills to real-world classrooms should be the subject of further study. Study 4 has shown that there is the potential for using VR as a teaching tool in ITE for the organisation and management of classrooms, however, this PhD represents only the first step in this process. The results of Study 4 support the work of Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) and Stavroulia *et al.* (2019) by indicating that VR can provide a suitable medium to develop the professional skills of teachers. Participants in Study 4 highlighted the potential of VR to bridge the gap between learning theory (coursework), and its application in the real-world. VR may offer the opportunity for ITE students to explain how learning theory might be put into practice in a controlled and replicable environment.

10.2. Implications of this Research

The results described in this thesis have contributed to the general understanding of the factors which influence how teachers organise and manage their classrooms. The physical characteristics of the learning environment can have a significant impact on the experience of both pupils and teachers (Ahmadi and Saiki, 2017). Classrooms are often designed, furnished and organised for the sole purpose of providing a positive educational environment for pupils (Booth-Butterfield and Sidelinger, 2010). However, the goals of teaching a class of pupils go beyond facilitating positive academic outcomes (Pezaro, 2016). The goals include skills acquisition, socialisation and welfare (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). Classroom organisation and management is a complex problem (Gremmen *et al.*, 2016) and a significant source of stress for new teachers (Evertson and Weinstein, 2006). However, where teachers are rarely involved in the design and furnishing of the classrooms in which they work, they are often solely responsible for the organisation and management of the same space. This PhD has contributed to the body of research with a holistic study (Study 1) into how teachers perceive the organisation and management of their classroom. The results of Study 1 have provided a list of characteristics and themes that may be interpreted as a framework of how teachers are influenced and approach the organisation and management of their classroom. This framework forms a basic understanding of how teachers organise and manage their classroom and should be applied to similar research in the future. Further research should be focused on feedback from teachers to refine the existing framework and take a holistic approach to understanding the complex and chaotic environment of the working classroom.

Based on the information gathered in Chapter 2 and the results of Study 1, it would naturally follow, therefore, that organisation and management of classrooms is an important element of preservice teacher's ITE experience, and one that would prepare them for this stressful, challenging and important part of the job. As discussed in Chapter 2 the available evidence suggest that this is not the case. Classroom organisation and management is rarely a specifically taught element of ITE, and when it is taught, presentation of the material is inconsistent across the UK and Europe. Often the advice given to preservice teachers relies heavily on the personal experience and anecdotal evidence provided by their lecturers. For this reason, competence in classroom

organisation and management is viewed as something that teachers learn by experience and observation. This thesis has identified a significant research gap around how preservice teachers are taught to organise and manage their classroom. The results of this PhD have demonstrated, by the feedback provided by teachers in each study, that the ability to organise and manage their classroom is entirely reliant on their own trial and error experience. This thesis has explored the potential for VR, which provides a safe, controllable simulated environment, to be a medium which would facilitate learning about the organisation and management of classrooms.

Modern VR is the current development in a long history of attempts to create simulated environments for experience, entertainment and learning (Jerard, 2016). Since 2016, mobile technology, optical tracking and modern computer graphics has been applied to the creation of simulated environments. The term VR now sits under the umbrella term XR, which also includes AR and MR (Arm Blueprint, 2022). VR has been applied to teaching and learning within several disciplines (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). This PhD has demonstrated that both 360° videos and VR have potential for learning and teaching in ITE. 360° videos are, according to the results of Study 2, an accessible immersive option that allow developers with limited or no programming knowledge to faithfully recreate real-world environments. 360° videos are, therefore, an accessible option for ITE educators who wish to include immersive technology as an element of an existing curriculum. This implies that 360° videos are a suitable subject for further research particularly for their potential inclusion into ITE. This PhD has also provided best practice guidance on the creation of 360° videos and VR experiences for the purposes of teaching and learning. The results of this PhD provide basic guidance and understanding of the best approach to using 360° videos and VR experiences to teach the organisation and management of classrooms. These should be considered and developed by future researchers.

The most important question that this PhD addresses is, *can VR be used in ITE to provide an effective means of teaching classroom organisation and management*. The answer to that question is strongly yes, but with some qualifications. This PhD demonstrated that VR provides a medium for discussion and reflection. However, this represents the first step in the process. This PhD should form the basis of future research, carried out in cooperation with ITE-educators, which would explore the integration of VR

learning with an existing curriculum. Using the framework identified in Study 1 this curriculum should begin to address the identified gap around how preservice teachers are taught to organise and manage their classrooms. The feedback from participants, particularly in Study 4, indicated that VR has a place in ITE and could be used to improve practice in classroom organisation and management. Participants expressed the opinion that VR could be a medium for ITE students to practice learning theory before applying it to the real-world. This thesis has demonstrated that VR is a potentially valuable tool for ITE and worthy of further investigation. The implications of this research are that VR has the potential to improve how ITE students are taught to organise and manage classrooms. It is possible that VR could be used to better prepare new teachers to face one of the most stressful parts of their job (Evertson and Weinstein, 2006). Gremmen *et al.* (2016) identified the organisation and management of classrooms as the biggest single cause of new teachers' burnout. The results of this PhD suggest that VR has the potential to make teacher education better by providing a medium for exploration and reflection, which would allow preservice teachers to better understand the complexities of classroom organisation and management before entering real-world practice. In addition, repeated exploration and reflection using VR classrooms has the potential to better link the physical aspects of classroom organisation and management with different pedagogies and learning theories for working teachers. Seen in the context of other research, for example Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b) and Stavroulia *et al.* (2019), this PhD is part of a growing body of work which shows that simulated environments can be positively used in teacher education. However, this research remains in the early stages and the overall benefits of VR learning within ITE are still emerging. Alongside the work of Stavroulia *et al.* (2018a), Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019a), Kvisgaard *et al.* (2019) and others, this PhD has provided an understanding of the best practice for creating VR environments for ITE and the potential for using VR to teach classroom organisation and management. Several studies have suggested that learning in VR is at best no more effective than other traditional forms of instruction (Eldred-Evans *et al.*, 2013). Also, the ability of VR to generate an emotional or empathic response, as demonstrated by Stavroulia *et al.*, (2019), has ethical implications which are still debated (Raz, 2022). Further research is clearly required, and this PhD has identified several avenues which future research could productively take.

This PhD has demonstrated that VR has the potential for teaching socially complex skills that involve participants exploring and interacting with their environment. Given VR's ability to provide repeated safe access to complex physical environment, this PhD has demonstrated that a suitable VR experience could provide additional effective training to preservice teachers in the field of classroom organisation and management. This would begin to address an existing research gap and better prepare preservice teachers for real-world practice. This PhD has undertaken the first stage of work to develop and critically assess this idea.

10.3. Strengths and Limitations

10.3.1. Strengths

This PhD has several strengths that have contributed to the success and the significance of the results. The research took a pragmatic multi-methods approach incorporating a sequential exploratory research design (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). This allowed the research to be adapted to the results of every study and to the changing social and technological conditions in the wider world. The ADDIE design framework (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019; Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2019b) was used to provide an overall structure to this PhD. This structured process allowed the researcher to focus on the goals appropriate to each stage. The ADDIE design framework also facilitated the iterative input of stakeholders, which improved the design of each of the four studies and validated the interpretation of the results at each stage. To improve the validity, relevance and fidelity of this research, a participatory approach to design was taken by involving stakeholders wherever possible. In addition, the multi-methods approach allowed flexibility in the chosen measures and the approaches to each study design. It also allowed triangulation of the results in Study 4, which further validated the researcher's interpretation of the data. A broad range of methods were used including qualitative analysis, systematic review and content analysis. This allowed the accumulation of a variety of data types with each study being informed by those which preceded it.

This PhD has explored an important area of technological development. VR, along with other related XR technologies, has the potential to change how we approach teaching and learning. This PhD has applied VR to an area of teacher education not adequately supported by traditional teaching methods. Indeed, this PhD has

demonstrated that VR may be uniquely suited to fill a gap in ITE and provide new teachers with an opportunity to practice and discuss classroom organisation and management. By exploring the use of an emerging technology, it has been possible to investigate innovative approaches to teacher education. By providing details of the design choices made along with best practice guidelines this PhD forms a firm basis for future research in this area.

10.3.2. Limitations

This PhD has several limitations to address. They primarily relate to: (i) the impact of the COVID-19 lockdown; (ii) the context of rapidly changing technology; and (iii) limitations of sample size and generalisability. These are outlined in turn below.

10.3.2.1. The impact of COVID-19

This PhD was significantly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. The nationwide lockdown started and continued throughout the key data collection timeline of the PhD. The studies had originally been designed based on having access to working classrooms. This would have built on the work of Barratt *et al.* (2015), who took a holistic approach to exploring the physical learning environment. Immediately prior to the first lockdown, in March 2020, the planned scope of this PhD included two key studies. The first of these studies had been fully designed and approved by the UWS ethics committee. The proposed method was to interview teachers in their classroom and support this data collection with photography and filming using a 360° camera. The second of these studies would have used the information gained in the first, particularly the photographs and 360° video, to create VR simulations of the classrooms. ITE students would view these simulations on Head Mounted Displays (HMDs). This intended path would have had the advantage that the design of the simulated classrooms was supported by direct reference to real physical environments. In addition, it would have been possible to compare participants' reactions to VR environments, 360° videos and photographs all representing the same classrooms. This alternative structure could have provided deeper understanding of how teachers organise and manage their classrooms by interviewing them on location and within the context of their own classroom.

Redesigning this research to accommodate the lack of access to schools took a significant amount of time. This delay was exacerbated by the lack of available guidance on carrying out any study or work that involved the use of HMDs or VR headsets. UWS

recognised early that HMDs could be a risk/hazard item with regards to the spread of COVID-19. The reasons for this were believed to be that repeated sharing of headsets between participants could provide a medium for the transmission of COVID-19; this is particularly the case because repeated cleaning with anti-bacterial wipes is impractical because it can damage the lenses and make the equipment unusable. It was likely, therefore, that use of VR in an experimental setting would be prohibited on ethical grounds if protocols could not be agreed to ensure participant safety. It took more than a year from the first lockdown before protocols were agreed that would permit the ethical use of VR equipment. By the time protocols were in place to manage the risk of COVID-19 transmission this PhD had been redesigned to accommodate the lack of access to schools. Direct access to working classrooms would have been preferable in providing a direct comparison between the real-world and the simulated reality. In addition, it would have provided additional insight into how teachers organise and manage their classrooms by referencing specific examples. However, significant elements of these proposed studies are still present in the final form of this PhD.

The supplementary 'micro-study' described in Chapter 8, where participants drew and described a familiar classroom, allowed this project to continue to use the approach of participatory design while COVID-19 restrictions limited access to teachers and their working environment. This allowed the development of the simulated classrooms to draw on experience of genuine working classrooms. This supplementary study had originally been designed to be carried out remotely via Zoom or other video conferencing platform. In practice, by the time data collection was being carried out, the restrictions had lifted so that interviews could be conducted in person (access to schools remained restricted). The section of Chapter 8 that describes reorganising the interview data from Study 1, provides the grounding for the similarities and differences between each of the three simulated classrooms. This source of data was a substitute for the data that had originally been planned by interviewing teachers in their own working classrooms. Direct comparison to a real-world setting, supported by photographs and videos, would have allowed for a more thorough assessment and would have included media other than VR. However, the method used allowed the participants to play a significant role in determining the key elements that would be represented in each simulated classroom. This maintained the approach of participatory design while respecting the COVID-19 restrictions.

10.3.2.2. Research using Rapidly Developing Technology

As mentioned in Chapter 3 this research took place in the context of rapid advances in XR technology. The VR consumer technology that was considered cutting edge at the start of this doctoral research, for example the Oculus Rift 2, was out of date and no longer in production before this research was complete. It is challenging to carry out research using immersing technology without running the risk that the technology will be surpassed in the course of the work. VR has become more accessible over the course of this work. The Unity3D game engine, for example, has been through several versions since the development of the simulated classrooms presented here. These new versions have added additional accessibility and user-friendly components to assist in the development of interactive and immersive VR environments. Technology has certainly improved since the start of this PhD. Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have suggested the potential for creating 3D environments by natural language AI interfaces instead of complex and specialist programming (Gamefromscratch, 2023). Being aware of the pace of advancing technology, every effort was made to set this research in context by accurately describing the media, hardware and software being used or examined at each stage. In addition, every effort was made, where possible, to relate the results to the design, development, implementation and assessment of XR technology in general. Future research will use more advanced development software and more advanced XR hardware, however, many of the conclusions drawn relating to the design, presentation and use of immersive systems are generalisable to the wider world of XR.

10.3.2.3. Limitations of sample size and generalisability

A common problem to many research projects is the potential limitations in ecological validity resulting from a small sample size. This project drew participants from within the teaching profession in Scotland. However, a great variety of schools and approaches to learning exist throughout the world. Effort was made to draw from international literature, predominantly American and European, but for the most part data was collected from sources within the UK and participants from Scotland. Anecdotal evidence provided by participants during interviews suggested that the approach to teaching and to classroom organisation and management changed significantly between countries. As does the access to emerging technology. The view of teaching and of classroom organisation and management upon which this PhD is based is, therefore, a

predominantly white, western European perspective. Further research would be required to be able to confidently apply these results to the global community of teachers who may face similar problems but who must consider additional variables that have not formed part of this research. The results of this research should be looked upon as a first step in the development and assessment of VR as a tool for learning classroom organisation and management.

The most noticeable area where a larger sample size would have been beneficial to the outcome of this research is in the content analysis performed as part of Study 4. A sufficiently large sample size had the potential to yield statistically significant results, representative of a larger group within the teaching profession. There are several reasons why a larger number of participants was not used for this project. Larger sample size means a larger volume of data and increased problems of data management. In the design stages for each study the number of participants was planned to be a sufficient number to achieve meaningful results. This was balanced in each case with the need to limit the volume of data to an amount manageable within the available timescale. In the latter stages of this doctoral research, when the risk of COVID-19 transmission was a factor, the number of participants was limited with this in mind. Participants had to be showing no outward symptoms, have a negative lateral-flow test and be able to meet in a space which limited the risk of transmission. In addition, a sufficient gap was left between participants to prevent transmission via the headset thereby preventing engaging with multiple participants in one session. In each study the number of participants was sufficient to achieve the research aims and to address the research question. However, future studies based on this research may benefit from drawing from a larger group of participants.

10.4. Future Research

There are several possible avenues for future research that could build on the work described here. Improvements in VR technology, and the increased usability and accessibility of development tools, means that more complex VR experiences are possible without the need for high level programming skills. As the accessibility of VR increases it is possible for the non-expert VR developer to add additional functionality and interactivity to the VR experience. Expanding the interactivity of the VR experience would allow more creative choices from the participants and potentially create a greater sense

of presence. Such a study should be based around the three elements of a VR experience – 360° environment, immersion and interaction. For example, participants could be placed at the centre of an empty classroom. They could then be given the opportunity to populate the classroom with furniture and equipment according to given criteria. One suggestion, provided by participants while drawing and describing their classrooms (Chapter 8), was that participants be asked to create their ideal classroom. Based on the multitude of influences that can affect the teacher's approach to classrooms organisation and management, instructions could be provided along the lines of, "arrange this classroom space to suit a primary five class of twenty-four pupils who are about to undertake a group assignment." This type of study could provide insight into the decision-making process undertaken by teachers when given a relatively free hand. It would also provide an opportunity for discussion between participants as they reviewed each other's choices. For example, one participant could arrange the classroom while another reviews it. This functionality, although available at the start of this PhD, is now much more accessible. The success of Study 4 in demonstrating that VR provides a useful platform for discussion and learning, means that a project involving this additional functionality has the potential to yield very interesting results.

Building on the idea of modifying the VR experience, several other potential avenues of research are possible while still focusing on classroom organisation and management for ITE. One possibility is to create a larger or more detailed or more specialist simulated environment and allow participants greater time and freedom to explore and comment on the space. Study 4 of this PhD focused on classrooms that were as generalisable as possible and avoided specialist areas or subjects. In addition, the size and complexity of the classrooms was limited, as was the time allowed for participants to spend in the VR experience. The reason for this was to limit the potential effects of nausea, cybersickness and other adverse effects from spending unaccustomed long periods in VR. The time allotted for participants in Study 4 seemed to be the ideal balance between allowing participants time to explore and limiting the negative effects of VR use. A longer study, which involved more specialist or detailed environment, could result in additional valuable insight from participants but would have to manage the negative effects.

Several participants who contributed to this PhD mentioned the idea of simulated students forming a part of the VR experience. However, opinions of participants were split between those who thought that the inclusion of simulated students would enhance the experience and those who felt that the inclusion would lack fidelity, mentioning the “uncanny valley” problem. Including simulated students in the VR experience would add the ability to examine social interactions and social behaviour in some future study. This is similar to the work of Stavroulia *et al.* (2016b) and Stavroulia and Lanitis (2019b). This PhD was concerned with how teachers organised and managed the physical environment of the classroom. However, as Study 1 demonstrated, social interaction with the pupils is an important part of that process. Behaviour management, communication and the relationship between pupils and teachers are key elements to how classrooms are organised and managed. The additions of simulated pupils would perhaps allow future researchers to explore this topic.

The simulated classrooms in this study used small changes in the environmental criteria to differentiate between the different classrooms and suggest different pedagogical approaches. One of the strengths of using VR as a tool for teaching and learning is that the instructor/researcher can have extensive control over the environment which the user experiences. VR allows the instructor/researcher to change certain environmental criteria (colour, lighting, floor area, ceiling height, sound levels, time of day) by measurable amounts in environments which can in all other ways remain consistent. This is something which would be near impossible and certainly impractical in a real-world setting. The effects of these criteria could be measured in participants’ responses to the simulated environment or, in line with the study described above, participants could be given control over the environmental setting and allowed to create their ideal environment. In this PhD, this idea has been explored only at the most basic level but the results suggest that this research idea could be taken much further.

Study 4 also allowed a comparison between participants at different levels of experience. There is a great deal of scope in future research for examining the behaviour of participants while using the VR experience. Additional technology such as motion capture, or a video record, for example Howie (2022), could be used to record and analyse participants’ movements in VR. A video record of their visual experience or eye tracking, for example Çağlar and Şimşek (2018), could be used to record where participants are

focusing their attention. In this way, it would be possible to compare the behaviour of participants with different levels of teaching experience as they explore a simulated classrooms environment. In addition, it would be possible to track and monitor changes in behaviour as participants gain experience using the VR equipment. Does the participant's behaviour change over time while using the VR equipment? Does the participant's approach to organising and managing the classroom change with repeated use of the VR experience? By recording the behaviour of participants in this way it might be possible to assess the real-world impact of learning classroom organisation and management using a VR experience.

Finally, future research could include the research approach that this PhD was unable to take due to COVID-19 restrictions. This would include building VR simulated environments based directly on working classrooms. This approach would allow comparison between participants reactions to the virtual classroom and the data provided by the teacher working in the real-world classrooms. This approach would also include recording in real-world classrooms using 360° videos and photography. A comparison between participants' responses to the 360° videos and the simulated VR environments would then be possible. Although VR is becoming more user-friendly 360° videos remain the most accessible way of creating a simulation of a real-world environment. The studies proposed here are the next logical step in assessing the viability of VR as a tool for teaching and learning in ITE. This PhD has demonstrated that additional research of this kind would be valuable and likely to yield interesting results. The results of this PhD should also form a best practice guidance as to how to set up VR research projects in the future.

Chapter 11. Conclusions

The aim of this PhD was to investigate the potential for using virtual reality (VR) as a tool for teaching and learning in initial Teacher Education (ITE). It specifically explored the potential use of VR and 360° video in ITE for the organisation and management of classrooms. An examination of current literature showed that classroom organisation and management played an important role in the learning experience of pupils. Classroom organisation and management was a complex challenge for teachers involving multiple interacting factors. Surprisingly, there was not a consistent approach to teaching the organisation and management of classrooms within ITE. Teachers typically learned by experience.

VR is an immersing technology which, since 2016, has been applied to teaching and learning in a diverse range of fields. VR has been successfully used to teach skills in medicine, engineering and dentistry. More recently applications of VR have demonstrated the potential for VR to be applied to the teaching of affective skills. Recent studies have shown that VR can be used to teach communication skills and provoke emotional responses. Some of these applications have been in the field of teacher education. The aim of this PhD was to assess the potential for applying VR to teaching the organisation and management of classrooms in ITE.

Study 1 explored how teachers managed and organised their classrooms. Insight from participants highlighted a complex and constantly evolving task that presented a unique combination of challenges in each classroom. Findings also provided a framework of ideas to illustrate how teachers approach the task. Study 2 investigated the potential for using 360° videos as a medium for teaching and learning. 360° videos were demonstrated to be a flexible and accessible medium but one that lacked the interactivity of full VR. Study 3 was a systematic review exploring the potential for using VR for teaching and learning in socially complex professional environments, such as classrooms. The results of nine included studies demonstrated that VR has potential in this area but that the research is in the early stages and further similar applications should be investigated. Study 4 evaluated the responses of 16 teachers who engaged with three different simulated VR classrooms. Study 4 found that VR could provide a medium for exploration,

reflection and discussion by teachers at various stages of professional development. Participant feedback identified VR as a flexible and controllable medium that may allow ITE students to bridge the gap between learning theory and real classrooms by practicing in a virtual environment.

This PhD has demonstrated the potential for using VR for teaching and learning in ITE. Specifically for teaching the organisation and management of classrooms. Its potential short to long-term impacts include directing future research on the topic, influencing the delivery of education within future ITE programmes and potentially impacting the experiences of new teachers as they embark on their teaching careers. This PhD has provided guidance for future research on this topic. However, this is only the first step in the process. Future research should investigate the long-term effects of teaching and learning in VR and if learned skills transfer to real-world classrooms. In future research, particular attention should be paid to the most effective pedagogical approach when creating VR learning experiences.

References

Acer, D., Gozen, G., Firat, Z. S., Kefeli, H. and Aslan, B. (2016) 'Effects of a redesigned classroom on play behaviour among preschool children', *Early Child Development and Care*, 186(12), pp. 1907-1925.

Adefila, A., Graham, S. and Clouder, L. (2016) 'myShoes—the future of experiential dementia training?', *The Journal of Mental Health Training, Education and Practice*, 11, pp. 91-101.

Ahir, K., Govani, K., Gajera, R. and Shah, M. (2019) 'Application on virtual reality for enhanced education learning, military training and sports', *Augmented Human Research*, 5(1), pp. 7.

Ahmadi, R. and Saiki, D. (2017) 'Strategies to assess studio spaces designed to enhance student learning', *Journal of Family & Consumer Sciences*, 109(1), pp. 57-61.

Allcoat, D. and von Mühlhelen, A. (2018) 'Learning in virtual reality: Effects on performance, emotion and engagement', *Research in Learning Technology*, 26, pp. 1-13.

Allen, W. C. (2006) 'Overview and evolution of the ADDIE training system', *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 8(4), pp. 430-441.

Allott, K. and Waugh, D. (2016) 'Creating the climate for effective communication', *Language and Communication in Primary Schools*. London: SAGE Publications.

Amini, H., Gregory, M. E., Abrams, M. A., Luna, J., Roland, M., Sova, L. N., Bean, C., Huang, Y., Pfeil, S. A., Townsend, J. and Lin, E. D. (2021) 'Feasibility and usability study of a pilot immersive virtual reality-based empathy training for dental providers', *Journal of Dental Education*, 85(6), pp. 856-865.

Arayici, Y. (2007) 'An approach for real world data modelling with the 3D terrestrial laser scanner for built environment', *Automation in Construction*, 16(6), pp. 816-829.

References

Arm Blueprint (2022) *XR, AR, VR, MR: What's the difference in reality?* Available at: <https://www.arm.com/blogs/blueprint/xr-ar-vr-mr-difference> (Accessed: 11/04/2022).

Aromataris, E. and Munn, Z. (2020) *JBI manual for evidence synthesis*. Available at: <https://synthesismanual.jbi.global>. .

Aubrey, C. and Ward, K. (2013) 'Early years practitioners' views on early personal, social and emotional development', *Emotional and Behavioural Difficulties*, 18, pp. 435–447.

Baines, E., Rubie-Davies, C. and Blatchford, P. (2009) 'Improving pupil group work interaction and dialogue in primary classrooms: results from a year-long intervention study', *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 39(1), pp. 95-117.

Barrett, P., Barrett, L. and Zhang, Y. (2016) 'Teachers' views of their primary school classrooms', *Intelligent Buildings International*, 8(3), pp. 176-191.

Barrett, P., Davies, F., Zhang, Y. and Barrett, L. (2015) 'The impact of classroom design on pupils' learning: Final results of a holistic, multi-level analysis', *Building and Environment*, 89, pp. 118-133.

Barrett, P., Zhang, Y., Moffat, J. and Kobbacy, K. (2013) 'A holistic, multi-level analysis identifying the impact of classroom design on pupils' learning', *Building and Environment*, 59, pp. 678-689.

Bedford Borough Council. (2019) *The Newly Qualified Teacher's Handbook*. Available at: https://bbcdevwebfiles.blob.core.windows.net/webfiles/Education%20and%20Learning/Teachers%20and%20Education%20Staff/CS022_17_NQT-Handbook_A4-%2019-20.pdf.

Bertrand, P., Guegan, J., Robieux, L., McCall, C. A. and Zenasni, F. (2018) 'Learning empathy through virtual reality: multiple strategies for training empathy-related abilities using body ownership illusions in embodied virtual reality', *Front Robot AI*, 5, pp. 26.

Bevan, C., Green, D. P., Farmer, H., Rose, M., Cater, K., Fraser, D. S. and Brown, H. 'Behind the curtain of the "ultimate empathy machine": On the composition of virtual reality nonfiction experiences'. *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1-12.

References

Blatchford, P., Kutnick, P., Baines, E. and Galton, M. (2003) 'Toward a social pedagogy of classroom group work', *International Journal of Educational Research*, 39(1), pp. 153-172.

Blewitt, C., O'Connor, A., Morris, H., Nolan, A., Mousa, A., Green, R., Ifanti, A., Jackson, K. and Skouteris, H. (2021) "It's embedded in what we do for every child": A qualitative exploration of early childhood educators' perspectives on supporting children's social and emotional learning', *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 18(4).

Bolinski, F., Etzelmüller, A., De Witte, N. A. J., van Beurden, C., Debard, G., Bonroy, B., Cuijpers, P., Riper, H. and Kleiboer, A. (2021) 'Physiological and self-reported arousal in virtual reality versus face-to-face emotional activation and cognitive restructuring in university students: A crossover experimental study using wearable monitoring', *Behavioural Research and Therapy*, 142, pp. 103877.

Booth-Butterfield, M. and Sidelinger, R. (2010) 'Co-constructing student involvement: An examination of teacher confirmation and student-to-student connectedness in the college classroom', *Communication Education*, 59(2), pp. 165-184.

Bosch, K. (2006) *Planning classroom management: A five-step process to creating a positive learning environment*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.

Bowers, B. (2010) 'Disrupting determinism: Classroom design as a technology', *The CEA Forum*(1), pp. 108-117.

Brackness Forest Council. (2020) *2020-2021 Handbook for newly qualified teachers in Bracknell Forest and surrounding areas*. Available at: <https://schools.bracknell-forest.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/bfc-nqt-handbook-2020-to-2021.pdf>.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77-101.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2013) *Successful qualitative research: A practical guide for beginners*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

References

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2014) 'What can "thematic analysis" offer health and wellbeing researchers?', *International Journal of Qualitative Studies of Health and Well-being*, 9, pp. 261-52.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2023) 'Toward good practice in thematic analysis: Avoiding common problems and becoming a knowing researcher', *International Journal of Transgender Health*, 24(1), pp. 1-6.

Braun, V., Clarke, V. and Rance, N. (2014) 'How to use thematic analysis with interview data (process research)', in Vossler, A. and Moller, N. (eds.) *The counselling & psychotherapy research handbook*. London: Sage.

Bryman, A. (2016) *Social research methods*. 5th edn. London: Oxford University Press.

Busetto, L., Wick, W. and Gumbinger, C. (2020) 'How to use and assess qualitative research methods', *Neurology Research Practice* 2(14).

Byers, T., Hartnell-Young, E. and Imms, W. (2018) 'Empirical evaluation of different classroom spaces on students' perceptions of the use and effectiveness of 1-to-1 technology', *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(1), pp. 153-164.

Caena, F. (2014) *Initial teacher education in Europe: an overview of policy issues* Brussels. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/education/policy/strategicframework/expert-groups/documents/initial-teacher-education_en.pdf.

Çağlar, C. and Şimşek, İ. (2018) 'Examination of The Virtual Reality Application For Foreign Language Education By Eye Tracking Method. (English)', *Yabancı Dil Öğrenimi için Sanal Gerçeklik Ortamlarının Göz İzleme Tekniği ile İncelenmesi. (Turkish)*, pp. 122-127.

Cameron, J., Gould, G. and Ma, A. (2021) *360 Essentials: A beginner's guide to immersive video storytelling*. Toronto: Toronto University Library (via Pressbooks).

Candela, L., Dalley, K. and Benzel-Lindley, J. (2006) 'A case for learning-centered curricula', *Journal of Nursing Education*, 45(2), pp. 59-66.

References

Cardellino, P., Araneda, C. and García Alvarado, R. (2017) 'Classroom environments: an experiential analysis of the pupil–teacher visual interaction in Uruguay', *Learning Environments Research*, 20(3), pp. 417-431.

Carr, K. (2021) *Hybrid learning and the social and emotional learning environment of primary-age students*. Ed.D., College of Saint Elizabeth.

Caruana, E., Roman, M., Hernández-Sánchez, J. and Solli, P. (2015) 'Longitudinal studies', *Journal of Thoracic Disease*, 7(11), pp. E537-40.

Chae, D., Kim, J., Kim, K., Ryu, J., Asami, K. and Doorenbos, A. Z. (2023) 'An immersive virtual reality simulation for cross-cultural communication skills: development and feasibility', *Clinical Simulation in Nursing*, 77, pp. 13-22.

Chisiu, C. M. (2015) 'The influence of classroom design on training primary school students through hidden curriculum', *Educatia Plus*, 12(1), pp. 135-142.

Chiu, H. Y., Kang, Y. N., Wang, W. L., Chen, C. C., Hsu, W., Tseng, M. F. and Wei, P. L. (2019) 'The role of active engagement of peer observation in the acquisition of surgical skills in virtual reality tasks for novices', *Journal of Surgical Education*, 76(6), pp. 1655-1662.

Cicchelli, T. (1983) 'Forms and functions of instruction patterns: Direct and nondirect', *Instructional Science*, 12, pp. 343-353.

Clarivate. (2021) *Endnote referencing software (Version 20.2.1)*. Available at: <https://endnote.com/?language=en>.

Clifton, J. and Palmisano, S. (2019) 'Effects of steering locomotion and teleporting on cybersickness and presence in HMD-based virtual reality', *Virtual Reality: research, development and applications*, Online First, pp. 1-16.

Cochrane, T. (2016) 'Mobile VR in education: From the fringe to the mainstream', *International Journal of Mobile and Blended Learning*, 8(4).

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2018) *Research methods in education*. 8th edn. London: Routledge Taylor Francis Group.

References

Cook, D. A. (2005) 'The research we still are not doing: An agenda for the study of computer-based learning', *Academic Medicine*, 80(6), pp. 541-548.

Cooke, A., Smith, D. and Booth, A. (2012) 'Beyond PICO: the SPIDER tool for qualitative evidence synthesis', *Qualitative health research*, 22(10), pp. 1435-1443.

Coolican, H. (2009) *Research methods and statistics in psychology*. 5th edn. London: Hodder Education.

Costiuc, N. (2021) *What is fidelity in simulation?* Healthy Simulation. Available at: <https://www.healthysimulation.com/30181/what-is-fidelity-in-simulation/>.

Cremin, T. and Arthur, J. (2014) *Learning to teach in the primary school*. 3rd edn. London: Routledge.

Creswell, J. and Plano Clark, V. (2018) *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2022) *CASP checklists*. Available at: www.casp-uk.net.

Cucoş, C. (2001) 'History of ideas and doctrines teaching pedagogy fundamental', *Polirom Iasi*, pp. 48.

Davey, L., Clarke, V. and Jenkinson, E. (2019) 'Living with alopecia areata: an online qualitative survey study', *British Journal of Dermatology*, 180(1377-1389).

Dekker, A., Wenzlaff, F., Biedermann, S. V., Briken, P. and Fuss, J. (2021) 'VR Porn as "Empathy Machine"? Perception of self and others in virtual reality pornography', *Journal of Sex Research*, 58(3), pp. 273-278.

DeWitt, D., Chan, S. F. and Loban, R. (2022) 'Virtual reality for developing intercultural communication competence in Mandarin as a Foreign language', *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 70(2), pp. 615-638.

Dieker, L. A., Rodriguez, J. A., Lignugaris/Kraft, B., Hynes, M. C. and Hughes, C. E. (2013) 'The potential of simulated environments in teacher education', *Teacher Education and*

References

Special Education: The Journal of the Teacher Education Division of the Council for Exceptional Children, 37(1), pp. 21-33.

Dillon, R. (2018) 'Room for Improvement: Becoming more intentional about classroom design can help teachers manage behavior, build community, and improve learning', *Educational Leadership*, 76(1), pp. 40-45.

Dovey, K. and Fisher, K. (2014) 'Designing for adaptation: the school as socio-spatial assemblage', *Journal of Architecture*, 19(1), pp. 43-63.

Dozio, N., Marcolin, F., Scurati, G. W., Ulrich, L., Nonis, F., Vezzetti, E., Marsocci, G., La Rosa, A. and Ferrise, F. (2022) 'A design methodology for affective Virtual Reality', *International Journal of Human Computer Studies*, 162.

Dubovi, I., Levy, S. T. and Dagan, E. (2017) 'Now I know how! The learning process of medication administration among nursing students with non-immersive desktop virtual reality simulation', *Computers & Education*, 113, pp. 16-27.

Ealing Borough Council. (2014) *Induction Handbook for Newly Qualified Teachers*. Available at: https://www.egfl.org.uk/sites/default/files/School_effectiveness/NQT/Induction%20Handbook%20for%20NQTs.pdf

Eccles, D. and Arsal, G. (2017) 'The think aloud method: what is it and how do I use it?', *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, 9(4), pp. 514-531.

Eldred-Evans, D., Grange, P., Cheang, A., Yamamoto, H., Ayis, S., Mulla, M., Immenroth, M., Sharma, D. and Reedy, G. (2013) 'Using the mind as a simulator: a randomized controlled trial of mental training', *Journal of Surgical Education*, 70(4), pp. 544-51.

Ericsson, K. (2006) 'Protocol analysis and expert thought: Concurrent verbalizations of thinking during experts' performance on representative tasks', in Ericsson, K., Charness, N., Feltovich, P. and Hoffman, R. (eds.) *The Cambridge Handbook of Expertise and Expert Performance*. London: Cambridge University Press.

References

Ericsson, K. and Simon, H. (1993) *Protocol analysis: Verbal reports as data (rev. ed.)*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.

Evertson, C. and Weinstein, C. (2006) *Handbook of classroom management: Research, practice, and contemporary issues*. Washington: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.

Fernandes, L. M. A., Matos, G. C., Azevedo, D., Nunes, R. R., Paredes, H., Morgado, L. and et al (2016) 'Exploring educational immersive videogames: An empirical study with a 3D multimodal interaction prototype', *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 35(11), pp. 907–918.

Fetters, M., Curry, L. and Creswell, J. (2013) 'Achieving integration in mixed methods designs-principles and practices', *Health Services Research*, 48(6), pp. 2134-56.

Fletcher, C., Ritchie, J., Lim, T. and Sung, R. (2013) 'The development of an integrated haptic VR machining environment for the automatic generation of process plans', *Computers in Industry*, 64(8), pp. 1045-1060.

Gaines, K. and Curry, Z. D. (2011) 'The inclusive classroom: The effects of color on learning and behavior', *Journal of Family & Consumer Sciences*.

Gale, N. K., Heath, G., Cameron, E., Rashid, S. and Redwood, S. (2013) 'Using the framework method for the analysis of qualitative data in multi-disciplinary health research', *BMC Medical Research and Methodology*, 13, pp. 117.

Gall, D., Roth, D., Stauffert, J. P., Zarges, J. and Latoschik, M. E. (2021) 'Embodiment in virtual reality intensifies emotional responses to virtual stimuli', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, pp. 674179.

Gamefromscratch (2023) *ChatGPT in Unity is insane!* Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1WnYAYbytVU>.

Gest, S. D. and Rodkin, P. C. (2011) 'Teaching practices and elementary classroom peer ecologies', *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 32(5), pp. 288-96.

Gray, D. E. (2021) *Doing research in the real world*. 5th edn. London: Sage.

References

Gremmen, M. C., van den Berg, Y. H. M., Segers, E. and Cillessen, A. H. N. (2016) 'Considerations for classroom seating arrangements and the role of teacher characteristics and beliefs.', *Social Psychology of Education*, 19, pp. 749-774.

Grotenhoff, M. (2021) 'Telling stories with virtual reality: The empathy machine', *Interactive Storytelling for the Screen*, pp. 101-105.

Grube, K. J. (2013) 'Detrimental effects of white valued walls in classrooms', *Educational Planning*, 21(2), pp. 69-82.

Haber, J., Xu, H. and Priya, K. (2023) 'Harnessing virtual reality for management training: a longitudinal study', *Organization Management Journal*, 20(3), pp. 93-106.

Hamilton, D., McKechnie, J., Edgerton, E. and Wilson, C. (2021) 'Immersive virtual reality as a pedagogical tool in education: a systematic literature review of quantitative learning outcomes and experimental design', *J. Comput. Educ* 8, pp. 1-32.

Han, I., Shin, H. S., Ko, Y. and Shin, W. S. (2022) 'Immersive virtual reality for increasing presence and empathy', *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 38(4), pp. 1115-1126.

Hancock, D., Bray, M. and Nason, S. (2003) 'Influencing university students' achievement and motivation in a technology course', *The Journal of Educational Research*, 95(6), pp. 365-372.

Harlacher, J. (2015) 'Establishing procedures and structure', *Designing effective classroom management*. Bloomington, IN: Marzano Research Lab.

Hartley, M. D., Ludlow, B. L. and Duff, M. C. (2015) 'Second Life®: A 3D virtual immersive environment for teacher preparation courses in a distance education program', *Rural Special Education Quarterly*, 34(3).

Higgins, S., Hall, E., Wall, K., Woolner, P. and CMcCaughey, C. (2005) *The impact of school environments: A literature review*. Callaghan, NSW: University of Newcastle [Online] Available at: <http://www.cfbt.com/PDF/91085.pdf> (Accessed: 2nd February 2021).

References

Hill, T. and du Preez, H. (2021) 'A longitudinal study of students' perceptions of immersive virtual reality teaching interventions', *7th International Conference of the Immersive Learning Research Network (iLRN)*, pp. 1-7.

Hollingsworth, H. L. and Winter, M. K. (2013) 'Teacher beliefs and practices relating to development in preschool: Importance placed on social–emotional behaviours and skills', *Early Child Development and Care*, 183, pp. 1758–1781.

Howie, S. R. (2022) *A framework for authentic assessment in room-scale virtual reality training simulations*. The University of the West of Scotland.

Huang, W., Roscoe, R. D., Craig, S. D. and Johnson-Glenberg, M. C. (2021) 'Extending the cognitive-affective theory of learning with media in virtual reality learning: a structural equation modeling approach', *Journal of Educational Computing Research*.

Huber, T., Paschold, M., Hansen, C., Lang, H. and Kneist, W. (2018) 'Artificial versus video-based immersive virtual surroundings: analysis of performance and user's preference', *Surg Innov*, 25(3), pp. 280-285.

Hughes, P. (2008) 'Establishing a safe and purposeful learning environment', *Principles of primary education*. Londo: David Fulton Publishers.

Immordino-Yang, M. and Damasio, A. (2007) 'We feel, therefore we learn: The relevance of affective and social neuroscience to education', *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 1(1), pp. 3-10.

Ingram, K. M., Espelage, D. L., Merrin, G. J., Valido, A., Heinhorst, J. and Joyce, M. (2019) 'Evaluation of a virtual reality enhanced bullying prevention curriculum pilot trial', *Journal of Adolescence*, 71, pp. 72-83.

IONOS. (2023) *Extended reality (XR): AR, VR, and MR explained and compared*. Available at: <https://www.ionos.co.uk/digitalguide/online-marketing/online-sales/extended-reality/>.

Irvine, K. (2017) *XR: VR, AR, MR—What's the difference?* Viget. Available at: [tps://www.viget.com/articles/xr-vr-ar-mr-whats-the-difference/](https://www.viget.com/articles/xr-vr-ar-mr-whats-the-difference/).

References

Ivanov, L. and Ramos, N. 'Bully': A virtual reality environment for anti-bullying education'. *Proceedings of the Thirty-Third International Florida Artificial Intelligence Research Society Conference (FLAIRS 2020)*, 312-315.

Izard, S. G., Juanes, J. A., García Peñalvo, F. J., Estella, J. M. G., Ledesma, M. J. S. and Ruisoto, P. (2018) 'Virtual reality as an educational and training tool for medicine', *Journal of Medical Systems*, 42(3), pp. 50.

Jackson, S. (2023) *3D Camera and virtual tour platform – Matterport* Available at: <https://go.matterport.com>.

Jansen, H. (2010) 'The logic of qualitative survey research and its position in the field of social research methods', *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung*, 11(2).

Jaspers, M., Steena, T., van den Bosb, C. and Geenenb, M. (2004) 'The think aloud method: a guide to user interface design', *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 73, pp. 781-95.

JBI Collaboration. (2020) *Joanna Briggs Institute Collaboration: JBI*. Available at: <https://jbi.global/about-jbi>.

Jensen, L. and Konradsen, F. (2018) 'A review of the use of virtual reality head-mounted displays in education and training', *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(4), pp. 1515-1529.

Jeon, L., Buettner, C. K. and Hur, E. (2014) 'Family and neighborhood disadvantage, home environment, and children's school readiness', *Journal of Family Psychology*, 28(5), pp. 718-727.

Jerard, J. (2016) *The VR book: Human centred design for virtual reality*. San Rafael: Morgan & Claypool.

Joda, T., Gallucci, G. O., Wismeijer, D. and Zitzmann, N. U. (2019) 'Augmented and virtual reality in dental medicine: A systematic review', *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 108, pp. 93-100.

References

Johnson, R. B., Onwuegbuzie, A. J. and Turner, L. A. (2007) 'Toward a definition of mixed methods research', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(2), pp. 112-133.

Johnston, J. and Halocha, J. (2010) 'Learning places', *Early childhood and primary education: Readings and reflections*. Maidenhead: McGraw-Hill Education.

Kaplan, A. D., Cruit, J., Endsley, M., Beers, S. M., Sawyer, B. D. and Hancock, P. A. (2020) 'The effects of virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality as training enhancement methods: A meta-analysis', *Human Factors*, 63(4), pp. 706-726.

Kaufeld, M., Bourdeinik, J., Prinz, L. M., Mundt, M. and Hecht, H. (2022) 'Emotions are associated with the genesis of visually induced motion sickness in virtual reality', *Experimental Brain Research*, 240(10), pp. 2757-2771.

Kim, J. (2020) 'VIVR: Presence of immersive interaction for visual impairment virtual reality', *IEEE Access*, 8, pp. 196151-196159.

Kim, Y.-L. and Chang, H. (2020) 'The effects of virtual reality space game on spatial sense and mathematical affective domain -focused on the sixth graders' building block activity', *School Mathematics*, 22(1), pp. 51-68.

Klein, A. S. (2008) *Creating peaceful environmental designs for the classroom*. Early Childhood News, The Professional Resource for Teachers and Parents. Available at: http://www.earlychildhoodnews.com/earlychildhood/article_view.aspx?ArticleID=390.

Kluwer, W. (2018) *Increasing fidelity and realism in simulation*. Available at: <https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en/expert-insights/increasing-fidelity-and-realism-in-simulation> (Accessed: 12/05/2022).

Knowlin, L. T., Min, H. J., Abelairas-Gomez, C., Liu, D. R. and Fijacko, N. (2023) 'Near-peer mentoring and virtual reality for adult basic life support education in high school students', *Resuscitation Plus*, 13, pp. 100356.

Ko, J., Sammons, P. and Bakkum, L. (2013) *Effective teaching: A review of research and evidence*. Sheffield: Centre for British Teachers Education Trust.

References

Koch, A., Pfandler, M., Stefan, P., Wucherer, P., Lazarovici, M., Navab, N., Stumpf, U., Schmidmaier, R., Glaser, J. and Weigl, M. (2019) 'Say, what is on your mind? Surgeons' evaluations of realism and usability of a virtual reality vertebroplasty simulator', *Surg Innov*, 26(2), pp. 234-243.

Kron, F. W., Feters, M. D., Scerbo, M. W., White, C. B., Lypson, M. L., Padilla, M. A., Gliva-McConvey, G. A., Belfore, L. A., West, T., Wallace, A. M., Guetterman, T. C., Schleicher, L. S., Kennedy, R. A., Mangrulkar, R. S., Cleary, J. F., Marsella, S. C. and Becker, D. M. (2017) 'Using a computer simulation for teaching communication skills: A blinded multisite mixed methods randomized controlled trial', *Patient Education and Counselling*, 100(4), pp. 748-759.

Kuhlthau, C., Maniotes, L. and Caspari, A. (2015) *Guided inquiry: Learning in the 21st century*. New Jersey: Rutgers University.

Kvisgaard, A., Ø Klem, S., Lund Nielsen, T., Rafferty, E., Christian Nilsson, N., Høeg, E. and Nordahl, R. 'Frames to zones: Applying mise-en-scène techniques in cinematic virtual reality'. *IEEE 5th Workshop on Everyday Virtual Reality (WEVR)*, 1-5.

Kweon, B.-S., Ellis, C. D., Lee, J. and Jacobs, K. (2017) 'The link between school environments and student academic performance', *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 23, pp. 35-43.

Kyaw, B. M., Saxena, N., Posadzki, P., Vseteckova, J., Nikolaou, C. K., George, P. P., Divakar, U., Masiello, I., Kononowicz, A. A., Zary, N. and Tudor Car, L. (2019) 'Virtual reality for health professions education: Systematic review and meta-analysis by the digital health education collaboration', *J Med Internet Res*, 21(1), pp. e12959.

Laal, M. and Laal, M. (2012) 'Collaborative learning: what is it?', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 31, pp. 491-495.

Lara, F. and Rueda, J. (2021) 'Virtual reality not for “being someone” but for “being in someone else's shoes”: Avoiding misconceptions in empathy enhancement', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12.

References

Laseinde, O. T., Adejuyigbe, S. B., Mpofo, K. and Campbell, H. M. (2015) 'Educating tomorrows engineers: reinforcing engineering concepts through virtual reality (VR) teaching aid', *2015 International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)*, pp. 1485-1489.

Lewkowicz, D. (2001) 'The concept of ecological validity: What are its limitations and is it bad to be invalid', *Infancy*, 2, pp. 437–50. .

Liaw, S. Y., Tan, J. Z., Lim, S., Zhou, W. T., Yap, J., Ratan, R., Ooi, S. L., Wong, S. J., Seah, B. and Chua, W. L. (2023) 'Artificial intelligence in virtual reality simulation for interprofessional communication training: Mixed method study', *Nurse Education Today*, 122.

Linney, J. A. and Seidman, E. (1989) 'The future of schooling', *American Psychologist*, 44(2), pp. 336-340.

Linton, K. F., Hannans, J. A., Nevins, C. M. and Linton, R. J. (2022) 'Randomized control pilot of virtual reality, empathy, knowledge, emotions, and self-efficacy among undergraduate health science students', *HETS Online Journal*, 13(1), pp. 6-31.

Lumivero. (2020) *Nvivo version 20*. Available at: <https://lumivero.com/products/nvivo/>.

MacLeod, A., Burm, S. and Mann, K. (2022) 'Constructivism: learning theories and approaches to research', *Researching Medical Education*, pp. 25-40.

Makransky, G., Lilleholt, L. and Aaby, A. (2017) 'Development and validation of the Multimodal Presence Scale for virtual reality environments: A confirmatory factor analysis and item response theory approach', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 72, pp. 276-285.

Makransky, G. and Petersen, G. B. (2021) 'the cognitive affective model of immersive learning (CAMIL): a theoretical research-based model of learning in immersive virtual reality', *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(3), pp. 937-958.

Marcolin, F., Wally Scurati, G., Ulrich, L., Nonis, F., Vezzetti, E., Dozio, N., Ferrise, F., Stork, A. and Basole, R. C. (2021) 'Affective virtual reality: how to design artificial experiences impacting human emotions', *IEEE Computer Graphics Applications*, 41(6), pp. 171-178.

References

Martin, C. S. A. (2016) 'Exploring the impact of the design of the physical classroom environment on young children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD)', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 16(4), pp. 280-298.

Martin, S. (2002) 'The classroom environment and its effects on the practice of teachers', *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 22(1), pp. 139-156.

Marunda-Piki, C. (2017) 'Rethinking Learning Space and Pedagogy in Africa', *International Educator*, 32(2), pp. 23-23.

Marx, A., Fuhrer, U. and Hartig, T. (2000) 'Effects of classroom seating arrangements on children's questionasking', *Learning Environments Research*, 2(3), pp. 249-263.

Mattimoe, R., Hayden, M., Murphy, B. and Ballantine, J. (2021) 'Approaches to analysis of qualitative research data: a reflection on the manual and technological approaches', *Accounting, Finance & Governance Review*, 27.

Mayor Silva, L. I., Caballero de la Calle, R., Cuevas-Budhart, M. A., Martin Martin, J. O., Blanco Rodriguez, J. M. and Gómez Del Pulgar García Madrid, M. (2023) 'Development of communication skills through virtual reality on nursing school students: clinical trial', *Computing Informatics in Nursing*, 41(1), pp. 24-30.

Mays, N. and Pope, C. (2000) 'Assessing quality in qualitative research', *British Medical Journal*, 320(7226), pp. 50-52.

McCorskey, J. and McVetta, R. (1978) 'Classroom seating arrangements: Instructional communication theory versus pupil preferences', *Communication Education*, 27, pp. 99-111.

McKeown, G., Spencer, C., Patterson, A., Creaney, T. and Dupré, D. 'Comparing virtual reality with computer monitors as rating environments for affective dimensions in social interactions'. *2017 Seventh International Conference on Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction (ACII)*, San Antonio, TX, USA, 464-469.

References

McKeown, S., Stringer, M. and Cairns, E. (2015) 'Classroom segregation: Where do students sit and how is this related to group relations? ', *British Educational Research Journal*, 42(1), pp. 40-55.

Mehrotra, P. (2021) *Gear VR will stop working on older Samsung devices after the Android 12 update*. Available at: <https://www.xda-developers.com/samsung-gear-vr-stop-working-android-12-update/>.

Mikropoulos, T. A. and Natsis, A. (2011) 'Educational virtual environments: A ten-year review of empirical research (1999–2009)', *Computers & Education*, 56(3), pp. 769–780.

Mikyung, H. A. and 박혜선. (2012) 'A study on the classroom design in middle school for preventing school violence', *Korean Institute of Interior Design Journal*, 21(3), pp. 163-173.

MIT Technology Review. (2021) *The metaverse has a groping problem already*. Available at: <https://www.technologyreview.com/2021/12/16/1042516/the-metaverse-has-a-groping-problem/> (Accessed: 11/04/2022).

Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J. and Altman, D. G. (2009) 'Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement', *PLoS Medicine*, 6(7), pp. e1000097.

Molka-Danielsen, J., Prasolova-Forland, E., Fominykh, M. and Lamb, K. (2019) 'Use of a collaborative virtual reality simulation for multi-professional training in emergency management communications', pp. 408-415.

Morse, J. (2015) 'Critical analysis of strategies for determining rigor in qualitative inquiry', *Qualitative Health Research*, 25(9), pp. 1212-1222.

Morse, J. and Cheek, J. (2015) 'Introducing qualitatively-driven mixed-method designs', *Qualitative Health Research*, 25(6), pp. 731-733.

Munn, Z., Moola, S., Riitano, D. and Lisy, K. (2014) 'The development of a critical appraisal tool for use in systematic reviews addressing questions of prevalence', *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 3(3), pp. 123-8.

References

Mura, C., Mattausch, O., Villanueva, A., Gobbetti, E. and Pajarola, R. (2014) 'Automatic room detection and reconstruction in cluttered indoor environments with complex room layouts', *Computers and Graphics*, 44, pp. 20-32.

Murphy, J. A., Center, K. B., Wood, D. P. and McLay, R. N. (2009) 'Relationship of cybersickness to post-traumatic stress disorder and mild traumatic brain injury in military personnel enrolled in a virtual reality graded exposure therapy treatment trial', *Cyberpsychology and Behaviour*, 12(1), pp. 111-111.

Napa, S., Moore, M. and Bardyn, T. (2019) 'Advancing cardiac surgery case planning and case review conferences using virtual reality in medical libraries: evaluation of the usability of two virtual reality apps', *JMIR Human Factors*, 6(1), pp. e12008.

National Careers Service. (2022) *Primary school teacher*: National Careers Service. Available at: <https://nationalcareers.service.gov.uk/job-profiles/primary-school-teacher>.

Nisbett, R. and Wilson, T. (1977) 'Telling more than we can know: Verbal reports on mental processes', *Psychology Reviews*, 84(3), pp. 231-259.

Njoo, M. and Jong, d. T. (1993) 'Exploratory learning with a computer simulation for control theory: learning processes and instruction support', *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 30(8), pp. 821-844.

Noble, H. and Heale, R. (2019) 'Triangulation in research', *Evidence-Based Nursing*, 22, pp. 67-68.

North Yorkshire County Council. (2017) *NQT induction and mentor tutor handbook*. Available at: [https://cyps.northyorks.gov.uk/sites/default/files/nqts/7.%20Mentor%20\(Induction%20Tutor\)%20Handbook.pdf](https://cyps.northyorks.gov.uk/sites/default/files/nqts/7.%20Mentor%20(Induction%20Tutor)%20Handbook.pdf)

Noyes, J., Booth, A., Cargo, M., Flemming, K., A., H., Harris, J., Garside, R., Hannes, K., Pantoja, T. and Thomas, J. (2022) 'Chapter 21: Qualitative evidence', in Higgins, J., Thomas, J., Chandler, J., Cumpston, M., Li, T., Page, M. and Welch, V. (eds.) *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions version 6.3*.

References

O'Connor, E. A. (2010) 'Instructional and design elements that support effective use of virtual worlds: what graduate student work reveals about Second Life', *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 38(2), pp. 213-234.

Oates, J., Carpenter, D., Fisher, M., Goodson, S., Hannah, B. K., R. Prutton, K., Reeves, D. and Wainright, T. (2021) *BPS code of human research ethics*. Available at: <https://explore.bps.org.uk/content/report-guideline/bpsrep.2021.inf180CTLG> - [].

Oculus. (2022) *Oculus compare headsets: VR systems compared*. Available at: https://www.oculus.com/compare/?locale=en_GB (Accessed: 11/04/2022).

Oliva, D., Somerkoski, B., Tarkkanen, K., Lehto, A. and Luimula, M. (2019) 'Virtual reality as a communication tool for fire safety: Experiences from the VirPa project', *GamiFIN*, 2359, pp. 241-252.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2013) *Innovative learning environments*, Paris.

Östlund, U., Kidd, L., Wengström, Y. and Rowa-Deward, N. (2011) 'Combining qualitative and quantitative research within mixed method research designs: A methodological review', *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 48(3), pp. 369-383.

Ott, M. and Freina, L. (2015) 'A literature review on immersive virtual reality in education: state of the art and perspectives', *eLearning and software for education (eLSE)*.

Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., McGuinness, L. A., Stewart, L. A., Thomas, J., Tricco, A. C., Welch, V. A., Whiting, P. and Moher, D. (2021) 'The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews', *Systematic Reviews*, 10(1), pp. 89.

Papadopoulou, K., Tsermidou, L., Dimitrakaki, C., Agapidaki, E., Oikonomidou, D., Petanidou, D., Tountas, Y. and Giannakopoulos, G. (2014) 'A qualitative study of early

References

childhood educators' beliefs and practices regarding children's socioemotional development', *Early Child Development and Care*, 184, pp. 1843–1860.

Parker, M. (2004) 'Review of the psychology of teaching and learning in the primary school', *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 22(2), pp. 313-314.

Parong, J. and Mayer, R. E. (2021) 'Cognitive and affective processes for learning science in immersive virtual reality', *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 37(1), pp. 226-241.

Parry, C., Pires, M. and Sparkes-Guber, H. (2007) 'Action Review Cycle and the After Action Review meeting', in Holman, D.a.C. (ed.) *The Change Handbook: The Definitive Resource on Today's Best Methods for Engaging Whole Systems*: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

Patole, S. (2021) *Principles and Practice of Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis*. London: Springer.

Pedaste, M., Mäeots, M., Siiman, L. A., de Jong, T., van Riesen, S. A. N., Kamp, E. T., Manoli, C. C., Zacharia, Z. C. and Tsourlidaki, E. (2015) 'Phases of inquiry-based learning: Definitions and the inquiry cycle', *Educational Research Review*, 14, pp. 47-61.

Pedro, N. (2017) 'Redesigning learning spaces: What do teachers want for future classrooms?', *International Conference Educational Technologies*, pp. ED579282.

Peterson, C. (2003) 'Bringing ADDIE to life: Instructional design at its best', *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, 12(3), pp. 227-241.

Peyser, A., Gerard, F.-M. and Roegiers, X. (2006) 'Implementing a pedagogy of integration: some thoughts based on a textbook elaboration experience in Vietnam', *Planning and Changing*, 37(1-2), pp. 37-55.

Pezaro, C. (2016) 'The role of a teacher and the purpose of education'. Available at: <https://npjscilearncommunity.nature.com/posts/13089-the-role-of-a-teacher-and-the-purpose-of-education>.

References

Pöhlmann, K. M. T., Föcker, J., Dickinson, P., Parke, A. and O'Hare, L. (2022) 'The relationship between vection, cybersickness and head movements elicited by illusory motion in virtual reality', *Displays*, 71.

Pohlmann, K. M. T., O'Hare, L., Dickinson, P., Parke, A. and Focker, J. (2020) 'The relationship between cybersickness, vection, and postural instability induced by optimized Fraser Wilcox illusions in virtual reality', *PERCEPTION*, 49(6), pp. 716-717.

Pritchard, A. and Woollard, J. (2010) *Psychology for the classroom: Constructivism and social learning*. Oxon, UK: Routledge.

Protogerou, C. and Hagger, M. S. (2019) 'A case for a study quality appraisal in survey studies in psychology', *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, pp. 2788.

Ragan, E. D., Bowman, D. A., Kopper, R., Stinson, C., Scerbo, S. and McMahan, R. P. (2015) 'Effects of field of view and visual complexity on virtual reality training effectiveness for a visual scanning task.', *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 21(7), pp. 794–807.

Ramirez, E. J., Elliott, M. and Milam, P.-E. (2021) 'What it's like to be a _: why it's (often) unethical to use VR as an empathy nudging tool', *Ethics and Information Technology*, 23(3), pp. 527-542.

Raque, J., Goble, A., Jones, V. M., Waldman, L. E. and Sutton, E. R. H. (2015) 'The relationship of endoscopic proficiency to educational expense for virtual reality simulator training amongst surgical trainees', *American Surgeon*, 81(7), pp. 747-752.

Ravenscroft, E. (2021) *What is the metaverse, exactly?: WIRED*. Available at: <https://www.wired.com/story/what-is-the-metaverse/> (Accessed: 11/04/2022).

Raz, G. (2022) 'Rage against the empathy machine revisited: The ethics of empathy-related affordances of virtual reality', *Convergence*, 28(5), pp. 1457-1475.

Real, F. J., DeBlasio, D., Ollberding, N. J., Davis, D., Cruse, B., McLinden, D. and Klein, M. D. (2017) 'Resident perspectives on communication training that utilizes immersive virtual reality', *Education and Health*, 30(3), pp. 228-231.

References

Real, F. J., Meisman, A. and Rosen, B. L. (2020) 'Usability matters for virtual reality simulations teaching communication', *Medical Education*, 54(11), pp. 1067-1068.

Recenti, M., Ricciardi, C., Aubonnet, R., Picone, I., Jacob, D., Svansson, H., Agnarsdóttir, S., Karlsson, G., Baeringsdóttir, V., Petersen, H. and Gargiulo, P. (2021) 'Toward predicting motion sickness using virtual reality and a moving platform assessing brain, muscles, and heart signals', *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 9.

Reddit. (2017) *An unexpected type of harassment*. Available at: https://www.reddit.com/r/EchoArena/comments/6mhr8u/unexpected_type_of_harassment/ (Accessed: 11/04/2022).

Reeves, R., Elliott, A., Curran, D., Dyer, K. and Hanna, D. (2021) '360° Video virtual reality exposure therapy for public speaking anxiety: A randomized controlled trial', *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 83, pp. 102451.

Rehman, A. A. and Alharthi, K. (2016) 'An introduction to research paradigms', *International Journal of Educational Investigations*, 3(8), pp. 51-59.

Reiners, T., Wood, L. C. and Gregory, S. (2014) 'Experimental study on consumer-technology supported authentic immersion in virtual environments for education and vocational training', *31st Annual Conference of the Australian Society for Computers in Tertiary Education, ASCILITE*.

Rho, E., Chan, K., Varoy, E. J. and Giacaman, N. (2020) 'An Experiential Learning Approach to Learning Manual Communication through a Virtual Reality Environment', *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 13(3), pp. 477-490.

Rhodes, I. (2019) 'EEF Improving behaviour in schools Report', *Education Endowment Foundation, (Environment)*.

Robertson, A. (2019) *Phone-based VR is officially over - The Verge*. Available at: <https://www.theverge.com/2019/10/16/20915791/google-daydream-samsung-oculus-gear-vr-mobile-vr-platforms-dead>.

Robson, C. and McCartan, K. (2016) *Real world research*. 4th edn. London: Wiley.

References

Rodriguez, J., Del-Valle-Soto, C. and Gonzalez-Sanchez, J. (2022) 'Affective states and virtual reality to improve gait rehabilitation: A preliminary study', *International Journal of Environmental Research in Public Health*, 19(15).

Rolls, E. (2007) *Emotion explained*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Roth, J. (2014) 'Examining the physical environment of your classroom', *Classroom Management for Successful Instruction*. Huntington-Beach, CA: Shell Educational Publishing.

Roy, E., Bakr, M. M. and George, R. (2017) 'The need for virtual reality simulators in dental education: A review', *Saudi Dental Journal*, 29(2), pp. 41-47.

Ryan, R. and Cochrane Consumers and Communication Review Group. (2013) *Cochrane Consumers and Communication Review Group: data synthesis and analysis* London. Available at: <http://cccr.org>.

Samsung. (2023) *Galaxy phone or tablet wont install apps from unknown sources*. Available at: <https://www.samsung.com/us/support/troubleshooting/TSG01001353/>.

Sangster, M. (2015) 'Part 1: Creating a good learning environment', *Challenging perceptions in primary education: Exploring issues in practice*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc.

Sapkaroski, D., Mundy, M. and Dimmock, M. R. (2022) 'Immersive virtual reality simulated learning environment versus role-play for empathic clinical communication training', *Journal of Medical Radiation Sciences*, 69(1), pp. 56-65.

Sauer, Y., Sipatchin, A., Wahl, S. and García García, M. (2022) 'Assessment of consumer VR-headsets' objective and subjective field of view (FoV) and its feasibility for visual field testing', *Virtual Reality*, 26, pp. 1089-1101.

Saunders, B., Sim, J., Kingstone, T., Baker, S., Waterfield, J., Bartlam, B., Burroughs, H. and Jinks, C. (2018) 'Saturation in qualitative research: exploring its conceptualization and operationalization', *Qualitative and Quantitative Research*, 52(4), pp. 1893-1907.

References

Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2019) *Research methods for business students*. 8th edn. New York: Pearson.

Schlembach, R. and Clewer, N. (2021) 'Forced empathy': Manipulation, trauma and affect in virtual reality film', *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, 24(5), pp. 827-843.

Schwind, V., Knierim, P., Haas, N. and Henze, N. (2019) 'Using presence questionnaires in virtual reality', *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pp. Paper 360.

Serge, S. R. and Fragomeni, G. 2017. Assessing the relationship between type of head movement and simulator sickness using an immersive virtual reality head mounted display: A pilot study. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*.

Shenton, A. (2004) 'Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects', *Education Informatics*, 22, pp. 63-75.

Shield, B., Conetta, R., Dockrell, J., Connolly, D., Cox, T. and Mydlarz, C. (2015) 'A survey of acoustic conditions and noise levels in secondary school classrooms in England', *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 137(1), pp. 177-188.

Shield, B. M. and Dockrell, J. E. (2008) 'The effects of environmental and classroom noise on the academic attainments of primary school children', *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 123(1), pp. 133-144.

Shussman, Y. M. (2017) 'Environmental psychology and classroom design as a tool for promoting meaningful learning', *Australian Educational Leader*, 39(1), pp. 48-52.

Siraj-Blatchford, I. and Sylva, K. (2004) 'Researching pedagogy in English pre-Schools', *British Educational Research Journal*, 30(5), pp. 713-730.

Smith, A. and Call, N. (2008) *The Alps approach resource book*. Stafford: Network Continuum Education.

References

Sora-Domenj3, C. (2022) 'Disrupting the "empathy machine": The power and perils of virtual reality in addressing social issues', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, pp. 814565.

South Ayrshire Council. (2020) *Newly qualified teacher handbook 2020-2021*. Available at: <https://blogs.glowscotland.org.uk/sa/public/leadershipandclpl/uploads/sites/11658/2020/07/29092059/SAC-NQT-Handbook-2020-2021.pdf>.

Stavroulia, K. (2015) 'Simulation-based training for Greek preservice teachers: developing a 3d classroom environment for professional development via practical experience', *International Conference on Information Communication Technologies in Education (ICICTE)*, pp. 51-60.

Stavroulia, K. and Lanitis, A. (2018) 'A systematic virtual reality-based approach to support the professional development of teachers', *International Conference on Information Communication Technologies in Education (ICICTE)*, pp. 29-38.

Stavroulia, K. and Lanitis, A. (2019a) 'Enhancing Reflection and Empathy Skills via Using a Virtual Reality Based Learning Framework', *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 14(7), pp. 18-36.

Stavroulia, K., Makri-Botsari, E., Psycharis, S. and Kekkeris, G. (2014) 'Using simulations as a tool to enhance classroom management practice', *International Conference on Information Communication Technologies in Education (ICICTE)*, pp. 205-217.

Stavroulia, K., Makri-Botsari, E., Psycharis, S. and Kekkeris, G. (2015) 'Emotional experiences in simulated classroom training environments', *International Conference on Information Communication Technologies in Education (ICICTE)*, pp. 390-401.

Stavroulia, K. E., Baka, E., Lanitis, A. and Magnenat-Thalmann, N. (2017) 'Virtual Reality-Based Learning Environments in Teacher Training: New Opportunities and Challenges', *10th International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation*, pp. 3562-3571.

Stavroulia, K. E., Baka, E., Lanitis, A. and Magnenat-Thalmann, N. 'Designing a virtual environment for teacher training'. *Computer Graphics International Conference*, Bintan, Indonesia, 273-282.

References

Stavroulia, K. E., Baka, E., Lanitis, A. and Magnenat-Thalmann, N. (2018b) 'Designing a virtual environment for teacher training: Enhancing presence and empathy', *Computer Graphics International Conference*.

Stavroulia, K. E., Christofi, M., Baka, E., Michael-Grigoriou, D., Magnenat-Thalmann, N. and Lanitis, A. (2019) 'Assessing the emotional impact of virtual reality-based teacher training', *International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*, 36(3), pp. 192-217.

Stavroulia, K. E. and Lanitis, A. (2019b) 'Enhancing reflection and empathy skills via using a virtual reality based learning framework', *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 14(7), pp. 18-36.

Stavroulia, K. E., Makri-Botsari, E., Psycharis, S. and Kekkeris, G. (2016a) 'Emotional experiences in simulated classroom training environments', *International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*, 33(3).

Stavroulia, K. E., Ruiz-Harisiou, A., Manouchou, E., Georgiou, K., Sella, F. and Lanitis, A. (2016b) 'A 3D virtual environment for training teachers to identify bullying', *Proceedings of the 18th Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference Melecon 2016*.

Stemler, S. E. (2015) 'Content analysis', *Emerging Trends in the Social and Behavioral Sciences*, pp. 1-14.

Stepan, K., Zeiger, J., Hanchuk, S., Del Signore, A., Shrivastava, R., Govindaraj, S. and Illoreta, A. (2017) 'Immersive virtual reality as a teaching tool for neuroanatomy', *Int Forum Allergy Rhinol*, 7(10), pp. 1006-1013.

Su, K., Chen, S., Lin, P. and Hsieh, C. (2020) 'Evaluating the user interface and experience of VR in the electronic commerce environment: a hybrid approach', *Virtual Reality*, 24, pp. 241-254.

Tai, J. and Ajjawi, R. (2016) 'Undertaking and reporting qualitative research', *Clin Teach*, 13, pp. 175–182.

References

Teaching Tolerance. (2016) *Reframing classroom management: A toolkit for educators*. Available at: [www.tolerance.org/sites/default/files/TT Reframing Classroom Managment](http://www.tolerance.org/sites/default/files/TT_Reframing_Classroom_Management) .

Thevin, L., Briant, C. and Brock, A. (2020) 'X-Road: Virtual reality glasses for orientation and mobility training of people with visual impairments', *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 13(2), pp. Article 7.

Tidbury, L., Jarvis, K. and Bridge, P. (2020) 'Initial evaluation of a virtual reality bomb-defusing simulator for development of undergraduate healthcare student communication and teamwork skills', *BMJ Simul Technol Enhanc Learn*, 6(4), pp. 229-231.

Toet, A., Mioch, T., Gunkel, S., Niamut, O. and van Erp, J. (2021) 'Assessment of presence in augmented and mixed reality', *PsyArXiv*.

Tretsiakova-McNally, S., Maranne, E., Verbecke, F. and Molkov, V. (2017) 'Mixed e-learning and virtual reality pedagogical approach for innovative hydrogen safety training of first responders', *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 42(11), pp. 7504-7512.

Trussell, R. (2008) 'Classroom universals to prevent problem behaviors', *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 43, pp. 179-185.

UCSanDiegoX. (2020) *How virtual reality works. Course material*. Available at: <https://learning.edx.org/course/course-v1:UCSanDiegoX+CSE165x> (Accessed: 11/04/2022).

Unal, Z. and Unal, A. (2012) 'The impact of years of teaching experience on the classroom management approaches of elementary school teachers', *International Journal of Instruction*, 5, pp. 41-60.

Unity. (2022) *Real-Time 3D Development Software for Games & More*. Available at: <https://unity.com/products> (Accessed: 13/04/2022).

University and College Admissions Service [UCAS]. (2022) *Teaching: UCAS*. Available at: <https://www.ucas.com/explore/subjects/teaching> (Accessed: 25/05/2022).

References

Vallikat, A. (2021) 'Objectives of teaching'. Available at: <https://blog.teachmint.com/objectives-of-teaching/>

Veloso, L. and Marques, J. (2017) 'Designing science laboratories: learning environments, school architecture and teaching and learning models', *Learning Environments Research*, 20(2), pp. 221-248.

Venkatakrishnan, R., Venkatakrishnan, R., Anaraky, R. G., Volonte, M., Knijnenburg, B. and Babu, S. V. (2020) 'A structural equation modeling approach to understand the relationship between control, cybersickness and presence in virtual reality', *IEEE 2020*, pp. 682-691.

Ventura, S., Badenes-Ribera, L., Herrero, R., Cebolla, A., Galiana, L. and Baños, R. (2020) 'Virtual reality as a medium to elicit empathy: A meta-analysis', *Cyberpsychology Behaviour Society and Networks*, 23(10), pp. 667-676.

Ventura, S., Cardenas, G., Miragall, M., Riva, G. and Baños, R. (2021) 'How does it feel to be a woman victim of sexual harassment? The effect of 360°-video-based virtual reality on empathy and related variables', *Cyberpsychology Behaviour Society and Networks*, 24(4), pp. 258-266.

VR Innovations. (2019) *The power of mobile VR. We love virtual reality but buying a pc...: AR/VR Journey: Augmented & Virtual Reality Magazine*. Available at: <https://arvrjourney.com/the-power-of-mobile-vr-e8a816999c92> (Accessed: 11/04/2022.

Wang, P., Wu, P., Wang, J., Chi, H.-L. and Wang, X. (2018) 'A critical review of the use of virtual reality in construction engineering education and training', *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 15(6).

Waring, M. and Evans, C. (2015) *Understanding pedagogy: Developing a critical approach to teaching and learning*. London: Routledge.

Weinstein, C. S. and Mignano, A. J. (2011) *Elementary classroom management: Lessons from research and practice*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

References

Wikipedia. (2022) *SEGA VR*. Available at: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sega VR](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sega_VR) (Accessed: 11/04/2022).

Wolcott, M. D. and Lobczowski, N. G. (2021) 'Using cognitive interviews and think-aloud protocols to understand thought processes', *Current Pharmacology Teaching and Learning*, 13(2), pp. 181-188.

Xu, Z. and Zhang, M. R. (2022) 'The "ultimate empathy machine" as technocratic solutionism? Audience reception of the distant refugee crisis through virtual reality', *Communication Reviews*, 25(3-4), pp. 181-203.

Yeo, N. L., White, M. P., Alcock, I., Garside, R., Dean, S. G., Smalley, A. J. and Gatersleben, B. (2020) 'What is the best way of delivering virtual nature for improving mood? An experimental comparison of high definition TV, 360° video, and computer generated virtual reality', *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 72, pp. 101500.

Yiasemidou, M., de Siqueira, J., Tomlinson, J., Glassman, D., Stock, S. and Gough, M. (2017) "'Take-home" box trainers are an effective alternative to virtual reality simulators', *Journal of Surgical Research*, 213, pp. 69-74.

Yin, M. S., Haddawy, P., Suebnukarn, S. and Rhienmora, P. (2018) 'Automated outcome scoring in a virtual reality simulator for endodontic surgery', *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 153, pp. 53-59.

Zhu, L. X. (2022) 'Work emotion intervention and guidance training method for enterprise employees based on virtual reality', *Occupational Therapy International*, 2022.

Appendices

Appendix 2.1. Summary of ITE scoping review

Within Chapter 2's literature review, the provision of information related to classroom management and organisation within ITE was explored in the evidence base. The aim was to identify what evidence-based information was provided to ITE students in their learning of classroom management and organisation.

A scoping review was undertaken using the University of the West of Scotland's *OneSearch* catalogue function and three relevant research databases: ERIC, EBSCO and PsycINFO. Based on pilot scoping searches, it was anticipated that studies on classroom organisation and management would be limited. A range of search terms were therefore used to capture a breadth of potential sources. Search terms included *primary education*, *secondary education*, *classroom organisation*, *physical learning environment*, *classroom layout*, *initial teacher education* and/or *newly qualified teachers*.

In brief, a search for "primary education" or "secondary education" in the source titles resulted in 14,761 results, of which 675 were textbooks. When this search was refined further using additional search terms such as "classroom organisation" or "physical environment" or "layout", 105 results were found, of which 2 were textbooks. The remainder were research articles of mostly irrelevant topics, such as articles discussing teaching pedagogies but with no reference to the classroom environment, or articles exploring student/teacher interactions but again with no reference to the classroom environment. An exception was one study exploring the broader architecture issues in Polish schools (Szpytma and Szpytma, 2022). This was, however, brief and lacked data to usefully inform the aim of Chapter 2's literature review.

Additional searches were undertaken using search terms including "initial teacher education" and "newly qualified teachers". This returned 1252 results, which mostly focused on teachers' learning styles and behaviour management, with little reference to how a classroom should be organised or set up. For example, Jolliffe & Waugh (2017) do briefly mention the physical layout of the classroom in one of their case studies, but mostly focus on all other aspects of new teacher education. Overall, most textbooks

focused on managing behaviour, for example the SAGE Encyclopaedia of Classroom Management (Scarlett, 2015), with minimal information on how this relates to the physical layout of the classroom. Others presented an opinion on best practice but with limited reference to the evidence base (Bennett, 2021) , or they focused on managing the classroom with rules and responsibilities (Allen Queen and Algozzine, 2010).

In summary, these scoping searches confirmed that there is minimal research data exploring the management and organisation of classrooms within ITE. Chapter 2's literature review therefore used an alternative method of seeking information from ITE textbooks. The results of this are detailed in Chapter 2.

References

- Allen Queen, J. and Algozzine, B. (2010) *Responsible Classroom Management, Grades K-5*. Thousand Oaks: Corwin Press.
- Bennett, T. (2021) *The Running the Room Companion: Issues in Classroom Management and Strategies to Deal with Them*. Woodbridge: John Catt Educational.
- Jolliffe, W. and Waugh, D. (2017) *NQT: The beginning teachers guide to outstanding practice*. London: SAGE publications.
- Scarlett, W. G. (2015) *The SAGE Encyclopedia of classroom management*. New York: SAGE publications.
- Szpytma, C. and Szpytma, M. (2022) 'School architecture for primary education in a post-socialist country: a case study of Poland', *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 52(4), pp. 519-542.

Appendix 4.1. Uncompleted Study interview schedule

School of Education and Social Science

Interview Schedule

Understanding teachers' use of their classroom.

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study. The interview should take no more than 50 minutes. If you want to take a break or stop at any time just tell me.

Review the background of the study:

The proposed study will form part of a doctoral research project. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between teaching practice and the organisation and management of learning spaces. Given that each learning environment presents a unique combination of challenges it is potentially enlightening to examine the practice of organisation and management with reference to a specific example. The aim is for you to teach us how you organise and manage your classroom.

Reiterate that the study is anonymous:

Did you read the information sheet? Have you initialled and signed the Participant Consent Form? You are aware that quotes from the interview may be used in future studies and in future publications? You are aware that video taken in the empty classroom along with still images may be used in future studies and publications? When the data from this study is analysed and used it will be made anonymous so that individual participants cannot be identified. Any video footage, images or audio recordings will also be anonymised.

Reiterate the right to withdraw:

You retain the right to withdraw from the study, without explanation at any time up to one week after the completion of the interview, since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Emphasise that no question needs to be answered:

If you don't want to answer any of the questions, even the quick background questions at the start that is of course okay. There are no right or wrong answers it is about your opinions and experience. Please feel free to add anything that you think is important but which I may not ask you about.

Appendices

Do you have any questions before we start?

Are you okay to proceed with the interview?

Part 1: The Introduction

To be recorded with a 360° video camera and a digital audio recorder.

Questions 1: Can you please give us a brief, around 5 minute, introduction to your classroom and why it is organised the way it is?

Prompt 1a: It is organised into Dedicated Areas?

Prompt 1b: Why are the desks arranged as they are?

Prompt 1c: How did you choose what to display on the walls?

Part 2: Demographic Information

To be recorded with a digital audio recorder only.

Question 1: Identifier:

Your name won't be recorded here and so the data you provide will be given the following identifier:

Question 2: Time of qualification as a teacher:

When did you qualify as a teacher? I'm trying to get measure of your experience.

Question 3: How long have you been teaching in this classroom?

Trying to get an idea of the time to have influence over its' layout.

Question 4: Do you share this classroom with any other teachers?

Do you therefore share influence in the organisation with other teachers?

Part 3: Interview

To be recorded with a digital audio recorder only.

Questions 1: How much of the way you organise your classroom is imposed on you for outside the school?

Prompt 1a: National government or Local Government Policy?

Prompt 1b: Local area and influence of parents or community groups?

Prompt 1c: Are there cultural or language considerations?

Questions 2: I what ways do you cooperate with or influence other members of staff in the way you organise your classrooms?

Prompt 2a: Are there influences from your colleagues or from management?

Prompt 2b: Are you limited in your organisational options by resources or time?

Prompt 2c: Are there specialist teaching requirement reflected in the organisation?

Questions 3: How have you overcome the physical restrictions caused by the type of school and the size of the classroom?

Prompt 3a: Have you arranged the desks to create clear lines of sight?

Prompt 3b: How do you store resources and how do the students have access?

Prompt 3c: Have you creates space for you to move around the room?

Prompt 3d: How have you arranged the room to improve behaviour management?

Prompt 3e: How do you use technology to improve communication with students?

Questions 4: How have you adapted the layout of the classroom to suit the curriculum?

Prompt 4a: How do you adapt to students varying abilities?

Prompt 4b: Do you display learning objectives or core tasks?

Prompt 4c: Do you display the students work?

Prompt 4d: Do the students contribute the layout, decoration and organisation of the room?

Questions 5: How do you try to create an atmosphere suitable for learning?

Prompt 5a: Do you display “the rules of the classroom”?

Prompt 5b: Can you control environmental factors like heat, light and noise?

Prompt 5c: How have you tried to make the environment feel safe for students?

Questions 6: How do you try to engage students in the organisation of the classroom?

Prompt 6a: How do you engage the students visually?

Prompt 6b: How do you give the students a feeling of ownership?

Prompt 6c: Do you feel a sense of ownership of the classroom?

Prompt 6d: How is this reflected in your organisation and management choices?

Appendix 4.2. Ethical approval letter for Uncompleted Study

02/04/2020

Dear Alan Matthews,

Your application 10922: Understanding teachers' use of their classroom environment., submission 9201, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. Our reviewers have made the following comments for you and your supervisor to consider.

Title	Comment
Where will the proposed research take place?	Good considerations are made here. Given the current coronavirus situation, it would be useful to consider how your interviews will be conducted should social distancing measures continue. Perhaps a Zoom interview with the teacher in their classroom for example.
Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	It would be useful to outline what you are classifying as 'identifying material'.
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	Section 'Do I have to take part': Make clear here that there are no expectations from their employer for them to take part either, and that participation or non-participation will not impact their employee-employer relationship. 'What happens if I take part': Explain here that identifying materials will be blanked out or removed from the video to reassure the anonymity of the teacher and their students.

At present UWS is following government guidelines on social distancing and self isolation. It is our position that once approved, changes in how you gather data (using an online method such as voice over internet protocols (VOIP) such as WebEx, comply with GDPR regulations. Please stay in contact with your experienced supervisor for adhering to these guidelines on data collection, storage and analysis.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix 5.1. A summary of the interview findings from Study 1

What the previous interviews were all about.

This study focussed on the physical characteristics of the learning environment and gathered information about how working teachers organise and manage their learning spaces. The study aimed to address the questions:

- How do in practice teachers organise and manage their learning spaces?
- What are the major influences?
- What are the key attributes of a well-functioning learning environment?

Six participants were interviewed, two female and four male. All had experience working as a teacher in Scotland. Three of the participants had teaching experience outside mainstream UK schools. This included prisons, military training, technical colleges, private schools and teaching abroad.

Transcripts were analysed using Thematic Analysis. Ideas which repeated in the data were grouped into themes. Eight themes were identified, described below.

8 themes were identified.

Theme Name	Description
Theme1: Cultural Influence	This theme includes influences from outside the school such as social and cultural norms, the expectations of parents, national and local government policy and the socio-economic status of the catchment area. Students in modern schools are increasingly representative of a broad variation in cultural traditions and linguistic backgrounds.
Theme 2: School Organisation	This theme represents influences from within the school including the physical layout of the building and the peer groups within the school. The social and organisational framework of the school is the most immediate influence on individual teachers and also the primary means of support.
Theme 3: Work Adaptation	Teachers can use flexibility in the curriculum including the objectives for each lesson, the core work of the class to change how lessons are taught and how the space is used. For example, additional work for more advanced students. There is a close relationship between what is being taught, how to

	teach it and how to use the learning environment to best effect.
Theme 4: Physical Adaptation	This theme includes all the physical attributes of the learning environment including available technology and resources, lighting, number of desks, power sockets, etc. Some of these are under the teacher's control and others are not, this will change from room to room and from school to school. It is not always so easy to define which characteristics of the classroom teachers will be able to change and which they will be bound by.
Theme 5: Teacher's Approach	Teachers are proactive in organising their classroom and not passively reacting to the environmental conditions. Their approach is mostly a product of their experience, their training and their pedagogical beliefs. Participant's ITE experience had little effect on their approach to managing and organising learning spaces. The most important part of their development is actual practical experience.
Theme 6: Learning Atmosphere	The creation and maintenance of a safe and comfortable environment suitable for learning is the primary responsibility of a teacher. This includes the use of sensory cues to put students in the right frame of mind, the management of expectations that structured learning is taking place and limiting distractions.
Theme 7: Engagement and Ownership	A learning environment is most productive when both the students and the teacher feel a connection, a responsibility and a sense of ownership to it. It is also important to use the environment (visual cues, sounds displays etc.) to engage students with the lesson.
Theme 8: Student/Teacher Relationship	The classroom is a physical expression of the relationship between the students and the teacher. This is a reciprocal relationship based on good communication and informed choices, some of which is within the teacher's control and some of which is not. Central to the teacher's role was to make this relationship be more productive by deliberate organisation and management of the classroom.

Some important observations.

Several important observations resulted from the analysis:

- Understanding all of the factors which effect how teachers organise and manage their learning environment was a large and complex undertaking, like asking, “How does a teacher teach?”
- Participants all looked beyond the physical limitations of the classroom and were influenced by many other factors some of which are physical, some social, some political and some emotional. An understanding of context was therefore necessary.
- Participants motivations also went beyond the physical characteristics and included the age and stage of the students being taught, behaviour from individual students, the relationship between teacher and students, the need to engage students and the need to provide students with a sense of ownership.
- A functional learning environment is not described as a series of physical characteristics but rather how those characteristics, taken in the wider social context, express a positive student/teacher relationship and create an atmosphere for learning.

How do these themes interact?

Teachers develop instinctive responses based mostly on classroom experience:

- The learning environment is truly a chaotic, complex system. It is a dynamic system made up of multiple interconnected parts which is extremely sensitive to small changes in any one of the multiple influential factors.
- Most participants described their approach to classroom organisation and management as something which is not taught so much as it is a combination of experience and instinct.
- This interconnectivity and unpredictability results in a situation where teachers learn progressively by experience, adapting to and solving their own problems, until they develop an instinct.

What do the themes suggest about organising classrooms?

By placing all 8 themes in a meaningful structure (see the table below) we can see that they express the organisation and management of the classroom from the teacher’s perspective. The themes express the broad context, the immediate environmental pressures, the potentially adaptable variables, the relationships and the ultimate goals.

This structure should allow us to quickly recognise those factors to focus on when providing meaningful experience of ITE students. It also allows us to separate the context of the learning environment from its physical and social attributes.

Theme	Individual Teacher's level of Influence	Explanation	Characterisation of Themes
1: Cultural Influence	No influence.	Provides context to the organisation and management of the classroom.	Contextual pressures and support.
2: School Organisation	Limited influence as part of peer group.		
3: Physical Adaptation	Some influence depending on available resources.	Represent the things which the teacher may be able to use in order to better organise and manage the learning environment depending on context.	Adaptable variables and limiting variables. It is not always so easy to define which characteristics of the classroom teachers will be able to change and which they will be bound by.
4: Work Adaptation	Some influence depending on external factors.		
5: Teacher's Approach	Some influence depending on experience and education.	Represents the filter through which problems are analysed, challenges are met and influences are considered.	
6: Learning Atmosphere	Large influence acknowledging environmental factors.	Collectively represent the goals of the process. Not only under the teacher's control but are also their responsibility. These three themes taken together are similar to the <i>hidden curriculum</i> in that they are not formalised or academic but that they represent the influence of the social and physical environment on the	
7: Engagement and Ownership	Large influence depending on type of teaching environment.		
8: Student/Teacher Relationship	Large influence depending on social and cultural factors.		
			Relationships and ultimate goals.

		development of the students.	
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Final thoughts and some limitations.

This study has demonstrated the difficulty in trying to create a definitive list of the physical attributes of a good learning environment. Each environment must be examined on its own merits. However, using this overall structure as a guide allows us to model the learning environment from the teacher's perspective. Also to more easily identify what the teacher's goals are, what tools they have available to achieve them and what limitations they face. This may be applied to future studies.

This study was limited by the following factors:

- It focused on a generalised discussion of a large and complex topic.
- Greater understanding could be gained by focusing on specific learning environments in detail.
- Each learning environment is highly individualised and constantly evolving but based on common influences and ideas.
- The interviews did not take place in an actual classroom. Having tangible examples on hand which demonstrate how a teacher is attempting to engage students or how the layout had been altered to improve visual access and lines of sight would provide valuable insight into classroom management and organisation.

Appendix 5.2. Participant Information, Study 1, Phase 1

Participant Information Sheet

Understanding teachers' perceptions and use of their classroom learning environment

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of the study is to explore how teachers approach classroom management and organisation and what factors influence their approach. The proposed study will form part of a doctoral research project. The overall doctoral project seeks to explore the relationship between pedagogical practice and the design of learning spaces through the use of virtual reality (VR) and eye-tracking technology. Ultimately the purpose of the research is to assess the potential for using VR technology to change and improve the provision of professional education and training by focusing on its potential application to Initial Teacher Education (ITE). This study is simply about understanding how teachers perceive classroom design and how they organise and manage their classroom.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are or were a qualified teacher who has spent some or all of their career teaching in primary or secondary school classrooms.

Do I have to take part?

No. In addition, participants retain their right to withdraw up to one week after the completion of the interview. Transcription will take place a week after the interview has been concluded and since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will take part in a short interview. The interviews will be approximately 40 minutes. The first stage of the interview will consist of a series of questions intended to establish basic background information about your teaching experience. The second stage of the interview will consist of a series of questions intended to explore your approach to classroom management and organisation and what factors influenced that approach. You can refuse to answer an individual question without withdrawing from the interview.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks of taking part.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no obvious benefits but your participation will improve our understanding of how teachers organise and manage classroom environments and how this might be used to enhance Initial Teacher Education (ITE).

Data Protection Privacy Notice

All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998). Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you. The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS).

The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-thegdpr/individuals-rights/>

All data gathered, including signed consent forms, audio recordings and notes, will be stored in line with UWS policy on password protected computers and accessed only by members of the research team. To assure anonymity no comment will be attributable to any individual and that each participant will be referenced by sex and number e.g. M1 for Male no 1 (the first male to be interviewed)", etc.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Upon completion of the interview these audio recordings will be downloaded on to a secure password protected UWS laptop with a single backup (a portable password protected hard disc or memory card as appropriate). The interview recordings will be subject to thematic analysis. The data provided by this analysis will form part of the principal researcher's doctoral dissertation. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between pedagogical practice and the design of learning spaces through the use of virtual reality (VR) and eye-tracking technology and to use that technology to improve provision of ITE. After the analysis is completed all audio files will be deleted upon completion of the doctoral research project.

Who has reviewed the study? MCS Ethics Committee

Thank you for taking part in this study. Contact for further information:

If you require any further information please contact:

Alan Matthews

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Personal details withheld.

Appendix 5.3. Informed Consent, Study 1, Phase 1

Project Title: Understanding teachers' perceptions and use of their classroom learning environment.

Ethics Approval Number:

Investigator(s): Alan Matthews

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet (PIS Initial Interviews v4 11.06.19) for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason up to one week after the completion of the interview. Transcription will take place a week after the interview has been concluded and since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Initials

I understand that the interview will be audio recorded, that my data will be treated confidentially and that any data disseminated will be anonymised. Actual quotes might be used in publications but these will be anonymised and will not be attributable to any individual.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Alan Matthews

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email at: [REDACTED]. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 5.4. Participant Information, Study 1, Phase 2

Participant Information Sheet

Understanding teachers' perceptions and use of their classroom learning environment

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

This study follows on from the interviews in which you have already participated. The purpose of this is to allow you to provide feedback on the analysis of those interviews and compare the results to your real-world experience. In addition, you will be asked to provide a description of a classroom in which you have worked to assist in the creation of a VR simulation. The overall doctoral project seeks to explore the relationship between pedagogical practice and the design of learning spaces through the use of virtual reality (VR). Ultimately the purpose of the research is to assess the potential for using VR technology to change and improve the provision of professional education and training by focusing on its potential application to Initial Teacher Education (ITE).

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are or were a qualified teacher who has spent some or all of their career teaching in primary or secondary school classrooms. Also, you are familiar with the aims of this project because you took part in the initial interviews.

Do I have to take part?

No. In addition, participants retain their right to withdraw up to one week after the completion of the interview. Transcription will take place a week after the interview has been concluded and since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be provided with a summary of the results of the analysis of the interviews which you took part in more than a year ago. You will also be provided with an interview schedule. You will be able to see the interview schedule in advance of the actual online interview being conducted. The interview will be approximately 40 minutes. The first stage of the interview will consist of a series of questions intended to allow you to comment on the analysis of the previous interview based on your own teaching experience. The second stage of the interview will require you describe in detail the physical layout of a classroom you are familiar with.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks of taking part.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Appendices

There are no obvious benefits but your participation will improve our understanding of how teachers organise and manage classroom environments and how this might be used to enhance Initial Teacher Education (ITE).

Data Protection Privacy Notice

All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998). Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you. The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS).

The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-thegdpr/individuals-rights/>

All data gathered, including signed consent forms, audio recordings and notes, will be stored in line with UWS policy on password protected computers and accessed only by members of the research team. To assure anonymity no comment will be attributable to any individual and that each participant will be referenced by sex and number e.g. M1 for Male no 1 (the first male to be interviewed)", etc.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Upon completion of the interview these video recordings will be downloaded on to a secure password protected UWS laptop with a single backup (a portable password protected hard disc or memory card as appropriate). The interview recordings will be subject to analysis. The data provided by this analysis will form part of the principal researcher's doctoral dissertation. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between pedagogical practice and the design of learning spaces through the use of virtual reality (VR) and to use that technology to improve provision of ITE. After the analysis is completed all audio files will be deleted upon completion of the doctoral research project.

Who has reviewed the study? MCS Ethics Committee

Thank you for taking part in this study. Contact for further information:

If you require any further information please contact:

Alan Matthews

University of the West of Scotland,
High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Name Dr Edward Edgerton

University of the West of Scotland,
High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Appendix 5.5. Informed Consent, Study 1, Phase 2

School of Media Culture and Society

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Project Title: Understanding teachers' perceptions and use of their classroom learning environment.

Ethics Approval Number:

Investigator(s): Alan Matthews

Researcher Email: alan.matthews@uws.ac.uk

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet (PIS Interviews v1 15.03.21) for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason up to one week after the completion of the interview. Transcription will take place a week after the interview has been concluded and since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Initials

I understand that the interview will be video recorded. That my data will be treated confidentially and that any data disseminated will be anonymised. Actual quotes might be used in publications but these will be anonymised and will not be attributable to any individual.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Alan Matthews

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email at: [REDACTED] Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 5.6. Interview Schedule, Study 1, Phase 1

School of Media Culture and Society

Interview Schedule

Understanding teachers' perceptions and use of their classroom learning environment

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study. The interview should take no more than 40 minutes. If you want to take a break or stop at any time just tell me.

Review the background of the study:

The purpose of this interview is to gather information about classroom design, how teachers approach classroom management and organisation and what factors influenced that approach. The proposed study will form part of a doctoral research project. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between pedagogical practice and the design of learning spaces.

Reiterate that the study is anonymous:

Did you read the information sheet? Have you initialled and signed the Participant Consent Form? Do you have any questions before we start? When the data from this study is analysed and used it will be made completely anonymous so that individual participants cannot be identified.

Reiterate the right to withdraw:

You retain the right to withdraw from the study, without explanation at any time up to one week after the completion of the interview. Transcription will take place a week after the interview has been concluded and since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Emphasise that no question needs to be answered:

If you don't want to answer any of the questions, even the quick background questions at the start that is of course okay. Missing out one question does not mean that you have to withdraw from the rest of the study. There are no right or wrong answers it is about your opinions and experience. Please feel free to add anything that you think is important but which I may not ask you about.

Are you okay to proceed with the interview?

Part 1: Demographic Information

Question 1: Identifier:

Your name won't be recorded here and so the data you provide will be given the following identifier:

Question 2: Time of qualification as a teacher:

When did you qualify as a teacher? I'm trying to get measure of your experience.

Question 3: Can you describe briefly your background and experience in teaching?

Prompt 3a: Did/do you teach in Primary or Secondary education?

Prompt 3b: Which schools have you taught in?

Prompt 3c: What where they like? Old/new? Big/small?

Prompt 3d: How long in each school?

Prompt 3e: Did you teach in any unusual school environments (e.g. special needs, disabilities)?

Question 4: Have you experienced different types of classroom design and layout?

Prompt 4a: Did/do you prefer to teach in open plan or enclosed classrooms? Why?

Part 2: Interview

Questions 1: Can you please describe in general terms your approach to teaching?

Prompt 1a: How did/do you change or adapt your approach depending on the situation (e.g. cohort, stage/age or demographic)?

Prompt 1b: How was/is your approach influenced by your curriculum plans?

Prompt 1c: How do/did you allow students to access resources?

Prompt 1d: What are the main factors which influence how you taught?

Question 2: This study is mainly interested in with how teachers organise and manage their classroom in terms of the physical space. So, can you describe your approach?

Prompt 2a: What factors influenced your approach?

Prompt 2b: How did/do you prefer desks to be arranged?

Appendices

Prompt 2c: How do/did you allow students to access resources?

Prompt 2d: What other factors (e.g. layout, routines and behaviour management) are important?

Prompt 2e: Do your children/pupils have any input?

Prompt 2f: How often were/are you able to teach out of the classroom (e.g. outdoors, field trips)?

Prompt 2g: What, in your opinion, are the key physical attributes of a learning environment which works?

Question 3: How much was your approach to classroom management effected by your ITE experience?

Prompt 3a: What, if anything, would you have changed about your ITE experience?

Prompt 3a: How did your approach change with experience?

Prompt 3b: How was your approach effected by other teachers?

Question 4: What do you think are the important physical characteristics of a classroom/learning space?

Prompt 4a: Which of these characteristics did you feel able to change/improve?

Prompt 4b: How often did/do you alter the physical characteristics of your classroom?

Prompt 4c: In what ways did/do you adapt your classroom management style to the physical environment?

Appendix 5.7. Interview Schedule, Study 1, Phase 2

School of Education and Social Science

Interview Schedule

Understanding teachers' use of their classroom.

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study. The interview should take no more than 40 minutes. If you want to take a break or stop at any time just tell me.

Review the background of the study:

It is the intention of this doctoral research project to create representative simulations of classrooms in VR and test their viability as a teaching tool for ITE students. For this reason it is important to be clear about the motivation behind why teachers organise and manage their classrooms as they do. It is also important to have guidance on the design and layout of the simulations which is grounded in real-world experience. The proposed study will form part of a doctoral research project. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between teaching practice and the organisation and management of learning spaces.

In this study it is hoped that you will be able to provide feedback on the analysis and conclusions drawn from the interviews which you took part in more than one year ago. In addition, it is hoped that you will be able to provide guidance on the construction of VR classroom simulations in the form of a described example from your own teaching experience.

Reiterate that the study is anonymous:

Did you read the information sheet? Have you initialled and signed the Participant Consent Form? You are aware that quotes from the interview may be used in future studies and in future publications? Any video footage, images or audio recordings will remain anonymous.

Reiterate the right to withdraw:

You retain the right to withdraw from the study, without explanation at any time up to one week after the completion of the interview. Since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Emphasise that no question needs to be answered:

If you don't want to answer any of the questions that is of course okay. There are no right or wrong answers, it is about your opinions and experience. Please feel free to add anything that you think is important but which I may not ask you about.

Do you have any questions before we start? Are you okay to proceed with the interview?

Part 1: Review of the Results of the Previous Interviews

Questions 1: Did you manage to read through the Summary of the Interview Findings? What questions do you have about the summary?

Prompt 1a: Did you feel like it made sense?

Prompt 1b: What parts, if any, would like some clarification?

Questions 2: How much do you feel like the Summary of the Interview Findings accurately reflected the experience of a teachers organising and managing their classroom?

Prompt 1a: What was obviously missing from the analysis?

Prompt 1b: What errors do you think were in the analysis?

Prompt 1c: Is there any way that the results could be improved to more accurately reflect real life?

Questions 3: Now having read the Summary of the Interview Findings what would you like to add to this study which you may have omitted from your previous interview?

Prompt 1a: Is there anything from your experience which was not reflected in the results?

Prompt 1b: Is there anything in the results which was over emphasised out of proportion to its real life significance?

Questions 4: Knowing that this study is now going forward to create VR simulations off classrooms what other relevant information would you like to add regarding how they are represented?

Part 2: Describing a Classroom

Questions 1: In order to provide guidance for the design and layout of classrooms in VR simulations please describe in detail a classroom from your own experience. Remember to include:

- Rough dimensions, wall to wall, floor to ceiling.
- Number of windows, type, direction of facing.
- Doors.
- Utilities, sinks, power sockets.
- Cupboards, bookshelves and storage.
- Location of displays, noticeboards and information.
- Desk layout and types of desks.
- White boards, chalk board and other communication.
- Technology, computers and other equipment.

Appendix 5.8. Ethical approval letter for Study 1, Phase 1

04/06/2019

Dear Alan Matthews,

Your application 8383: Understanding teachers' perceptions and use of their classroom learning environment., submission reference 6734, has been approved, with conditions, by the Media Culture and Society SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	All of the feedback is suggested improvements or changes that can be negotiated with your supervisors and approved by them.
Where will the proposed research take place?	Shouldn't all research take place on University grounds to be in line with the general testing risk assessment? Please delete if this is not the case or does not apply for PhD / staff projects.
Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	More details behind the project would have been advantageous. However, the bare minimum has provided here.
Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:	How will you securely dispose of your data/audio files, and hand notes? need to follow GDPR in terms of destroying data. Check the latest advice to make sure your practise is compliant.
Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:	How will you securely transfer your data from one computer to another? Again make sure your practise is compliant.
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	This does not explain how the data will be collected. How will the research strategically target the population? Where are these contacts from? Will there be any recruitment emails / letters sent? If so, these need to be sent to the ethics committee too, please (MCS.Ethics@uws.ac.uk). I understand that the populations might be individuals already known to the researcher, but the way this has been communicated, it sounds like the participants have already been approached?
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	Could the information sheet please explain clearly how the participant's data will be anonymised (i.e use of pseudonyms).
Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)	Consent form: will you be using direct quotes? If so, you need to get consent for this
Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application	Teachers might not have access to these materials provided, do you have better lay-summaries of studies somewhere if they wish to know more? Also, you should let them contact you for the results of the study
Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application	This debrief needs rewriting. There is a lot of repetition from the information sheet, when the debrief should shed new light on the project (insight in to aims etc.) and give as much information as possible. Information that has been provided on the consent form (i.e. how to make a complaint about the research and who to) should be made clear here too. How helpful and accessible is stating references for further reading? The debrief should communicate this literature and provide context rather than making the participant seek out the additional information.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Christopher O'Donnell

Appendix 5.9. Ethical approval letter for Study 1, Phase 2

27/04/2021

Dear Alan Matthews,

Your application 8383: Understanding teachers' perceptions and use of their classroom learning environment., submission 13589, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix 5.10. Participants' Demographic Information – All Studies

Study 1 Phase 1 (n=6)			
	n	%	M (range)
Gender			
Male	4	66.66	
Female	2	33.33	
Background			
Primary	5	83.33	
Secondary	1	16.66	
Retired			
Yes	2	33.33	
No	4	66.66	
Years from qualification to 2023			27.83 (16 – 52)

Study 1 Phase 2 (n=4)			
	n	%	M (range)
Gender			
Male	2	50.0	
Female	2	50.0	
Background			
Primary	3	75.0	
Secondary	1	25.0	
Retired			
Yes	2	50.0	
No	2	50.0	
Years from qualification to 2023			33.00 (16 – 52)

Study 2 (n=6)			
	n	%	M (range)
Gender			
Male	5	83.33	
Female	1	16.66	
Background			
Lecturer	2	33.33	
PhD Student	2	33.33	
PhD Student (Qualified Teacher)	2	33.33	
VR Experience			
None	0	0	
Limited	2	33.33	
Regular	2	33.33	
Technical Expertise	2	33.33	

The 'Drawing Classrooms' Micro Study			
	n	%	M (range)
Gender			
Male	2	50.0	
Female	2	50.0	
Background			
Primary	3	75.0	
Secondary	1	25.0	
Retired			
Yes	2	50.0	
No	2	50.0	
Years from qualification to 2023			33.00 (16 – 52)

Study 4 (n=16)			
	n	%	M (range)
Gender			
Male	3	18.75	
Female	13	81.25	
Group			
Preservice Teacher	4	25.00	
In-practice Teacher	4	25.00	
ITE Educator	4	25.00	
Retired Teacher	4	25.00	
Background			
Primary	8	50.00	
Secondary	8	50.00	
VR Experience			
None	13	81.25	
Limited	0	0	
Regular	2	12.50	
Technical Expertise	1	6.25	
Used VR for Teaching/Learning			
No	14	87.50	
Yes	2	12.50	
Years from qualification to 2023			23.44 (-1 – 53)

Appendix 5.11. Description of Codes, Study 1

Code	Description
Cultural Influence	
<p>Multiple Languages – pupils in modern classrooms speak many different languages.</p> <p>Cultural Differences – pupils and teachers from different cultural backgrounds have different expectations from the school experience.</p> <p>Results Driven – classroom work being driven or directed to optimise exam results.</p> <p>National Government Influence – national government policy and how it effects the operation of schools.</p> <p>Local Government Influence - local government policy and how it effects the operation of schools.</p> <p>Socio-Economic Status – economic status of the local area.</p> <p>Parent Influence – the influence of the expectations and involvement of parents.</p> <p>Legal Issues – legal considerations faced by schools, for example, health and safety</p>	
School Organisation	
<p>Teacher's Limited Autonomy – the limitations places on teachers regarding the decisions they can make about their classrooms.</p> <p>Specialist Teaching Requirements – specialist needs of individual pupils including dyslexia, behavioural problems and physical disabilities.</p> <p>Peer Influence – inspiration and advice provided by other teachers.</p> <p>Admin Influence – the influence administrative concerns on the classrooms, for example, taking the register.</p> <p>Management Influence – the influence of the teacher's managers and the heads of school.</p> <p>Time Pressure – teachers working with limited time to undertake certain tasks.</p> <p>Limited Resources – limited or insufficient resources available, for example, textbooks.</p> <p>Closed vs Open Plan – the effect of closed or open plan classrooms on a teacher's behaviour.</p> <p>Room Size – the physical dimensions of the classroom.</p> <p>Number of Pupils – the number of pupils in the class at any time.</p> <p>Adapt to Physical Environment – changing other behaviour to suit the physical environment of the learning environment.</p> <p>Type of School Building – the physical characteristics of the school, for example, old or modern.</p>	

Teacher's Approach
<p>Training Influence – the influence of a teacher's training, specifically their ITE experience.</p> <p>Training Not Influence – the lack of any influence from their ITE experience on a teacher's behaviour.</p> <p>Pedagogy – the instructional style, strategies and techniques that take place between the teacher and the pupils.</p> <p>Teacher's Experience – the accumulated influence of a teacher's time working in classrooms with pupils.</p> <p>Teacher's Instinct – the teacher's instinctive response or gut reaction to a given situation.</p>
Physical Adaptation
<p>Lines of Sight – the ability of the teacher to see to all areas of the classroom or to see all the pupils and for the pupils to see the teacher.</p> <p>Students Access Resources – the ability of students to access classroom resources.</p> <p>Available Resources – the teaching resources which are available to the teachers and the pupils.</p> <p>Space to Move Around – the open access space around the classroom which isn't blocked by furniture or people.</p> <p>Technology – the inclusion of technology, like computers, laptops or tablets, as a classroom resource.</p> <p>Outdoor Space – the environment immediately outside the school, especially when used as a learning environment.</p> <p>Desk Layout – the physical arrangement of desks or tables within the classroom.</p> <p>Dedicated Areas – areas of the classroom which are set aside or equipped for specialist activities.</p>
Work Adaptation
<p>Adapt to Subject – the adaptation of the curriculum to suit the physical environment of the classroom.</p> <p>Learning Objectives – the intended outcomes of a lesson, work plan or series of activities planned by the teacher.</p> <p>Group Work – pupils working in groups to achieve learning outcomes.</p> <p>Flexibility in Curriculum – the extent to which the teacher can alter the content of the lessons.</p> <p>Core Work – the primary, essential work of the class.</p> <p>Additional Challenging Work – additional work provided to pupils with abilities or time.</p>
Learning Atmosphere

<p>Safe Environment – the requirement to provide a safe environment for teachers and pupils.</p> <p>Atmosphere for Learning – the creation of an environment which is suitable for learning but also where there is an expectation to learn,</p> <p>Noise – the sound level inside and outside of the classroom.</p> <p>Light – the brightness, glare and lighting in the classroom.</p> <p>Temperature – the temperature of the classroom including available heating.</p> <p>Clear Rules – the establishing of classroom rules between the pupils and the teacher.</p>
<p>Engagement and Ownership</p>
<p>Reality/Relevance – the ability of the teacher to relate the lesson to the real-world and real experience.</p> <p>Visual Engagement – engaging pupils in learning through colourful displays or images.</p> <p>Engagement through Fun – engaging pupils in learning through fun activities.</p> <p>Play Based Learning – building learning around play based activities.</p> <p>Pupils Own Learning – the pupils’ sense of ownership over their own learning experience and the schoolwork they do.</p> <p>Teachers Own Space – the teacher’s sense of ownership over the physical space of the classroom.</p> <p>Pupils’ Work as Ownership – the use of pupils’ schoolwork around the classrooms to give them a sense of ownership over the space.</p> <p>Pupils Own Space - the pupils’ sense of ownership over the physical space of the classroom.</p>
<p>Pupils/Teacher Relationship</p>
<p>Communication – the ability of and the multiple ways in which the teacher communicates with the pupils.</p> <p>Behaviour Management – the ability of the teacher to manage the behaviour of the pupils.</p> <p>Pupils/Teacher Relationship – the relationship between the pupils and the teacher.</p> <p>Student's Varying Ages – the ages of students in one classroom or throughout the school.</p> <p>Pupils’ Varying Abilities – the different abilities of individual pupils to carry out schoolwork.</p> <p>Teacher's Choice – the teacher can make a choice about the organisation and management of the classroom.</p> <p>Pupils’ Choice – the pupils can make a choice about the organisation and management of the classroom.</p>

Appendix 6.1. Participant Information, Study 2, Phase 1 and 2

Participant Information Sheet Developing a 360 Degree Video of a Classroom Setting

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of the study is to develop 360° video footage of a classroom environment. The process of filming will provide training in the use of equipment for researchers and the study is intended to optimise the use of 360 video technology in future research.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a student in a class where the lecturer has agreed to allow 360° filming of an additional teaching session that will take place immediately after the regular class that you attend.

Do I have to take part?

No. All relevant coursework material will have been covered in the first hour of teaching (along with logging the student's requirement for attendance) and the research will take place in an additional 40 minute session. Participants retain their right to withdraw up to the commencement of filming. After filming has begun, if a participant wishes to withdraw their consent to participate in the research they will be asked to contact the principal investigator [REDACTED]. Their image will then be removed if possible or blurred in the video files and similarly removed or blurred in any of the still images.

What will happen to me if I take part?

After the first hour of your normal session, during which all relevant coursework will be covered and your attendance will be logged, you will be asked to remain for an additional 40 minutes. During this time you will participate in a prepared lesson which will be recorded using one or more 360° video camera. It is the intention to record classroom activities and use rather than individuals and so during this time you will be required to act normally and as far as possible as if you were participating in a normal class.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks of taking part.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Appendices

There are no obvious benefits but your participation will improve our understanding of how 360° films of classroom environments might be used to enhance Initial Teacher Education.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998). Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you. The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS).

The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-thegdpr/individuals-rights/>

All data gathered, including signed consent forms and video footage, will be stored in line with UWS policy on password protected computers and accessed only by members of the research team.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The immediate results of the study and the video footage will be made available to UWS staff within the UWS Immersive Group. Upon completion of the study the video footage will be deleted (all video footage will be retained for no more than 1 year). A small number of still images may be retained for staff training and publication. In such cases any identifying imagery (faces, etc) will be blurred out so that participants will not be identified. The video footage will not be used or seen outside the UWS Immersive Group. Ultimately the results of the study will contribute to further PhD research.

Who has reviewed the study?

MCS Ethics Committee

Thank you for taking part in this study!

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Alan Matthews

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Name Dr Edward Edgerton

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Appendix 6.2. Informed Consent, Study 2, Phase 1 and 2

School of Media Culture and Society
RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Developing a 360 Degree Video of a Classroom Setting
Ethics Approval Number:

Investigator(s): Alan Matthews

Researcher Email: alan.matthews@uws.ac.uk

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet (PIS 360-video Version 1.5 20.02.19) for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to the commencement of filming without giving any reason. After filming as begun participants are free to remove themselves from the class at any time and request that their image be blurred in any images used for publication.

Initials

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any images resulting from this work can, at my request, be modified so that I cannot be identified.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Alan Matthews

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email at: [REDACTED]. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Media, Culture and Society, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 6.3. Questionnaire, Study 2, Phase 3

Questionnaire

Optimisation of 360° Video in a Classroom Setting.

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study. The purpose of the study is to investigate the potential uses of 360° video footage of a classroom environment. The process of filming has already provided training and experience in the use of 360° video equipment for researchers. The feedback provided by this study is intended to optimise the use of 360° video technology in future research. The purpose of this questionnaire is to provide basic feedback on the experience of viewing a classroom environment through the medium of 360° video.

Background of this Study:

This study forms part of a doctoral research project. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between teaching practice and the organisation and management of learning spaces. Virtual Reality (VR) is being investigated as a potential method of representing learning environments and providing students with an immersive tool for learning. Each learning environment presents a unique combination of challenges. The aim here is to provide feedback on the experience of viewing a classroom through the medium of 360° video. The feedback will be used to inform how to most effectively use this medium in future studies.

Your Participation

This study is being conducted remotely due to the ongoing problems resulting from the COVID-19 restrictions. Your participation will consist of the following steps:

1. Please download the two videos by accessing the link provided in the accompanying email along with instructions. If you have any problems please contact: [REDACTED]
2. Please watch the two videos. If possible please watch them on a virtual reality head mounted display. If one is not available please watch them on a mobile VR device. If neither is available please watch them on a suitable desktop application.

3. Please answer as many of the questions as possible in the questionnaire below. The answers should be your own impressions of the videos and if possible how to improve them. There are no right or wrong answers.
4. When completed, please email this completed questionnaire, along with any additional questions, back to: [REDACTED]

Please Note

You retain the right to withdraw from the study, without explanation at any time up to one week after the completion questionnaire, since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Anonymity

Please be aware that quotes from the questionnaire may be used in future studies and in future publications. When the data from this study is analysed and used it will be made anonymous so that individual participants cannot be identified.

Part 1: Demographic Information

Question 1:

How would you characterise your experience in using Virtual Reality? (Choose one, .)

I have never experienced Virtual Reality.

I have some previous experience Virtual Reality (once or twice in my whole life).

I have regular experience using Virtual Reality (once or twice in a month).

I experience Virtual Reality regularly and have a technical understanding of how it works.

Question 2:

How did you view these videos? (Choose one.)

I viewed these videos on a desktop monitor.

I viewed these videos on a mobile phone using a VR headset.

I viewed these videos using a VR head mounted display.

Part 2: Feedback on the Experience – Open Ended Questions

Question 1: What, if anything, did you enjoy about experiencing the classrooms though 360° video? (For example: Did you feel present in the virtual environment? Did you find the experience engaging?)

Video 1:

Video 2:

Question 2: What, if anything, did you dislike about experiencing the classrooms though 360° video? (For example: Did you experience limitations in the clarity/resolution of the virtual environment?)

Video 1:

Video 2:

Question 3: While viewing the 360° video to what extent were you able to get a sense of the layout of the classrooms? (For example: Did you experience a sense of depth or perspective?)

Video 1:

Video 2:

Question 4: In what ways, if any, did you find viewing the classrooms through 360° video disorientating? (For example: Were you able to locate yourself in the environment?)

Video 1:

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Video 2:

Question 5: How did it add or detract from your experience to view the rooms from different perspectives? (For example: Was there one perspective which was most comfortable?)

Video 1:

Video 2:

Question 6: In what ways could these videos be improved to better demonstrate the organisation and layout of the classrooms?

Video 1:

Video 2:

Question 7: In your opinion, what advantages or disadvantages does this medium have as a learning environment? Would you be prepared to experience a lecture/tutorial/lesson in this way?

Video 1:

Video 2:

What Happens Next?

Please add any additional notes or thought which may further illustrate your experience when watching these videos and how the presentation of the virtual environment might be improved to give a better ideas of the organisation and layout of the learning environment. Please email this completed questionnaire, along with any additional questions, back

Appendix 6.4. Participant Information, Study 2, Phase 3

Participant Information Sheet Optimisation of 360° Video in a Classroom Setting.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of the study is to investigate the potential uses of 360° video footage of a classroom environment. The process of filming has already provided training and experience in the use of 360° video equipment for researchers. The feedback provided by this study is intended to optimise the use of 360° video technology in future research. The purpose of this questionnaire is to provide feedback on the experience of viewing a classroom environment through the medium of 360° video.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a part of the UWS Immersive Groups and are therefore permitted to watch this video footage.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participants retain the right to withdraw from the study, without explanation at any time up to one week after the completion questionnaire, since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

What will happen to me if I take part?

This study is being conducted remotely due to the ongoing problems resulting from the COVID-19 restrictions. Your participation will consist of downloading two videos, watching them on suitable device and then completing a questionnaire that asks you some open-ended questions about the videos. Once completed, you will then be required to email the questionnaire with your answers back to me at: [REDACTED]

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks of taking part.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no obvious benefits but your participation will improve our understanding of how 360° films of classroom environments might be used to enhance Initial Teacher Education.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998). Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you. The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS).

The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

All data gathered, including signed consent forms and video footage, will be stored in line with UWS policy on password protected computers and accessed only by members of the research team.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Quotes from the questionnaire may be used in future studies and in future publications. When the data from this study is analysed and used it will be made anonymous so that individual participants cannot be identified. The feedback provided by this study is intended to optimise the use of 360° video technology in future research. The purpose of this questionnaire is to provide basic feedback on the experience of viewing a classroom environment through the medium of 360° video.

Who has reviewed the study?

MCS Ethics Committee

Thank you for taking part in this study!

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Alan Matthews

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Name Dr Edward Edgerton

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Appendix 6.5. Informed Consent, Study 2, Phase 3

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Optimisation of 360° Video in a Classroom Setting.

Ethics Approval Number: 8084

Investigator(s): Alan Matthews

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet (PIS 360-video Version 1.5 20.08.20) for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I retain the right to withdraw from the study, without explanation at any time up to one week after the completion questionnaire. Since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Initials

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and that quotes from the questionnaire may be used in future studies and in future publications. When the data from this study is analysed and used it will be made anonymous so that individual participants cannot be identified.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Alan Matthews

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email at: [REDACTED] Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Media, Culture and Society, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 6.6. Ethical Approval Letter for Study 2, Phase 1 and 2

21/03/2019

Dear Alan Matthews,

Your application 8084: Optimisation of 3600 Video in a Classroom Setting, submission 6506, has been approved by the Media Culture and Society SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Christopher O'Donnell

Appendix 6.7. Ethical Approval Letter for Study 2, Phase 3

14/10/2020

Dear Alan Matthews,

Your application 8084: Optimisation of 3600 Video in a Classroom Setting, submission 11628, has been approved by the Media Culture and Society SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Christopher O'Donnell

Appendix 8.1. Unity Asset Store, 3D assets

All 3D digital assets used in the creation of the prototype classroom and the VR experiences, Study 4 (*AMClassroom1*, *AMClassroom2* and *AMClassroom3*), are available online at the Unity Asset Store: <https://assetstore.unity.com/>

All 3D digital assets were used according to the terms of the Standard Unity Asset Store EULA: <https://unity.com/legal/as-terms>

Elements of the following assets were used in this PhD:

- AZERILO – Free Rug Pack
- SEAN DUFFY – Deep Space Skybox Pack
- QATMO – QA Books
- STEN ULFSSON – Office Supplies Low Poly
- ALP – Grass Flowers Pack Free
- TIRGAMES ASSETS – School Scene
- RPGWHITELOCK – AllSky Free – 10 Sky / Skyboxes
- MAKSIM BUGRIMOV – PBR Textures(pack)for floor
- A DOG’S LIFE SOFTWARE – Plank Textures PBR
- VERTEX STUDIO – Big Furniture Pack
- ELCANETAY – Office Room Furniture
- ASSET STORE ORIGINALS – Snape Prototype | Office
- A.R.S|T. – Achool Assets

Appendix 9.1. Participant Information, Study 4

Participant Information Sheet

Investigating Teachers' and ITE Students' Responses to Simulated Classrooms.

Data Collection using VR Headsets

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The proposed study will form part of a doctoral research project. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between teaching practice and the design of learning spaces through the use of virtual reality (VR). Ultimately the purpose of the research is to assess the potential for using VR technology to change and improve the provision of professional education and training by focusing on its application to Initial Teacher Education (ITE). During a previous study it became apparent that each learning environment presented a unique set of challenges based on contextual factors. The purpose of this study is to assess the potential for simulating that environment using VR technology as a teaching tool for ITE students.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are an ITE student, an in-practice teacher or an ITE educator.

Do I have to take part?

No. There are no expectations from UWS to take part. For those participants who are ITE students, participation in this study will have no effect at all on your ongoing studies. In addition, participants retain their right to withdraw up to one week after the completion of the interview. Transcription will take place a week after the interview has been concluded and since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will experience three simulated classrooms using VR equipment. In each classroom the researcher will provide you with a few short questions to address. Your response to these questions will typically be for you to describe aloud how you would change or improve the physical layout of the classrooms in order to improve its use as a learning space or more specifically suit your approach to teaching. This will be followed by a short semi-structured interview which will reflect on your experience using the VR classrooms and allow you to provide additional information.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks of taking part.

Health and Safety.

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A full risk assessment has been carried out. This will be made available to you before participating in the experiment. A few key points and measure to ensure your safety during the study is noted here:

Motion sickness or other signs of discomfort.

A small number of participants may experience a form of motion sickness. This is highly unlikely given the nature of the simulated environment. Should you feel uncomfortable, you will be allowed to stop, a seated break will be suggested. If discomfort persists you will be offered the opportunity to participate in the study via a desktop monitor or, if preferred, withdraw from the study altogether.

COVID-19

Participants will be required to follow all current precautions while being on UWS campus. Hand sanitiser and VR face covers will be provided and their usage mandatory. Face coverings must be worn when not wearing the VR face cover. Participants will be scheduled with at least 30-minute gaps. All such information will be provided by email to registered participants beforehand, and verbally at the start of each individual user study. All equipment will be sanitised, following UWS protocols, after each participant.

Anyone feeling COVID-19 symptoms is advised not to come on campus and to self-isolate in line with NHS advice. If anyone develops symptoms whilst on campus and/or develop symptoms after being on campus, you must immediately arrange to return home and inform the principal investigator by email. Your email address will be asked for in case you need to be contacted for contract tracing. This information will be kept separate from your unique id and any user data gathered.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no obvious benefits but your participation will improve our understanding of how teachers and students relate to their learning environments and how this might be used to enhance Initial Teacher Education (ITE) using VR technology.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998). Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you. The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS).

The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

All data gathered, including signed consent forms, audio recordings and notes, will be stored in line with UWS policy on password protected computers and accessed only by members of the research team. To assure anonymity no comment will be attributable to any individual and that

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each participant will be referenced by sex and number e.g. M1 for Male no 1 (the first male to be interviewed)", etc.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

All of the data provided by this analysis will form part of the principal researcher's doctoral dissertation. The data may also contribute to papers for publication in peer-reviewed and other (including online) journals. The audio recordings, notes and unedited transcripts will only be accessed by the Principal Researcher and Supervisory team. These will be deleted upon completion of the doctoral research project. Anonymised portions of the transcripts may be included in the principal researcher's doctoral dissertation or other future research work.

Who has reviewed the study? MCS Ethics Committee

Thank you for taking part in this study. Contact for further information:

If you require any further information please contact:

Principal Researcher:

Alan Matthews

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

E-mail

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Name Dr Edward Edgerton

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

[REDACTED]

Appendix 9.2. Informed Consent, Study 4

School of Education and Social Science
RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Project Title: Investigating Teachers' and ITE Students' Responses to Simulated Classrooms.

Ethics Approval Number:

Investigator(s): Alan Matthews

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet (PIS Classroom Simulations v1) for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason up to one week after the completion of the interview.

Initials

I understand that the interview will be audio recorded, that my data will be treated confidentially and that any data disseminated will be anonymised. Actual quotes might be used in publications or in further studies but these will be anonymised and will not be attributable to any individual.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)
Alan Matthews

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email at: Christopher.odonnell@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 9.3. Interview Schedule, Study 4

School of Education and Social Science

Interview Schedule

Investigating Teachers' and ITE Students' Responses to Simulated Classrooms.

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study. The VR experience and the Interview should take no more than 80 minutes. If you want to take a break or stop at any time, especially when using the VR, just tell me.

Review the background of the study:

The proposed study will form part of a doctoral research project. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between teaching practice and the organisation and management of learning spaces. An equally important purpose of this study is to assess the potential using VR technology as a teaching tool for ITE students by assessing several simulated environments.

Given that each learning environment presents a unique combination of challenges this study seeks to explore how in-practice teachers, student teachers and educators respond to classroom environments which have been simulated in VR.

Reiterate that the study is anonymous:

Did you read the information sheet? Have you initialled and signed the Participant Consent Form? You are aware that quotes from the interview may be used in future studies and in future publications? When the data from this study is analysed and used it will be made anonymous so that individual participants cannot be identified. Any images or audio recordings will also be anonymised.

Reiterate the right to withdraw:

You retain the right to withdraw from the study, without explanation at any time up to one week after the completion of the interview, since the data will be anonymous after that date, it will then not be possible to withdraw.

Emphasise that no question needs to be answered:

If you don't want to answer any of the questions, even the quick background questions at the start that is of course okay. There are no right or wrong answers it is about your opinions and experience. Please feel free to add anything that you think is important but which I may not ask you about.

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Do you have any questions before we start?

Are you okay to proceed?

Part 1: Demographic Information

Question 1: Identifier:

Your name won't be recorded here and so the data you provide will be given the following identifier:

Question 2: Time of qualification as a teacher (or when do you expect to qualify):

Prompt 2a: When did you qualify as a teacher? I'm trying to get measure of your experience.

Prompt 2b: have worked mostly in primary or secondary classrooms?

Prompt 2c: How many different classrooms have you worked in?

Question 3: Describe your experience, if any, in using Virtual Reality (VR)?

Prompt 3a: Have you ever used VR in a teaching setting?

Prompt 3b: Have you ever used VR in an academic setting?

Prompt 3c: What is your technical understanding of how VR works?

Part 2: VR Experience – Introduction and Prompts

Introduction: Assuming the participant has little or no experience using VR the first experience will be of fantastical simulation which retains the same interactivity as the classroom simulations.

Ensure that the headset is comfortable, secure and that the image is in sharp focus.

Ensure that the participant is familiar with the guardian and the boundaries.

Allow the participant to practice teleportation and rotational movement.

Allow a few moments to acclimatize and ask questions.

Task 1: Your first task is to describe the room. Please describe what you consider to be the important physical characteristic of the classroom? (3 minutes, approximately)

Prompt 1a: Describe the desk layout, lines of sight, is there space to move around?

Prompt 1b: What pedagogy, if any, does the layout of the room best suit?

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Prompt1c: What are the obvious problems with the room's layout?

Prompt 1d: What other things catch you eye or seem to be important?

Task 2: Your second task is to describe as many ways as you can in which you would change the physical layout of the room to better suit your own ideas about teaching. (3 minutes, approximately)

Prompt 2a: How would you change the room to improve the learning atmosphere (expectation to learn, enthusiasm for class)?

Prompt 2b: In what ways could the room be changed to better engage students in their learning?

Prompt 2c: How could you change the room to provide a sense of ownership (sense of belonging, desire to improve) for you and your students?

Prompt 2d: In what ways does the layout of this classroom contribute to a positive or negative student/teacher relationship? How could that be improved?

Part 3: Interview

Question 1: Which of the three classrooms you observed in VR did you feel was the best classroom to suit your approach to teaching?

Prompt 1a: What factors about each classroom were most important to you?

Prompt 1b: Which important factors did the other classrooms lack?

Prompt 1c: Is there another option which would be better which was not considered among those three?

Question 2: What was the primary influence on your assessment of each of the three classrooms?

Prompt 2a: How much of an influence was your ITE experience?

Prompt 2b: How much of an influence was your working experience?

Prompt 2c: How much of your assessment is an instinctual response?

Question 3: How would you rearrange any of the three classrooms to reflect your ideal classroom environment?

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Prompt 3a: Have you arranged the desks to create clear lines of sight?

Prompt 3b: How do you store resources and how do the students have access?

Prompt 3c: Have you created space for you to move around the room?

Prompt 3d: How have you arranged the room to improve behaviour management (manage troublesome students, control student interactions)?

Prompt 3e: How do you use technology to improve communication with students?

Question 4: With reference to the three VR examples, how would you adapt the layout of the classroom to suit the curriculum?

Prompt 4a: How do you adapt to students varying abilities?

Prompt 4b: Do you display learning objectives or core tasks?

Prompt 4c: Do you display the students work?

Prompt 4d: Do the students contribute the layout, decoration and organisation of the room?

Prompt 4e: Would you split the classroom into dedicated areas?

Question 5: How would you describe the experience of using VR to simulate a classroom environment?

Prompt 5a: What things did you like about the experience?

Prompt 5b: What things did you dislike about the experience?

Question 6: In what ways do you think VR simulated classrooms have potential as a teaching tool for ITE students?

Prompt 6a: Could you imagine using VR to your own benefit?

Prompt 6b: What are the advantages of VR over more 2D experiences?

Question 7: What do you think are the limitations involved in VR as a teaching tool for ITE students?

Prompt 7a: Did you experience any discomfort while using the VR headset?

Prompt 7b: Did you consider limitation in multi-tasking or social interaction?

Appendix 9.4. Debrief, Study 4

Debriefing Information

Investigating Teachers' and ITE Students' Responses to Simulated Classrooms.

This study has formed part of a doctoral research project. The overall project seeks to explore the relationship between teaching practice and the design of learning spaces by applying virtual reality (VR). This current study is intended to build upon the work already carried out and address the research question: Is it possible to demonstrate important qualities of classroom environments that are easily identifiable by students based on different VR models? The data provided in this study will be analysed to assess if the participants' described experiences reflect the design and layout as interpreted by current literature and the results of previous studies. This will include an assessment of how each participant might change or improve the environment. Finally this study will begin to assess the potential for using VR as a teaching tool for ITE.

Traditional approaches organise the learning space to be teacher-centred, whereas more current approaches emphasise exploratory behaviour in the students and working in groups. Despite the fact that classroom organisation remains largely the responsibility of the individual teacher, the decisions remain tacit and intuitive (Cremin and Arthur, 2014). During a previous study conducted by this researcher, it became apparent that each learning environment presented a variety of different challenges based on contextual factors. A greater understanding could therefore be gained by focusing the next study on specific learning environments. From this analysis it is hoped to gain a better understanding of how primary students and primary teacher relate to their physical surroundings.

Whilst individual schools have established approaches to classroom organisation and practical limitations effect what a teacher is able to change, classroom organisation is still primarily considered the responsibility of the teacher. Again, during a previous study by this researcher, it became apparent that teachers identify some aspects of the learning environment which are beyond their control and some of which they are able to influence but all of which effect how the learning environment is manage and organised. The aim of this study has been to address this approach with reference to a specific example. Building on the analytical approach carried out by Knauf (2018) by analysing the physical characteristic of the learning environment in combination with how teacher perceive the environment.

VR may provide a unique learning environment suitable for this aspect of teacher education. The purpose of these interviews is to provide a general understanding of the practicalities of classroom management and organisation as it is recognised by working teachers. If you are interested in reading more about this area please see below:

Appendix 9.5. Ethical Approval Letter for Study 4

22/09/2021

Dear Alan Matthews,

Your application 16725: Investigating Teachers' and ITE Students' Responses to Simulated Classrooms., submission 14021, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee